

DH Benelux Journal

VOLUME 6:

CROSSING BORDERS: DIGITAL HUMANITIES
RESEARCH ACROSS LANGUAGES AND MODALITIES

Fall 2024

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digital : *Benelux*
humanities : *Journal*

DH Benelux Journal 6. Crossing borders: digital humanities research across languages and modalities.

ISSN: 2666-6952

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This journal was typeset in L^AT_EX by Marijn Koolen using *varianTeX* — a reusable template for journals in the Humanities, developed by Wout Dillen. *varianTeX* is open source, available on GitHub, and deposited in the Zenodo Open Science Repository. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3484651.

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Editors’ Preface

For the sixth time since 2019, the Open Access DH Benelux Journal issue gathers contributions presented during the annual conference DH Benelux. The DH Benelux conference is organized in turn by universities in the Netherlands, Belgium, and Luxembourg, but it is open to a broad international community that joins every year. The current issue presents papers that were presented in the 2023 edition. As we do every year, authors of all accepted contributions were invited to submit a full paper based on their presentation. Each full paper underwent an entirely new round of peer-review, and was accepted on the basis of the evaluation of three peer reviewers. We are glad to share that this year we are publishing 12 articles, a number which testifies of the high engagement of the community with this journal.

The 2023 edition was a particularly festive one, marking the 10th anniversary of the DH Benelux conference. It was hosted from the 31st of May to the 2 of June in the impressive building of the KBR (Royal Library) of Brussels, the national library in charge of collecting and preserving Belgian publications and cultural heritage. Such a venue, bringing together the different Belgian communities, was particularly suited for the conference’s theme ‘Crossing borders: Digital Humanities research across languages and modalities’, chosen by the program committee constituted by Isabelle Gribomont, Jason Jongepier, and Suzan Verberne, who are also the guest-editors of this issue of the DH Benelux Journal. The articles contribute from different perspectives to this overarching theme, as the guest editors explain in their preface. We thank them for proposing such a stimulating program and for curating the publication process of the papers.

We would also like to thank the local organizers who made the DH Benelux 2023 conference possible, ensuring a pleasant stay for all of us and providing a space for all the selected contributions despite the steadily rising number of submissions.

As guest editors, we hope that you will enjoy this volume, that you’ll join us at the DH Benelux conference in the coming years.

November 15, 2024
Amsterdam, Borås, Nijmegen and
Leuven

Wout Dillen
Margherita Fantoli
Marijn Koolen
Julia Neugarten
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Introduction: Crossing Borders: Digital Humanities Research across Languages and Modalities

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The Digital Humanities (DH) Benelux 2023 conference took place from 31 May to 2 June 2023 at the KBR (Royal Library), Brussels, Belgium. This was the 10th edition of the annual conference, which serves as the go-to platform for the community of interdisciplinary Digital Humanities researchers to meet, present and discuss their latest research. Contributions could be submitted in five different formats: (1) long papers; (2) short papers; (3) posters; (4) application and tool demonstrations; and (5) workshops. As a result, the conference had an interesting mix of keynotes, workshops, panels with thematically organized oral presentations, posters, and demonstrations.

The central theme of the DH Benelux 2023 was “**Crossing borders: digital humanities research across languages and modalities**”. We considered of particular interest contributions that address multilingualism or integrated processing of sources in different forms as images, maps, sounds, texts and datasets.

As with previous editions, participants of DH Benelux 2023 were invited to submit an extended version of their paper or abstract for publication in the DH Benelux journal. In total, 13 manuscripts were received and sent out to review. Each paper was reviewed by three anonymous peer reviewers. If the reviewers requested minor revisions, the paper was accepted after one revision round. If the reviewers requested major revisions, the paper was sent back to the reviewers after the revision for a final review round. After this review process, 12 papers were ultimately published in this issue.

As the title of the conference indicates, a wide range of subjects is covered in this issue. From a variety of disciplinary perspectives, all contributions deal to a certain extent with methodological challenges encountered when undertaking humanities research with digital methods.

Three contributions address issues related to the digital analysis of historical texts. Laura Soffiantini presents a geoparsing experiment on Pliny the Elder’s *Natural History* with the goal of automatically identifying and extracting place entities. Nynke van ’t Hof, Vera Provatorova, Mirjam Cupera and Evangelos Kanoulas investigate OCR error detection and post-correction with word2vec and BERTje on Dutch historical

data. Gabor Mihaly Toth proposes a novel technique to quantify information flow in Early Modern Europe with Bayesian time-to-event analysis.

Another four contributions focus on literary analysis. Isabelle Gribomont and Lucie Mentalechta introduce a typology to classify literary bots on social media. Nulette Heyns and Menno van Zaanen create and leverage an annotated database to train a computer system capable of automatically annotating literary texts according to their structural components. Julia Neugarten maps the relationship between violence and the gender of the fictional characters in relationships in fanfiction about Greek myth. Finally, Felix Hermans and Dirk Van Hulle introduce a digital manuscript chronology that lists information found in manuscripts, notebooks, and letters in order to elucidate the compositional histories of literary works.

Taking the Digital Humanities themselves as an object of study, Aida Horaniet Ibañez presents a classification of current approaches to data visualisation in DH. Theodoros Georgiakakis and Tim van der Heijden contribute to cultural heritage studies by addressing the role 3D technologies can play in the virtual reconstruction of cultural heritage objects. In the field of archaeology, Irene Agües-Escolano designs a methodology for the digital recording and documentation of historical graffiti using photogrammetry. From the perspective of urban and cultural geography, Dan C. Baciú, Sunit Kajarekar and Anna Abramova present a geospatial discovery tool for text collections. Finally, at the intersection of education sciences and game design, Austin Mason, Franziska Funken, Emmanuel Guardiola, Marie-Paule Jungblut and Johannes Pause introduce a co-design process for historical game development. This wide-ranging combination of themes and methodologies offers a compelling sample of current Digital Humanities research carried out in the Benelux and beyond.

We extend our sincere gratitude to all the authors, reviewers, and conference participants who contributed to the success of DH Benelux 2023. It is their enthusiasm, expertise, and commitment that make this conference an important, high-quality, yet welcoming gathering for the Digital Humanities community in the Benelux (and beyond). We hope that the insights shared within this issue inspire further exploration, collaboration, creation and alteration in the Digital Humanities.

Documenting Historical Graffiti: A Digital Approach

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We present the registration and documentation work conducted on a set of 144 graffiti incised in the 18th and 19th centuries on the walls of a house in Villa Joiosa (Alicante, Spain). First, we analyze the advantages and disadvantages of the most common digital registration techniques. Based on the specific characteristics of our graffiti set, we propose photogrammetry as the most suitable registration method. After the registration, documentation tasks are performed on the orthophotogrammetric model obtained from the photogrammetric survey. The primary task is digital tracing, which requires enhancing the visibility of some motifs. To address visibility issues, we employ the Python library OpenCV. This paper details the application of Sobel, Scharr and Prewitt operators, as well as the Canny edge detector, to improve graffiti visibility. The documentation of historical graffiti currently lacks a standardized approach among researchers, with its execution contingent on factors such as the nature of the set, preservation status, tool availability, temporal and financial constraints, and the expertise of the researchers. We propose to analyze the feasibility of conducting all recording of historical graffiti using digital methods. Our goal is to design a methodology for high-quality digital recording and documentation, providing valuable content for interpretative tasks. This includes justifying the use of photogrammetry, highlighting its limitations, and demonstrating how to address these limitations through computational methods.

Keywords: Historical Graffiti; Digital Recording; Orthophotography; Image Processing; OpenCV.

1 Introduction

Gonzalo Viñuales, the author behind one of the most recent publications about the state of art of historical graffiti research in Spain, suggests that while numerous definitions of graffiti have emerged in recent years, each is valid, but none is complete and unanimous (Ferreiro, 2020, p.12). In the Spanish-speaking territories, the lack of a unified terminology further complicates matters, with scholars interchangeably using ‘grafito’ and ‘graffiti’. The first term is gaining prominence at the expense of the latter (Ángel García Serrano, 2012, p.23). English-language works are rooted in the Italian

origin of the term, maintaining the usage of 'graffiti', as popularized in publications dating back to the 1980s (Bucherie, 1982; Cinquabre, 1982). While unanimity is not a reality yet, researchers generally agree on the unofficial nature of these graphic expressions, often created by anonymous individuals using diverse techniques on surfaces not originally intended to host them (Maturana, 2017, pp.21-22), (Gozalo, 2013, pp.9-10). Addressing the chronology of historical graffiti, the term encompasses creations spanning from Antiquity to the latter half of the 20th century, marking the onset of contemporary graffiti (Ferreiro, 2020, p.11).

Prehistoric artistic manifestations fall beyond the purview of this field of study. However, due to the similarity in the needs of documentation, the influence of rock art studies is significant. Much like the absence of a common definition, there exists a lack of consensus regarding criteria for registration tasks. In this context, works of prehistoric art are acknowledged as integral part of the academic recording tradition (Ugarte et al., 2022, p.45). It is commonplace for the demands of the reproduction, registration, and systematization processes faced by researchers in the study of historical graffiti to find resolution through the application of methodologies akin to those employed in the examination of prehistoric paintings and engravings (Alcaraz, 2015, p.32).

Regardless of the chronology, support, and technique, the prevailing registration methods encompass direct tracing, Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI), photography, and the use of structured light and laser scanners. The selection of a recording tool depends on multiple factors, including the specific attributes of the set to be documented, its state of preservation, the availability of time, funds, and the tools themselves. It is important not to overlook the proficiency levels demanded from researchers by certain digital techniques (Valente and Barazzeti, 2020, p.8). Although we will not address this aspect, the question of the requisite level of technical and computing proficiency for digital humanists has been a topic of discussion, particularly concerning programming (Hernández-Lorenzo, 2022, p.147).

We present part of the registration work conducted on a set of 150 graffiti created in the 18th and 19th centuries on two walls of a house in the city of Villa Joiosa (Alicante, Spain). The first task was to evaluate the different digital registration techniques that have been employed in graffiti studies for historical periods in Europe, and to assess the advantages and disadvantages of each technique based on the needs of our case study. Considering the characteristics of our graffiti set, we propose photogrammetry as the most suitable registration method for our purpose. The rest of the work focuses on extracting the maximum amount of information from the 2D files obtained from photogrammetry and minimizing the visibility issues that may arise when studying graffiti exclusively with digital media. Specifically, we concentrate on improving the visibility of graffiti using the Python library OpenCV, aligning our work with the principles of what some researchers have termed "visual digital humanities" (Münster and Terras, 2020, pp.367-368).

We take as reference the study of graffiti at the Basilica di San Marco in Venice conducted by Abate and Trentin (2019). They were the first authors to present the results obtained by applying image processing operators for edge detection on the orthophotography of historical incised graffiti. Specifically, they utilized the Sobel image processing operator in the Orfeo ToolBox environment (Abate and Trentin, 2019, p.4). We explore Sobel, Scharr, and Prewitt operators, as well as Canny edge detection, using the OpenCV library in Python, with the objective of contributing new options in the field of image processing in the study of historical graffiti.

2 Techniques for recording Historical Graffiti

In the last decades there has been a logical increase in digital recording techniques in studies in historical graffiti (Valente and Barazzeti, 2020, p.7). However, direct contact tracing continues to be a widely used method of recording, as seen in the two theses defended in Spanish territory on the subject (Alcaraz, 2015; Maturana, 2017). This method involves placing transparent sheets over graffiti surfaces and manually tracing the graffiti with markers. The execution of this registration method has been characterized as a slow and complex process, posing potential threats to the preservation of both the graffiti and their supporting surfaces. Moreover, it encounters challenges when applied to large areas (Maturana, 2017, p.101), (Ángel García Serrano, 2012, p.25). The use of direct contact tracing as the main method may result in the loss of spatial information, compromising the analysis of the set within its context and the relationship between motifs (Abate and Trentin, 2019, p.1). Another consideration involves the storage of the tracing sheets, ensuring optimal preservation conditions. In certain instances, these sheets represent the only documentation available for groups of graffiti that have deteriorated over time or have been entirely lost (Ugarte et al., 2022, p.28).

Digital recording techniques are presented as a solution to the listed issues but also as a response to the focus bias detected in contact tracing processes. The work carried out in the Latin Chapel of the Church of Panagia Aggeloktisti in Kiti (Cyprus) revealed how the capabilities and knowledge of diverse researchers can lead to a subjective reproduction of motifs. Two researchers traced the same graffiti creating two different rubbings and the results differed in key aspects. These discrepancies were resolved with a new register work using the RTI technique (Demesticha et al., 2017, p.348). RTI is the most used digital technique in the registration of historical graffiti (Valente and Barazzeti, 2020, p.7). Its success can be attributed to the availability of free and user-friendly software for model creation, along with its substantial enhancement of the visibility of engraved graffiti. This is achieved by leveraging the reflective properties of the surface. Once the surface is registered, the software enables digital adjustments to the lighting conditions, highlighting lines that are difficult to perceive with the naked eye (Valente et al., 2019, p.733). This technique has been successfully tested in the infrared light spectrum for registering graffiti incised on pigmented surfaces (Cosentino et al., 2015, p.28).

Digital recording techniques are particularly important on pigmented surfaces, where the objective is to avoid any direct contact with the surface. Photogrammetry offers favourable results when recording graffiti on frescos (Valente and Oreni, 2017; Valente et al., 2019). In Spain, numerous studies utilize this recording method, mainly in sets located on flat surfaces. Occasionally, this technique is complemented by others, such as laser scanning or infrared photography (Bendicho et al., 2020; Felipe, 2013; Granell et al., 2021). Photogrammetry provides the advantage of facilitating direct measurements and expediting documentation tasks. Its application, however, extends beyond the registration of walls and plastered surfaces. It is also utilized on other types of surfaces, including marble (Abate and Trentin, 2019) and even within caves (Silvente and López, 2020).

The advantages of utilizing photogrammetry as the primary recording method are not limited to operational considerations related to funding and time constraints. Metric information is undoubtedly important, and the value is enhanced when the graffiti are documented within their spatial context. Although photogrammetry primarily

produces a 3D file, in the study of graffiti, the orthophotography derived from the model is used more often than the 3D model itself. This file facilitates measurements, context analysis and digital tracing. Usually, 3D files are leveraged during the diffusion phases. Obtaining the tracing on the orthophotography eliminates some of the challenges inherent in direct manual tracing. This task, also common on rectified photographs and RTI files, usually involves vectorizing strokes using programs like Inkscape or computer-aided design software (CAD) (Valente and Barazzeti, 2020). Additionally, certain works utilize raster graphics editing programs such as GIMP or Adobe Photoshop for digital tracing (Dhoop et al., 2016; Valente and Oreni, 2017).

By vectorizing strokes with computer-aided design software, we generate geometric information linked to each line, which can be stored for subsequent analysis and interpretation tasks. These programs facilitate the grouping of objects, as well as the assignment of attributes and the introduction of descriptive content, improving and completing the documentation process. Noteworthy are the distribution maps, which highlight patterns based on values such as chronology and typology. Although generated during documentation phases for research purposes, these graphic documents are also included in the diffusion strategy (Valente and Barazzeti, 2020, p.11). However, digital tracing remains a task that relies on the researcher's manual input and decisions, making it susceptible to challenges in correct identification. This issue can be addressed digitally through the application of filters or algorithms that, by adjusting and interpreting lights and colours, enhance the visibility of graffiti (Abate and Trentin, 2019, p.4).

3 The potential of machine learning for Historical Graffiti Research

To enhance the visibility of incised graffiti, one particularly useful Python library is OpenCV; an open-source computer vision library with more than 2,500 algorithms. In the realm of Digital Humanities, specific manuals (Kokensparger, 2018; Mattingly, 2023) and university training programs (Pimenta and Gomes, 2019) support the utilization of Python language. In Archaeology, Python finds application in projects like the recognized ODATE project (Graham et al., 2020). In this work, we propose the use of the OpenCV library to enhance the visibility of incised graffiti. This can be achieved through various methods; we focus on the Sobel, Scharr, and Prewitt operators, as well as the Canny edge detector. These operators approximate the intensity gradients of an image, detecting changes interpreted as the edges of elements within the image. To achieve this, the operators employ separate convolutions on the input image with distinct kernels for each axis, allowing us to apply it with varied parameters for both x and y directions. This adaptative approach enables us to reduce interference from peak marks of the wall, acknowledging the potential cost of omitting crucial lines of graffiti. The Canny edge detector, on the other hand, uses a multi-stage algorithm that includes noise reduction with a Gaussian filter, gradient calculation, non-maximum suppression, and edge tracking by hysteresis.

The application of edge detection algorithms significantly enhances the visibility of graffiti, thereby facilitating classification and cataloguing, tasks typically performed by the researcher. Although automatic image classification models have been satisfactorily tested in Humanities, including Archaeology (Münster and Terras, 2020, p.369), attempting to apply these machine learning techniques to historical graffiti studies presents a series of specific challenges. In contrast to epigraphy and textual graffiti, for

which automatic image classification has been tested and yields good results, figurative graffiti do not exhibit the same regularity (Gatica-Perez et al., 2017; Gordienko et al., 2018a,b). In addition to the intricate geometry of figurative graffiti, we must also consider the challenges in gathering information to construct datasets.

For the work conducted at St. Sophia Cathedral in Kyiv, a dataset of over 4000 images was created from a location where more than 7000 graffiti have been recorded (Gordienko et al., 2018a, p.3). In contrast, the most extensive study we have for the south-east of Spain is from the city of Villena (Alicante, Spain), where slightly more than 400 graffiti were recorded across 8 different locations (Alcaraz, 2015). This limited number could potentially be increased with data from other graffiti sets, but there are currently no available datasets of figurative modern-era graffiti, which would require unified typologies and, in general, the application of a common methodological framework. Automatic classification is not the sole application of machine learning in the study of historical graffiti. It also holds potential for analyzing geometric data extracted from graffiti vectorization. However, the limitations we identified regarding datasets for image classification would also apply in this case. Even if we cannot incorporate machine learning into our research, Python offers libraries such as Pandas, NumPy, and Matplotlib that can assist us in our work and generate valuable information from the geometric data collected via AutoCAD.

If we do not want to dismiss the possibility of working with models trained on images or geometrical data of historical graffiti, we must consider two fundamental aspects of Digital Humanities: the collaborative work and the promotion of open data. Integrating machine learning technologies into our projects requires the involvement of computer scientists responsible for the technical aspects of the process. The outcomes of these collaborations, including the results and the code employed, are anticipated to be diffused in open-source (Hernández-Lorenzo, 2022, p.145). In the realm of historical graffiti, open diffusion of the images along with metadata could propel us toward a transformative reality, enabling the development of a diverse-level corpus, not only to deepen our understanding but also to protect this fragile heritage (Ángel García Serrano, 2012, p.18). Furthermore, this approach would provide us with a substantial volume of data, facilitating the application of Big Data methods and techniques. It's noteworthy that, as seen in the previous paragraph, in Humanities, the scale of data is noticeably smaller compared to the vast datasets used in the fields of IT and business (Hernández-Lorenzo, 2022, p.146).

4 Application to a case study: set of Carrer Major in La Vila Joiosa

On December 18, 2018, La Vila Joiosa City Council published a press release on its official website, reporting the discovery of a set of historical graffiti at house number 17 on Calle Mayor in the framework of rehabilitation works. The documentation process for the graffiti was an integral part of the archaeological monitoring conducted by the Municipal Department of Archaeology and Historical Heritage of La Vila Joiosa, given that the property is in an area designated as an Asset of Cultural Interest. The graffiti were found on two of the walls on the second floor, covering a total area of 25 m². After the removal of the plaster layers that covered the graffiti, the restorer from the municipal museum, Vila Museu, treated the walls with ethyl silicate for consolidation, while cleaning and accentuating the engravings. Subsequently, the set was photographed to generate the photogrammetric model using a 50 Mpx Full

Figure 1: Workflow.

Figure 2: Selected portion of the orthophoto; the overlapping strokes and wall damage are evident.

Frame sensor camera (Canon 5Ds) and professional lighting equipment. The primary goal was 3D virtualization, aiming to preserve and diffuse the set. However, the orthophotographs of the two walls were generated, meaning the commencement of digital tracing tasks within the doctoral thesis project currently underway¹ (Figure 2). In this process, visibility issues were identified in some motifs, to which we applied several edge detection operators from the OpenCV library in Python (Figure 1).

¹ Els grafitis com a informadors històrics: el segle XVIII a La Vila Joiosa a través dels grafitis parietals (Graffiti as Historical Informants: the 18th century in La Vila Joiosa through parietal graffiti). The project is being developed within the Instituto Universitario de Investigación en Arqueología y Patrimonio Histórico at the University of Alicante, and since 2022, has been founded by the Vice-Rectorate for Research and Knowledge Transfer of the same University. UAFPU20-01. Orthophotographs created by DStoa Patrimonio y Tecnología SL and deposited in the digital archives of Vilamuseu by the owner of the property located at C/ Mayor, 17 in Villajoyosa, Happy Vila Real Estate.

Figure 3: Digital tracing made with AutoCAD. The different colours correspond to different typologies: blue, indeterminate; black, ships; pink, geometry.

4.1 Digital Tracing with AutoCAD

The tracing was made with AutoCAD, using drawing tools, primarily polylines (Figure 3). The set is characterized by an abundance of overlapping lines, complicating readability. For this reason, we decided to trace without pre-identifying specific motifs. Once all lines were digitally traced, isolating strokes, and defining the contours became more manageable. Identified motifs were then organized into distinct layers based on typology. Any lines not associated with a figurative motif were categorized as 'indeterminate'. The ability to activate or deactivate layers facilitates the study. Following this process, we successfully characterized the set and made an initial count. The problem of overlapping strokes and the deterioration of specific motifs and areas hindered the completion of the tracing task. Initially, were identified 144 graffiti, with 49% attributed to boats. The subsequent significant category is epigraphy, followed by accounting elements. The graffiti typologies include geometric, anthropomorphic, and zoomorphic motifs.

Within the epigraphy, we discovered a date that places the set in the latter half of the 18th century, coinciding with the Mediterranean navigation of all the represented ship types. This discovery provides a generic characterization that guides the remainder of our research tasks. Given the variety of eight distinct boat types, differentiated by sails, it becomes essential to meticulously register the motifs due to their significant role in dating. To facilitate this, we devised a routine in the AutoLisp language. This routine allows us to seamlessly store both geometric and descriptive information in a single file directly from the AutoCAD environment. This approach not only streamlines the process but also mitigates potential errors derived from manual data entry across multiple programs.

Upon invocation, the routine initiates by prompting the selection of the pertinent graffiti. Subsequently, it requests the motif's inventory number, along with details such as the type and quantity of sails, automatically storing both geometric data and location coordinates. This information is stored in a plain text file that is easily transferable to spreadsheet or database. This process accelerates registration, yielding data that, when appropriately processed, become relevant information for our investigation. An alternative route, devoid of programming prerequisites, involves the utilization of the DATAEXTRACTION command. By working with blocks and attributes, a

document with similar information can be generated. Assisted design environments offer tools to both fulfil and enhance registration tasks. This methodology enables us to manage a more extensive dataset, reduce time, and avoid the issues of direct contact tracing inherent in large graffiti sets. In our case, the motifs are spread across the walls from ground level to two and half meters high, spanning over nine linear meters. However, we cannot ignore the inconveniences associated with digital tracing. It becomes important to engage filters or algorithms that modify orthophotography properties to enhance visibility. Given that we operate remotely, the solutions must reside within the digital realm.

4.2 Image processing with OpenCV

Faced with the impossibility of accurately defining some graffiti, impeding the completion of inventory tasks, our initial attempts involved experimenting with various configurations of levels and color curves using GIMP. While there was some improvement in visibility, it was not enough. Consequently, we decided to explore the capabilities offered by the Open CV library. In our efforts to enhance the visibility of orthophotographs, we take as reference the study of graffiti at the Basilica di San Marco in Venice (Abate and Trentin, 2019). In their work, edge detection is on orthophotography using the Sobel image processing operator. In their case, this process was executed through dedicated software rather than within a programming environment.

Initially, after converting the orthophoto to grayscale and minimizing noise, we implemented the Sobel operator (Sobel and Feldman, 1990). We generated three images: one displaying the contours of both axes, x and y (Figure 4); and two additional images, each corresponding to an individual axis (Figure 5 and Figure 6). In the same way, we tested the Scharr operator, which is known for working with more complex operator and promises more precise results in edge detection (Scharr, 2000). However, in our case, this sophistication led to a notable increase in artifacts, rendering the results unreadable (Figure 7, Figure 8 and Figure 9). Among all the filters under consideration, the Prewitt operator has yielded the best results in terms of improving visibility, despite being the most limited operator in terms of specific adjustments permitted in its implementation (Prewitt, 1970) (Figure 10). It is interesting to observe the different images obtained when limiting the output to a single axis. We observe that using the x-axis emphasizes vertical edges, leading to the disappearance, for example, of lines such as the keel and hull lines of the boats (Figure 11), whereas with the y-axis, the masts disappear (Figure 12). Here, fundamental parts of the motifs are disappearing, but similarly, we can also use the algorithm in this way to eliminate overlaps, always cautious of potential losses of relevant information.

The most famous edge detector is the Canny algorithm, which generates a binary image with detected edges, unlike previous methods that merely highlight intensity changes (Canny, 1986). Essentially, Canny is more effective at detecting finer edges and provides control over the outcome. Much like other operators, the first required step is the conversion of the orthophotography to grayscale followed by noise reduction using a 5x5 Gaussian filter. On the smoothed image, the Canny operator is employed for edge detection, with threshold values set at 50 and 100. The `cv2.findContours()` function is then applied to identify contours. We control the process with `cv2.RETR_EXTERNAL` to store only the external contours and `cv2.CHAIN_APPROX_SIMPLE` as the contour approximation method. This culminates in the rendering of detected contours with a 1-pixel thickness on a white background (Figure 13).

The contour detector identifies 3,235 contours in this image based on the specified

Figure 4: Sobel operator for axis x and y.

Figure 5: Sobel operator for axis x.

Figure 6: Sobel operator for axis y.

Figure 7: Scharr operator for axis x and y.

Figure 8: Scharr operator for axis x.

input values. The inclusion of the `cv2.findContours()` function enables the extraction of additional information such as contour area and perimeter. While in our case, where imperfections in the wall register as contours, this feature may not offer significant advantages, it presents a compelling alternative in datasets featuring well-defined motifs and minimal interference. This option offers a faster and automated means of gathering geometric information compared to traditional vectorization programs.

5 Discussion and conclusion

We have observed that substituting direct contact tracing with digital registration methods is not only feasible but preferable in cases like ours, where graffiti extends across large surfaces. In such instances, photogrammetry emerges as the most cost-effective and rapid technique, yielding satisfactory results. In our scenario, when attempting digital tracing of the graffiti in AutoCAD, we encountered some visibility issues, prompting this work to propose their resolution using computational image processing methods. Our objective was to extract the maximum amount of information from photogrammetry files. We have found that utilizing the OpenCV library provides us with control over the parameters of edge detection operators and algorithms. This

Figure 9: Scharr operator for axis y.

Figure 10: Prewitt operator for axis x and y.

flexibility allows us to adjust the parameters individually to the specific requirements of each motif, considering factors such as the depth of incisions, surface deterioration, and overlap of strokes, which vary across the graffiti surfaces. Moreover, this approach could pave the way for the implementation of more complex processes, such as machine learning, in our projects.

As posited by the authors of *The Open Digital Archaeology Textbook* (Graham et al., 2020), we assert that the digitization of archaeology must come with a change in our thinking. As evident from the presented case study, proposing the study of historical graffiti from these perspectives is indeed challenging, and the outcomes are intricately tied to the inherent characteristics of the dataset, mirroring the nuances of the employed techniques. Despite the endorsement of photogrammetry by some as a potential standard in documenting historical graffiti, we find ourselves distant from unified protocols (Valente and Barazzeti, 2020, p.8). Nevertheless, the future trajectory of this discipline hinges on the development and adoption of a standardized digital registration methodology. This, coupled with the principles of open access, would facilitate the creation of knowledge of superior quality, extending its validity beyond specific territories (Hernández-Lorenzo, 2022, pp.144-146); a crucial step given the prevalent regionalism in the study of historical graffiti. As emphasized earlier,

Figure 11: Prewitt operator for axis x.

Figure 12: Prewitt operator for axis y.

prioritizing the establishment of reference corpora becomes imperative. To tackle these challenges, collaborative efforts across disciplines are essential. These partnerships should not only result in the implementation of cutting-edge tools but also in the construction of robust theoretical and methodological frameworks. These frameworks must guide us in using these tools judiciously, ensuring the preservation of information integrity and upholding the quality of the research.

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Figure 13: Canny edge detection.

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Geospatial Discovery in Collections of Text

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Geospatial discovery enables people to search for “hotels nearby,” “museums nearby,” or perform other similar geospatial queries. We extend this concept to collections of text. Our present article comes with a prototype of a geospatial discovery tool for text that facilitates queries such as “news that deals with the area around this museum” and “news that connects the area near the museum with the one near this hotel.” Through these and similar examples, we introduce geospatial discovery in collections of text, discussing its broad relevance. Furthermore, we also demonstrate how geospatial queries in collections of text can be used to formulate metrics for the assessment of cultural connectivity in urban spaces. In particular, we coin the terms “geospatial iso-lex” and “cultural avenues.” They are discussed in more detail in the article.

Keywords: Geospatial Discovery, Geospatial Queries, Text Mining, Libraries Services

1 Geospatial Discovery, Isolexes, and Cultural Avenues

Geospatial discovery is becoming increasingly important (Burrough et al., 2015; Shekhar and Chawla, 2003; Wang and Goodchild, 2018). Many search engines support it. For example, geospatial discovery is used by people to explore where to go shopping, what events are taking place nearby, or where their upcoming vacations could take them. Typical queries include “bars near me,” “events near the Eiffel Tower,” or “hotels in Rome.” Geospatial discovery goes beyond analysis or exploration; it helps people find what they are looking for by supporting geospatial queries and selection.

This present article builds on a series of presentations and preprints in which we have introduced a new idea: Geospatial Discovery in Collections of Text (Baciu, 2019, 2020b,c, 2021b; Baciu and Kajarekar, 2022; Baciu et al., 2023). Our innovation is to expand geospatial discovery to textual data such as news, books, or any other data written in natural language. Note that we are primarily interested in the content of the texts. For example, if a book mentions the “Eiffel Tower” somewhere in the text, we enrich the text with the geolocation of the Eiffel Tower. This information is then used towards geospatial discovery.

To expand geospatial discovery to textual data, we introduce two types of geospatial query: (1) queries for texts that deal with one contiguous search area, e.g., “news that deals with the area near the Eiffel Tower” and (2) queries for texts that deal with multiple independent search areas, e.g., “news that deals both with the area near the Eiffel Tower AND the area near the Louvre.” At DH Benelux 2023, we provided a fully functional prototype of a tool that can perform these queries. Multiple versions are available at Baciú and Kajarekar (2022, 2023a,b).

Our tool responds to the two queries mentioned above by displaying a list of texts that fulfil the search criteria. Additionally, a map is displayed to geographically visualize the search results. This map makes our interface multimodal, by combining text and map. Before our work, many library interfaces were primarily text-based, yet we believe that multimodality is an added quality. Specifically, the geospatial discovery tool that we showed at DH Benelux integrates geospatial queries with string-matching, thematic, and multifaceted queries.

To understand the workings of our tool, it is relevant to grasp the idea that each text that one reads builds not only a thematic but also a geospatial narrative. Together the geospatial narratives of multiple texts connect different parts of the world, often in unexpected ways. Building on this insight, we visualize how texts connect the world, and we use this information to support geospatial discovery with the queries that we have already mentioned. For the first type of query, the map that is returned by our interface shows how texts connect the search area with the rest of the world. For the second type of query, the map shows how texts connect the two search areas with each other and with the rest of the world.

Our **Geospatial Discovery Tool for Textual Data (GDT)** represents an innovation of significant practical value, as illustrated by the following concrete examples:

1. With the geospatial discovery capabilities that we have developed, any library patron can formulate geospatial queries. This capability is crucial, for example, for scholars who believe in the importance of diversifying their research and studying geographical areas that have long been understudied. With a geospatial discovery tool, such scholars can both identify which areas have been understudied (geospatial analysis) and direct their attention towards texts that have dealt with these areas (geospatial discovery).
2. Geospatial discovery is useful to many different groups of both scholars and practitioners. A group of practitioners that benefits from our tool is architects. The work of architects is often dedicated to specific urban areas. With a GDT, architects can now easily find books, news, or social media posts that deal with the area that they are presently working on. Finding and reading this news and other textual data will provide architects with cultural insights that would be difficult to obtain otherwise, and yet are relevant in making design decisions. In this context, see also Kuneva (2024). Our tool makes it easy to design a building not only in response to the built fabric around it, but also considering the soft, cultural dimensions of urban space.
3. GDTs are beneficial not only for scholars and practitioners, but also for the geographers themselves. One task of geography and environmental science is to study how pollution is distributed, see for example Abramova (2023). In this context, the question arises of how environmental awareness responds to pollution. A study of how people lived with pollution and how environmental awareness emerged in response is found in Baciú and Abramova (2020). Such a

study could benefit from a GDT. Through geospatial discovery, geographers gain new capabilities when they explore how social media or news discusses pollution. For example, one can now directly search for news about areas in which the level of contamination peaks, and one can study whether this news accurately reflects the type and degree of contamination present in the environment.

Our idea to expand geospatial discovery to text does not come out of thin air. In traditional library settings, people occasionally used traditional string-matching or thematic searches as a workaround to indirectly perform geospatial discovery. For example, a full-text search for “Paris” returned texts that mentioned this city. Yet, technically speaking, this query is not a geospatial query. When one searched for “Paris” or “Montmartre” through string-matching, one found texts that literally mentioned “Paris” and “Montmartre,” but one did not also find texts that mentioned the “Moulin de la Galette,” although the latter is located in Montmartre, Paris. What was missing was the ability to formulate actual geospatial search criteria, such as “texts that deal with the area I have drawn on the map.” Combined with conventional string-matching and thematic search engines, the advantage of a GDT is that it allows all user groups (students, scholars, researchers, practitioners, consumers, lay audiences, etc.) to perform geospatial queries consciously and directly.

Since we first proposed the idea of a GDT, some libraries have started to implement maps on their websites. We feel that this is a partial success. Nevertheless, the success is not complete. Library websites that show maps still use text metadata for mapping purposes. For example, they tell you where a text was published, and visualize this on a map. However, we feel that it is even more important to (1) provide geospatial discovery capabilities, i.e., let people formulate geospatial queries, (2) provide these discovery capabilities on the content of the texts, not only on metadata; there is a difference between a text that was published in Paris and one that actually discusses Paris, (3) visualize the geospatial narrative of each text towards analysis, exploration, and discovery.

Beyond its practical value, our tool is opening new research directions. Specifically, we hope that our ideas will raise awareness of the importance of the cultural dimensions of urban space. To illustrate this, we have introduced two quantitative measures, which we shall refer to as “geospatial isolex” and “cultural avenue.”

An isolex is the cultural equivalent of an isochrone. The difference is that isochrones are used as a measure for urban mobility, whereas isolexes can serve as a measure for cultural connectivity in urban space. Isochrones and isolexes are computed in the following manner: A 15-minute isochrone from the Eiffel Tower is the answer to the question of how far people can get from the Eiffel Tower by taking all modes of transportation 15 minutes in all directions. By contrast, a 15-sentence isolex from the Eiffel Tower is the answer to the question of how far people can get from the Eiffel Tower by opening all available books at the spot where they mention the Eiffel Tower and reading 15 sentences. Let us define the isolex as the set of geolocations that can be extracted from these sentences. As mentioned, isochrones give information about mobility, whereas isolexes give information about cultural connectivity. Isochrones are about traveling, whereas isolexes are about the places that people can get to virtually, by reading. The GDT that we have developed can automatically compute isolexes.

In principle, isolexes can be defined and visualized in many alternative ways. One can speak of a 15-sentence isolex, as mentioned before. One can also speak of abstract-length isolexes, to give another example. An abstract-length isolex from the Eiffel Tower selects all abstracts that mention the Eiffel Tower and collects all geolocations

that can be extracted from these textual data. It is also possible to define isolexes in terms of time. A 1-minute isolex from the Eiffel Tower would open all books to the spot where they mention the Eiffel Tower, and instead of reading a fixed number of sentences, it reads a fixed amount of time in each book. This approach combines textual and temporal analysis. Perhaps the result would be aptly called an isoclex, combining the Greek words “chronos” for time, as in chronometer or chronograph, with the word “lex” for speaking, as in “lexicon.”

Multiple isolexes can also be combined into a joint query. We have already mentioned that our tool can perform queries of the type “texts that deal with the area near the Eiffel Tower AND the area near the Louvre.” The result of such a query unites two isolexes with an AND operation. An important outcome of this query is that it displays cultural connections between the two areas. We call these connections “cultural avenues.”

Discovering “cultural avenues” in urban space may be of particular importance for urban planners and architects as well as urban activists. Planners, activists, and architects often encounter segregation. As Thomas Schelling has demonstrated, segregation is often undesirable. People do not wish to be segregated, but segregation nevertheless takes place. It can be described as a problem of large-scale coordination in large populations of individuals (Baciu, 2015, 2023; Baciu et al., 2022; Shelling, 1971). Given this problem of large-scale coordination, it is common for planners, activists, and architects to be entrusted with the goal of reducing segregation. Typically, segregation can be reduced by strengthening the physical connections between segregated areas. For example, if there is a street or avenue that connects the two areas, one can help reduce segregation by embellishing and enhancing it. With the tool that we have developed, it is now possible to go beyond the enhancement of streets and avenues. With a mouse click, one can suddenly discover which cultural avenues connect segregated areas. A click may sometimes not even be needed, as the process of discovery can be automated, letting a computer calculate cultural avenues and automatically detect cultural segregation. The same computer can then make suggestions on how to alleviate the segregation it has discovered. The role of the human in this process becomes to evaluate the computer’s automated suggestions. Planners, activists, and architects can thus rely on early-warning systems to discover cultural segregation more easily and strengthen both physical and cultural avenues between segregated areas.

To summarize, we have developed a geospatial discovery tool for text. The tool is of practical value for libraries and people, and it has also led us to formulate new fundamental research concepts. To complement the existing concept of “isochrones,” which is used in urban mobility, we have formulated the concepts of “geospatial isolexes” and “cultural avenues,” which can be used to study cultural connectivity in urban space.

Now just think big! Geospatial discovery for textual data together with the ability to compute isolexes and cultural avenues will open countless new research opportunities. Everything that has been done with isochrones can now also be done with isolexes, and the results that are obtained show a new, cultural perspective on cities.

Cities are not only about hard physical objects such as streets and buildings. Above all, cities are about people and their cultures. Devoid of people, cities are worthless hazard zones. Thus, it is very important to be able to study urban cultures. Our tool and the research concepts that we have developed provide researchers with new capabilities and with a quantitative approach to many soft, cultural questions about urban space.

In the spirit of developing a digital tool of practical utility and explaining theories through practical applications, the rest of this article is written in an object-oriented style. The following sections are structured as follows: First we formulate the problem of geospatial discovery for textual data. Then, we explain our motivation and approach to solving the problem. Third, we demonstrate how the tool works, and we do this based on three concrete examples. Finally, we explain how the tool has led us to formulate the two concepts of “geospatial isoplex” and “cultural avenues,” which we visualize with an additional example. The article concludes with additional technical considerations, a final discussion, and our offer to provide support to implement geospatial discovery for text for any library, company, or interest group that reaches out to us.

To facilitate interactive engagement with our article, we have created a GPT-chatbot in our “Conversing with Science” series. The chatbot can be accessed at <https://doi.org/10.25496/W2301K>

2 Problem statement and solution

If one visits a library with the intention of reading a book or an article, one is rarely asked what areas around the world one is interested in, and even if one comes with a particular geospatial interest, it is very hard to let it flow into library queries. Our point of departure is the desire to change this situation. We provide a geospatial discovery tool for textual data. To support patrons, our tool considers both metadata and the actual written text.

The geospatial discovery tool has, in particular, the following capabilities:

1. It can read text and geolocate the places, institutions, well-known infrastructures, buildings, monuments, and the like, that are mentioned in the text.
2. The geospatial information that is extracted has fine-grained (street-level) resolution. This makes the tool useful for people who wish to study particular areas of cities or landscapes, especially areas that do not have a name, but have easily definable geographical ranges. For example, the “1km square area around the Eiffel Tower” is an area that is easy to draw on a map, but it has no commonly known name.
3. Our tool solves problems of polysemy and homonymy. For example, New York can refer to both the city and the state, which is ambiguous, and it can also be written as NY or NYC, which are homonyms when used to refer to the city. Our solution in this context builds on the outstanding work of Biemann et al. (2007); Cheng and Roth (2013); Mihalcea and Csomai (2007); Pilehvar et al. (2013); Roth et al. (2014); Sil et al. (2018).
4. We provide an interactive, multimodal, online interface that allows people to define geospatial queries, combining geospatial search criteria with a multifaceted search. Typically, library queries are text-based, but we felt motivated to develop a multimodal query that uses text in combination with maps, to make the searching experience more engaging to users.
5. The interface visualizes the geographical selection criteria and the selected texts on the map. Each text is represented as a geospatial narrative—a curved gradient line that passes through all geolocations that can be extracted from the text.

Typically, the end-goal of geospatial discovery is to identify a location such as that of a bar, grocery, supermarket, hotel, or event. In our application, the end-goal is different. The GDT is not looking for a book's physical geolocation and does not help users locate a physical copy of the book. Instead, the tool uses geospatial search criteria to discover textual data that mention entities such as infrastructures, monuments, or institutions that fulfill certain geospatial search criteria. In this sense, the end-goal is not to find a geolocation, but to use geospatial search criteria to find a text.

3 Motivation and approach

Since the early 2010s, libraries have become increasingly digitized. Due to this transition, texts written in books have become increasingly available in digital format. However, libraries have been rather slow in evaluating these digitized texts and using textual analysis to help patrons search for new readings. We pressed changing this situation early on, when few people understood why textual analysis matters. In 2015, we proposed algorithms for libraries to process and analyze their text Baciu (2016). Meanwhile, algorithms similar to the one that we proposed have been implemented in many a library. We would now like to look ahead and make another step forward by proposing to facilitate multimodal searches that unite text with non-textual modes of representation. The present tool unites text and geospatial discovery.

In our continuing work, we have gained extensive experience with geographical information retrieval from text. We have used a supercomputer to process more than 50,000,000 pages of books and periodicals that mention the term "Chicago school" Baciu (2016, 2017, 2018a,b, 2021b). We have also processed roughly 200,000 news items and 1,000,000 social media posts about science and humanities Baciu (2020a); Liu et al. (2022), as well as other material Baciu (2021a); Baciu and Cellucci (2022); Baciu et al. (2023). The information obtained from processing these data was used, for example, to map how the idea of the Chicago school has spread over the world, and how the Humanities and Science are perceived in the United States and abroad. We have developed the present tool in parallel to such research. Previous versions of our tool can be found in our previous articles.

4 How does the tool work?

Most libraries allow patrons to do some kind of multi-faceted search: patrons can narrow their queries by focusing on specific publication years and places, they can specify whether they want to search books or articles, and they can perform full-text queries on the textual content. All of the queries just mentioned are text-based.

What we now introduce is a map. On the map, each book is represented as a gradient line. The first vertex on this line is the publication place of the book. All other vertices are things such as cities, institutions, buildings, or birthplaces of famous people that are mentioned in the text. These latter data are obtained through our method of geographical information retrieval first published in Baciu (2020a).

The main geospatial discovery capability that we provide consists of giving patrons the possibility to narrow down their search based on geospatial criteria. In addition to other criteria they use in their search, they can now specify a geographical search window, and they can use this window to further narrow down their search.

In theory, the geographical search window can have any shape. To make our tool easy to work with but also powerful, we let users create up to two squares. This choice

is arbitrary and easy to change.

To further advance the idea of multimodal searches, our tool can also be applied to allow users to search texts on a timeline that reflects the age of the entities that are mentioned in the text. We shall call this capability “historical discovery in collections of text.” It is also a new idea that we are introducing. An application of this type of analysis and discovery is found in Baciu (2020a)

5 Examples

Figures 1, 2 and 3 illustrate a practical demonstration of our tool, each displaying a distinct collection of texts acquired through previous collaborations. In all figures, our geospatial discovery tool represents each text as a gradient line on the map. We have chosen the colors of the gradient lines as follows: each line starts in white, after which it becomes green, yellow, and red. White is chosen for the publisher location. The gradient from green to red is for the textual content. We represent the content in reading direction. The gradient line is green where the text starts and red where it ends. The longer the text, the more saturated is the red hue. The illustrations demonstrate how geospatial queries are used to narrow search results.

6 New methods and concepts

The geospatial discovery tool that we developed not only empowers people to perform multimodal and geospatial queries; it also opens new research directions. In particular, new research concepts emerge in the study of urbanization and cultural geography. The maps shown in Figure 3 can already help us develop two new concepts.

In Figure 3, when we selected “Chicago” and “Washington DC,” we created two visuals. Actually, these visuals are more than just visuals; they are a type of analysis. Let us explain the value of this analysis by comparing it to another well-known type of analysis — the isochrones analysis.

An isochrone shows how far one can get from a given point in space, given a fixed amount of traveling time, for example, 5 minutes. Imagine someone starts in the geographical center of Chicago. A 5-minute isochrone shows how far one can travel in this amount of time. Of course, one can specify what type of transportation is used for the analysis. One could choose to use private or public transportation or both.

Our analysis performs the equivalent of the isochrones analysis, but with text. The difference is that we are not using a transportation system. Instead, we evaluate how far one can get from the center of Chicago by reading textual data. In the given example in Figure 2, the maximum distance is one page, while in Figure 3, the maximum distance one is reading is an abstract, and one reads each abstract in a corpus of dissertations. Thus the transportation system is replaced, in our example, by a collection of texts. The traveling time is replaced by a distance in text. Other distances for our analysis could be 5 sentences, 5 paragraphs, 1 chapter, etc. Let us call this type of analysis a “geospatial isolex.” We use “iso-” as in isochrone and “lex” as in lexicon. Isolexes of this kind are analyses in the family of isochrones, isotherms, isonomes, or isolines more generally. In Figure 4 we discuss several sample isolexes visualized with our tool.

Now let us attract your attention to Figure 3, below. This figure is also not just a visual but a type of analysis. In the example given in the figure, we query two geographical selection windows at once: “Chicago AND Washington.” Only texts

Figure 1: This figure shows a collection of some 500 news articles written by Ada Louise Huxtable (compiled by staff of the Getty Research Institute in Los Angeles, which holds the Ada Louise Huxtable Papers, 1859–2013, 2013.M.9, <https://www.getty.edu/research/collections/collection/113YNR>). We begin by showing all articles, after which we narrow the search window onto a square area roughly 1 mile around the New York Times building. We also show a zoomed-in detail in New York. Note that the number of articles is diminished as the search is narrowed. Given that our geographic information retrieval method has high resolution, one can choose small geographical search windows, such as shown here. In addition, one can also combine geospatial queries with other conventional text-based queries, and one can select individual records from the table of records. The visuals shown in Figure 1 are interactively available at <https://doi.org/10.25496/W26P4J> Geospatial Discovery Tool for Ada Louise Huxtable’s articles, Baciu and Kajarekar (2023a)

Figure 2: This figure shows a collection of several thousand records that mention Chicago schools of architecture, fiction, theology, art, music, and several other fields. The collection is taken from Baciu (2017). We demonstrate how geospatial discovery works, following the same procedure as in Figure 1. We begin by showing all texts, after which we narrow the search window onto a square area roughly 1 mile around the University of Chicago. We also show a zoomed-in detail in Chicago. Note that the number of texts is diminished as the search is narrowed down. Also, one can hover with the cursor over a line, which identifies the textual record for this particular line, here a line leading to the Robie House, located near the University of Chicago, which has served as center for the area used in the geospatial query. The texts in this collection are much longer than in either the Ada Louise Huxtable or the dissertation corpus, which is why the lines are predominantly red.

Figure 3: This figure shows a collection of art history dissertation abstracts, initially collected and provided by Adams and Lucarelli (2021), and further enhanced by staff of the Getty Research Institute in Los Angeles (Um, 2020; Um and Hagen, 2021). We begin again by showing the mapping results for all texts. The search window is then narrowed, first onto “Chicago,” then onto “Washington DC,” and finally onto both “Chicago AND Washington,” together. The square query areas of roughly 60 miles (as selected by the user) are highlighted in red on the map. This corpus has only abstracts, hence the predominance of white and green, compared to the previous visual that has longer texts. The visuals shown in Figure 3 are interactively available at <https://doi.org/10.25496/W2BC7T> Geospatial Discovery Tool for Art History Dissertation Abstracts, Baciu and Kajarekar (2023b)

Figure 4: Comparison of multiple isolexes. The figure shows four 10-step isolexes, in a corpus about the Chicago school that we created as part of our earlier research Baciu (2017, 2021b). The isolexes all start at University of Chicago and consider the ten following geolocatable entities. As before, the lines start green and end red. The publishers are again drawn in white. The comparison of the two isolexes above shows that texts that mentioned the Chicago School of Architecture have connected the globe more broadly than those that mentioned the Chicago School of Theology. The isolexes below show that the Chicago School overall, supported more cultural connectivity in 1990-2000 than it did in 1950-1960, in the corpus under consideration. A similar analysis can also be performed with social networks, rather than with text, calculating how far one can get through several degrees of friendship (also known as small-world-problem, discussed for example by Watts (1999)). We shall call the analysis through degrees of social networks in geographical space an isonex analysis, to differentiate it from isolexes.

are shown that pass through both windows. What is interesting about this analysis is that it shows cultural connections between the two areas. We shall call this set of connections a “cultural avenue.”

The analysis of cultural avenues may be particularly relevant for reconnecting urban areas that are segregated. Segregation is a common phenomenon in urbanism. Often, it emerges on its own, with detrimental effects for the populations of the segregated areas. Although the majority of the population of segregated areas may collectively favor living without segregation, the process of segregation is hard to stop or reverse without some kind of coordination (Baciu et al., 2022; Shelling, 1971). Architects and urban planners are often entrusted with the task of supporting such coordination. They may try to stop segregation by revitalizing streets and avenues that connect the segregated areas.

A cultural avenue analysis may now provide new ways to reconnect areas. Through cultural avenue analysis, it is possible to identify cultural connections between two areas. Once the connections are known, one can try to strengthen them, as one would do with physical connections, in order to reconnect segregated areas.

Together, isoplexes and cultural avenues are examples of new research concepts that our geospatial discovery tool has inspired. We hope for many more such concepts to come.

7 Implementation for libraries and online services

Let us ask: Should geospatial discovery become a common feature in libraries? We say “Yes!” Compare just how attractive the front pages of “Google Explore” and “Google Things To Do” look compared to “Google Books” or “Google News.” We feel that the latter pages could also provide geospatial discovery (Figure 5).

When presenting the idea of geospatial discovery, we have proceeded in an object-based manner, often talking about libraries and patrons. Yet the geospatial discovery tool presented here may prove most useful when used by companies online. We would like to encourage them to further develop our idea and to contact us to support product development.

We are equally happy to help forward-looking or traditional libraries implement our tool or develop new versions of it. We’ll try to support anyone who contacts us. The requirement is that the textual data are available in digitized format, or that we may contact the data provider to arrange an agreement. In previous work, we have developed safe practices to work with copyrighted data and may not even need access to the data ourselves. For this approach see also Organisciak and Downie (2021).

8 Technical considerations

To create a tool for geospatial discovery in collections of text, as we propose, the following components are necessary:

1. Access to a collection of text.
2. Geocoding, to provide geolocations for entities that are mentioned in the text.
3. Storage of the processed data or parts thereof.
4. An algorithm or machine that can perform queries.

Figure 5: Comparison of the front pages of Google Explore, Google Things to do, and Google Books. The first two make excellent use of geospatial discovery. We would like to suggest and support the implementation of geospatial discovery for books and news, too.

5. An interactive interface that lets users formulate queries and receive the results from their queries.
6. Or, instead of this interface, a tool that can formulate the queries on behalf of a user and let the query results serve the user with or without an interface. (For example an AI chatbot can execute geospatial discovery on behalf of a user, or a search for “Culture near me” could display not only cultural venues but also cultural news articles on the map, even when a query for news has not been consciously formulated.)

The prototype that we have developed performs geocoding through Natural Language Processing with enhanced use of geodata from a large knowledge base (Wikipedia). The accuracy of the Natural Language Processing tasks is discussed by Roth et al. (2014); Tsai et al. (2016). Given this setup, old place names and institution names are considered, as are alternative names or abbreviations. We pioneered this approach in Baciú (2020a). The Natural Language Processing identifies named entities based on both the name that is mentioned in the text (surface shape), and the context in which this name is mentioned. It is also possible to do the geocoding with standard methods of geographic information retrieval, relying solely on gazetteers, without Natural Language Processing, or to combine both types of methods.

If the geocoding accuracy achieved on a corpus is not sufficient (for example, because the text quality is low), we recommend considering whether it helps display items only if they have more than one entity located in the query window. This leads to an increase in accuracy. For example, if the code has a 0.1 error rate for each geocoded item, the probability that two items are both inaccurately geocoded, independently, is $0.1 \times 0.1 = 0.01$. Thus, if one lists query results by their relevance for the selected area, the first results are overall correct even if the geocoding accuracy is low due to poor text quality.

From a technical perspective, we expect that future GDT implementations will be available on much larger datasets. In addition, an interesting area of future research will be the application of continual and multilingual learning, as discussed in Praharaj and Matveeva (2023), to keep the code behind geospatial discovery up-to-date and multicultural.

9 Definitions

Our article introduces the idea of geospatial discovery for textual data, and it suggests two quantitative measures for urban connectivity. To facilitate communication about these measures, we suggest using the terms with the meaning listed below.

Geospatial discovery: We use here the term “geospatial” because we let users formulate geospatial queries with geospatial search criteria such as geospatial distances from a given location in geographical space. We use the term “discovery” because, through the queries, users can discover the material. This goes beyond analysis or exploration. An example of geospatial discovery is to support users to search and select bars near the Eiffel Tower. Geospatial exploration and analysis differ from geospatial discovery. Compared to geospatial discovery, geospatial exploration does not need to let users perform queries and selection. Geospatial exploration is performed on any map that visualizes geospatial information for users to explore. Geospatial exploration becomes geospatial discovery when geospatial queries are introduced. Geospatial analysis, on the other hand, is about analyzing, not discovering. An example of

geospatial analysis is the question how many of the bars near the Eiffel Tower provide access to the internet, and whether the geospatial distribution of these bars reflects knowledge of designers that the Eiffel Tower has long served as an antenna. Like geospatial exploration, geospatial analysis is not focused on geospatial queries and selection.

Geospatial discovery for textual data: We speak of geospatial discovery for textual data when geospatial discovery is facilitated for textual data. Geospatial discovery for textual data should not stop at providing information about where a physical copy of a book is located or where the book was published. Instead, geospatial discovery for textual data should support users in finding texts that have been written about user-defined, geographical areas of interest. A text that says "There was a celebration near the Eiffel Tower" is a text about the Eiffel Tower. The author may be located in New York and the text may have been published in the San Francisco Bay Area. At the same time, the text is about an entity located in France.

Geospatial isoplex: Given a collection of textual data, given a certain area of departure (for example a circular area of 500 meters around the Eiffel Tower), and given a textual distance (for example 10 sentences), an isoplex answers to the question how far one can get from the area of departure by mining the collection of textual data for items that are located in the area of departure, reading the given textual distance in the texts, and collecting the geocodes of all entities found in these textual data. Technically, an isoplex is a set of connected points and/or polygons. It is easy to see that these points can be represented as a network, as points, or, using a scale of analysis, as a density map, or, analyzing equal density zones in the density map, the same data can be represented with isolines. We call the analysis an isoplex independent of how it is visualized. Let us suggest terminology with respect to the various types of visualization: We suggest to use the terms "geospatial isoplex network" when visualizing the network with points and lines, as we have done it in this article, "geospatial isoplex density map" when visualizing the same data as a density map, "geospatial isoplex heat map" when visualizing the data as heat maps, etc. We suggest "geospatial isograph" for an isoplex used to visualize isoplex data. Please feel free to shorten these terms when using them.

Isoplex: An isoplex defined by measuring reading distance in time (for example, a 1 min. isoplex). The term is derived from uniting isochrone and isoplex.

Isonex: An analysis of geospatial connectivity through degrees of connection in social or other networks. As the isoplex, an isonex is a set of connected points. It can be represented as a network, as points, as a density map, or with isolines.

Cultural avenue: Given a collection of textual data, and given multiple geographical areas, a cultural avenue is a set of textual connections between the two areas. Cultural avenues are a special case of isoplex analysis. Cultural avenues can be represented as a network, as points, and therefore also as a density map, or with isolines.

Social avenue: The equivalent of a cultural avenue, but calculated on a social network, rather than through textual data. It can be represented as a network, as points, as a density map, or with isolines.

Geospatial isograph: We suggest to use this term for the isolines used to represent isoplexes or isothemes. We derive the term from "iso-" and "-graph," with the latter as in the Greek word for writing.

Isotheme: Given a collection of textual data, given a theme or topic (for example, textual fragments about physical science in this collection, or words pertaining to a topic of discourse), and given a particular geospatial scale of analysis, an isotheme is the equivalent of an ecological isonome, it is any line along which the topic is

covered at roughly constant density. We derive the term from “iso-“ and “-theme,” with the latter as in the Greek word for subject or theme. Examples of isotheme analyses visualized as heat maps or as networks are found in Baciu (2020a); Baciu et al. (2022). Specifically, we have shown that most topics in the public discourse have distinct geospatial footprints or isothemes, representable as networks, heatmaps, density maps, or with geospatial isographs; examples are found in Baciu (2020a).

Historical discovery for textual data: This is the equivalent of geospatial discovery for textual data, but instead of formulating geospatial search criteria, one formulates historical search criteria. Examples for a historical query is “texts that have dealt with the period 1830-1869” or “texts that have dealt with entities that are have been created in the period 1830-1869” or “texts that have primarily dealt with entities in one of the years 1830-1889.” Our geospatial discovery tool facilitates this type of discovery.

10 Conclusion

We have developed a geospatial discovery tool for textual data. Library patrons can now find their readings in a multimodal way using text and maps. We believe that this practical advancement is significant, changing how people do science and how they read in a globalized world. Geographic information that previously remained hidden in the text is now visible on maps, which can help readers more easily direct their attention to geographical areas of their choice.

The tool that we have developed can be applied in standard library settings as much as it is relevant online or for chatbots. News and social media platforms as well as AI application providers could use our tool or self-made GDTs either for similar purposes as libraries or integrated in automated recommendation systems. Furthermore, our tool (or derivate versions of our idea) can be used for geospatial discovery for text in any imaginable setting as well as in languages other than English.

As many people desire, it is now possible to actively direct research efforts and public attention to areas around the world that are understudied or receive insufficient public attention. This capability changes an entire perspective towards human cultural production and its geospatial discoverability. In addition, we believe that the new tool will also lead researchers to work with new concepts such as geospatial isolexes and cultural avenues to reconnect segregated areas and support mutual understanding among people who live in different geographical areas.

11 Summary

If you are planning to travel around the world and are searching for potential hotels to stay at, you can often expect that the search engine that you may use asks you about your destination right away, only later continuing to other travel details such as arrival and departure dates. Even before those latter questions are answered, you are presented with hotel options, and you get very quickly accustomed to comparing your options on a map. The map thus becomes a tool for geospatial discovery. A different situation is encountered if you want to read books from around the world. Unlike the tourism industry, libraries have not yet implemented geospatial discovery. In this article, we introduce a first tool for geospatial discovery for textual data. Our tool reads and interprets textual data, maps it, and helps you find your books on the map. If you search books about, say, a particular area of San Francisco, our tool can help you find books in which well-known buildings, institutions, and inhabitants have been

mentioned that have a tie to this area. In a globalized world, we hope that geospatial discovery for text will support a new consciousness for the geospatial dimensions of cultures. At DHB2023, our audience was encouraged to test the tool during our presentation held in the Royal Library of Belgium, Brussels, Belgium, June 2, 2023 (Baciu and Kajarekar, 2022)).

Besides introducing new geospatial discovery capabilities, our tool also opens new research paths in urban and cultural geography. We hope that our quantitative measures for cultural connectivity will lead to new discoveries and geospatial concepts, especially among researchers who have been working in the field independently. Interesting examples of recent and ongoing work that have reached us through peer reviewers are Bodenhamer et al. (2013); Meijers and Peris (2019); Tongjing et al. (2023). There could be much more awareness of the cultural dimensions of the built and natural environments.

12 Contributions

Dan C. Baciu: first author. Sunit Kajarekar: equally contributing author, programmed the interface. Anna Abramova: support at revision stage. The support of the Getty Research Institute in Los Angeles and its staff during project development is thankfully acknowledged.

13 Acknowledgments

Dan C. Baciu would like to acknowledge funding received from Architektur Studio Bellerive, Bern, Switzerland and the Getty Reserach InSTITUTE, Los Angeles, CA, USA, for early stages of tool development.

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Is this a Mash-Up or a Template? Towards a Typology for Literary Bots

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This paper introduces the LabEL literary bot typology, which was developed empirically from 588 literary bot accounts on Twitter. The typology features eight categories that capture various aspects of bot procedural-ity. It abstracts the processes reliant on specific files, resources, tools, and scripts into stable elements. The typology is introduced with a contextual overview of the Twitter platform, since bots’ formal elements are influenced by their technosocial environment. We provide several case studies to illustrate the practical application of this typology, showcasing its strengths and limitations. Finally, we briefly explore potential applications for studying and preserving literary bots. In addition to offering tools for analysing literary bots individually, within collections, or alongside other types of generative electronic literature, the typology also aids in preserving a fragmented memory of this form and contextualising it within the broader landscape of digital literary art.

Keywords: Digital Literature, Literary Bots, Typology, Twitter, Twitterature

1 Introduction

Since the early days of computing, technical innovations have prompted literary experiments. From Christopher Strachey’s 1953 automatically generated love letters to poems written by ChatGPT, a history of digital literature would include all major advances in computing and Natural Language Processing. The development of hypertext technology, the World Wide Web and probability-based language models, to name a few, have all played a major role in the multifaceted history of digital literature. The combination of strict constraints and possibilities to transcend norms imposed by print media has provided a fertile ground for writers to innovate.

With the democratisation of informatics, especially the apparition of content publishing platforms in the late 1990s, digital literature has become increasingly accessible to laypersons. Since then, specialist knowledge is no longer a prerequisite to creatively engage with digital technologies. Although literary creation online still requires a degree of material and societal privilege, the advent of social media platforms has

further lowered the barrier to entry and led to the emergence of countless literary voices online.

Twitter is one such corner of the internet which has been quietly conquered by professional and amateur writers alike. The character limit becomes a structural constraint akin to a modern-day versification while the affordances of hashtags, threads, tags, bots, community access and a massive mode of distribution can be harnessed for aesthetic and conceptual innovations.¹ More than these new constraints and affordances, the specific context of a social media platform such as Twitter drastically alters the literary and publishing paradigms found in other contexts.

Literary bots, in particular, have been a popular literary form on Twitter due to the possibilities afforded by the API and services such as *Cheap Bot, Done Quick!* which allowed users to create bots without coding skills or an API account. A Twitter bot is a Twitter account which posts automatically, in reaction to other tweets or on a schedule. Misinformation and propaganda bots have received the most attention, but Twitter bots have been created with a wide range of objectives, including art, literature, activism and entertainment (Ortega, 2020). Like all literature on Twitter, literary bots belong to the third wave of electronic literature, as defined in Flores (2021b). This third wave is characterised by the use of digital platforms (i.e. content creation platforms, social media platforms and digital writing platforms), where aesthetic innovations are often replaced with "remixes" of existing content (Flores, 2021b). In contrast, digital works belonging to the first and second generations tend to prioritise formal and aesthetic experiments. This preoccupation is often contextualised within the literary and artistic traditions of avant-garde movements such as dadaism, surrealism and Oulipo. Nevertheless, literary Twitter bots tend to be more connected to the traditions of these avant-gardes than most other forms belonging to this third wave, to the point that it could be argued that they create a bridge between them.

The study of *Twitterature*, whether it is automatically generated or not, has been hindered by the difficulty of identifying and collecting literary tweets on a large scale. The research presented here is part of a larger initiative aiming to (semi-)automatically identify and label literary tweets in existing Twitter archives such as the general Twitter Stream grabbed by the Archive Team, which contains 6.7 TB of Twitter data streamed from 2012 to 2021.² This project would allow for the creation of a literary Twitter archive and, as a consequence, the emergence of more systematic studies of *Twitterature*. With the change in leadership and API solutions proposed, the future of literature on Twitter in general, and bots in particular, is uncertain. As the community started developing in other platforms, such as Mastodon, it is a good time to look back at the history of this form.

This paper introduces the LABEL literary bot typology, which was developed empirically from a corpus of 588 literary Twitter bot accounts.³ The outline of the typology is prefaced by a contextual overview of the Twitter platform and existing typologies. We then present a few case studies to demonstrate how this typology applies to practical cases and showcase its strength as well as its limitations. Finally, we briefly discuss possible applications in the context of the study and preservation of literary bots.

¹ Although Twitter was rebranded as "X" in July 2023, we have opted to use "Twitter" throughout this paper since it was the name in use during most of the relevant time period.

² URL: <https://archive.org/details/twitterstream>

³ This research was developed in the context of LABEL (Laboratory for Electronic Literature), a collaborative research project at KBR (Royal Library of Belgium) and UCLouvain dedicated to digital literature.

2 Twitter and Twitter bots: a retrospective

Although the purpose of this article is not to analyse a corpus of literary Twitter bots, but to introduce the typology which emerged from it, we incidentally provide an overview of this highly media-specific form. Therefore, in what is likely to become a retrospective, this article is also an opportunity to offer preliminary reflections on the characteristics of literary Twitter bots, within their "technosocial context" (Marino, 2020). It is evident that the history of literary bots is intertwined with the history of the platform itself. The following overview focuses on the ways in which changes in the platform's leaderships and user base influenced the development of literary Twitter bots. Because Twitter is not primarily a literary platform and became a stage for high-stake political and ideological struggles, the increasing hostility of the Twitter environment for literary bots can be read as a collateral damage in a fight against disinformation and political propaganda. However, the reality is more complex, since the history of the platform is also intertwined with a struggle for profit and influence emanating from its leadership, where the disregard for not-for-profit, small-scale third-party initiatives should also be read politically.

2.1 The creation of a network

Twitter was created by Jack Dorsey, Biz Stone, and Evan Williams and launched in July 2006. It initially aimed to be a lightweight microblogging service that allowed users to share updates within a 140-character limit. It was imagined as a means to revolutionise communication on an interpersonal level. Twitter's initial concept revolved around a "status" service concept accessible via a website and via SMS in the United States. The character limit imposed by SMS constraints fostered creativity in crafting succinct messages and encouraged immediate interactions on the platform (Burgess and Baym, 2020). The minimalist interface and only guideline ("What's your status?") did not provide much clarity in the way it was to be used. In the words of Burgess and Baym: "Twitter's ambiguity almost demanded that its users develop their own ideas about what to do with it" (p. 7).

In its early days, public opinion was instrumental in shaping the platform. Features such as @ mentions, hashtags and retweets were suggested by users and incorporated in 2006 and 2007. If the implementation of such requests demonstrated an acknowledgment of the users' needs, it often resulted in new issues. For instance, the use of the hashtags to create trending topics became problematic, as users were encouraged to use the feature maliciously, to disseminate spam or engage in propaganda (Burgess and Baym, 2020).

2.2 From social network to (dis)information outlet

Twitter has undergone a significant evolution from a startup to a key player in the social media landscape. This evolution is the result of the multiple changes in governance, among other factors (Chang et al., 2023; Novoa et al., 2022). In 2009, Evan Williams, one of the founders and CEOs, declared: "Twitter is not a social network, it's an information network" (Burgess and Baym, 2020, p. 13). At this time, the platform's prompt changed from "What are you doing?" to "What's happening?". Williams took part in the construction of a world-centred, public and news-oriented Twitter (Burgess and Baym, 2020). The platform started to be used as an information channel, and its unique position at the intersection between a social network and a news

platform transformed it into a major stage of political activism, news dissemination, and international relations. For instance, Twitter was used extensively by Barack Obama during the 2008 presidential campaign. Since this particular event, such practices blending politics and social networks have become common place (Evans et al., 2014).

Its growing role in breaking news and its open door to citizen journalism have also led Twitter to become a “vector for disinformation”. The microblogging service is particularly susceptible to these assaults because of the casual form of the exchanges and asymmetrical structure of the network’s nodes: following a user does not grant any reciprocal effect, and the information flows only from the followed account to the follower. In addition, Twitter provides an opportunity for organisations that would otherwise not have had the resources to conduct (dis)information campaigns (Chamberlain, 2010).

Twitter bots, in particular, have played a major role in several key disinformation campaigns such as the 2016 elections in Europe and the US (Schiffrin, 2017) or post-truth spreading in Mexico with the “Peñabots” posting pro-Enrique Peña Nieto propaganda (Velasquez, 2019). More recently, during the COVID-19 pandemic, the company was forced to expand its policy against malicious uses of the platform, and its automated moderation tools have challenged over 1.5 million accounts for spam or manipulative behaviour in COVID-19 discussions (Singh and Blase, 2020). This aspect of the platform has brought negative press over the years and pushed the network to take measures aiming at limiting this phenomenon, notably by repeatedly updating their API permissions and content moderation policies.

2.3 Literary Twitter bots in the face of API changes, automated content moderation and Elon Musk

From 2008, to counter misinformation, but also to maintain a coherent brand image and protect users’ data, Twitter made iterative changes to its Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) and development policies. The company bought third-party applications deemed fit for incorporation, such as their search engine, from a company named Summize in 2008, and blocked others through API modifications. This strategy impacted mobile app developers and many of the services and tools initially developed independently from Twitter, such as URL shortening services and image-sharing applications. Towards 2010 and 2011, Twitter definitely turned away from “open innovation”, and marched toward a centralised and advertising-driven paradigm. From 2010, as the APIs matured, more restrictions were introduced, affecting third-party platforms such as Google, YouTube and Facebook (Burgess and Baym, 2020; Jünger, 2021).

Three types of access restriction were progressively incorporated into Twitter’s APIs. The first consisted in the introduction of open authorisation for API access (OAuth), requiring all requests to be authorised, marking a departure from the previous more open access policy. This first measure caused many developers to struggle with its implementation as well as the changes in user experience that came with it. This event is known on Twitter as the “#oauthcalypse”. The second mandated that third-party apps on mobile and entertainment devices, especially those with more than 100,000 users, undergo app reviews before they could operate in production mode, effectively limiting the development of new clients without Twitter’s collaboration. The third included the imposition of rate limits on all API endpoints, limiting the amount of data that could be requested within specific sliding time frames. These changes made access more complex and generated some negative reactions within the ecosystem,

shaping the foundation of Twitter's API as it stands today (Jünger, 2021; van der Mersch, 2016). The community of bots and apps thriving on Twitter before this shift was decimated by these changes, since users which were not in capacity to adapt to updates were disabled. As a result, only very few literary and artistic bots created before 2010 continued to operate (Flores, 2021a).

Following Elon Musk's acquisition of Twitter for 44 billion dollars in October 2022, drastic changes to the APIs have been implemented. At the time of writing, a year after the change in leadership, four different tiers are offered, as per the documentation published on the Twitter developer platform. The free tier allows 1,500 tweets to be posted per month, but does not allow any tweets to be read. The basic tier, priced as \$100/month, offers the option of posting 3,000 tweets per month, with a 10,000 tweets read limit. The pro tier, priced at \$5,000/month, offers a 300,000 tweets posting limit and a 1 million tweets reading limit. In addition, the pro tier offers access to the Filtered stream API, full-archive search, and the Ads API. Finally, the enterprise tier starts at \$42,000 per month and offers custom commercial-level access. Although some literary bots could technically operate using the free tier, those that use Twitter as their source would need the pro tier to function.⁴ Importantly, along with countless third-party applications, tools like *Cheap Bot*, *Done Quick!* which allowed users to create bots without coding skills and a Twitter developer account can no longer afford to operate after this latest change. On the 6th of April 2023, when the service closed down, a large portion of literary and artistic bots stopped posting.

In addition to API changes, automated content moderation is another long-standing enemy of literary bots. Around 2020, Twitter estimated that roughly 5% of its accounts were spam bots. The platform permits automated bots if they do not violate their terms. However, the company disclosed that it removed approximately one million spam bot accounts daily and temporarily locked millions more each week until their operators pass anti-spam tests. Over the years, Twitter increasingly relied on automated and machine learning content moderation tools, acknowledging that this may lead to moderation errors, including mistakenly suspending legitimate accounts, as the platform seeks to combat disinformation and malicious bots (Arroyo-Machado et al., 2023; Singh and Blase, 2020). The fight against spam bots has allegedly become more virulent under Musk, who has claimed that their prevalence reached 33% of users (Arroyo-Machado et al., 2023).⁵

Finally, the figure of Elon Musk has also contributed to driving literary and artistic bots away from the platform. When Musk bought Twitter, an unusual spike in accounts deactivation was noted (Chang et al., 2023). One of the automated tools tracking "inauthentic behaviour" on Twitter, *Bot Sentinel*, reported the deactivation of around 877,000 accounts and a further suspension of 497,000 accounts between October 27th and November 1st, 2022. These numbers hint at a 208% increase in account losses in the days after Musk purchased the company. Two factors are considered to be a possible explanation for these numbers. First, the deliberate account deletion could be the result of a movement of protest from the users, unhappy with the platform's integrity values with Musk at its head. Secondly, the raise in automated suspension of accounts could be the consequences of voluntary violations of Twitter's rules as a mean to test the new regulations under Musk's leadership (Stokel-Walker, 2022).

⁴ The academic API, which allowed researchers to harvest up to 10 million tweets per month is now defunct and no other solution has been offered to date.

⁵ Previous studies suggest different estimates, between 3% and 15% (Chavoshi et al., 2016; Varol et al., 2017).

Several literary bot accounts have posted that they were moving to Mastodon, an open-source self-hosting micro-blogging platform, following Musk's acquisition and prior to the API changes. Between users who saw their account being suspended as they were violating the updated Twitter rules, and those who cannot continue to operate using the free API, Twitter appears to be a hostile environment for literary bots, as well as many other niches of users. The exodus towards Mastodon is supported by the development of new tools. The farewell message on the website of *Cheap Bot, Done Quick!* mentions *Cheap Bots, Toot Sweet!* a new service operating using the same syntax on Mastodon, as a solution to move bots to the alternative micro-blogging platform. Alternatively, actions to "rescue" Twitter literary bots are also undertaken. For instance Flores produced standalone web versions of some of his Twitter bots, previously powered by *Cheap Bot, Done Quick!* (Flores, 2023). The current inhospitality of "X" suggests that the era of Twitter bots as we once knew them has ended. Nonetheless, their legacy lives on on other platforms and through archival projects.

3 Existing typologies for Twitter bots

Literature on literary Twitter bots is scarce. Flores, notably through his "I love e-poetry" blog is the leading scholarly voice on this topic.⁶ In a book chapter dedicated to this form, Flores (2021a) proposed the list of nine bot subgenres quoted below:

- Chatterbots are interactive characters.
- Open/Green bots search through endless data sources and act upon the results to produce their output.
- Closed bots work their way through a finite corpus.
- Ebooks bots publish random samples from a static or dynamic corpus.
- Markov bots generate texts based on a probabilistic analysis of a textual corpus of static or streaming data
- Template bots generate texts by filling in blanks in phrases or sentences.
- Mashup bots combine work from different sources.
- Emoji bots assemble pictorial art and narratives from emoji (small images that act as ideas and are deployed as textual objects).
- Pseudo bots involve partial generation with human curation, or human bot-like performances.

In this typology, Flores focuses on the primary feature of the bot, while acknowledging that the list is not exhaustive and that many of the bots have characteristics of several subgenres (Flores, 2021a). Our own typology builds on Flores' and attempts to isolate different features of the bots (the type of source, the treatment of the source, the interactivity, the variation, etc.) in order to document the full spectrum of bots and avoid reducing them to one of their features.

⁶ URL: <http://iloveeepoetry.org/>

Figure 1: Twitter bot typology by Tully Hansen.

Hansen (2013) proposed another typology which divides bots into two main classes: those which are independent of Twitter inputs, and those which operate in response to Twitter inputs (see fig. 1).⁷ Within those two classes, Hansen proposes subclasses which describe the behaviour of the bots. Although this division is highly relevant in the case of Twitter bots, the binary classification suggests that those two classes exhibit a different set of behaviours. However, there is a large overlap. In addition, bots which rely on another open source accessed through an API are not taken into consideration. This typology illustrates that privileging one of the bot features (here, whether it reacts to Twitter data) over others (e.g. the ways in which it parses input) can be useful to make a specific reading of a set of bots, but also reduces the efficiency and versatility of the typology. To allow for a greater granularity in comparison to Flores' and and greater versatility in comparison to Hansen's, our typology combines multiple categories.

4 The LABEL literary bot typology

By nature, bots can be dissected into a series of formalised steps revolving around three axes: the input (Twitter, other online sources, static texts/data or a combination of the three), the process (ranging from selecting one line from a file at random to a complex algorithm taking several sources as input), and the output (the tweet). The eight fields/categories of this typology describe elements from these three axes. "Source number" and "source type" describe the input ; "procedure", "script number", and "generation axis" describe the process ; and "interactivity", "lexical constancy" and "syntactic equivalence" describe the output. Although each category has a limited number of classes (in fact, six of them are binary classes), they can be combined in many ways. If all combinations were possible—which is not quite the case—we would arrive at 1,024 combinations. Because of this modularity, the typology captures both

⁷ This figure was posted by Hansen on imgur. URL: <https://imgur.com/bKXNQ0V>

the similarities and the differences between bots. Within a collection of bots, we are able to quantify the rarest combination of classes, the most popular, and everything in between, as well as identify the area where any two bots—or groups of bots belonging to the same set of classes—converge or diverge.

Procedure	Source number	Source type	Script number	Interactivity	Lexical constancy	Syntactic equivalence	Generation axis
Quote	Single	Open	Single	Yes	Yes	Yes	Syntactic
Transformation	Multiple	Closed	Multiple	No	No	No	Lexical
Template							Semantic
Algorithm							Metric
							Intertextual
							Statistical
							Orthographic
							Graphic

Table 1: The LABEL literary bot typology

Although only one label per category would usually apply to each bot, potential exceptions are highlighted when relevant. As mentioned in the introduction, this typology focuses on the formal elements of bots. Therefore, using this typology encourages the annotator to trace back the processes which allow the bot to function. In essence, without having access to the code, the annotator infers parts of its structure.

4.1 Procedure

- Quote: The bot quotes existing material *verbatim*.
- Transformation: The bot quotes existing material after operating a transformation.
- Template: The bot generates tweets according to a template. This can be by filling in blanks in an existing phrase or sentence, or generating entire tweets by concatenating a sequence of phrases and/or words according to a pre-established structure. These phrases/words are generally selected at random from a list.
- Algorithm: The bot generates tweets following an algorithmic procedure which is not captured by the three previous procedures. In practice, algorithm bots tend to be more complex, as the generation procedure involves probabilistic or machine learning processes.

4.2 Source number

- Single: The bot relies on one source.
- Multiple: The bot relies on multiple sources.

4.3 Source type

- Open: The source is an open corpus. The most popular open corpus is Twitter itself, but some bots crawl other areas of the Web.
- Closed: The source is finite. This can be a closed corpus (e.g. the complete works of Shakespeare), or a lexical resource (e.g. a list of all adverbs in the English language, or a list of sci-fi film titles).

If the bot relies on both open and closed sources, it can be labelled with both classes. Alternatively, a "mixed" label can be introduced.

4.4 Script number

- Single: All tweets from the bot account are generated according to the same formula, or script.
- Multiple: All tweets from the account are not generated according to the same formula. This is often the case for template bots, for instance, where tweets are sometimes generated according to dozens of different templates. We consider that a bot uses different scripts where the first step in the generation process appears to be choosing between several procedures.

It would be possible for a bot to have different scripts whose characteristics would be different. For instance, we can imagine that a template bot could use one script with a lexical constant and one without (see 4.6). More drastically, a bot could have different scripts which would generate texts according to completely distinct procedures (e.g. a quote and a probabilistic model). Those cases are rare since the interest of the bot is often tied to the single concept it relies on. If needed, we could imagine that scripts could be annotated, instead of bots, or that multiple labels would be used to annotate such accounts.

4.5 Interactivity

- Yes: The bot performs retweets, tweets in answer to other tweets or tags other accounts.
- No: The bot does not directly interact with other tweets or Twitter accounts.

4.6 Lexical constancy

- Yes: All tweets issued by the same script share at least one lexical constant (i.e. they share at least one token).
- No: All tweets issued by the same script do not share a lexical constant.

4.7 Syntactic equivalence

- Yes: All tweets issued by the same script share one syntactic structure. We do not consider quoted elements which do not alter the sentence structure to assess syntactic equivalence. If a script includes film or book titles within the structure of the sentence, for instance, we will consider that the syntactic equivalence is preserved even if the titles have different syntactic structures. We also choose to consider omissions as valid options. For instance, if all tweets have the same syntactic structure, but some omit an adverb, we still consider that they are syntactically equivalent.
- No: All tweets issued by the same script do not share one syntactic structure.

4.8 Generation axis

The generation axis describes the linguistic focus of the text generation procedure.

- **Metric:** The generation revolves around metric. This label is typically used for transformation bots which work their way through a corpus to find tweets or sentences which can be reworked according to a specific meter, such as a haiku.
- **Syntactic:** Tweets are generated following syntactic constraints. For instance, this label is used for template bots which rely on syntactic categories to create syntactically sound sentences.
- **Intertextual:** Intertextuality is the driving force of the bot. One could argue that all literary Twitter bots are intertextual, as they often repeat patterns and structures linked to literary and artistic traditions. However, we use this label for bots which explicitly showcase traces of one or several specific authors or works.
- **Lexical:** The bot acts or relies on lexical elements. For instance, this label would apply to a transformation or quote bots which acts on tweets or sentences which contain a specific word.
- **Semantic:** Semantic relations are at the center of the generation process. This label would describe a template which uses the semantic relations of a resource like WordNet, or lists of semantically related phrases (e.g. film titles, list of colours)
- **Statistical:** The bot uses count-based information to generate text. This label could be used for a bot generating tweets based on the probabilistic analysis of an existing corpus.
- **Graphic:** The visual element of writing influences the text generation procedure. This label is used when tweets create specific shapes or takes into account visual elements such a word length.
- **Orthographic:** The process(es) enacted by the bot rely on spelling.

A bot can work around several linguistic axes. For instance, a bot which generates texts following probabilistic distributions of Shakespeare's plays is both statistical and intertextual. Similarly, a bot which tweets lines from Shakespeare's play if they follow a specific syntactic structure or contain a specific token is intertextual, but also syntactic or lexical, respectively.

5 Case studies

In this section, we illustrate how the typology applies to a few representative examples of literary Twitter bots (see Table 2). Through these examples, both the strengths and limitations of the typology become evident. On the one hand, the combination of the different categories allows us to account for a wide variety of configurations. On the other hand, reducing the complexity of all literary bots to a small number of labels remains illusory, as illustrated by cases which defy this categorisation. In addition, the case studies provide an overview of the main procedural mechanisms at play in literary Twitter bots

User name	Procedure	Source number	Source type	Script number	Interactivity	Lexical constancy	Syntactic equivalence	Generation axis
@mybestdayever	Quote	Single	Open	Single	No	Yes	No	Lexical
@carsonbot	Quote	Single	Closed	Single	No	No	No	Intertextual
@accidental575	Transformation	Single	Open	Single	Yes	Yes	No	Intertextual
@BigramPoetry	Transformation	Single	Open	Single	No	Yes	No	Lexical/Metric
@regrettoegret	Transformation	Single	Open	Single	No	Yes	No	Lexical
@SubstitutionBot	Transformation	Single	Open	Single	No	No	No	Lexical
@gutenboy2bot	Transformation	Single	Closed	Single	No	Yes	No	Lexical
@SpellerBot	Template	Single	Closed	Single	No	Yes	Yes	Orthographic
@is_like_a	Template	Single	Closed	Single	No	Yes	Yes	Lexical/Semantic
@IsItArtBot	Template	Single	Closed	Multiple	No	Yes	Yes	Syntactic
@WhitmanFML	Template	Multiple	Open/Closed	Single	No	No	No	Intertextual
@SnowballPoetry	Algorithm	Single	Closed	Single	No	No	No	(Ortho)graphic
@a2b_bot	Algorithm	Single	Closed	Single	No	No	Yes	Semantic
@AutoImagist	Algorithm	Single	Closed	Single	No	No	No	Graphic

Table 2: Labelled case studies

5.1 Quote bots

@mybestdayever crawls Twitter for tweets including the phrase "best day ever" and copies them in a new tweet. It has a single open source (Twitter) and its generation axis is lexical. @carsonbot tweets a quote from the Canadian poet and essayist Anne Carson every two hours. Its source is a single closed corpus (Anne Carson's work) and its generation axis is intertextual. Although they are characterised by the same overarching procedure, since they both quote existing text *verbatim*, these two quote bots adopt radically different creative processes. One relies on an open corpus and the other on a closed one. One relies on a lexical condition, which leads to the presence of a lexical constant between all tweets, and the other tweets sentences at random, as long as they belong to the chosen corpus. This modular typology allows for these nuances to be captured while acknowledging the commonalities between the two bots.

Quote bots, by definition, have a single source per tweet. If two *verbatim* quotes are combined, we are facing a type of template, since the modality of the combination has to be defined. We could imagine a bot which quotes randomly from one source or from another. Whether we would consider them to be multiple sources or multiple scripts is subject to debate, since we do not have access to the source code and files. This is a recurrent issue in this exercise. Often, the same outcome could have been achieved with different procedures. On the one hand, in digital literature, and especially in literary text generation, where the materiality of the creation process is central, the implications of these nuances can be key to read the creative impulse of the bot. On the other hand, the relative opacity of some Twitter bots is also part of their creative identity. When the creation process is not fully transparent, the ambiguity of the account forces the reader to pause and consider the purpose and effect of the generated text, thereby emphasising a defamiliarisation effect at play when literary content is published on social media platforms.

5.2 Transformation bots

Most transformation bots crawl open corpora and tweet sentences/phrases if they match a selection criterion, after operating a transformation. A popular selection criterion is metric. @accidental575 retweets tweets which can be transformed into

Figure 2: Examples of quote bots.

haikus, i.e. tweets which contain 17 syllables that can be written with a three-phase format distributed in a 5-7-5 pattern. In the quote tweet (retweet with a comment), the bot adds line breaks to transform the tweet into a haiku, credits the original account and adds the hashtag #accidentalhaiku, which becomes a lexical constant. This bot has a single open source (Twitter) and is interactive since it uses the "quote tweet" function and tags the source account. Several accounts works with very similar principles, like @youinhaiku, @HaikuD2, and @haikuincidence.⁸ Various accounts apply the same principles to other sources, whether closed (e.g. @SimpsonsHaiku, which mines scripts from *The Simpsons*), or open (e.g. @WikiHaikuBot, which mines Wikipedia, @nythaikus, which mines the New York Times and @HaikuNewsBot,⁹ which mines 50 English news sources using the free News API).¹⁰

Figure 3: Examples of transformation bots with a metric generation axis.

@BigramPoetry is an example of a transformation bot which works with another metric, since it turns tweets which contain the #machinelearning hashtag into bigram poems.¹¹ In this case, the generation axis is ambiguous since the selection criteria is lexical but the transformation is metric, according to a loose definition of metric. Apart from this additional generation axis, and the lack of interactivity, it has the same

⁸ URL: <https://github.com/warmlogic/haikuincidence>

⁹ URL: <https://roche.io/2017/07/haikunewsbot>

¹⁰ URL: <https://newsapi.org/>

¹¹ URL: <https://dev.to/tomweinand/building-a-twitter-bot-in-python-to-write-bigram-poems-1dcj>

combination of labels as @accidental575.

Figure 4: Examples of transformation bots with a lexical generation axis.

Mining tweets for a specific lexical element, which is then swapped by another is a popular process as well. @regrettoegret mines tweets containing the word "regret" and replaces it by "egret". @SubstitutionBot substitutes specific phrases by others in headlines from the Guardian accessed through their API.¹² @gutenboy2bot similarly replaces "boy" with "bot" in classic literature found on project Gutenberg. These three bots are very similar, but the typology allows for their different features to be documented. The generation axis is lexical and they all work with a single source and script. However, the variety of phrases being swapped by @SubstitutionBot is documented by the lack of lexical constancy which is present in the other two bots and the fact that @gutenboy2bot works with a closed corpus instead of crawling an open source through an API is documented in the source type category.

5.3 Template bots

Templates bots are by far the most common literary Twitter bots. Some are very simple and tweet a single phrase with a one-word variable (e.g. @makeamericabot, @dstroyeveryword, @wearable_things). However, most have multiple interrelated variables. This is the case of @SpellerBot and @is_like_a, for instance. The first tweets the phrase "Can't spell X without Y.", where Y is a substring of X, and both X and Y are existing wordforms. The second tweets the phrase "X is like Y since they are both Z", where ZX and ZY are both collocations. These two examples are based on specific lexical resources. Both bots rely on one closed source and one script, and show a lexical constant and syntactic equivalence. The only difference is the generation axis, which is orthographic for the former, and lexical/semantic for the latter. The typology recognises that the formal processes are essentially identical, but that the bots revolve around different linguistic aspects.

For the bots mentioned in the previous paragraph, the combination of lexical and syntactic constancy is a central feature. However, many bots, on the contrary, play with a wide variety of templates so as to "hide" to an extent the bot-like nature of the generation. For instance, @IsItArtBot, uses more than a dozen templates to ask whether an object or a concept is art. The object/concept in question appears to be any possible noun, although we do not know where the vocabulary list comes from. This bot has one closed source (the vocabulary list) and several scripts (i.e. several templates, in this case). There is a lexical constant and equivalent syntax in all tweets generated by the same script, but syntactic equivalence is not maintained across the

¹² URL: <https://github.com/molly/SubstitutionBot/blob/master/substitutionbot.py>

Figure 5: Examples of template bots.

different scripts/templates. Although multiple scripts are most common in template bots, since they multiply the "randomness" characteristic of the procedure, where a simple pattern produces a large variety of different outputs, they can occur in any of the four overarching procedures.

Figure 6: Examples of template bots.

Finally, whether they are based on one or several scripts, many template bots use entire phrases as variables instead of single words. For instance, @WhitmanFML combines lines from Walt Whitman's *Leaves of Grass* with tweets that use the #FML hashtag. The ways in which the two are combined is not immediately evident, but the snippet of Python script in the cover picture of the account and a careful examination of the output suggests that the bot looks for sentences with a comma or conjunctions (such as "and", "but", "or" and "either") around the middle of the sentences/tweets. We can assume that this was only done once for *Leaves of Grass* while the #FML tweets are regularly crawled among recently posted tweets. It picks randomly whether to start the tweet with a Whitman sentence slice or a #FML tweet slice and one sentence from each list. The first sentence is read up to the comma/conjunction (excluded) and the second is appended from the comma/conjunction (included). The bot is based on one open source and one closed source, does not show lexical constancy (since not all tweets include the #FML hashtag) or syntactic equivalence. The generation axis is intertextual, as well as syntactic, since the two variables are united by a conjunction or a comma. This example is different from the other template bots, since the sentences produced by the same script are not syntactically equivalent, as we are not facing a "fill the blank" type procedure. Although the tweets are still produced sequentially via a

template with two variables, these variables are truncated according to a rule before being slotted in. For this reason, it could be argued that this bot is not truly a template bot, but an algorithm bot, since an extra rule is needed after the bot randomly selects the variables from a list.

In Flores' typology, mash-ups are their own category. The decision to abandon this class boils down to the focus of this typology on formal elements. Mash-ups can be achieved by template bots or algorithm bots. In addition, a bot which mixes several sources which do not belong to "recognisable" sources such as Walt Whitman's *Leaves of Grass* and the #FML phenomenon would not be readily considered a mash-up. This is because the label alludes to a political and artistic tradition, in addition to the act of mining different sources. However, intertextual templates with multiple sources and no syntactic equivalence or lexical constant are highly likely to be examples of mash-ups, in contrast to syntactic templates, for instance.

5.4 Algorithm bots

The most popular generation algorithm for literary Twitter bots is the Markov chains algorithm, a count-based predictive model which generally generates each word based on the probability that it follows the previous one. Markov bots have been trained on the Bible (@rewrittenbible, @KJVBlockchain), song lyrics (@MtnGoatsMarkov, @horse_bluegrass), literature (@Fakespearean, @EdgarAllanBot), book titles (@MarkovBooksBot), and tweets from other accounts (@Lin_MarkovBot, @MarkovFollowers), to name a few.

Figure 7: Examples of algorithm bots implementing a version of the Markov chains algorithm.

Some bots combine this procedure with others. @SnowballPoetry generates snowball poems, i.e. poems in which each line is a single word, and each successive word is one letter longer. The two-step program is detailed in the README file of the GitHub repository linked to the account.¹³ First, the input files (from project Gutenberg) are preprocessed: the program looks for any phrases in which the length of each word varies from the previous word by one letter, e.g. "his face", "in the land" and saves each phrase as a separate line in a preprocessed "corpus" text file. Then, words which are not part of a validation lexicon list (Spell Checker Oriented Word Lists) are removed. The bot works by starting with one letter words and randomly traversing a Markov tree that links the second word of one pair to the first of another if they are the same word, until it reaches a dead branch. This bot illustrates the ambiguity of "sources". Are we talking about the raw text files from project Gutenberg, or the preprocessed corpus? Do text files from project Gutenberg count as one or several sources? In this study, we

¹³ URL: <https://github.com/nossidge/snowball>

opted to consider that, in such cases, the text files issued from project Gutenberg are a single source, since they are essentially treated as one text. Preprocessing is part of the bot activity, and, therefore, we do not consider the processed corpus as the source. Nevertheless, we rarely have as much information about the processes, and some bots rely on sources preprocessed by third-parties.

@a2b_bot is a bot created by German digital artist Mario Klingemann. The bio reads "A bot traveling on an associative route through word2vec space. Written by @Quasimondo. #botALLY". The bot uses the word2vec algorithm, which relies on a neural network model to learn word associations from a corpus of texts. This algorithm can identify the semantic nearest neighbours of a given word in a corpus. We can infer that the bot, given two words, finds the shortest path between them in the semantic space created by the word2vec algorithm, taking into account the n nearest neighbours of each word, or setting a maximum semantic distance between each word included in the path. This bot has a single closed source (i.e. the corpus it was trained on). According to our definition, the syntactic equivalence is maintained, although there is no syntax to speak of. The generation axis is semantic.

The bio of @AutoImagist reads "Generating imagist-style poetry by combining random picture descriptions, powered by Microsoft Azure. A bot by @zachwhalen, #botALLY". The bot uses Microsoft Azure's Computer Vision API to describe random photos from Flickr, combines two or more of those descriptions to make similes or juxtapositions, then formats it like a poem "in the style of imagist poets like William Carlos Williams".¹⁴ The bot uses a single open source: the image hosting website Flickr. This source has the particularity of not being textual, ahead of the transformation operated by Microsoft Azure's caption generation algorithm. In addition, this generation algorithm was itself trained on a dataset. The generation axis is primarily graphic, although the text generation itself relates to the semantic axis, to a large extent, since it aims to extract meaning from a picture. This last example highlights that the concept of "source" is ambiguous in more ways than one. Recent machine learning models are often trained on a huge dataset which becomes a source for the text generation procedure. As bots leveraging pre-trained Large Language Models become more common, distinguishing text generation procedures which rely on specialist corpora which were specifically chosen for the task (e.g. @carsonbot and @a2b_bot) from those which rely on sources which are independent from the bot's specific purpose (e.g. @AutoImagist) will become important.

6 The design process

6.1 Data

The corpus from which this typology was developed was created by manually searching for literary bot accounts in English on Twitter. We adopted an inclusive understanding of literature and included all text-based bots with an artistic/creative component. We retrieved 588 bot accounts and 15 million literary tweets in total (which included non-bot accounts as well). This corpus does not include bots whose output exclusively contains emojis or visual material. The collection took place in January and February 2023.

The corpus is therefore not exhaustive, nor can we argue that it is representative of the form. Crucially, we could not retrieve the numerous literary bot accounts which

¹⁴ URL: <https://github.com/zachwhalen/AutoImagist>

Figure 8: Examples of algorithm bots relying on Machine Learning algorithms.

were deleted or banned before the collection took place. However, considering the sample size, this corpus provides a significant sample of the main genres and types of literary bots.

6.2 Method

Designing the annotation was an iterative process. We started with a baseline annotation scheme with had two categories only: procedure and interactivity. We worked in batches and calculated the inter-annotator agreement for each class. A low agreement meant that the class was ambiguous, and that criteria needed to be refined or that the typology needed to be revised.

This typology became increasingly granular as we encountered the need to differentiate between several types of templates, since they are highly heterogeneous and constitute the bulk of the corpus. We added this granularity by documenting the type of sources and the extent to which the tweets differed from each other. For instance, we wanted to distinguish templates with one-word variables—which output near identical tweets—from templates where variables are entire phrases—which output tweets that have very little in common, both lexically and syntactically. We attempted to assess the proportion of "variables" vs. "constants" in templates, but it proved difficult. We considered focusing on the number of tokens or word sequences which either remained constant or were "filled in" for each tweet. The two approaches led to drastically different template groupings. Many templates contain repeated words. Should these count for one variable/constant or several? In addition, template bots which work with several templates largely complicated the matter since not all templates acted similarly. The issue was partially solved by separating lexical and syntactic similarity, and making the decision to reduce lexical similarity to a binary class (i.e. asking whether there is at least one lexical constant).

Since we worked with template bots to define these new ways of differentiating bots, we initially used them to separate the template class into several different classes. However, the type and number of sources, the number of scripts, and the lexical and

syntactic constancy are also relevant for the other procedures. Therefore, we made the decision to include this information in separate categories and use the procedure category for the overarching four types of procedures only. The generation axis was added last to account for the fact that some bots enact different formal processes but work around the same linguistic axis, and vice versa.

7 Discussion and conclusions

Although Alan Turing's "imitation game" is arguably the starting point of the history of bots, literary Twitter bots rarely aim at passing for humans. On the contrary, they often draw attention to their own procedurality. This typology describes bots as the sum of various formal elements. From a research perspective, this approach can provide a relatively detailed distant reading of a corpus. It allows researchers to observe correlations between different categories, identify trends in the distributions and combinations of labels and, conversely, identify bots which have an uncommon or unique combination of labels.

In addition, this typology is also useful in the context of preservation efforts for digital literature. The history of Twitter reminds us that, in terms of preservation, Internet is not forever. Social media, in particular, is dependent on constantly evolving platforms which cause the content to change, break, or disappear. Moreover, both legal constraints linked to Data Protection and the constant flow of massive quantities of data encourage us to rethink conservation and preservation practices. As argued by Giselle Beiguelman, adequate terminologies and methods are needed to address the cultural output of digital media and the masses of data and memories that "vanish [...] in collective and personal archives on the internet" (Beiguelman, 2014, p. 175). The unpredictability, uniqueness and open-endedness of social media feeds also have implications for the archiving of literary works on social media. A fixed version of the "restitution form" (Bachimont, 2007), i.e. the content as consumed by readers, cannot be captured and preserved. When exposing various approaches to the preservation of digital literature, Bouchardon and Bachimont (2013) argue that preserving a description of the content, instead of the content itself, bound to be incomplete, is the most potent on a theoretical level. A dataset of bot metadata becomes a form of preservation. This typology abstracts the processes dependent on specific files, resources, tools and scripts into non variable elements, e.g. the fixed or open-ended nature of the source material, the transformation/generation processes applied to this material, and the formal variability of the output. In addition to providing tools for analysing literary bots, individually, within a collection or alongside other types of generative digital literature works, it also contributes to a fragmented memory of this form, and its contextualisation within the landscape of digital literary art.

Although bots lend themselves more readily to this type of abstraction than most other types of literature, this reduction of complexity nevertheless favours a specific reading. Recording the content rather than the form, for instance, would lead to a very different clustering of these bots. Is the bot humorous, "feel-good", political/subversive, didactic, poetic, narrative, entertaining, reflexive? Does it revolve around a specific event, a specific theme or a specific fandom?

Even when focusing on formal elements, many other categories could be added to this typology, and, within the existing categories, some classes could be refined. For instance, algorithm bots include a wide range of procedures, from simple Markov chains generators all the way to text generators built from Transformers. This lack of

refinement is due to the comparatively small amount of bots pertaining to this class in our dataset. Since the methodology was built empirically, departing from our data, and not from everything that would be technically possible, the level of granularity offered is tailored to this specific corpus. Nevertheless, as technologies evolve and this typology adapts to other platforms and other datasets, it could be important to specify the nature of the algorithms. Another blind spot of this typology concerns the tools used to develop these bots. For instance it would be interesting to know the bots which used *Cheap Bot, Done Quick!* or the SSBOT tool developed by Zach Wahlen, when this information is available.

In addition, the existing typology also presents some challenges. Namely, when a bot relies on several scripts whose processes do not belong to the same classes, we are forced to adopt a multi-label approach, which implies a loss of precision. Even when bots are limited to one script, they sometimes require multiple labels per category. For instance, many algorithm bots are also templates, since the outcome of the algorithmic process is arranged into an output according to a specific pattern (see @a2b_bo in 5.4). In fact, bots which resist the simplicity of the typology are often the most interesting, since they push the envelope of literary bot formulas. For instance, @AliciaWnderland is a bot which translates the Esperanto translation of *Alice's Adventures in Wonderland* back to English. It is a transformation bot, since it quotes existing material after operating a translation. However, this transformation is much more complex than those seen in any of the other transformation bots present in our corpus. Instead of substituting a word with another, or rearranging the text according to a specific metric, it algorithmically generates a new text from the source text. In this case, whether the transformation or algorithmic procedure has precedence is not obvious. This bot exposes the imprecision of the term "algorithm". Because other transformation bots relied on comparatively simplistic processes, and because other algorithm bots do not take single sentences from existing material as sole input, the ambiguous boundary between these two procedures was not clearly apparent before it was confronted with this specific example. Moreover, the generation axis of this bot is intertextual, but it also revolves around translation, making a case for a new class to be added to this category.

The countless ways in which bots can defy and alter this fragmentary typology obscure the fact that, in spite of this creative diversity, the Twitter environment is highly constrained. The character limit is prescribed, but so is the visual appearance of the tweets (font, font size, font colour, layout). The opportunities for interactions are also limited, since they are circumscribed to the features enabled by the platform, which is not designed for literary processes. The possibilities for user input in the creation process are therefore restricted. The narrow "wobble room" afforded by Twitter facilitated the development of this typology. Since so many elements of the bots are fixed by the platform itself, few variables are left to the creators' discretion. If the platform is so limiting, why has it proved relatively attractive for creators? With these constraints, comes the ease of creating and publishing a literary bot. Thanks to tools like *Cheap Bot, Done Quick!* and the platform itself, a bot could be created with no coding skills, hosted for free for an indeterminate duration, and easily shared with others.

In addition, these constraints also contribute to the continuum between literary bots and the avant-garde movements which inspired many of them, explicitly or implicitly. Dadaist "cut-up" techniques, surrealist "cadavres exquis", Oulipian combinations, and other constraint writing techniques all find illustrations in the bots presented in this

article. This continuity is often acknowledged by the bot creators themselves. @SnowballPoetry explicitly refers to Oulipo, the literary movement that coined snowball poems as part of their constrained writing practice. The profile photo of @IsItArt is Marcel Duchamps's urinal (*Fontaine*). This bot playfully mirrors the dadaist challenge of the accepted definitions of art, and does so by making a type of computationally enabled chance collage, reminiscent of dadaist writing techniques.

The duality of chance and constraint is illustrated by the numerous "accidental haiku" bots mentioned in 5.2, since they work with a constraint which was met by chance. However, this duality of chance and constraint is ubiquitous in most literary bots, since they integrate an element of randomness and work with a set of constraints. We could even argue that it is the case for all tweets, for which the reading, to an extent, is a function of their random location on a timeline and juxtaposition with other tweets. This juxtaposition is the reason why, as a platform which is not created for literature, Twitter is an interesting stage for literary bots. In the context of social media, the cut-up techniques favoured by dadaist poets contribute to a defamiliarisation of such platforms and comments on the "noise" created by the overabundance of published content. The relentless tweeting and the near infinite number of closely related tweets created by literary bots reflect the constant updates of our social media timelines, where the same content appears time and again, with small differences. It is in part because literary Twitter bots reveal their own procedurality that they are able to draw attention to the endless illusion of novelty encouraged by social media platforms.

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Crossing the Border between Archive and Edition: The Samuel Beckett Digital Manuscript Chronology

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Within the digital humanities, it is common to distinguish between digital archives and digital editions. This paper argues that research into an author’s writing processes benefits from digital projects that cross the border between the two. It introduces a work-in-progress digital manuscript chronology that lists information found in manuscripts, notebooks, and letters on a malleable timeline. As such, it presents the data preserved in the archive in a way that elucidates the compositional histories of literary works. The main advantage of this tool is that it visualizes the geneses of different works within the same environment, facilitating the study of “creative concurrence.” The oeuvre of Samuel Beckett serves as a case study.

Keywords: genetic criticism, digital scholarly editing, Samuel Beckett

1 Introduction

Digital textual scholarship often distinguishes between digital archives and digital scholarly editions. While the consensus now seems to be that they are not mutually exclusive, both orientations have different rationales, both equally valuable to study our textual heritage. To study authors’ oeuvres as the creative ecologies they represent, including both published and unpublished materials, it is necessary to cross the border between archives and editions. In this paper, we will introduce a work-in-progress digital manuscript chronology of Samuel Beckett’s works as one of the means toward achieving that goal.

The tool is set to be incorporated into the Beckett Digital Manuscript Project (BDMP; www.beckettarchive.org), which operates both as a digital archive of Beckett’s works and as a genetic “complete works” edition organized into 26 modules, 10 of which are currently available online. The BDMP digitally reunites Beckett’s manuscripts, notebooks, and personal library, while also offering a set of tools that facilitate the study of the geneses of his works. The Beckett chronology lists all the dates found in the archive on a dynamic and interactive timeline. In so doing, it aims to offer a digital expansion of John Pilling’s *A Samuel Beckett Chronology* and Ruby Cohn’s *A*

Beckett Canon (Cohn, 2001; Pilling, 2006). While these initiatives are bound to the print medium in which they appeared, a digital manuscript chronology tries to fully exploit the potential of computational methods and user interfaces. A chronological presentation of the manuscript material not only allows us to track Beckett's day-by-day progress in depth, but it also promises to introduce a new way of showcasing the fluid nature of some writing processes. A writer like Beckett, for instance, often worked on multiple projects at once. As a result, several unfinished manuscripts occupied his desk for months or even years, occasionally resulting in cross-fertilizations between writing projects across genres and media. Thanks to a digital Beckett chronology, such instances of "creative concurrence" (Van Hulle, 2021, 2022) can be more finely traced and studied, since it presents the archival material of the entire oeuvre rather than collecting documents relating to separate works.

2 Digital Archives and/or Editions

There currently exists no universally accepted definition of digital scholarly editions and it still remains difficult to define what precisely separates them from digital archives. Many digital projects that aim to present the textual history of literary works blend properties traditionally assigned to both archives and editions. In general, these initiatives aspire to be as extensive as a literary archive, collecting and presenting digital facsimiles of manuscripts, notes, proofs, or books in an author's personal library. At the same time, it is not uncommon that they also provide additional aids that help users navigate this labyrinth of archival material, such as transcriptions of handwritten passages, reading texts, or a set of tools that facilitate the comparison of documents. In an ongoing debate, attempts to establish definitions of digital scholarly editions have appeared piecemeal in the past few years (Gabler, 2010; Pierazzo, 2016; Robinson, 2013; Sahle, 2016). Much of the difficulty seems to stem from the absence of a standardized form that is adopted by all digital editions online today. Their appearances and functionalities frequently differ according to their publication dates, the specificity of the edited work, and the aims of the editors, all factors that may have contributed to the lack of consensus among scholars. A dense fog still obscures these discussions and until that fog has lifted it is good to engage in a healthy debate on the ontology of digital scholarly editions.

One widely accepted characteristic of digital scholarly editions appears to be the publication of an extensive collection of documents. In theory, the digital medium has the potential to include a large number of facsimile scans of original documents, such as an author's notes, sketches, or drafts taken from various archives, repositories, and collections scattered around the globe. In "The Primacy of the Document in Editing," Hans Walter Gabler stresses the importance of these reproductions in digital editions and argues that "it is documents that we have, and documents only" (Gabler, 2007, p.199). The work of textual scholars and editors ultimately begins with the investigation of documents. Before editors can make any statement about a text, they first need to extract these texts from the documents in which their surviving versions are contained. Only then can texts be read, interpreted, and edited. According to the Swiss editor-scholar Hans Zeller the "manuscript requires interpretation [...] and the result of the interpretation is the text. This act of interpreting the manuscript is the constitution of the text" (Zeller, 1995, p.43).¹ Consequently, digital editors generally ensure that the documents on which their arguments are based are rendered visible.

¹ However, Daniel Ferrer counters that "the draft is not a text, or a discourse; it is a protocol for

The effort of digitally representing original documents has become a core feature of digital editions. In a later article, Gabler duly notes that this may even “be considered the primary concern and duty of scholarly manuscript editing today” (Gabler, 2016, p.68). As this aspect of digital editions enables users to check the editors’ transcription at any point, it contributes significantly to the edition’s accountability, which goes a long way in giving shape to what Patrick Sahle called a “digital paradigm” (Sahle, 2016, p.28) in textual editing.

But a digital scholarly edition is, or often aspires to be, more than a mere collection of related documents and transcriptions. While they select, order, and publish archival documents online, scholarly editions also aim to elucidate a textual history. The archival material presented in digital scholarly editions offers a wide array of information in order to do this, but pieces of information become particularly useful when they are related to one another by editors. Anne Baillot and Anna Busch remark that “editors are still in dire need of a set of standards that would give the kind of direction the scholarly book tradition would provide them with” (Baillot and Busch, 2021, p.181). We could potentially arrive at such an editorial model for the digital age by considering the effort of finding and presenting meaningful connections between documents as one vital task of editors. Peter Shillingsburg points to the necessity of joining texts and documents: “[t]he first job of all editors is to gather relevant variant forms of the work to be edited and [...] establish the relationship they bear to one another” (Shillingsburg, 1996, p.134). Barbara Bordalejo also notes that “[a]n editor who has collected materials, gathered evidence, and compared variants eventually has to decide what does it all mean, who will care about it and how to present it; but most importantly how those materials relate to each other” (Bordalejo, 2013, p.64). Scholarly editions present critically established links across or within archival documents, which could help illuminate part of the genesis or serve as starting points for further investigations into the history of a text.

These links can take different forms. One example is providing users with a synoptic overview of the different versions of a sentence, paragraph, or line of verse by means of digital collation. But when we study literary writing processes, we tend to focus on the geneses of individual works, such as novels, short stories, or poems. In doing so, we often overlook the reality that works of literature typically come into being within wider creative landscapes. They are conceptualized, written, and rewritten within certain creative clusters. The creative process involved in writing a work of literature is typically influenced by many events happening simultaneously. It is therefore important to bear in mind that the creative continuum is often not limited to single writing projects, since it is common for writers to work on several assignments simultaneously. In *Ways of Escape*, the second volume of his autobiography, Graham Greene writes that he used to work on two novels at once in 1938, devoting his mornings to the thriller *The Confidential Agent* and his afternoons to *The Power and the Glory* (Greene, 1980, p.91). In an interview with *The New Yorker*, Jennifer Egan recently revealed that she adopted a similar method, writing *Manhattan Beach* and *The Candy House* at the same time (Treisman, 2023). Earlier examples can be found as well. Stephen Greenblatt, for instance, suggests that Shakespeare may have written parts of *A Midsummer Night’s Dream* and *Romeo and Juliet* concurrently (Greenblatt, 2004, p.52). The hypothesis we wish to develop here is that highlighting the connections between overlapping writing projects could also help to turn an archive into an edition. We will illustrate this by analyzing a short poem Beckett composed in 1974.

making a text” (Ferrer, 1998, p.261).

3 Case study: “hors crâne” and “creative concurrence”

On 1 January 1974, Beckett started the new year by writing a new piece of prose in French, which was eventually to become a poem called “hors crâne.” In the early manuscripts, when it was still a piece in process, it was not much longer than a paragraph, written on a loose sheet of white paper. Beckett kept revising it over the following days. The first draft is followed by three further drafts of the same piece of prose, all on the same page. After these four versions, still on the same piece of paper, he decided to turn it into a poem, numbering the four three-line stanzas, signed and dated 4 January 1974.

While he was writing this poem, a few other projects were on his desk. One of them was a collaboration with the visual artist Jasper Johns. In November 1973, they had met to discuss their book project *FOIRADES/FIZZLES: Echo and Allusion in the Art of Jasper Johns*. Beckett translated three short *foirades* (short prose pieces) from French into English: *Il est tête nue* into *He is barehead* on 31 November 1973, *Horn venait la nuit* into *Horn came always at night* on 12 December 1973, and *J'ai renoncé avant de naître* into *I gave up before birth* on 15 December 1973 (Pilling, 2006, pp.193-194). At the same time, he was working on the translation of his play *Not I*, from English into French (*Pas moi*) – or at least this translation was a project that had been on his desk since March 1973. It would take him until May 1974 to finish a first draft of the translation. There are indications that in the meantime this translation project was on his mind. For instance, on 8 December 1973, he wrote to American director Alan Schneider: “Still haven’t translated *Not I*” (Beckett, 1998, p.311).

One of the play’s most striking features is that the text is spoken by nothing but a mouth, reducing the stage basically to just a set of moving lips, speaking from the dark. Beckett appears to have come up with this idea in the summer of 1971, when he asked Ruby Cohn: “Can you stage a mouth? Just a moving mouth with the rest of the stage in darkness?” (Cohn, 2001, p.315). But the talking mouth is a radicalization of his earlier idea to stage just a head. That idea goes back at least ten years further in time, to the abandoned “Kilcool” fragments, which Beckett referred to as his “lit face” play, as in his letter of 26 August 1963 to Barbara Bray (Beckett, 2014, p.567) – and perhaps even earlier, to the second act of the play *Happy Days*, in which the main character, Winnie, is buried up to her neck in a mound, so that only her face is still visible. The stage directions of “Kilcool” (TCD MS 4664, 10r; BDMP10, AS1) describe an even further minimized set with just a “Woman’s face alone in constant light. [...] Nothing but fixed lit face & speech” (Little and Neyt, 2022). This isolated head appears to have been an image that preoccupied Beckett for many years. On several occasions, he mentioned Caravaggio’s painting *The Beheading of St John the Baptist*, which he saw in Valletta Cathedral when he was on holiday in Malta in 1971, as a source of inspiration – especially mentioning the onlookers (Little, 2021, pp.148-149). But the isolated head was in the first place a literary image for Beckett, who had probably encountered it for the first time in Dante’s *Divina Commedia*. In *Inferno*, Canto 32, Dante and Virgil stumble upon Bocca degli Abati in Antenora, the second division of the ninth circle of Hell, which is depicted as a frozen lake that houses traitors. Bocca, who had betrayed the Guelf party, is buried in the ice up to the neck.

The development of this Dantean image was not limited to the genre of drama, however. In 1969, Beckett had started writing a piece of prose fiction in French which was to become *Pour finir encore* (*For to End Yet Again*).² By 3 September 1970, he wrote

² The earliest manuscript toward *Pour finir encore* is dated 8 and 10 November 1969 (Pilling, 2006,

to Ruby Cohn that he had “written 200 sentences” (Beckett, 2016, p.239). As is often the case, the text’s incipit - “Pour finir encore crâne seul dans le noir lieu clos” (Beckett, 1976, p.7) - did not coincide with the start of the text’s genesis. It took Beckett five years to arrive at the final version of the text in 1975, published by Les Éditions de Minuit in 1976 together with the other “fizzles” as *Pour finir encore et autres foirades*.

At first sight, Beckett seems to have been in the short prose mood when, on 1 January 1974, he started writing a new text, as if he was just continuing the series of *Foirades* – which would make sense, given the ongoing book project with Jasper Johns. But, as indicated above, after four versions he turned the text into a poem, thus definitely moving away from the *Foirades* format. And while it may seem as if *Pour finir encore* signals the end of the “closed space” texts, the earliest versions of this text do not mention this theme, nor even an isolated head or skull. It is more likely that the concurrent work, “hors crâne,” prompted Beckett to introduce the theme of the skull being the last closed space. First, it was not yet a skull but a head: “Où la tête cette fois. Difficile à dire. Finis les lieux clos” (BC MS 1991001/11/4/1, 01r, translation: “Or the head this time. Difficult to say. No more closed spaces”). In the third version, he then introduced an explicit reference to Dante, “tel Bocca dans la [xxx] glace” (BC MS 1991001/11/4/1, 01r, translation: “like Bocca in the ice”). And in the fifth version, when he turned the text into a poem, he also changed “tête” [head] into “crâne” [skull].

While *Pour finir encore* may have served as a starting point for Beckett in the early stages of writing “hors crâne,” the creative concurrence also works the other way round: the poem changed the course of the writing process of *Pour finir encore*, because it introduced the theme of “hors crâne seul dedans” – which recurs almost literally in the late drafts written in 1975 as well as the published version of *Pour finir encore*: “crâne seul dans le noir lieu clos” (Beckett, 1976, p.7).³ Moreover, the early versions of “hors crâne,” still in short prose format, started with “Là quelque chose,” which became the opening line for another poem in English, “something there” – yet another writing project lying on his desk almost simultaneously. And Bocca, meanwhile, kept prompting new poems, as he is mentioned in the first draft of “dread nay” (started in the same month as “hors crâne,” on 31 January 1974). It is obvious that this kind of creative concurrence effectuates cross-pollination and self-pollination, but how do we visualize this and enable users to study this concurrent pollination in a digital environment?

4 Toward a Digital Manuscript Chronology

What distinguishes genetic criticism from related disciplines, such as bibliography, book history, and archive studies is its focus on the temporal unfolding of the creative process. Literary composition inevitably occurs in time, and one of the tasks of geneticists is therefore to reconstruct the chronological order of writing events. Pierre-Marc De Biasi even argues that the novelty of genetic criticism lies in its investigations into “the unexplored expanse of a new object structured by time” (De Biasi, 2004, p.42). At some point during their analysis, genetic critics will need to decide what was

p.182). In a letter of 8 November 1969 to Barbara Bray, Beckett writes: “Wrote first sentence this morning désespoir de cause again of God knows what and who cares. Feels like beginning *Molloy* only 1/4 century worse” (Beckett, 2016, p.192).

³ Several manuscripts of *Pour finir encore* have only recently been donated to the Bibliothèque nationale de France; among these as yet uncatalogued documents is a manuscript dated 15 May 1975 (archival research at BnF, Dirk Van Hulle, 22 November 2022).

written first and what was added, deleted, or corrected later. They will also need to pinpoint the length of the interval between the different writing stages and define the chronological order of the documents.

There are several ways to present the chronology of a writing process in a genetic edition. The publication of a genetic dossier is one common method to reach this goal. Such a dossier not only compiles the extant documents that have contributed to a writing project, but it also visualizes their order of composition because, as Almuth Grésillon suggests, these documents are best organized according to the chronology of the successive writing stages (Grésillon, 1994, p.242). This system of organization is mostly situated on the level of the document, showing the chronological sequence of notebooks, manuscripts, typescripts, and proofs. More pertinently, genetic dossiers are created for individual works rather than creative clusters consisting of drafts belonging to separate projects.

Additionally, editors could resort to another common method, namely the creation of a so-called “genetic map” (Van Hulle, 2020). This type of representation visualizes the timeline of both documents and versions leading up to a work. As a result, a genetic map provides an insight into the trajectory of a writing process. Moreover, these maps could also point to parallel geneses, albeit in a rather rudimentary fashion. The BDMP’s genetic map for *Fin de partie / Endgame*, for instance, shows that Beckett worked on several other texts during the composition of this play, such as *Acte sans paroles I* and two versions of the unpublished “Mime du rêveur.” While these “maps” are currently some of the most detailed items that genetic editors can incorporate into their editions to present the chronology of writing, they remain simplified and static illustrations of something more complex, designed to be easily publishable both online and in print form. The benefit of digital scholarly editions is that different ways of organizing the documents can co-exist. Next to genetic dossiers and maps that organize documents and versions chronologically, digital scholarly editions could also benefit from a more fine-grained tool that fully exploits the potential of the digital medium and that is designed specifically to study the interactions between concurrent writing events.⁴

The digital manuscript chronology lists all the dated material in the BDMP on a vertical timeline (see Figure 1). It allows users to scroll through the dates found in manuscripts, notebooks, and books in Beckett’s personal library as if they were using a chronology that we find in many print scholarly editions, which certainly helps to map the progression of the geneses of Beckett’s works. It also enables users to refine the results by decade, year, or work, and clicking the facsimiles they wish to analyze more closely will take them to the corresponding page in the genetic module for that work. Since many of Beckett’s manuscripts are undated, it is also possible to include documents with “uncertain” or “inferred” dates, derived from ancillary archival materials.

To reconstruct the chronology of Beckett’s writing processes more accurately, it is necessary to incorporate information drawn from documents not currently preserved in the BDMP, such as Beckett’s correspondence. In many cases, letters shed light on the genesis of a text, and they can often help us date it. The chronology therefore offers brief summaries of statements in Beckett’s correspondence that could be related to his creative process, such as those referring to a text he is writing, a work he is

⁴ Our proposal for a new tool echoes recent calls for a more experimental approach to digital scholarly editing. Christopher Ohge, for example, invites editors to move “from abstract-rationalist models to a programme of action and experimentation” (Ohge, 2021, p.121).

translating, or a book he is reading. In addition to data based on Beckett's published letters (Harvard University Press, 1998; Cambridge University Press, 2009-2016), the tool also aims to include information drawn from unpublished correspondence. The incorporation of these references results in a much more detailed picture of Beckett's work schedule. Lois More Overbeck, one of the editors of the four-volume edition of Beckett's correspondence published by Cambridge University Press, notes that "Beckett's letters reveal the gradual shifts that take place between his original conception and the realisation of his work" (Overbeck, 2013, p.431). These day-to-day progressions become particularly evident once the statements in Beckett's letters are linked with his manuscript drafts, allowing users to compare the remarks in the correspondence with the facsimiles in the archive.

The Chronology feature uses an eXist-db database that retrieves data from the XML files that are the basis of the BDMP. All the encoding is done in XML, in accordance with the guidelines of the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI). The information drawn from the notebooks, manuscripts, and the Beckett Digital Library is complemented by an additional XML file for the correspondence (see Figure 2). The latter file contains a list of <date> tags, each with a unique identifier and a set of attributes that further specify when the letter was written and the type of document it concerns. The statements Beckett makes in his letters that could be related to his creative process are briefly summarized within these <date> tags. The data also note the place from where Beckett sent the letter as well as the source where the full letter can be found, in many cases the edition published by Cambridge University Press, but sometimes also unpublished letters, kept in libraries or public archives.

To illustrate how the tool may help dissect creative clusters, let us zoom in on the period that coincides with the writing of Beckett's first published novel, *Murphy*. The six notebooks containing the manuscript already provide us with an exceptionally high number (145) of dates, and the chronology also incorporates information found in 137 letters sent during the novel's composition, the bulk of which derives from Beckett's elaborate correspondence with his friend Thomas McGreevy. Scrolling through the chronology immediately points to the interplay between different events. For example, the first entry reveals that in a letter of 1 January 1935, Beckett wrote to McGreevy that he had consulted a book on the German expressionist painter Heinrich Campendonk, which he found "very interesting" (Beckett, 2009, p.240). The Chronology shows that shortly after Beckett also composed an undated short story titled "Lightning Calculation," whose protagonist is planning to write a book, titled *The Pathetic Fallacy from Avercamp to Campendonk*, which has the painter as a subject. At the end of the month, Beckett sent the story to the publisher Lovat Dickson, who would eventually reject it about a week later (Beckett, 2009, pp.243,247). The idea that his story would remain unpublished may have been a reason for Beckett to recycle some of its elements in his novel, which he started writing on 20 August. In the fifth notebook, in a passage dated 25 January 1936, the title of the book reappears once again, although the painter's name has now been changed into "Kampendonck" (UoR MS 5517/5, 25r). Even this brief example shows how the chronological presentation of Beckett's activities, derived from multiple sources, helps us not only to analyze the genesis of *Murphy* but also to trace the novel's relationships with other archival material.

CHRONOLOGY

This feature presents all dates in manuscripts in chronological order.
It can be enriched with two other datasets by selecting any of these options:

include dates from other sources include uncertain/inferred dating UPDATE

Previous 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Next

LET
TER

08 / 09 / 1935

SB writes to Thomas McGreevy that he told Chatto and Windus to send *Proust* and *More Pricks Than Kicks* to Simon and Schuster. He is expecting proofs of *Echo's Bones*, to be published in November 1935 by The Europa Press, and is working over his poems, especially 'The Undertaker's Man' ('Malacoda') proves to be difficult. He mentions that he has been working on something new and that he witnessed old men flying kites at the Round Pond in a passage that echoes the end of *Murphy*.

Place: 34 Gertrude St [London]
Source: *The Letters of Samuel Beckett*, vol. I, 1929-1940, pp. 272-276

Murphy, MS-UoR-5517-1, f. 31r

09 / 09 / 1935

9/9

REFINE

Found 453 entries.

Refine by decade: 1930's, 1940's, 1950's, 1960's, 1970's, 1980's

Refine by year: -select year- refine

Refine by work:

Murphy (145)
(137)
Molloy (56)
Malone meurt / Malone Dies (23)
L'Innommable / The Unnamable (20)
Stirrings Still / Soubresauts (17)
Not ! / Pas moi (17)
Fin de partie / Endgame (10)
Krapp's Last Tape / La Dernière Bande (9)
That Time / Cette fois (6)
Comment dire / what is the word (4)
En attendant Godot / Waiting for Godot (4)
Footfalls / Pas (3)
(2)

Figure 1: The interface of the digital chronology in the BDMP.

```
<date xml:id="SB-MCG-08-09-1935" when="1935-09-08" type="letter">
  SB writes to Thomas McGreevy that he told Chatto and Windus to send <hi rend="i">Proust</hi> and
  <hi rend="i">More Pricks Than Kicks</hi> to Simon and Schuster. He is expecting proofs of <hi rend="i">Echo's Bones</hi>,
  to be published in November 1935 by The Europa Press, and is working over his poems, especially 'The Undertaker's Man' ('Malacoda')
  proves to be difficult. He mentions that he has been working on something new and that he witnessed old men flying kites at the
  Round Pond in a passage that echoes the end of <hi rend="i">Murphy</hi>. <lb/><lb/>
  Place: 34 Gertrude St [London] <lb/>
  Source: <hi rend="i">The Letters of Samuel Beckett</hi>, vol. I, 1929-1940, pp. 272-276
</date>
```

Figure 2: An excerpt of the XML encoding for the Digital Beckett Chronology.

5 Conclusion

In his book *The Fluid Text*, John Bryant writes that genetic criticism “assumes that the creative process is a continuum of overlapping and interpenetrating actions flowing seamlessly from one to the next” (Bryant, 2002, p.73). The tool we have introduced in these pages may help communicate such a creative continuum in a digital scholarly edition. While still incomplete, the digital timeline’s aim is to provide a more detailed overview of the gradual development of Beckett’s oeuvre. The main advantage of this type of interface is that it gives us an insight into both diachronic and synchronic processes of composition. A digital chronology presents the drafts belonging to different writing projects side by side rather than organizing and separating them according to the work to which they belong. As such, it points to relationships not only within but also across genetic dossiers. The tool is a welcome addition to a digital complete works edition of Beckett’s texts, since he not only divided his time between multiple projects, but also because this practice was an important aspect of his creative process, one that drove him more than once to compose new works across genres and media. A digital manuscript chronology could therefore offer an illuminating way of showcasing creative concurrence within the archive and turn the two-dimensional text into a 3D object, as it were, by giving shape to what Louis Hay has called “the third dimension of literature” (Hay, 2002, p.245): time.

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Automatic Narrative Structure Identification in Literary Texts

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Numerous tasks in the field of computational literary analysis require a high-level understanding of the structure of a text. The ultimate goal of this research is to create and leverage an annotated database to train a computer system capable of automatically annotating literary texts according to their structural components. By aligning human expertise with computational methods, this research aims to reshape our understanding and engagement with literature in the digital age, offering new insights and opportunities for exploration in the world of literary analysis. This research article introduces an approach to annotating literary texts according to their underlying structural elements. Our objective is to bridge the gap between human interpretation and computational capabilities by developing a set of guidelines for annotating literary texts based on their structural intricacies. This article also outlines the process of constructing a database of short stories annotated according to the guidelines defined in this article, which serves as a valuable resource for future studies. Additionally, it addresses the vital issue of inter-rater annotator agreement, ensuring the reliability and robustness of the proposed guidelines through multiple annotator involvement.

Keywords: narrative structure, computational literary analysis, scene segmentation, LDA

1 Introduction

In an era marked by technological advancements and digital transformation, the need for systematic and standardised methods of text analysis has become increasingly apparent. The ability to understand narrative trends by comparing different narratives on a large scale can benefit researchers in a wide range of fields.

Scholars from different disciplines, like linguistics, literary criticism, psychology, and sociology, have been studying story structures and their roles in our communication and understanding of the world. Recently, studies in economics, climate science, political polarisation, and mental health started using narratives to understand human behaviour (Piper et al., 2021). Fields related to computer science that also benefit from story structure analysis include video game development, bot development, summarization tools, automatic essay grading, or narrative popularity predictions.

Ouyang and McKeown (2014) refer to a couple of different uses of automatic narrative structure detectors. They argue that information about the narrative structure can provide a measure of the quality of the narrative. For example, orientating information is usually found at the start of a narrative. If it is placed too late in the narrative, it might be hard for the reader to understand the narrative. Ouyang and McKeown (2014) also argue that narrative generation systems can be improved by knowing the preferred structure of the narrative. For example, a narrative-generating system might present all orientating information at the start of a narrative, while human narrators might have preserved some information for later.

Structure theories are typically analysed using qualitative approaches or manual approaches that result in a fine-grained analysis. However, with the rise of digital text and computational processing power, large-scale analysis of texts has become possible. Although quantitative analysis of a text cannot replace the human expertise provided by a qualitative analysis, a quantitative approach can provide scholars with empirical evidence for a narrative structure theory and allows for large scale comparisons, among others.

The development of tools to analyse digital texts has been neglected mostly due to the lack of annotated data. Even the tools that have been developed are not always properly evaluated and tend to target a commercial market. Specifically, in an academic setting, the evaluation of tools is important to ensure the quality of the analysis generated by the tool.

This research will contribute to the field by creating comprehensive guidelines for annotating literature texts based on their structural intricacies. The guidelines are based on existing structure theories. We construct a database comprising three short stories annotated following our guidelines, thus establishing a valuable resource for future scholars.

Furthermore, we recognise the critical importance of human annotator agreement when applying structured annotations to literary texts. The article seeks to assess the inter-rater annotator agreement level by involving multiple annotators in the annotation process, ensuring the reliability and robustness of our guidelines.

Our objective extends beyond the theoretical domain into the practical application of these guidelines. Ultimately, this research will bridge the gap between human analysis and computational capabilities. We will use the annotated database to train a computer system that can automatically annotate literature texts according to their structural components. This development holds significant potential for literary analysis and applications in various fields. The system could also provide scholars with empirical evidence for a narrative structure theory.

2 Background

A narrative does not only refer to the narrative in a novel, but it extends to a wide range of fields. We use narratives when we communicate historical events, political agendas,

race, religion, identity and time (Wake, 2006). All of these notions explain the way the world is experienced through an individual's narrative thereof. This definition of the narrative does, however, not include all forms of text or spoken word. Prince (1982) explains that a narrative has specific traits that distinguish it from other forms. Prince (1982) claims that we have "internalised certain rules about what constitutes a narrative and what does not". In general, a narrative is the "representation of real or fictive situations and events in a time sequence" (Prince, 1982). A narrative can thus be described as specific elements following specific rules in a specific order. The study of these elements and the order in which they are found is called narrative structure theory.

As we have mentioned, the narrative consists of elements like situations and events. A situation refers to the circumstances or context in which events, actions, or interactions take place within a narrative. Situations provide the backdrop against which characters operate and events unfold. They encompass the setting, the characters' relationships, their motivations, and the broader societal or cultural context. Situations can be dynamic and subject to change as the story progresses, influenced by the characters' decisions and external forces.

Events typically refer to occurrences or happenings within the narrative that drive the plot forward, shape character development, and contribute to the overall progression of the story. On the other hand, the absence of events, or what Prince (1982) refers to as non-events, can also hold importance in narrative structure and meaning. Non-events, refer to instances where something expected or anticipated does not happen within the narrative. The absence of anticipated events can create tension, suspense, or surprise, depending on the context. Non-events can be just as meaningful as actual events in shaping the narrative structure and character development. Examples of non-events include a character's failure to act in a crucial moment, a planned meeting that does not occur, or the absence of an expected outcome. While events propel the narrative forward, non-events add nuance, complexity, and unpredictability to the storytelling process, enriching the reader's experience and inviting deeper interpretation.

Narrative structure describes how different parts of a narrative relate to one another. A paradigmatic approach to narrative structure focuses on the underlying structure of a text without taking into account the linear order of events (Propp, 1968). The structure of a text is not necessarily linear but can be affected by changes in location or time, or by actions or events (e.g., flashbacks or flash-forwards). The structure determines how the plot of a story unfolds and has an effect on how it is perceived. Connecting elements of a narrative through the structure of a text leads to the development of a story line.

A longstanding tradition in literary criticism is to analyse narratives according to plot elements or thematically similar units centred around the actions of characters. Propp (1968) argued that all Russian folktales can be characterised by the combination and organisation of 31 basic plot motifs.

However, there is a superfluity of different narrative structure theories all aiming to describe the complicated nature of narrative form. These theories are based on the claim that regularities can be found in narrative structures. These theories aim to organise narrative elements, including the introduction, rising action, climax, falling action, and resolution. We will look at several well-known structure theories to demonstrate the overlap between sections. Ultimately we will focus on two of these theories, the three-act and the four-part structure theories. We want to apply these theories to our text to evaluate which theory suits our suggested genre, short mystery stories

better. Short stories are generally believed to follow a three-act structure, whereas the mystery genre tends to follow a four-part structure. When combining short stories and the mystery genre, which will determine the structure of a text, if there is indeed a common structure?

2.1 Structure theories

Structure theories aim to describe the combination and/or order of events in a text, by dividing a text into different sections (sometimes referred to as acts or parts). Each section contains events with similar goals. Many structure theories often share common elements or concepts, resulting in overlapping sections. This means that while each theory may have its unique perspective or emphasis, there are areas where they intersect or coincide in their analysis of narrative structure. These overlapping sections indicate common ground among different theories, highlighting key aspects of storytelling that are widely recognised within the field.

2.1.1 The six-part structure

It is worth mentioning Labov (2013) further extended their three-act structure theory to include the abstract, resolution, and coda. This creates a six-part structure consisting of the *abstract* that serves as an introduction to the story and often contains a description of the core event. The *orientation* act introduces the setting and characters by providing background information. The *complicating action* consists of a chain of events that lead up to the core event. The *evaluation* of the story is where the author attempts to provide credibility to the story, present alternative outcomes or assign praise or blame to characters. The *resolution* extends the chain of events to a final resolution of the situation. The *coda* relates the events of the narrative to the present. We will not use this structure theory in this work as short stories do not generally include an abstract and coda.

2.1.2 Freytag's pyramid/five-point dramatic structure

Another expansion of the three-act structure was introduced by Freytag (1894). This structure is usually used in Greek tragedies or tragic contemporary tales. The *exposition* introduces the setting and characters. In the *rising action* the basic conflict and obstacles are introduced. During the *climax* there is a turning point that effects a change for the better or for worse. During the *fall of action*, unexpected incidences can create suspense, but overall, the conflict is resolved. During the *resolution* the protagonist achieves or fails their goal.

Similarly, Todorov Todorov (1971) identifies five stages in a narrative. *Equilibrium* shows a glimpse of the daily routine that a character follows at the start of a narrative. During the *disruption* stage, the daily life of the character is disturbed. *Recognition* is where the character realises the cause of the disruption. In the *repair* stage the character tries to solve the problem that causes the disruption. At the end of the narrative, the character returns to the *equilibrium stage* where they continue or adjust to daily life.

2.1.3 The seven-point structure

The seven-point story structure is a relatively new structure compared to the ones discussed until now. It is commonly identified as the structure used in the Sci-fi genre and was popularised by Wells (2010) after claiming that he used the structure in his

novels. The *hook* is the introduction to the setting and characters. The *call to action* is driven by an event that sets the protagonist on an adventure. The *first setback* is usually due to the introduction of the antagonist or the major conflict. The *turning point* is where the protagonist starts taking action. In the *second setback*, the conflict increases and the protagonist feels discouraged. Some new element is introduced in order for the protagonist to *solve the problem*. A *resolution* is reached when the major conflict is resolved and the antagonist is defeated.

2.1.4 The Hero's Journey

Campbell (2008) base the Hero's journey on common motifs and themes found in world mythology and folklore, suggesting that these narrative patterns resonate deeply with human experience and psychology. Campbell's work in identifying and popularising this structure has had a significant influence on storytelling across various mediums, from literature and film to video games and beyond. It outlines the stages a protagonist typically undergoes as they embark on an adventure or quest, facing challenges and transformation along the way.

The Hero's journey consists of 12 stages. In the *call to adventure* the hero is introduced to a problem or challenge that sets them on their journey. This could be a direct call or an unexpected event that disrupts the hero's ordinary life. Initially, the hero may hesitate or refuse the call to adventure due to fear, doubts, or obligations to their current life. This stage is known as the *refusal of the call*. After refusing the call, the hero will *meet the mentor* or guide figure who provides advice, tools, or wisdom to help them on their journey, resulting in the hero committing fully to the adventure or *crossing the threshold* and leaving behind their familiar world, entering into the unknown or unfamiliar territory. In the stage of *tests, allies, and enemies* the hero faces various challenges, meets allies, and confronts adversaries as they progress on their journey, learning important lessons along the way. The hero approaches a significant challenge or ordeal, often represented as a metaphorical "cave" or inner conflict that they must confront in the *approach to the inmost cave*. Here the hero faces their greatest trial or battle in what is known as the *ordeal*, undergoing a profound transformation or revelation as they overcome this obstacle. After overcoming the ordeal, the hero receives a *reward*, which could be an object, knowledge, or insight that will help them in their ultimate goal. The hero begins the *journey back* to their ordinary world, but they may encounter further obstacles or face the consequences of their actions. The hero experiences a final moment of death and rebirth in the *resurrection*, symbolising their ultimate transformation and growth. The story ends with the *return with the elixir* stage, where the hero returns to their ordinary world, bringing back the knowledge, experience, or boon gained from their journey, which benefits themselves and/or their community.

2.1.5 The three-act structure

The three-act structure divides the story into three parts. This theory is often credited to Aristotle, however, the three-act structure we are familiar with today has been expanded on by multiple theorists. A popular version of this theory was proposed by Labov and Waletzky (1967). The first act is called the *orientation*. This act introduces the setting and characters as well as the basic conflict. The second act is used to describe the *complicating action*. Usually, the protagonist tries to solve a problem, only to raise the conflict further. The third act is the *evaluation* of the story, where the conflict is

resolved. Steele (1981) notes that many commentators have noticed the Aristotelian properties of classic detective stories. This is the main reason we chose to use the three-act structure theory for this work, as we will be annotating detective stories in this experiment.

2.1.6 The four-part structure

The four-part structure cannot be attributed to a single source, but several theorists have contributed to our understanding of the four-part structure. Similar to the five-part structure attributed to Freytag (1894) and the six-part structure, the four-part structure is also derived from the three-act structure mainly attributed to Aristotle, but it divides the second act into two parts. Most four-part structures can easily be placed into a three-act structure and vice versa. Mystery genres are also described as having a four-part structure. The *introduction and setup* introduces the protagonist and a crime. The protagonist decides to solve the crime. During the *discovery phase*, the protagonist looks for clues. The protagonist might encounter obstacles in this phase that can lead them to become puzzled or discouraged. In the *funnel* phase, new evidence comes to light and subplots are closed. In the *reveal*, the villain is confronted, the crime is explained and a conclusion is reached.

3 Previous and related work

Research on the computational analysis of narrative structure includes Jockers (2015) who aims to identify the change in sentiment over a text, while Finlayson (2016) and Droog Hayes et al. (2018) present a case for inferring Propp's functions using machine learning methods. Finlayson (2016) mentions that even though Propp described the functions in detail, there is still some ambiguity when annotating text according to functions. They argue that the description of the function groups is at times unclear, implied, or in disagreement with each other. This caused a greater variation in human annotations of the text. They solved this problem by creating panels that discussed the text until they were in agreement. Semantic role labelling was also performed by the annotators using the PropBank scheme. The first step of their algorithm is to extract a timeline from the annotations. They then associate each event with an agent and patient using the semantic role. This approach is extremely resource-intensive and requires a lot of human judgment.

A number of studies (Barth, 2021; Ketschik et al., 2019; Reiter et al., 2019; Wren and Ek, 2021) have created guidelines for human annotation of narrative boundaries to train and test models to identify the start and end of scenes within a text. These studies define scene changes as the change in narrator, event, time, place, or the constellation of characters. They base their work on Jahn (2005) who in turn adapts an idea from Genette et al. (1980) where they distinguish between different levels of narration. According to Genette's theory, narrative levels occur when there are stories within stories. Their work aims to identify scene boundaries as well as the relation between sub-stories in a text in terms of their narrative level. Here our work differs in terms of what we consider a segment. Where these studies consider a segment to consist of a single scene, we propose a segment consisting of one or more scenes that have a common purpose. We are interested in the order in which events and scenes are clustered together to create a segment as well as the possible repetition of a segment in the same text or across multiple texts in the same genre.

Ouyang and McKeown (2014) introduced a system to automatically detect one of the narrative structure elements based on William Labov’s theory of narrative analysis (Labov and Waletzky, 1967) as mentioned in Section 2.1.5. They present experiments where they detect the Complicating action element in Labov’s theory with a 71.55 f-score. They make use of a corpus consisting of twenty oral narratives collected by Labov (2013) as mentioned in Section 2.1.1. Although this work has the same goal as ours, they rely on properties of speech data to identify boundaries. This technique would not work with text data.

In previous work (Heyns and van Zaanen, 2021, 2022), we describe a method to identify high-level textual transitions in text using Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) (Blei et al., 2003). A transition is found when there is a relatively large contrast between LDA topics before and after a position in the text. This means that a transition is not simply found when the LDA topic changes, but rather when a group of LDA topics that co-occur changes. For this study, we are considering the segments created by these transitions to function as a story act. We specify the number of segments to divide the text into. We then measure the distance between corresponding segments of different text. This creates a tool to measure the applicability of a structure theory on a text and decide where to place narrative transitions.

Similar studies (Gius et al., 2021) have shown that inter-rater annotation can vary greatly because of the subjective and context-dependent nature of a text. Reiter (2015) has found that summarising a text before attempting to annotate it, helped to create greater agreement between manual annotations.

4 Methodology

We will use three short stories from the mystery genre. In Section 5 we will discuss the development of a database where five human annotators will annotate the text. We will rate the agreement between human annotations. In Section 6 we will describe the system we will use to analyse the text. We will then compare the human annotations with the system annotations.

5 Data

Gius et al. (2019) argues that manually annotated datasets are imperative for developing automatic scene or narrative detection systems. This work will take inspiration from Gius et al. (2019) by establishing rules to identify sections in a text. We will create a human-annotated dataset that will also benefit future studies in automatic scene and narrative detection. This dataset will serve as a baseline for comparing the automatically identified sections using the system described in Heyns and van Zaanen (2022).

5.1 Data collection

For now, we will focus on mystery short stories. Because we have to manually annotate the data, we will keep the dataset relatively small. We will be using three short stories from Agatha Christie. The length of the text can affect the ideal number of topics to use. For now, we will use short stories of similar length to eliminate that variable.

Table 1: Number of words (Word), number of segments (Seg), and average number of words per segment (Word/seg) for each short story.

Text	Word	Seg	Word/seg
The adventures of the Italian nobleman	2409	66	35.97
The jewel robbery at the grand metropolitan	3495	94	36.05
The mystery of Hunter’s Lodge	2811	77	35.25

5.2 Data processing

Pre-processing is done on the text. Stopwords are removed using NLTK¹. The texts are lowercased, lemmatized, and the punctuation is removed using spaCy².

Two of the texts (*The adventures of the Italian nobleman* and *The Mystery of Hunter’s Lodge*) contain section breaks to indicate a lapse of time. This section break was removed during pre-processing, although human annotators would have had access to that visual clue.

To apply LDA to the text, we split the text into smaller segments. If a sentence consists of more than 30 words, it is used as a segment; if not, sentences are concatenated to create segments of 30+ words. This is done so that each segment is of a similar length, but it does not interrupt a sentence. Table 1 shows the short stories we chose to use as well as their length. The average segment length is 35.75 words.

5.3 Data annotation

We asked five human annotators to annotate the text. The purpose of the annotation is to identify the different sections in the story structure, as well as explain the reasoning behind grouping sections. The annotator should read through the short story and decide where to add a transition that will break the story into different parts. The annotation should include a summary of the section, following the reasoning of Reiter (2015) that summarising the text before annotating it helps create a greater agreement between manual annotations. For this study, we will only include events, simplifying the nature of a literary narrative by leaving out the nuanced information that a non-event can provide for a literary analysis.

There will be two rounds of annotation. For the first round annotators should divide the story into three parts by stipulating the line number where a boundary should be placed. The annotator should identify the line number where a phase starts and ends. Note that each phase (except the first) will start on the next line to where the previous phase ended. For example, if phase 1 ends on line 24, phase 2 will start on line 25. They should also give a summary of each part, followed by a motivation of their reasoning for placing a boundary on a specific line. For the second round, the same annotations should be given, but the annotator should divide the story into four parts.

5.3.1 First round: three-act structure

The three-act narrative structure is a framework that many storytellers use to construct a short story. The three parts generally consist of:

¹ <https://www.nltk.org/>

² <https://spacy.io/>

1. Exposition: The main character and setting are introduced. An event (in the case of a mystery, a crime/mysterious event) sets the story in motion.
2. Rising action: The protagonist is drawn into the event; for example, the protagonist starts to investigate the crime/mystery. Clues are revealed. During this phase, the protagonist might encounter obstacles that will cause the protagonist to become puzzled or discouraged.
3. Climax and resolution: The villain is confronted, the crime is explained, and a conclusion is reached.

5.3.2 Second round: four-part structure

The four-part narrative structure is a framework that many storytellers use to construct a mystery novel. The four parts will consist of:

1. Introduction: The protagonist and a crime or mystery are introduced. The protagonist decides to investigate the crime or mystery.
2. Discovery: In this phase, the protagonist investigates the crime or mystery. Clues are revealed. The protagonist might encounter obstacles that will cause the protagonist to become puzzled or discouraged.
3. Funnel: During this phase, new evidence comes to light or the protagonist examines old evidence with a new approach. Subplots are closed. The protagonist narrows the suspect down to one, but the villain is not yet revealed to the reader.
4. Reveal: The villain is confronted, the crime is explained, and a conclusion is reached.

Table 2 gives an example of a completed annotation form.

6 System

In previous work (Heyns and van Zaanen, 2022), we have proposed a system to automatically identify transitions in a text. Here, transitions are considered to be a location in the text where there is a relatively large change in the composition of topics. The text is first split into sentence-length segments. Topics are then identified in the text using LDA.

To identify the best transition points, the overall entropy of the distribution of LDA topics is computed and compared against the combined entropies of both parts in case a transition is inserted. This information is combined as information gain. Transitions are placed at the highest information gain position in the text. This will be the position with the most contrast between the LDA topics before and after a transition.

Note that the system does not simply identify a position where the LDA topics change, but rather where a group of LDA topics that co-occur, change.

We concatenate all the text in the corpus, that has been split into segments. We then train an LDA model that represents the entire corpus. Therefore an LDA topic is assigned to each segment, resulting in a sequence of LDA topics: $LDA(S) = \langle LDA(s_1), LDA(s_2), \dots, LDA(s_n) \rangle$. Heyns and van Zaanen (2022) have experimented with different numbers of LDA topics. The sequence for each text in the corpus is then separated so that the transitions can be identified in each text. We rely on a

Table 2: Example annotation for The Kidnapped Prime Minister by Agatha Christie. Phase (P), start line (S), end line (E), summary and motivation are provided.

P	S	E	Summary	Motivation
1	1	10	The story begins with the Prime Minister of a country being kidnapped by a group of terrorists. We are introduced to the main characters, including the Prime Minister, the leader of the terrorists, and the members of the Prime Minister's security detail who are working to rescue him. We learn about the political tensions in the country and the reasons behind the kidnapping.	An event that sets the story in motion. The main characters are introduced. The political setting is introduced.
2	11	21	The main part of the story focuses on the efforts to rescue the Prime Minister. The security team follows clues and tracks down leads in their search for the Prime Minister, while the terrorists do everything in their power to keep him hidden. There are several close calls and tense moments as the two sides engage in a game of cat and mouse. As the story progresses, the stakes get higher and the tension increases, leading to a climactic moment where the security team finally locates the Prime Minister.	The protagonist is drawn into the event trying to rescue the Prime Minister. Clues are revealed.
3	22	50	The story concludes with the successful rescue of the Prime Minister and the capture of the terrorists. The Prime Minister is reunited with his family, and the country celebrates his safe return. The resolution also includes a moral lesson about the importance of strong security measures and the need to work together to combat terrorism.	The terrorists are captured, a conclusion is reached.

method from previous work (Heyns and van Zaanen, 2021) that has been expanded on in Heyns and van Zaanen (2022) to recognise multiple transitions in texts using an information gain-based method. We specify the number of transitions that we want to identify in the text beforehand and the algorithm finds the optimal place for each transition, where the most information gain is obtained. The transitions divide the text into sections. The number of sections that a text is divided into represents the structure of the text and can be compared to one of the story structure theories mentioned in Section 2.1 of this article.

For example, if a text is divided into three sections, then we can test the three-act story structure of that text. For each text sequence (with $x = 1 \dots n - 1$) every position between two segments (s_x, s_{x+1}) is considered as a potential transition point. The information gain at each potential position is computed and the position with the highest information gain is considered the real transition point. If multiple positions have the same information gain, the system selects the first position. If multiple transitions have to be identified, the system will divide the sequence in two at the transition point. The algorithm is repeated on the side with the least information gain.

The system developed in Heyns and van Zaanen (2022) uses no manual annotation, which is ideal when trying to analyse narratives on a large scale. However, it is difficult to evaluate the accuracy of proposed transitions without comparing them to human judgement.

6.1 Number of LDA topics

In previous work (Heyns and van Zaanen, 2021) we have found that increasing the number of LDA topics generally decreases the performance of the system. As the number of LDA topics increases, the system will, more often, propose the wrong transition leading to a misplaced section more frequently. We have previously (Heyns and van Zaanen, 2021) established that the system performs best with two LDA topics and gradually deteriorates as more topics are introduced.

We can, however, expect that the optimal number of topics may change according to the length of a book. Longer books will generally discuss more topics than a short story. However, for this experiment, we will be using the results of two LDA topics to make comparisons.

Uglanova and Gius (2020) argues that topic modelling is used as a statistical tool to break down the themes of a text, but in fact, it is only recognising the statistical patterns within a text's structure. Therefore, the topics relate to the structural elements of a text as opposed to the content of the text. van Zundert et al. (2022) further supports this idea by asserting that the topics generated through topic modelling, are more aligned with genre signals rather than semantic fields. van Zundert et al. (2022) found that contextual details from a literary text, such as the location, time, language community, or cues from the author, collectively influence the LDA topics. So, in fact, we might not be measuring narrative structure, but rather attributes that occur around a narrative change. We see words like [evening, long, night, sky, dark] that indicate time, and words like [door, house, window, world, side] indicating location, that co-occur in topic 1. Meanwhile, we find words like [hear, find, look, answered, understand, ask, remark] indicating actions and words like [inspector, police, friend, woman, doctor, father] indicating people that co-occur in topic 2. These topics are intertwined in the text, so by no means can we say a specific section is only focusing on one of these topics. The system we propose here simply finds the location where the order of these topics gives the most information gain. For example, for the three-act structure of *The*

jewel robbery at the Grand Metropolitan, topic 2 dominates the section by 69%, 65% of segments in section 2 are tagged as topic 2 and 57% of segments in section 3 are tagged as topic 3.

topic 1: [felt, evening, green, long, night, sky, mind, dark, great, fact, door, house, sound, good, strange, thing, window, world, side, life]

topic 2: [inspector, police, dead, interest, case, friend, voice, woman, doctor, father, hear, find, face, look, answered, round, understand, eye, ask, remark]

7 Evaluation

We compare the transitions identified by the system, with human-annotated transitions. We would like to know if the system agrees with human judgment. We compare the automatically identified sections with human-annotated sections using a distance metric. We compare the start and end points between the automatically annotated sections and the human-annotated sections.

To take into account the distance between the two transitions we use the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). RMSE allows us to measure the distance between a predicted value and an observed value. In this case, we will see the computer-identified transition point as the predicted value and use the human-identified transition point as the actual value, to determine how well the computer and human annotators compare. This allows us to take the distance between the transition points into account instead of just ruling a transition as wrong when it is not the same. RMSE is defined as follows:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (p_i - p_r)^2}{n}}$$

where n is the number of observations, where each human annotation counts as a separate observation. p_i is the position of the proposed transition position (which can range from one to the number of lines in the text), and p_r is the position of the real transition (in this case, the line number of the human-identified transition). To calculate the RMSE for multiple texts, the RMSE is computed for each transition and these values are combined using the average. A higher RMSE value indicates a lower agreement between the predicted and actual value. The scikit-learn Python package³ was used to calculate the RMSE.

7.1 Inter-rater annotator agreement

We compare different human annotations of the text to assess the agreement between their annotations.

From Table 3 we can see that human annotators reach a greater agreement with the three-act structure theory than the four-part structure theory. This is unsurprising seeing that as the number of parts to annotate increases, the chances of making a mistake also increase.

To understand if the difference in agreement is significant, we added a random baseline where we divided the text into three and four equal parts. We then compare the RMSE between the baseline of each theory and the annotator's transition placement. Table 4 shows the average RMSE of all annotators compared to the baseline. Here we see that there is no real difference in the average annotation standards when compared

³ <https://scikit-learn.org>

Table 3: The average RMSE between annotators for the individual texts as well as the average over the three texts. Results are provided for both the three-act and four-part analysis. The lower the RMSE, the higher the agreement is between annotators.

Text	Three-act	Four-Part
The adventures of the Italian nobleman	0.014	0.084
The jewel robbery at the Grand Metropolitan	0.147	0.317
The mystery of Hunter’s Lodge	0.020	0.180
Average	0.061	0.193

Table 4: The average RMSE between the baseline and the annotators for the individual texts as well as the average over the three texts. Results are provided for both the three-act and four-part analysis. Higher RMSE values indicate larger distances between the location where the annotator placed a transition and where the random baseline placed the transition.

Text	Three-act	Four-Part
The adventures of the Italian nobleman	0.383	0.333
The jewel robbery at the Grand Metropolitan	0.557	0.564
The mystery of Hunter’s Lodge	0.448	0.518
Average	0.463	0.472

to a baseline. Although if we look at each annotator individually in Table 5, we see a bigger difference in agreement between annotators for the four-part theory, than for the three-act theory. This difference is mostly just for the *The jewel robbery at the Grand Metropolitan*. Results from Table 3 also show that for both structure theories, the annotators struggled most with *The jewel robbery at the Grand Metropolitan*. If we look at the text, section breaks were added to *The adventures of the Italian nobleman* and *The Mystery of Hunter’s Lodge* to indicate a lapse of time. This visual indication is where the annotators placed their transition in the three-act structure, and it also seemed to guide their transition choice in the four-part structure. However, *The jewel robbery at the Grand Metropolitan* does not contain such section breaks, and this can explain why the annotator agreement is lower for this text. Overall, the annotator agreement is high with an average RMSE value of 0.06 for the three-act structure and 0.19 RMSE value for the four-part structure.

7.2 Human annotator versus computer annotator

Table 6 shows the average RMSE between the human annotators and the computer annotator. Here we see a similar trend where *The jewel robbery at the Grand Metropolitan* shows a higher RMSE value that indicates a lower agreement between annotators and the system. Since the section breaks were removed during pre-processing, it could not have played a role in this case. This might have to do with the text itself. Perhaps the transition points were not as clear-cut in this text.

On the other side of the spectrum, if we look at the first text, we can see that the RMSE value is the lowest for both structure theories, which also agrees with the results of the inter-rater annotator agreement.

In general, the system performs similarly to human annotators with a 0.09 RMSE value for the three-act structure and a 0.144 RMSE value for the four-part structure.

Table 5: RMSE per annotator compared to the random baseline. RMSEs higher than the average are in red, indicating that the specific annotator added the transition further away from the baseline than other annotators. The blue RMSEs indicate the annotator added the transition closer to the baseline transition. This does not mean that the annotator is right or wrong for adding the transition at a specific place, but rather just indicates how close their annotation compares to a random baseline.

Text	Annotator				
	1	2	3	4	5
<i>Three-act structure</i>					
The adventures of the Italian ...	0.383	0.386	0.393	0.367	0.386
The jewel robbery at the Grand ...	0.500	0.634	0.513	0.524	0.614
The Mystery of Hunter’s Lodge	0.473	0.440	0.440	0.446	0.440
Average	0.452	0.487	0.449	0.446	0.480
<i>Four-part structure</i>					
The adventures of the Italian ...	0.302	0.305	0.308	0.282	0.469
The jewel robbery at the Grand ...	0.542	0.412	0.644	0.809	0.411
The Mystery of Hunter’s Lodge	0.585	0.355	0.632	0.408	0.608
Average	0.477	0.358	0.528	0.500	0.496

Table 6: The average RMSE per structure theory where a higher RMSE value indicates a lower agreement between annotators and the system.

Text	Three-act	Four-part
The adventures of the Italian nobleman	0.044	0.070
The jewel robbery at the Grand Metropolitan	0.159	0.224
The mystery of Hunter’s Lodge	0.073	0.139
Average	0.092	0.144

Table 7: The average RMSE per section where a lower RMSE shows a higher agreement between annotators and the system per section.

Text	Section		
	1	2	3
<i>Three-act structure</i>			
The adventures of the Italian nobleman	0.058	0.021	–
The jewel robbery at the Grand Metropolitan	0.229	0.071	–
The Mystery of Hunter’s Lodge	0.078	0.068	–
Average	0.122	0.053	-
<i>Four-part structure</i>			
The adventures of the Italian nobleman	0.068	0.139	0.021
The jewel robbery at the Grand Metropolitan	0.229	0.314	0.113
The Mystery of Hunter’s Lodge	0.078	0.187	0.154
Average	0.125	0.214	0.096

7.3 Comparing structure theories

If we compare the three-act and four-part structure results with each other, both the human annotators and the system show better results for the three-act structure theory. The three-act structure seems to fit this type of text better.

7.4 Comparing sections

We can see that there are specific sections that are easier to identify than others. We expected the first section to have a lower RMSE value, due to the first section always starting with the first sentence of a text. Because the start point is consistent only the transition point will cause a fluctuation in the distance between transitions. For later sections, the start position will depend on the transition point in the previous section. Therefore, it is expected that there will be more variation in later sections. However, we see that this is only the case in two of the texts. For the three-act structure, all sections can be identified similarly easily, except for the first section of *The jewel robbery at the Grand Metropolitan* where the RMSE value is disproportionately high compared to the other sections.

For the four-part structure, the first section is easier to identify for two of the text. Here we again see that *The jewel robbery at the Grand Metropolitan* has a higher RMSE value for the first and second sections. In the third section, it seems to compare well with the other two texts. The first and third sections have a lower average RMSE than the middle sections, implying it is easier to identify the introduction and resolution of a crime than to determine exactly when the investigation starts and ends. This information has the potential to tell us something about the specific text, how the plot unfolds and how it differs from other texts in this genre.

The hierarchical approach used is “local”, which may cause a preference for narratives featuring a two-part structure, allowing for further subdivision of one part. Consequently, this preference may lead to a sub-optimal initial split for a three-act structure. To assess potential bias towards either structural theory, the system is compared against a random baseline. Table 8 shows that the system does place three-act

Table 8: The RMSE between the system and a random baseline to evaluate the system’s bias for a specific structure theory. A higher RMSE value indicates a lower agreement between the system and baseline.

Text	Three-act	Four-part
The adventures of the Italian nobleman	0.411	0.311
The jewel robbery at the Grand Metropolitan	0.491	0.457
The mystery of Hunter’s Lodge	0.451	0.442
Average	0.451	0.302

structure transitions slightly further away from the baseline transitions than for the four-part structure.

8 Discussion

Computational literary analysis relies heavily on the ability to identify the high-level structure of a text. To do this, we first need to identify transitions within the text. It is important to refer to existing theories and research when deciding on what type of transitions to identify.

Some work in this field (Barth, 2021) aims to identify scene transitions. Other work (Jockers, 2015) base their transitions on the sentiment in the text. We follow Heyns and van Zaanen (2022) and Ouyang and McKeown (2014) in using structure theories to identify transitions in a text.

In this article, we review specific theories behind the structure of a text, that help provide clear and actionable guidelines for understanding and analysing narrative structure computationally. According to these theories, we create guidelines for annotating a text according to its structural elements. We also create a small dataset, using these guidelines and comparing the inter-rater annotator agreement. In contrast to previous work using this system, we now use human-annotated data to test the system.

The task of annotating data according to its structure is time-consuming, but this experiment showed promising results by proving that the system can identify transitions similar to human annotators.

9 Future work

Overall the system reflects very similar results to that of human annotators when identifying the overarching structure. However, the structure may become more complicated. For instance, when there are sub-stories told within the narrative. These sub-stories can also follow a structure different from the main narrative, or they may or may not have an effect on the main story line. Although we can use the same method to identify more sub-plot sections in a story, confirming that a section is a sub-plot proves a little more challenging.

Furthermore, structure theories often overlap in sections that share a common purpose as shown in Section 2.1. There also exist multiple theories with a similar number of sections, but the description/purpose of each section might be different. To that end, it might be beneficial to not only divide the text into sections but also identify the purpose of each section.

In Section 5.3 we refer to the fact that we are only taking into account the events that take place in a narrative and that this simplifies the structure of a narrative by excluding the significance of non-events or dialogue-text. Dialogue-text specifically can reveal conflicts through characters' speech and interactions. The pace may also be affected by dialogue, as dialogue tends to have a faster pace compared to narrative text which may involve more descriptive passages and a slower pace. For now, this falls outside of the scope of this project. But it remains an interesting concept to explore in future work.

In the current work, we create segments on a sentence level to avoid the unlikely event of a transition mid-sentence, identified by the system. However, this might not be the optimal length for the LDA model to identify a topic. We can consider concatenating multiple sentences to create a segment, but the usefulness of this will need to be addressed in future research that focuses on the fine-tuning of the model or the use of LDA for this purpose.

There is evidently still a substantial amount of work remaining on this topic. We will leave this for future investigation. As for the near future, we will move on to investigating the characteristics of these plot points.

10 Conclusion

In conclusion, this article presents a computational approach to annotating literary texts based on popular structure theories. This approach is motivated by the need for systematic and standardised methods of literary analysis in the digital age. In the article, we have outlined a set of guidelines for annotating literary texts based on their structural elements, and have described the process of constructing a collection of short stories annotated according to these guidelines. This collection serves as a valuable resource for future studies, and it has been used to assess the inter-rater annotator agreement, ensuring the reliability and robustness of the proposed guidelines.

The ultimate goal of this research is to leverage the annotated database to train a computer system capable of automatically annotating literary texts according to their structural components. By aligning human expertise with computational methods, this research aims to reshape our understanding and engagement with literature in the digital age, offering new insights and opportunities for exploration in the world of literary analysis. The system shows promising results by reflecting similar results for the automatically identified structure and the human-annotated structure.

In this specific research, a three-act structure shows a higher agreement between annotators as well as between human annotators and the system. This can, in part, be because fewer transitions had to be assigned, and therefore, there was less chance for a mistake. But we also compare the human and system annotations to a baseline which did not show a significant difference, meaning that both human annotations and the system do not show any bias towards either structure theory. From this, we can conclude that the three-act structure is indeed a better fit for the specific texts used. On a more general level, the evaluation showed that the system has a high agreement with human judgement and can be applied to a wider number of structure theories and texts.

The automation of literary annotation is still a relatively new area of research, but it has the potential to transform the way we study and engage with literature. It can enable us to conduct large-scale analyses of literary texts that would be impossible or impractical to perform manually. It can also help us to identify patterns and trends

that may be difficult to discern with the naked eye. The work presented in this article provides a valuable foundation for future research in this area but still poses important questions for future work.

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Digital Humanities at the Intersection of Three Approaches to Data Visualisation: Statistical Graphics, Data Humanism, and Humanistic Interpretation

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Digital humanities has a critical role in the progress of the data visualisation field. First, humanities scholars engage with the concept of knowledge as interpretation. Second, they leverage computational tools and statistical methods for the analysis and visualisation of data and metadata. And finally, Digital Humanities projects are a space for experimentation where different epistemic cultures (which often go beyond the Humanities and Computer Science) negotiate new forms of knowledge. Digital Humanities are therefore in a privileged position to benefit from the full potential of data visualisation, using and improving existing methods and tools, and participating in the development of those that are much needed but do not yet exist. This article presents a classification of current approaches to data visualisation into (I) statistical graphics, (II) data humanism and (III) humanistic interpretation. These three approaches are based on four main aspects: a) the intellectual habits around the definition of data, b) the characteristics of the data visualisation and its objectives, c) the relation between the data and the data visualisation, and d) the expected user interaction. The classification is not intended to narrowly categorise any data visualisation, but rather to help navigate the visualisation continuum across epistemological practices. Moreover, based on a large collection of data visualisation examples compiled in an online gallery, several techniques are identified, that allow to make the transition between the different approaches, potentially facilitating interdisciplinary projects such as the LuxTIME Machine, that leverage multiple types of sources across languages and modalities.

Keywords: digital humanities, data visualisation, statistical graphs, data humanism, interpretation

1 Introduction

This research is developed in the context of the LuxTIME Machine (LuxTIME), an interdisciplinary project about the industrial history of Belval, Luxembourg. We use data visualisation to explore, understand and communicate about data from historical archives, scientific data from the fields of eco-hydrology and cheminformatics, and socio-cultural data. In LuxTIME, we hypothesize that data visualisation can facilitate interdisciplinary work, this research provides one study for understanding the needs of the different disciplines, the common grounds, and the options for visualising data integrating different approaches.

Leveraging data visualisation for research involving multimodal and interdisciplinary data requires understanding the needs and current practices along the epistemological continuum across quantitative, qualitative, rhetorical, and creative practices. In this research, I aim to answer the following three central questions: 1) Is there a data visualisation classification that could help us understand the needs and navigate the different solutions across epistemological practices? 2) What distinguishes the different approaches to data visualisation? And 3) which specific data visualisation techniques are used to transition between those approaches?

In section 3.1, I propose a classification into statistical graphics, data humanism and humanistic interpretation, based on a) the intellectual habits around the definition of data, b) the characteristics of the data visualisation and its objectives, c) the relation between the data and the data visualisation, and d) the expected user interaction. This classification is intended to help us understand the main needs and how they are reflected in the practice of data visualisation in the different fields. In section 3.2, with the aim of understanding which specific data visualisation techniques enable the transition from statistical graphics to data humanism and humanistic interpretation, I curate and analyse a collection of 400 data visualisations.

Finally, in section 4, I discuss the current gaps between the approaches, the possibilities for future development to facilitate the use of a variety of data visualisation techniques across fields of research, and the role of the Digital Humanities.

2 Methods

This part of the research project, which lays the theoretical foundation for further practical experimentation, is conducted in three phases.¹ First, I explored a collection of data visualisations from research articles, mainly published in journals in the related fields of the project: Hydrology (e.g., *Hydrology Sciences Journal*, *Advances in Water Resources*), Environmental Cheminformatics (e.g., *Exposome Journal*), and Digital Humanities (e.g., *Digital Humanities Quarterly*, *Journal of Digital History*, *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities*). This initial exploration resulted in a predominance of visualisations using standard statistical graphs, including bar charts, histograms, line plots, heatmaps, scatterplots, pie charts, contour plots, networks graphs and choropleth maps, among others. This is probably due, among other factors, to the fact that numerous data visualisation tools mostly support this type of

¹ In this article only the theoretical framework is discussed. The practical application to the project has been discussed in a separate article (Aida Horaniet Ibañez and Dagny Aurich, 2023)

standard graphs, accessible to all types of users with minimal technical and statistical knowledge. During this initial phase of the research, some data visualisations, later classified as humanistic interpretation, were also found. This initial collection gathered about 200 data visualisations ²(see Figure 1), extracted from the different volumes of each journal starting with the most recent publications. It is important to mention that the use of data visualisation in the Digital Humanities goes beyond Digital Humanities journals. It is present in discipline (and subdiscipline) -specific journals such as Digital History, Digital Art History, or Literary Studies, among others. Similarly, among the publications in data visualisation journals, there are design studies focusing on use cases in the humanities that have not been included in this first exploration. It is beyond the scope of this research to make an exhaustive collection of all data visualisations in the field.

Figure 1: Initial collection

Secondly, I gathered and explored a collection of about 400 data visualisations (see Figure 2) that excluded those using strictly standard charts.³ As it will be discussed in section 4.2, the number of visualisations currently published in the online gallery is 400 because many links are no longer valid, but the number has been higher throughout the project. In addition to research articles, this second collection also includes non-research data sources such as online newspapers and magazines (e.g., *Nightingale*, *National Geographic*, *South China Morning Post*, *Scientific American*), social media posts (e.g., Twitter/X, Instagram), information designers' portfolios, data visualisation tool galleries (e.g., Tableau Public Gallery), community projects (e.g., Viz for Social Good, *journaldataviz*) and data visualisation awards (e.g., Information is Beautiful Awards). Due to the variety of sources, this collection has been compiled

² This collection of data visualisations is collected in a Miro board. The separation into statistical graphics and humanistic interpretation was done later to integrate the latter in the second gallery and analysis.

³ This collection of 400 data visualisations is available on Github (<https://aidahi-unilu.github.io/AlternativeDataViz>), including author(s), title, description, source, and the applied techniques, as discussed in the results section. This collection may be enlarged in the future with submissions from other practitioners in the field, through a call for contributions.

manually, with the sole criterion of excluding standard statistical graphs. The reason why I exclude statistical graphs in this second phase is that there is abundant literature on their use, and therefore, they do not introduce new evidence. Only with the initial exploration I can confirm that they potentially represent an approach on their own, how they later differ from the second gallery, and validate the existing literature as to their characteristics.

Figure 2: Non-standard charts gallery

Finally, based on these two collections, I propose a classification of approaches to data visualisation, and describe their main characteristics. Moreover, I identify a list of techniques used to move between these approaches. In the second collection, I have labelled the techniques used in the visualisations, and not in which approach they should be classified, because in some cases different combinations of the techniques allow to create visualisations belonging to different approaches. In other cases, the classifications are ambiguous, as the visualisations apply concepts from different approaches.

The classification is intended to help us to read the current landscape in general terms, while the techniques, give us the practical tools to move between the different approaches. These could be potentially used to explore epistemologically distant

techniques in interdisciplinary setups and to be standardized and integrated in data visualisation tools.

3 Results

3.1 Classification overview

Table 1 presents a very concise summary of the classification that will be described in detail in the following sections. It includes the suggested name for the approach, the intellectual habits around the definition of data as given i.e., a representation of a pre-existing fact or taken i.e., actively constructed, the main objectives of the data visualisation and its characteristics, the relation data to data visualisation, the expected user interaction, and the fields where it is most frequently used.

Table 1: Summary of Approaches to Data Visualisation

Approach	Data	Objective	Characteristics	Data to Visualisation Relation	User Interaction	Main Fields
Statistical Graphics	Given	Complexity reduction, decision-making	Summary statistics, single clear message	Representational	Known charts, formatted answers	Business, Engineering, Natural Sciences
Data Humanism	Given (context emphasis)	Emotional connection, engagement	Details, context, multiple narratives	Representational	Custom visual vocabularies, open exploration	Journalism, Education, Information Design
Humanistic Interpretation	Taken	Model interpretation	Non-standard metrics	Non representational	Close reading, marking, interpretation	History, Art, Literature

3.1.1 Approach names

To facilitate the subsequent analysis, each approach has been identified with a name that describes it as closely as possible: Approach 1: Statistical graphics, Approach 2: Data humanism and Approach 3: Humanistic interpretation.

Statistical graphics includes all the known forms of graphical representation based on statistical principles used to describe and summarize data, including plots such as scatter plots, histograms, box plots, choropleth maps, bar charts, line charts or heatmaps. The name chosen for the category is the most frequent name for this set of charts. I have included networks in this approach, because although they depict individual entities and relationships; they are standard charts (unless they include variations) based on mathematical structures, often used to gather statistics. In Figure 1, a collection of standard statistical graphs was presented.

Data humanism is based on the concept defined by (Lupi, 2017) where she claims that “whenever the main purpose of data visualisation is to open people’s eyes to fresh knowledge, it is impractical to avoid a certain level of visual complexity”. This approach refers to a practice that embraces complexity in data visualisation, slowness, engagement looking at details – the grain, understanding the individual cases behind the numbers, avoiding standards when they do not fit the purpose, and adding context to understand the uniqueness of the representation. In Figure 3, we can see a

collection of data visualisations that introduce some of these ideas.

Figure 3: (1) (Sonja Kuijpers, 2019), (2) (Alenka Gucek, 2023), (3) (Valentina D’Efilippo and Lucia Kocincova, 2017), (4) (Gambrell, 2018), (5) (Annette Hexelschneider, 2023), (6) (Lupi and Posavec, 2016), (7) (Kadambari Komandur, 2022), (8) (Gabrielle Merite, 2020), (9) (Alberto Molina Arce, 2022), (10) (MoMA Archives, 1946), (11) (Pablo Robles, Darren Long, Dennis Wong, 2019), (12) (Giorgia Lupi, 2017), (13) (Samuel Parsons, 2020), (14) (Stefanie Posavec, 2019)

Humanistic interpretation refers to the approach that uses data visualisation to model interpretation and produce knowledge. A non-representational approach, in which data visualisation is not a surrogate of the dataset but the primary act of knowledge production (Drucker, 2020). Besides the basic graphical features used in other approaches, it uses activators and inflectors and dimensions of interpretation, such as point of view or relative scales. This concept is based on the work of Drucker.⁴ In Figure 4, we can see a less homogeneous collection of data visualisations representing humanistic interpretation. As we will discuss later, the examples are fewer, and thus we observe several attempts at interpretation through visualisation, from a mixture of proposed sketches from articles, physicalisations, and personal projects, among others.

3.1.2 Data

The intellectual habits around the definition of data are the first element of differentiation among approaches: given or taken.⁵ I refer to the intellectual habits, and not to the definition of data itself, because all data is taken (as opposed to found or given). However, in the three approaches presented here, we observe different levels of engagement with the data construction process, or how that data is taken or produced, before being reused.

In statistical graphics, the intellectual habit is to use data as the starting point, a pre-existing fact, used practically as if it was given. In science and business, a

⁴ (Drucker, 2011, 2017, 2020; Drucker and Nowvskie)

⁵ Based on Drucker’s concept of data as *capta* being taken instead of given (Drucker, 2011)

Figure 4: (1,2,3,5,6,18,19)(Drucker, 2011), (4,7,8)(Drucker, 2017), (9)(Lauren Klein et al., 2016), (10)(Alessia Musio, 2022), (11)(Streamers, 2013), (12)(Stefanie Posavec, 2014), (13)(Sarah Stern, 2022), (14)(Stefanie Posavec, 2023), 15)(Martina Zunica, 2023),(16)(Syennie Valeria, 2022),(17)(Stefanie Posavec, 2011),(20)(Camilla De Amicis, 2022)

data-driven culture suggests to always “start with the data” (Patil and Mason, 2015), what somehow implies that the data is “the truth”, a value-neutral object. The visualisations cite the data source, and if that source is considered reliable in the context in which it is presented, that is sufficient. Information about uncertainty is collected statistically in the form of confidence intervals and mathematical errors. Data is observer independent.

Data visualisation, as we predominantly know it today is the result of two main transformations: first, the data collection that is the mapping of a phenomenon to data, and second, the data visualisation or generation of a visual display from that data. This process involves a series of decisions from the occurrence of the phenomenon to the data visualisation, and beyond to the understanding of it: what elements do we collect depending on the physical or emotional context, the purpose, the person’s previous knowledge or the configuration of the machine; what is grouped together; where the data is stored; which elements we choose to visualise, using which representations, what level of granularity or aggregation we choose and why. Even before adding the complexity of more advanced statistical models, the process involves many decisions, and each combination of them leads to a different result, a different dataset, and a different data visualisation. “Rethinking histories of data requires not only better answers to existing questions, but also better questions” (Strasser and Edwards, 2017). In Big Data is the Answer... But What is the Question? Strasser and Edwards suggest several questions such as “What counts as data?”, “How are objects related to data?”, or “Why do we keep data, and how do we decide which data to lose or forget?”.

In data humanism, the intellectual habit is still to use data mostly as if it was given. However, a greater effort is made to situate it and to understand the reductive process that occurs during its generation. This will be visible later in the exploration of the data visualisation that becomes co-dependent with the user. In this approach, citing

the data source, regardless of how trustworthy it is, is not enough. It requires a problematisation of the provenance of the data, an identification of the stakeholders, and other more human elements necessary to understand “the where, why, and how of data” (D’Ignazio, 2017). It interrogates the context, limitations, and validity of the same. It could be argued that such problematisation allows to classify data humanism in the intellectual habit of using data as taken and not given. Nevertheless, in many of the examples analyzed, we see that the discussion occurs mostly at the level of the visualisation, and to a lesser extent at the data level. It remains true that some visualisations classified within this approach could indeed fit into the category of taken.

In humanistic interpretation, the intellectual habit is to always approach data as taken. Loukissas states that “things become data within interpretative acts” (Loukissas, 2019). Rosenberg emphasizes on the rhetorical meaning of data: “Data has no truth (...). It may be that the data collected has no relation to truth or reality whatsoever beyond the reality that data help us to construct” (Gitelman, 2013). Drucker refers to data as *capta*, ‘taken’ actively, while data is assumed to be a ‘given’ able to be recorded and observed” (Drucker, 2011). In this approach to data visualisation, special attention is paid to the process itself, to the sources and their cultures because “when data are assembled from heterogeneous sources, each with their own local conditions, multiple settings are juxtaposed, creating a clash between discordant originating data cultures (Loukissas, 2019); where it is stored since “making data means bringing a subject into a pre-existing system, defined by durable conditions of data collection as well as storage, analysis, and dissemination” (Loukissas, 2019). Manovich refers to datasets as not just any collection of information but “objects structured in ways that allow them to exist within a computational medium and be analyzable by particular methods” (Manovich, 2020). It looks at the limitations of the data itself, what exactly it represents, and the definition of social identities created through the definition of categories (Suchman, 1993).

While the intellectual habits around the definition of data in statistical graphics are clearly different from the other two approaches, the difference between data humanism and humanistic interpretation is subtle. Perhaps because a large part of the visualisations classified as data humanism comes from statistical graphics practitioners who have started to experiment with new visual vocabularies and high levels of granularity to avoid the limitations of the graphics they know, but without the critique of the process more rooted in the humanities. Furthermore, data humanism constitutes an attempt to make data more human, while humanistic interpretation, born out of the humanities disciplines, studies artefacts created by humans, objects of culture.

3.1.3 Objectives and characteristics

The second factor of differentiation between approaches concerns the objectives of the data visualisation and how they characterize the graphical representation.

Statistical graphics aim at simplifying complex topics, they follow a reductionist approach that allows to convey high amounts of information into digestible charts very quickly. The objective is to support effective decision-making and to communicate a clear message to a given audience. To achieve this goal, the visualisations are

characterized by their abstraction, reduction, standardization, representation, and legibility. Using predefined charts and standard practices facilitates the fast processing of the content. These charts are selected based on the number of dimensions and measures, the type of data to be represented (e.g., continuous, discrete, categorical) and the data relationships that need to be displayed (e.g., deviation, ranking, flow, part-to-whole). The extensive research about graphic semiology and use of visual elements (e.g., color, shapes, size), the mechanics of the sight (e.g., Gestalt principles) and user experience, is applied to optimize the process, that is to ensure that the user receives the message as effectively as possible. It adheres to the concept of data-ink ratio introduced by Tufte (Tufte, 1999), according to which any visual elements that interfere with the attention to the data are clutter, and therefore they should be avoided.

Data humanism focuses on promoting human values to foster an emotional connection with the user. Data visualisations show complex topics in depth. The objective is to engage the user in the interpretation of the visualisation, introducing multiple narratives when necessary. Granularity, specificity, full coverage, high realism, physicality, i.e., how data is perceived through human senses, and situatedness, i.e., the relation between the data and the context (e.g., space, time), are the main characteristics of this approach. Special importance is given to showing the gaps in the data and the complexity of the visualisation process itself. Unique visual vocabularies adapted to the visualisation of a particular theme are introduced, using organic shapes and original elements. These are defined from any combination of visual elements such as color, shape, angle, or size; and they are often explained in a "how to read" section. The use of non-essential or embellishment visuals is common. Communication and storytelling theory is applied to facilitate the navigation through the visualisation of the multiple narratives (e.g., audience analysis, story structure). It embraces pluralism and includes multiple perspectives to increase reflexivity (D'Ignazio and Klein, 2020).

In humanistic interpretation, the goal is the interpretative process itself. A co-dependent constructivism allows to directly construct arguments through visual means. The visualisations are characterized by the use of non-standard visual elements such as non-discrete categories, unequal scale divisions, metrics as a factor of a point of view, of assumptions, presumptions or convention; non-continuous, non-homogeneous and multidirectional temporalities (Drucker, 2017). Figure 5 revisits Snow's cholera chart, where Drucker suggests looking at the individual profiles of the people behind the dots (what would be considered as data humanism), but she goes further and suggests to "take the rate deaths, their frequency, and chart them on a temporal axis inflected by increasing panic". Redrawing the urban streetscape to express the emotional landscape is humanistic interpretation.

3.1.4 Relation between data and visualisation

The third differentiator explores the relation between the data and the visualisation. In statistical graphics and data humanism, data is the starting point and from the data we generate the data visualisation. They are both based on a representational approach in which "the relation between data and display is uni-directional, the data precede the display, and the data are presumed to have some reliable representational relation to the phenomena from which they have been abstracted" (Drucker, 2017). Humanistic interpretation focuses on a non-representational approach, that uses the "graphical

Figure 5: Snow's chart revisited to show the individuals behind the dots, emphasizing that "each dot represents a life, and none of them are identical" (Drucker, 2011)

input as primary means of interpretative work" (Drucker, 2017). The interaction with the data visualisation changes the data or creates new versions of it.

3.1.5 User Interaction

Last, in statistical graphics, the user is expected to know the charts used in the visualisation. It requires a certain data literacy, including knowledge about statistical graphs (e.g., selecting the right charts or knowing how to read them). A user who knows how to read a type of graph can quickly read a graph related to any data set, ask predefined questions (e.g., in the case of a histogram: where most values fall and how much the variation is among values), and generate formatted answers. A critical approach is expected in terms of assessing whether the rules of statistical graphs are respected such as using the wrong graph, manipulating the axes, partially selecting data, or going against conventions to mislead the user. The user can interact with the visualisation by using filters or drilling up and down to different levels of aggregation (e.g., by date – monthly, yearly; by category). The visualisation is designed to effectively answer these predefined questions.

In data humanism, the user does not know beforehand what to expect from the visualisation. The design and the topic stimulate the user's interest in exploring it further. No standard graphics are used, and if they are, they have been significantly redesigned in some way. Based on the user's own understanding of the data representation, guided by the frequently used 'how to read' section, the visualisation allows to ask open questions and explore the answers. The user is expected to take ample time to explore it, as effectiveness is not an important factor. We do not know if special skills or some level of data literacy is required to read the visualisations, as they are not standardized and are usually accompanied by instructions. Lupi, in her manifesto, "Data Humanism, The Revolution will be Visualized" states that "the first wave [referring to cheap marketing infographics] was successful in making others more familiar with new terms and visual languages", implying that some kind of learning process is required to read these data visualisations (Lupi, 2017). We "might want to move beyond literacy with datasets and towards literacies with infrastructure"

since “datasets do not simply neutrally designate aspects of the world, they also render the world in accordance with different visions, values and cultures, making it navigable through data” (Gray et al., 2018). To gain an in-depth understanding of the implications, data literacy research needs to be extended to data humanism and humanistic interpretation.

In humanistic interpretation, the user interacts with the visualisation to build knowledge, the process happens through a series of interactions in which the user can mark and annotate the data. A set of tools allow the interaction with the visualisation, such as activators to introduce attraction and repulsion, weight, force, or sequence; or the use of graphical elements of interpretation such as point of view, layers, slices, tilt, fold, parallax or split (Drucker, 2017). Finally, the visualisation produced is also subject to interpretation. The user of this type of visualisations usually has a humanistic background, accustomed to the principles of ambiguity, complexity, and interpretation.

3.2 Data visualisation techniques: from statistical graphics to data humanism and humanistic interpretation

Based on the second collection described in section 2. I identified several techniques to move between statistical graphics and data humanism, and humanistic interpretation. They range from subtle variations of standard charts (e.g., eliminating the grid or the tick marks in a bar chart), decomposing data showing the granularity behind the aggregated values, using custom visual vocabularies such as organic shapes, overlaying multiple layers of information using data glyphs, to completely challenging the principles of standard charts such as homogeneously spaced time units. All of them allow us to walk that continuum across epistemological practices. In the following sections, they are discussed separately in detail. Furthermore, these techniques are not mutually exclusive, but can be applied simultaneously, as can be seen in the online gallery through the multifilter selection.

3.2.1 Variations of statistical graphs

When using standard statistical charts, a series of rules are applied to convey the information efficiently. These rules include, among others, the selection of a graph adapted to the data and the analytical purpose, the right level of aggregation, the precise display of axes, labels, gridlines, legends, or annotations; or a low data-ink ratio avoiding distracting elements. In this analysis, I consider variations of statistical graphs, all those data visualisations including graphs where the standard graph is still recognizable, and knowing the rules that apply to such a graph, one or more rules are not applied for a specific purpose.

The options are multiple, but from the collection studied, it is worth noting the total elimination of grids, axes, or tick marks, to draw attention to the changes and not the specific values (Kim Albrecht, 2016);(Lopez et al., 2019); the turning, superposition and use of curved axes (Pentagram, 2021); and the over-encoding, using multiple visual attributes to encode the same information (Lazzaroni, 2020). It is not considered a variation of a statistical graph when the graphs are misleading (e.g., extending the y-axis to minimize a variance), or when, for no specific purpose, the rules of standard charts do not apply (e.g., the legend is missing and there is no way to understand the content). These visualisations must be based on decisions made deliberately by the

designer, to move between different approaches. Although the techniques presented below could be generally described in some cases as other types of variations, in the online gallery, I have only identified in this category those where the reference graph is fully recognizable.

3.2.2 Custom encoding

The use of custom visual vocabularies implies leaving aside the standard visual attributes associated with statistical graphs such as lines, rectangles and circles and creating an alternative way of encoding data variables, from replacing some of the elements of a standard statistical graph to completely redesigning all the elements of the visualisation.

Frequently observed encodings include organic forms (Clark, 2022; Kadambari Komandur, 2022; Martina Zunica, 2023; Sonja Kuijpers, 2018), but also new combinations of geometric forms (Nwosu, 2022). Among others, the use of custom visual vocabularies allows us to disaggregate information (by not having the constraint of standard graphs based on aggregate metrics), to display simultaneously multiple layers of information by integrating multiple variables in the visual vocabulary (see multivariate data glyphs below), to use rhetoric to attract the reader's attention (see mapping rhetoric below), and to potentially remove barriers to data literacy, since the reader does not need prior knowledge in statistics to read the visualisation⁶. This type of visualisation requires a "how to read" section, so that learning to read it is part of the process.

3.2.3 Rhetoric and embellishment

Contrary to data visualisations with a low data-ink ratio, where "extra" elements are avoided, there are also data visualisations where these "embellishing" elements are used with a rhetorical purpose to inform, persuade or motivate a given audience in a particular situation. These elements can be external to the graphics and therefore not linked to the data, in the form of images or drawings. Furthermore, rhetoric and embellishment elements can be part of the graph, not directly to encode the data but for example by using colour to create a specific effect (Gabrielle Merite, 2020; Scientific American, 2015), customizing the layout (Valentina D'Ef Filippo and Lucia Kocincova, 2017), rotating and superimposing graphs or through annotations (Bravo, 2020). Last, rhetoric can also be applied directly in connection to the data, often in combination with the use of custom encodings through rhetorical mapping, where the visual attributes used to encode the data, apply visual metaphors to present the data in terms of the topic, the context, or the implications (Ervin Vinzon, 2021; Kate Wong et al., 2021). Besides "mapping rhetoric", or "the information presentation via the data-to-visual transfer function" (Hullman and Diakopoulos, 2011), Hullman and Diakopoulos also describe other rhetoric techniques (e.g., information access rhetoric, provenance rhetoric, linguistic-based rhetoric, procedural rhetoric).

⁶ From The Historical Archive To The Citizens: Visualizing Census Data From Brill Street in 1922 (Aida Horaniet Ibañez et al., 2023) presents an example of the use of custom encodings to make historical data accessible to citizens.

3.2.4 Granularity

Granularity is defined in this research as the intent to disaggregate summary data typically presented in standard statistical graphs. The “grain” in a dataset is the smallest unit collected. In a data visualisation focused on granularity, importance is given to individual and unique cases behind the aggregated numbers. There might be different levels of aggregation/disaggregation, and they might be combined in the same data visualisation (drill-up/down approach). For example, in the data visualisation about the history of national team appearances in a world cup (Sonja Kuijpers, 2018), the grain would be the data related to each national team’s appearance (e.g., year, result), the semi-aggregated data would present summary metrics by country (e.g., number of appearances, total number of points), and the aggregated data would describe the worldwide data (e.g., total number of tournaments, average number of points, total number of regions). These levels of aggregation are relative to the objectives of the visualisation, since the data can be broken down from many different perspectives. The granularity presented in a data visualisation gives us an important clue as to where it is situated in the epistemological practices. On the one hand, the Natural and Applied Sciences use predominantly quantitative methods to measure an “objective” reality conceptualised as cause-effect relationships that can be generalized, that requires to summarize to explain and predict. On the other hand, the Humanities use predominantly critical and rhetorical methods to interrogate particular symbolic actions in order to understand a “subjective reality”. The closer to the “grain” the closer to the Humanities, the rhetorical analysis and the interpretation; the more aggregated, the closer to the Natural and Applied Sciences, standardization, and generalization.

Based on the collection studied, one of the most commonly used techniques is displaying individual points, icons or drawings to humanize data, such as arrests during a protest (Post, 2020), Covid-19 deaths (Pentagram, 2020), personal experiences (Lupi and Posavec, 2016) or cells in a Jupyter notebook to create a unique article fingerprint (C2DH, 2021). Another approach consists of replacing (or overlaying) traditional shapes, such as the bars in a bar chart, with the data points that constitute them (Gambrell, 2018), showing both the aggregated and the disaggregated view at the same time; or using direct visualisation (Manovich, 2011), preserving to some extent the original form of the grain (Flavio Gortana et al., 2018); (Ferry, 2020).

3.2.5 Multivariate data glyphs

A way to display multiple layers of information simultaneously, while maintaining a certain degree of granularity, is the use of multivariate data glyphs, a visual representation of data where the attributes of the graphical entity are defined by the attributes of the data record. To form the data glyphs, the encoding might rely on standard graphs and different levels of variations (Silvia Romanelli, 2022), customized visual vocabularies (Kimly Scott, 2023), or a combination of both. Every data glyph defines the lowest level of detail and they usually appear as small multiples, where each representation is derived from the same design structure, to leverage visual consistency, economy of perception and uninterrupted visual reasoning (Chuah and Eick, 1998).

3.2.6 Non-representational and interpretation

In contrast to representational approaches, in a non-representational approach, the existence of data or other representations is not assumed prior to the interpretative work. Examples include data visualisations that use visual attributes to collect data not based on measurements or observations, such as personal experience or perception (Panagiotidou et al., 2020; Pentagram, 2021; Streamers, 2013). Another example is the use of visual vocabularies for interpretation, such as the uncertainty about a time duration (Nadieh Bremer, 2016) or more complex concepts such as point of view, layers, scales or folds (Drucker, 2017). Finally, it includes data visualisations where not only the graph elements can be aesthetically modified, but also the underlying principles, using for example ambiguous categories, multidirectional or perceived timeliness (Drucker, 2011). Although these elements could be evaluated separately, I have decided to group them together because there are very few visualisations that implement them.

4 Discussion

4.1 Approaches and gaps

The classification proposed in this article helps us to understand the current landscape in data visualisation beyond disciplinary boundaries. The collection of data visualisations belonging to data humanism and humanistic interpretation allows us to identify, through numerous examples, a series of techniques linking these three classifications along the continuum of epistemological practices.

Data humanism and humanistic interpretation, both present options for shifting beyond statistical graphics. However, it is also interesting to discuss the gaps between the two as possibilities for future research. First, both promote the use of new visual vocabularies, however the "interpretative" visual language described in humanistic interpretation is perhaps more along the lines of a new standardization than the freedom to use any visual language, i.e., a specific symbol would mean attraction, as opposed to the designer deciding which representation of attraction is the most appropriate to a specific case, as it would be the case in data humanism. Second, both use variations of statistical graphs: In data humanism the aesthetics of the graph elements are modified, while in humanistic interpretation, the basic principles of their construction are challenged. Even so, aesthetically, the latter seems closer to the statistical graphs. In the literature, data humanism and humanistic interpretation are closer to each other than to statistical graphics (e.g., relevance of context to situate the data, transparency of the design process). However, based on the examples analyzed in the gallery, visually, it is data humanism that is more distant. In addition, we find numerous examples that symbolize the gradual transition between statistical graphics and data humanism, as well as between statistical graphics and humanistic interpretation (in proportion to the lower number of examples available in this category). We do not find so many examples situated between data humanism and humanistic interpretation, though. This leads to the question of what case studies would require such a combination, and how to bridge this gap between the two approaches, which are not the same.

4.2 Future applications and development

The techniques discussed above, among others, have been applied in the continuation of the LuxTIME project to facilitate interdisciplinary work (Aida Horaniet Ibañez and Dagny Aurich, 2023). In addition, the identified techniques could be used as a reference to standardize certain functionalities in the existing data visualisation tools, since as we can observe, most of them have been created either with design programs (e.g. Adobe Illustrator), sacrificing the connection with the data and the interactivity; or with programming libraries such as (d3.js), limiting the accessibility to users without development knowledge. With some basic statistical and digital knowledge, any user can create standard statistical charts using tools like Excel or Tableau. However, moving away from statistical graphics requires specialized tools. This implies that the natural and applied sciences are not exposed to other approaches, and that the Humanities, which need these techniques for interpretative work, are limited to quantitative analysis and standard visualisations. Without any doubt, some of the elements discussed above, especially regarding rhetorical elements and customized visual vocabularies, have a degree of variability that makes their development challenging, but offering some options would already be a step forward. Despite the existence of many successful design studies specific to the Digital Humanities e.g., (McCurdy et al., 2016) and tools that address one or more humanities challenges (e.g., Voyant), these are rarely integrated into other existing tools, so often their impact remains limited. Such integration would support the cross-fertilisation between the different approaches and facilitate the use of different methods and techniques in disciplinary and interdisciplinary contexts.

In this analysis, I have decided to group together certain techniques that could be analyzed extensively on their own. However, the lack of a gallery of data visualisations that would allow us to do so, and in cases, such as in humanistic interpretation, the lack of applied examples, make the disaggregation difficult at this stage. This gallery has been created with the objective of having a reference point for the analysis of data visualisation across disciplines and beyond the standard statistical graphs. There are other galleries (Maarten Lambrechts, 2023; Manuel Lima, 2014; Yan Holtz, 2022), but to the best of my knowledge, none focused on the analysis of the approaches described in this research. Future research can leverage this collection and extend the metadata (e.g., time period, sources, interactivity) to perform further analyses, or the identified techniques used could be studied independently in more detail. The collection could be enlarged collaboratively, or automatically through the use of image similarity algorithms. It is worth noting that from the beginning of the project, when I started collecting data visualisations about two and a half years ago, almost one-fifth of the links have been lost. Many of these projects come from social networks, personal blogs, company websites, newspapers and magazines, and other media with very variable lifespans. Consequently, it would be necessary to archive all the visualisation websites in a lasting way (e.g., using web archives), that allows us to maintain and do further research taking into account their specific context, and not only the images.

4.3 The role of the digital humanities

In recent years, numerous research projects in the field of Digital Humanities have focused on other ways to visualise data (Brüggemann et al., 2020; Hinrichs et al., 2019;

Lauren Klein et al., 2016). However, in research articles, as discussed above, the use of standard statistical graphics presenting summary metrics, and network diagrams to depict relationships, continues to predominate. It is possible that by gradually integrating techniques from different disciplines that allow us to walk along this line between objectivity and subjectivity, first in a "manual" way, and then standardizing them in the tools, the possibilities available to all the disciplines will increase. The development of these tools requires researchers accustomed to working in an interdisciplinary way encompassing quantitative and qualitative methods, computational analysis and development, but also familiar with rhetorical analysis and interpretation, as well as the use of aesthetic methods and the creation of knowledge through experience. All these factors are present in the Digital Humanities, which places them in a strong position to advance the field of data visualisation.

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Balancing Education and Engagement: A Suggested Co-design Process for Historical Game Development

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Historical game development is a still-emerging area of Digital Humanities theory and praxis that crosses and challenges many disciplinary borders. Requiring strong humanities expertise in historical research and educational theory, as well as many artistic and technical skills from the fields of computer science, digital art, and game design, such projects foster strong multi-disciplinary teams. This paper discusses the co-authors’ ongoing collaboration to develop an educational historical game called *The Migrants’ Chronicles*, which seeks to balance pedagogical goals with engaging gameplay in order to create a game that is equally fun and educational. After providing an overview of the project origins, a detailed discussion of the pedagogical concepts driving the game, and the practical methodologies used to translate historical knowledge into game play, the paper concludes by suggesting a series of best practices for a collaborative co-design process for historical game development.

Keywords: History, Game Studies, Game Design and Development, Migration, Digital Pedagogy, Education, Mapping, Spatial Humanities

1 Introduction

In the past several decades, history-based video games have become increasingly popular, sophisticated and economically successful. Games from leading commercial studios like the *Assassin’s Creed* series, *Age of Empires*, and Sid Meier’s *Civilization* are eagerly played by millions, and public interest in their historicity is high. *History Respawned* and similar YouTube channels feature playthroughs with running commentary by professional historians that garner thousands of views, while sites like *Play the Past* host essays that dissect the intersection of cultural heritage and games for a public audience (Roy and Christiansen, 2024; Whitaker, 2013).

Figure 1: The logo for the first installment of *The Migrants' Chronicles*.

Academics and educators have taken notice. There is a large and growing body of literature that tackles the challenges of teaching history with and through commercial video games, where historical accuracy has often been sacrificed for the sake of entertainment (Burgess and Jones, 2022; Kee, 2014; Kee et al., 2009). Game designers are also acutely aware of the challenge of balancing authenticity and playability in historical games, and much has been written on this topic from the point of view of game developers as well (Lelièvre, 2019; Lux et al., 2021). Most educators and game designers would agree that the best path to develop quality historical games would be to balance pedagogical goals with engaging gameplay in order to create games that are equally fun and educational. Yet very little scholarship has been devoted to outlining practical methodologies for creating such balanced games.

This paper discusses the co-authors' ongoing collaboration to develop a balanced educational historical game, called *The Migrants' Chronicles*. Historical game creation is a still emerging area of Digital Humanities theory and praxis that crosses and challenges many disciplinary borders. Requiring strong humanities expertise in historical research and educational theory, as well as many artistic and technical skills from the fields of computer science, digital art, and game design, such projects foster strong multi-disciplinary teams. Our particular project concerns migrations across national and linguistic borders that force a consideration of multilingualism both historically (in the language barriers our migrants encounter in-game) and procedurally (in the need to work with numerous languages for team communication and product localization for multiple publics). After providing an overview of the project origins and a detailed discussion of the pedagogical concepts driving the game and the methods used to translate historical knowledge into game play, the paper concludes by suggesting a series of best practices for a collaborative co-design process for historical game development. The central question is how the insights of historical research can be translated into game principles without overly unbalancing the playability or the educational content of the game.

2 Overview: The Migrants' Chronicles 1892

The Migrants' Chronicles is a digital history game aimed at middle grade students (11-14 years old) in which players actively learn about migration history through a simulated migration experience. Like the classic text-based game *The Oregon Trail*, *The Migrants' Chronicles* allows players to confront the difficult choices historical migrants had to

Figure 2: The playable character choice screen at the start of the game.

navigate in order to successfully leave their homes, travel long distances, and arrive safely in a new country, but updated to reflect the latest advances in technology, game design, and pedagogical strategies. The pilot episode traces the historical migrations of Luxembourgers to the United States in the late nineteenth-century.

This first instalment is set in 1892, when the US opened Ellis Island as an immigration station, and just before the first Chicago World's Fair, which employed many Luxembourg tradespeople. Students choose one of three playable characters: a widow with young children, a wealthy couple with a family vineyard, or a young craftsman from the rural north of the country (Figure 2). As they race against the clock to get to the US, they make critical decisions along the way - such as what to pack or which port to leave from - each with its own set of consequences.

While the journey itself is presented on a world map that can be scrolled and zoomed (Figure 3), the main interactions take place at the central stations of the journey, i.e. in cities such as Luxembourg, Brussels, Paris and Hamburg, on the passenger ship crossing the Atlantic, or on Ellis Island. All of these locations offer opportunities for interaction, which may be necessary to organize the journey, but can also open up side quests and provide historical information. Another central game mechanic involves the management of finite resources: money, time, possessions, nutrition, and mental and physical health, which are tracked on in-game character sheets. An auto-generated diary translates the events of the game into a story formulated from the point of view of the character being played.

2.1 The Migrants' Chronicles Consortium

The game is being developed by an international and multilingual consortium of academics, game developers and students. The *Faculty of Humanities, Education and Social Sciences of the University of Luxembourg* contributes competencies in historical research, historical pedagogy and, through its Department of Behavioural and Cognitive Sciences, also qualifications in psychological evaluation to the project. The *Cologne*

Figure 3: The in-game map showing routes traveled and discovered through game play.

Game Lab of the University of Applied Sciences Cologne brings expertise in digital art, programming and game design theory, while the *Digital Arts & Humanities program at Carleton College (USA)* brings a record of innovation and experimentation in Digital Humanities and History pedagogy to the collaboration. The core team consists of Marie-Paule Jungblut and Johannes Pause, a public history expert and a media scientist from the University of Luxembourg, a group of game designers and developers from the Cologne Game Lab led by Prof. Emmanuel Guardiola and Franziska Funken, and Austin Mason, a historian and digital humanities expert at Carleton College. Undergraduate and graduate students at all three institutions are also key members of the team, who contribute vital learning perspectives and research skills to the project.

The multidisciplinary nature of our game development team is intentional and designed with educational goals at all stages. The collaboration is not hierarchical, but consortial: an interdisciplinary working group proposes concepts for the implementation of historical material in the game, which are critiqued, refined and implemented by the entire team in regular meetings. By working collaboratively in this way, humanities scholars learn to see digital games as tools that add value to knowledge transfer, while game developers learn to interact with humanities scholars as providers of meaningful content, and undergraduate and graduate students in multiple fields gain valuable experience in team-based digital humanities research and development.

2.2 Development History

The initial concept phase of the project began in early 2020 through shared interests between the project leads and pre-existing connections between the three primary institutions. With a total budget of roughly €500,000, the initiative received funding

Figure 4: Concept art tested with students from the target age group in the pre-production phase to inform player-centred educational game design choices.

from the Oeuvre Nationale de Secours Grand-Duchesse Charlotte, the Service de Coordination de la Recherche et de l'Innovation pédagogiques et technologiques (SCRIPT) of the Ministry of Education and Digital Luxembourg, along with financial and in-kind contributions from the project team's home institutions: the University of Luxembourg, TH Köln, and Carleton College. A timeline was established with a pre-production phase to start in 2020, a production phase in 2021 and a target initial release in 2023, although that timeline was pushed back to early 2024 due to complications of covid pandemic working conditions and bureaucratic challenges of transferring funds to partners across international borders.

The pre-production phase proceeded throughout 2020, with research on both sides of the Atlantic establishing the necessary historical reference material in many different forms: images, maps, and GIS datasets all served as an essential complement and corrective to traditional textual sources (Marti-Henneberg et al., 2021, e.g.). Luxembourgish emigration to the USA is well documented in the Luxembourg National Archives, the Library of Congress in the USA, and in many smaller museums and archives like the Red Star Line Museum in Antwerp, Belgium and the Luxembourg American Cultural Center Museum in Belgium, Wisconsin. Documentary sources, particularly surviving diaries and letters of historical migrants, were used to establish a draft narrative arc for the game, while visual sources informed several concept art prototypes that were tested with students of the target 11-14 year old age group in June 2021. While the adult members of the design team preferred the collage aspects of several designs that incorporated historical photos and hand drawn line art, the overwhelming response of student testers was in favor of the more familiar digital art style in the top right image of Figure 4. Following player-centred educational game design principles (Guardiola et al., 2019), we respected the target audience participation in the creative process and chose that design style for the game art.

After initial interviews were conducted with teachers at Luxembourg schools to refine the educational goals of the project, the production phase of development started

in July 2022 and the team delivered a beta version targeted to Android tablets to make a pilot educational impact evaluation in April 2023. This version was then tested in two school classes for its usability and motivational potential (Mayer, 2019). The usability tests yielded many insights that were incorporated into the development of the game and helped to improve its playability - for example, by shortening the dialogues, by improving the menus, or by better integrating individual events into the main narrative of the game. Students also confirmed that the game was motivating and contributed to a greater personal ownership of the topic of migration, though this has not yet been systematically evaluated.

Following the initial release of the game in early 2024 on the Apple App Store and Google Play Store (for use on iOS and Android mobile devices and ChromeOS Chromebooks), a more rigorous impact evaluation is planned to assess the educational potential of the game. While the beta tests focused primarily on discrete features of gameplay, such as comparing a time-based approach with a turn-based approach (see Section 5.2), the impact evaluation will assess the value of the game as an educational tool. We plan to investigate the success of our game design choices on educational outcomes using approaches from various models of serious games analysis like the Learning Mechanics-Game Mechanics and Activity Theory-based Model of Serious Games frameworks (Arnab et al., 2015; Carvalho et al., 2015). However, the pilot test results already indicate that *The Migrants' Chronicles* can serve as a template that can accept a variety of content of other historical and contemporary migratory waves. Future episodes could look at different immigrant experiences, such as modern emigration from the Middle East to Europe, or climate migration, for example. We will open source the code so that developers can freely develop their own variants to pursue whatever migration stories they wish to tell.

2.3 Potential Impact

The Migrants' Chronicles 1892 is primarily intended for middle-grade students (11-14 years old) for use in formal educational environments and in museums. Developed in English and translated into Luxembourgish, the bilingual game is targeted for use in Luxembourg and the USA, but will be accessible to any English-speaking players. Educators may include the game in school curriculum units on migration and in museum educational programs in a number of ways (see Section 3). Teaching educators how to use the game will also be an essential part of the next phase of the project. In Luxembourg, this will occur as part of the continuing education of teachers and training sessions for museum educators. In the US, the project team will collaborate with specific museums and middle schools in Luxembourgish communities and seek to introduce its pedagogical potential during teacher professional development sessions in Minnesota.

The historical scenario also allows for a general discussion of migration; by fostering empathy for historical emigrants, the game implicitly raises the question of how to deal with issues of immigration today. As Luxembourg is currently known primarily as a destination for immigrants, the game addresses an issue (net *emigration*) that is rarely discussed in public in Luxembourg. In 2020, the Luxembourg National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies described Luxembourg explicitly as a "land of immigration" (STATEC, 2020). Indeed, in 2019, Luxembourg's immigration rate was 16.3 per thousand, compared to 2.6 per thousand in the EU. On the one hand, immigration is based on the country's prosperous economy, with a GDP per capita of \$136,701 in 2022 (Ivanov et al., 2022). On the other hand, Luxembourg is a signatory

to the 1951 Geneva Refugee Convention. In May 2023 alone, 219 people from countries such as Syria, Eritrea, Algeria, Turkey, Ukraine, Afghanistan, Morocco, Albania, Tunisia and Guinea-Conakry applied for international refugee protection (Le Gouvernement du Grand-duché de Luxembourg). Against this backdrop, it is all too easy to forget that in the nineteenth century the country was a land of emigration due to poor harvests, high taxes and unemployment. *The Migrants' Chronicles: 1892* commemorates the emigration of Luxembourgers to the US, thus offering young players an opportunity for increased understanding of the complex issues surrounding migration, both historical and contemporary.

3 Pedagogical Concept

The Migrants' Chronicles can be categorized as a “serious game” because it has “an explicit and carefully thought-out educational purpose and [is] not intended to be played primarily for amusement” (Abt, 1987). Research on serious games has shown that learning success depends greatly on how well such games are embedded in appropriate classroom activities (Bellotti et al., 2010). In our case, *The Migrants' Chronicles* will serve as an interactive component of a broader teaching unit on the topic of migration. The game itself should take less than an hour to play, but should motivate students to play it several times. Depending on how it is embedded, it can be played as a preparation for a lesson at home, or as a prelude or conclusion to a series of sessions on migration.

The overall learning objectives of the lesson include enabling students to 1) identify reasons for emigration at specific points in space and time (e.g. Luxembourg 1892), 2) describe the migration process as an intercultural experience, and 3) compare historical and contemporary migration movements. Aims of the game are not only to increase the motivation of the pupils and to provide material for class discussion, but above all to contribute to an embodiment of knowledge (Coltrain and Ramsay, 2019): By playing an individual migration experience, it becomes possible to make comparisons with the pupils' own migration experiences or with current migration movements discussed in the media. In this way, the game encourages people to explore history from the perspective of the present, with reference to their own experiences and to current issues. Additionally, the game provides insight into the everyday culture of the late nineteenth-century, as well as the political power structures of the time and their impact on individuals. To achieve these ends, we have incorporated into our design process several pedagogical approaches and theoretical frameworks from educational and game studies.

3.1 Science of Learning and Game Studies Theories

When used in schools, *The Migrants' Chronicles* aims in the first instance to foster empathy for those who had to emigrate in the past by allowing students to wrestle with the often-difficult choices faced by historical migrants. Similar to the classic 1970s serious game *The Oregon Trail*, the game relies on travel as a narrative structure and employs problem-based game mechanics (McCall, 2012) that make existential hardships, such as disease or hunger, tangible. The game thus draws on the challenges of organizing a journey, which students can relate to from their own lives, but at the same time highlights the historical differences between traveling in 1892 and 2023. This approach follows the concept of *generative learning* – “the process of constructing

Figure 5: "Stealth learning" possibilities in *The Migrants' Chronicles* include meeting famous historical figures, like the painter Claude Monet.

meaning through generating relationships and associations between stimuli and existing knowledge, beliefs, and experiences" (Hanke, 2012) –, by placing learners in a specific historical situation that builds upon their everyday knowledge but requires them to adapt and transform this knowledge.

The game's basic structure is scenario-based, containing various migration scenarios that can be compared. In each episode, students can play different characters who emigrate for different reasons, encounter different challenges, and settle in different locations. Future possible episodes that explore more recent migration events (for example, where refugees from Ukraine or Syria travel to Luxembourg), might allow players to identify similarities and differences between distinct waves of migration. Besides learning *about* history, the game thus also seeks to enable learning *from* history. The game scenarios generate *procedural knowledge* that is situational and perspective-based (Rooney, 2012). During class discussion or other follow-up activities, this knowledge can later be transformed into *declarative knowledge* (e.g. more abstract knowledge about the transformation of Luxembourgish/US-American society through migration).

Alongside the problem-based mechanics of the core gameplay, there is also a more exploratory dynamic within the game that takes advantage of a game-based learning strategy called "stealth learning" (Gee, 2003). A *stealth learning* approach seeks to "hide" the serious content within a fun game, so that players may notice only after playing that they have learned something useful (Dörner et al., 2016). During journey's within *The Migrants' Chronicles*, players encounter situations that extend beyond the game's main tasks and offer the opportunity for exploratory discovery. For instance, characters in the game may interact with famous individuals of that time like Claude

Monet (Figure 5); discover contemporary novels, culturally distinctive foods, historical media technologies, or location-specific souvenirs; or encounter norms and cultural conventions that might be shocking or surprising from a modern perspective, such as historical attitudes about gender roles or discrimination. While the core problem-based game mechanics align with *cognitivist theories of learning*, the game here thus also seeks to facilitate a *constructivist type of learning* (Hwang and Kim, 2016; Wu et al., 2012). Through play, students combine information from different contexts to form a comprehensive understanding of the time, which they will be asked to reexamine and articulate upon completing the game.

This stealth learning pedagogical aim depends upon players experiencing a certain level of immersion within the game. Janet Murray (Murray, 2017, pp.98-99) describes immersion as the feeling of being surrounded by a completely different reality that engages our entire attention, our entire perceptual apparatus. *The Migrants' Chronicles* does not aim for perceptually realistic immersion as in 3D simulations, but rather for imaginative and challenge-based immersion mechanisms (Ermi and Mäyrä, 2011, p.103) that arise from the flow of the game's perspective-taking experience. The game's representation of the historical world remains deliberately stylized, following a "conceptual simulation style" that is "concerned with exploring the systems and processes behind history" (Copplestone, 2017, p.419). As such, the game focuses on key information that players must interpret and mentally assemble into a coherent picture of the period (Barton and Maharg, 2006, p.117).

4 Balancing Veracity, Empathy, and Playability

Attempting to teach history through interactive gameplay naturally raises questions about historical fidelity, and the appropriate balance between historical veracity, historical empathy, and playability. Here, we use Lisa Gilbert's (Gilbert, 2019) definition of historical empathy in video games as comprising both elements of *perspective recognition* (a sense of otherness/shared normalcy, and contextualization of past and present) and *caring* (about history, for historical actors, that it mattered, and to apply lessons learned to the present). To what extent then does a game need to reconstruct historical facts accurately to be pedagogically valuable? Can 'errors' within a game be used for educational purposes, for example? And how is it possible to mediate between different concepts of historical accuracy (Copplestone, 2017)? For a serious game on a historical topic, we have taken the view that authenticity (recreating plausible conditions encountered by historical actors) is more crucial than absolute accuracy (meticulously capturing every historically attested detail) (McCall, 2019; McCall and Chapman, 2017, 2018).

4.1 Historical Veracity

We have conducted extensive research on historical characters, important events, and places to ground the game in concrete facts of late nineteenth-century Europe and America. This does not mean, however, that a serious game should become a mere historical reconstruction, plotting a historically attested personal biography from point A to Z. In order to play a game, as opposed to a virtual simulation, a player must be able to make non-trivial decisions with unsure outcomes; if the outcome is completely predictable, it is no longer a game. To remain motivated, therefore, players must feel free to make their own decisions. But while commercial games often give their players

the freedom to change the historical circumstances over the long term, serious games usually aim for a game design that only allows for actions that are historically possible. The question of what can be considered 'historically possible' is not always easy to answer. In the case of the often-documented fates of emigrants, however, it seems obvious to classify as 'possible' those game paths for which correspondences can be found in historical sources. *The Migrants' Chronicles: 1892* has constructed all of our scenarios from details researched in surviving letters, diaries, and other relevant historical sources, but crafted a choice of narratives that are more akin to historical fiction than absolute fact.

Commercial games with historical settings also tend to combine historical sources with other literary, artistic and popular culture references, which would be problematic in a serious game. For example, the *Assassin's Creed* series is known for its detailed historical reconstructions, and *Assassin's Creed: Odyssey* (2018), which is set in ancient Greece, even has a discovery mode in which players can freely explore the reconstructed historical world and learn about history, religion, architecture, everyday life and other areas of knowledge (Chapman, 2018, p.38). However, the game mixes its reconstruction of history with a pop-cultural mashup logic, bringing popular myths and popular cultural adaptations into the game. *Assassin's Creed: Odyssey* quotes Herodotus as well as Zack Snyder's highly stylised comic book adaptation *300* (USA 2006); it allows you to climb the meticulously reconstructed lighthouse of Alexandria as well as fight the mythological Nemean Lion (Cole, 2022). This mashup strategy, characteristic of many games, makes it clear that history games – whether commercial or educational – always presuppose a certain state of memory culture (Caselli, 2021). However, it is incumbent on educational game creators to critically question popular historical misconceptions, and encourage players to do so as well (Boom et al., 2020).

The mediation between historical accuracy and playability can be seen as a central challenge in the design of serious history games, and has become a major area of research in game studies. Matthew Kapell and Andrew Elliott consider the "veracity of games that engage with history [to be] less about their ability to represent an accurate past and more about their ability to present what 'feels' like an authentic one" (Kapell and Elliott, 2013, p.361). Such a feeling is created, for example, by conveying the game world through the perspective of a historical actor that could have been involved in the processes depicted. Verisimilitude does not mean that all actions, possessions and utterances of the game character have to be accurately documented, but that they are credible and consistent within the historical scenario. According to Adam Chapman (Chapman, 2018, p.272), the translation of historical sources into playable stories that correspond to historically possible courses of action already represents an interpretation of history. By influencing these courses of action and choosing between different options, the players can experimentally test the ideas they have about a historical epoch and playfully create new interpretations.

4.2 Historical Empathy

For this reason, educational games that seek to bring their players closer to a specific historical period tend to rely on the empathy effect created by the playful experience of a personal history. Some games achieve this effect using a graphic first-person perspective, such as *Walden, a game* (USC Games, USA 2017) or *Blackhaven* (Historiated Games, USA 2021), while others choose a more abstract representation of reality inside the game world, in which the individual experience is conveyed more strongly through game mechanics, narration and text (Bai et al., 2023). In both approaches, the empathy

Figure 6: Decisions in the game are turned into first-person diary entries at the end of each day, increasing players' historical empathy for the playable characters.

that players develop with the historical protagonists whose fates they relive leads to a better understanding of their actions. The difference to other narrative media such as film or the historical novel lies precisely in the experience of variable plot designs (Böhme et al., 2014, p.7): games focus less on what historical actors actually did and more on how their scope for decision-making was structured, i.e. what alternatives were available to them and under what constraints and hardships they had to act. They are therefore suitable for a form of historical study that seeks contemporary references: In this understanding, historical consciousness includes an interpretation of the past that provides a framework of orientation for the present (Hintermann, 2007, p.483).

In line with these considerations, *The Migrant's Chronicles* focuses on the individual experiences of well-developed game characters, who are not taken directly from historical sources and are therefore not historical figures, but in which various experiences of historical migrants are brought together in a condensed form. The 1892 game begins with an explanation of the decision to emigrate, which also sets the boundaries for the decisions that can be made during the game: some of the characters have to reach the USA in a certain amount of time, others have money problems, and so on. Accordingly, the options during the journey are different for each player. Also, the diary and the dialogue system in *The Migrant's Chronicles* reinforce a strong element of perspective-taking on the historical events depicted: In the diary, events are narrated from the first-person perspective of the game character and are thus integrated into a historical point of view for which the player takes more responsibility with each game decision (Figure 6). In the dialogues, players can choose between different possible answers, each within the framework of what the historical game character might actually have thought. Certain answers that the players would give from today's perspective are

excluded in this way. Again, through their choices, the players become more familiar with certain historical perspectives by taking charge of them directly.

5 Translating Knowledge to Game Design

While the selection of a date and elaboration of the possible characters was the starting point of our game development, many of the central game mechanics were only created during the design process in a continual dialogue between the historians, media scholars, and game developers on the production team. As in many Digital Humanities collaborations, *The Migrants' Chronicles* project team is deliberately multi-disciplinary, and from the beginning we adopted an iterative process that involves continual co-design at all stages of the project.

Although common in DH, such an open approach is, in fact, in stark contrast to the usual development process for historical video games, where either 1) a game development studio has an idea for a project and hires historical advisors as consultants, or 2) a historian or educator has an idea and hires a game studio to build an educational game to their specifications. Research has shown that historical video games are thereby usually created by an industry whose modes of production tend to support hegemonic interpretations of history as well as other existing power structures (Hammar, 2019). A successfully balanced historical game, on the other hand, is according to our experience best created by an interdisciplinary team paying attention to and respecting the expertise that different members bring to the table and holding regular meetings to iteratively refine the balance of different perspectives. Moreover, such collaboration allows students from different disciplines (history, game design, DH) to get directly involved in the interdisciplinary development of the game. In this way, not only the finished product but also the production process itself generates educational benefits.

In the following sections, we discuss three examples of problems we encountered during development of *The Migrants' Chronicles*, where this continual co-design process led to concrete solutions that better balanced authenticity and playability and increased both the educational and ludic impact of the project: bridging the past and present through strategies to generate historical empathy (Section 5.1); representing the passage of time in game (Section 5.2); and helping teachers turn students' individual game play experiences into collective classroom learning (Section 5.3).

5.1 Building Historical Empathy for Luxembourg Migration

Although some historians believe that as many as 25% of Luxembourgers left their homeland between 1841 and 1891, the history of emigration is still underrepresented in the collective memory of the established population. As a result, the Luxembourg-American cultural heritage has not yet been recognised as part of Luxembourg's cultural heritage. The fact that emigration is not part of Luxembourg's official policy of remembrance makes it virtually impossible for the population that has immigrated to Luxembourg to relate to it (Wiegmann). *The Migrants' Chronicles 1892* therefore faces a double challenge: on the one hand, it wants to initiate a process of historical learning that will lead young people with and without an immigrant background to recognise the material and immaterial evidence of Luxembourg's emigration history as Luxembourg's cultural heritage. On the other hand, it wants to contribute to young people recognising the testimonies of the cultural heritage of different immigrant

Figure 7: The physical and emotional health of playable characters *and their dependents* are tracked in-game, where afflictions from homesickness to cholera can affect the outcomes.

groups as cultural assets, even if they do not accept them as relevant to themselves.

But how can students be persuaded to build empathy with characters with whom they think they have nothing in common? As mentioned above, the game takes two basic strategies from the prototypes on which it is based: the educational game classic *The Oregon Trail* (1974), which was used in US schools as early as in the 1970s, and the more recent migration game *Bury Me, My Love* (2017). The former focuses on the organization of a pioneer trek to new settlement areas in Oregon in the mid-nineteenth century, and is primarily based on the management of resources that keep the settlers alive. The latter develops its plot in the form of a dialogue between a woman who has fled Homs, Syria, and her family who remain in their homeland, which takes place via Whatsapp. These two mechanisms - the management of resources and the narrative that unfolds through dialogue - are also central for the 'empathy strategy' of *The Migrants' Chronicles: 1892*.

Empathy for the playable characters is created in the game primarily by placing existential hardships such as illness, hunger or economic constraints at the center of the plot. The story is then retold in the diary from the characters' perspective. As already mentioned, the diary entries summarize the decisions made by the players and supplement this information with descriptions of the characters' emotional states and health, as well as other events to which the players must react. The homesickness of a child the character must care for, for example, can thus have a significant impact on the game (Figure 7). Like in *The Oregon Trail*, the main topic of the game is the organization of a journey, which allows an immediate understanding of the task and the difficulties to be overcome. The organization of the journey defines a "problem space" (McCall, 2012) that is already known to the students, but which has to be

mastered in a new situation. The problem allows for a number of different solutions, but at the same time clearly limits the field of possible actions. For example, there are a number of destinations to choose from that are not necessarily close by, such as Bremen and London, so detours can lead to delays and create new problems. Historical and random events, such as the outbreak of a cholera epidemic, on the other hand, can influence the decisions of the players, so that the feeling of freedom of choice is repeatedly confronted with the hardships that existed in the real historical situation.

Although the players cannot change the general historical or biographical conditions in which the characters act, the choices offered by the game do go beyond those available to historical travelers. In fact, most emigrants in the nineteenth century had their journeys organized by agencies, so they hardly made any decisions themselves beyond the initial one of contracting with an agent. To make this discrepancy apparent within the game, it was decided to implement two different game modes: After successfully completing the 'adventure mode', which simulates the unusual case of a self-organized journey, players can also experience a pre-organised journey in which they have only few options for intervention. The experience of passivity contradicts the medium of the game and thus also allows a reflection on the medial character of historical representations, which can also be extended to other media, such as books and films in popular culture. By juxtaposing an adventure mode with an authenticity mode, the game thus aims to reflect on the player's relationship to the historical characters and to the medium of games as such.

5.2 The Representation of Time

It is a commonplace to say that the past seems distant and disconnected from our current experiences. Young people might show resistance to acquiring knowledge about a subject that appears to have no contemporary relevance. The challenge of any history game is to make players understand people and events that no longer hold any presence in the present. This is especially true for travel experiences that were very different in the nineteenth century before the advent of planes and automobiles. A crucial aspect of this is time: journeys in the past simply took much longer than they do today. However, *The Migrants Chronicles* is designed to be played in a short time: less than an hour for a typical school lesson. The questions that arise: How to condense a 17-day journey into a game that needs to be played within a school class period of approximately 50 minutes? How to make the users experience and appreciate the passage of time during the journey?

The representation of time is crucial to the game's concept, as time is one of the three resources that players have to manage, along with money and health, which are in constant conflict (Figure 8, left). For example, an illness can force the player to stay in one place for a longer period of time, while the decision to use faster means of transport usually costs more money. In consideration of the balance between historical accuracy and playability, the team's first strategy was time-based, meaning that the passage of time would be represented by time itself. A timer would run in the background that would automatically end a "day" after an arbitrary amount of minutes, forcing players to distribute their food and rest overnight.

The development team implemented this approach to support the speed at which players move through the game, and to transfer in-game timeframes, such as an 8-hour train journey, into the game world. However, through playtesting the team realized that this mechanic was confusing, frustrating and too complex for the scope of the game, since night would often fall arbitrarily in the middle of a conversation or day-

Figure 8: To represent time, the most challenging of the three resources players must manage, the game controller uses activity points, each converted to a number of hours for the player in order to balance game logic demands with historical understanding.

time action. It was decided to iterate the game design to make it more fit for purpose and drop the time approach to work with activity points instead (Figure 8, right).

Activity points would be earned by completing actions (dialogues, purchases, travel legs, etc.), with a low cap on the number of points available in a single in-game day. This had the benefit of preventing awkward disruptions for night time, but raised its own concerns. For the educational goals of *The Migrants' Chronicles*, it was crucial that players remain aware of the passage of time so that they get a sense of the slower rate and longer duration of all forms of travel in the nineteenth century. The final decision was to retain points within the game controller logic, but to assign each a number of hours when displayed to the user: two activity points represent one day. This means that the player has to think carefully about how to use the limited hours of daylight. Sometimes, however, an activity point must be spent 'doing nothing', representing the passing of time: for example, when waiting for a train. This approach reinforces the learning goal of planning the journey with care and attention in order to successfully complete it, but it also gives players agency to engage with the content in their own time frame. The game can be played in a condensed way, by flying through all activities in perhaps half an hour, or slowed down to last for several hours of leisurely gameplay. The choices different players make can therefore impact both how much of the game they encounter and how deliberately they reflect on those experiences for their own learning.

5.3 The Facilitation of Teaching

Since the game is intended to be played in a formal educational setting, a major development goal was to facilitate the ability of teachers to incorporate the game into their classrooms. During initial interviews with teachers at Luxembourg schools and throughout the development of the game, a number of "instructional tools" (Carvalho et al., 2015, p.174) were designed and refined to enable the teacher to address the learning success of the game. They include a debriefing feature for teachers and a tool that allows students to download game data, including the map, diary entries and transport information from their individual journeys. Both are valuable tools for educators, which are to be used in different ways:

- Individual player analysis: The debriefing feature allows teachers to access a

detailed breakdown of each player's decisions during the game. This includes decisions made, resources used and progress made. This information can help teachers identify individual strengths and areas for improvement.

- **Comparative analysis:** Teachers can compare the decisions and outcomes of different players. This feature is valuable for class discussions, as it allows students to learn from each other's strategies and see the consequences of different choices.
- **Discussion guides:** Within the debriefing feature, it is possible to provide discussion guides or prompts that teachers can use to facilitate meaningful post-game discussions. These prompts could encourage critical thinking, analysis of consequences and exploration of alternative strategies.
- **Alignment with learning objectives:** It is essential that the debriefing function is aligned with the specific learning objectives of the game. Teachers should be able to see how each player's decisions relate to the desired educational outcomes.

To facilitate both individual journeys and classroom comparisons, the development team included the ability to download a first-person perspective "travelogue" PDF, and a GeoJSON file of the route taken from point of emigration to final destination.

- **Game Data PDF:** The Game Data PDF will contain comprehensive information about the game session. This can include a summary of the scenario, key decision points, a timeline of events and a breakdown of each player's actions.
- **Diary entries:** Automatically generated journal entries from the players' in-game journeys will capture their thought processes and the challenges they faced. The teacher can discuss the reasoning behind the decisions with the students.
- **Transportation data:** The PDF shows the summary statistics as well as the means of transport used by each player between cities. This information can be useful for discussions about resource management and efficiency
- **GeoJSON integration:** The GeoJSON file allows teachers and students to visualize the routes taken by different players on a map. They can be used to track the routes that the different players took and combine them to a map, which can help students better understand the spatial aspects of the game and the consequences of their decisions.

The GeoJSON file has to be user-friendly, which means that it needs to be easily manipulated by both teachers and students. This means that the development team needs to consider including features such as layering, switching between player routes, and highlighting key locations or events on the map. Part of the teacher training, which also contains a set of guidelines for guiding the students during playing, will be to show them how to integrate the game data into subsequent lessons. They can use the information to illustrate real-world applications of the concepts covered in the game and to encourage discussion about decision making in complex scenarios.

It is therefore important that the features are user-friendly for both teachers and students. The team will seek feedback from educators during the development process and after initial release to ensure that the debriefing and data analysis tools effectively meet their needs. The debriefing and data download features are key to supporting the interaction between the in-game experiences and the desired knowledge transfer and ensuring the success of the pedagogical goals of the project.

6 Conclusion

The open development process used to produce *The Migrants' Chronicles* has contributed to a number of decisions being made that were not envisaged by any of the team members before the collaboration began. Section 5 has shown that these are often rather minor refinements to the mechanics of the game, but can potentially make a big educational difference. While this paper has largely focused on the descriptions of these game mechanics and their impacts, we will conclude by attempting to characterize in more detail the mode of tri-national collaboration between historians, DH specialists, media scholars, educators, and game developers in Germany, Luxembourg and the USA that made these decisions possible.

Based on our experiences collaborating to develop *The Migrants' Chronicles* as a balanced educational historical game, we have identified a number of emergent principles and practices, which we think would benefit others as a model co-design process for historical game development, with implications for creating other historical digital humanities projects that cross languages, borders and disciplinary boundaries.

1. Continuous Collaborative Co-Design

A successful balanced historical game must be developed through an iterative process of true collaboration that involves continual co-design at all stages of the project. No one on the team should be merely a consultant or implementer of other's ideas. A successful balanced historical game is best created by an interdisciplinary team paying attention to and respecting the expertise that different members bring to the table and holding regular meetings to iteratively refine the balance of different perspectives. As the example of the treatment of time has shown, such an approach is suitable for creating workable compromises between the different pedagogical and technical demands placed on an educational game. At the same time, such collaboration not only results in a superior finished product, but also allows students from different disciplines to learn from the interdisciplinary development process throughout the production of the game.

2. Design with Purpose

The desired impact of a balanced historical game on the end user needs to be clearly defined, centered consistently in the development process, and used to drive the work of all team members. Since the goal of educational games is not to sell x number of copies or merely to entertain, decisions about what to include or how to structure engaging game play must always foreground the intended purpose of the project. In historical games, players should usually gain a deeper understanding of historical processes and an increased empathy for playable characters' experiences. These considerations must guide decisions about the allocation of limited development resources; the scope and timing of deliverables; and the flexibility to refine initial parameters of the project at regular intervals, e.g. after testing an alpha prototype. From the outset, the development of *The Migrants' Chronicles: 1892* took place in exchange with teachers and institutions from both the Luxembourgish and American school systems, whose feedback led to much time being spent on developing debriefing and analysis tools for classroom use.

3. Aim for your Audience

The intended audience and ideal use cases of balanced historical games must be identified at the outset and guide decisions about the appropriateness of both game mechanics and content. Our project is intended for middle grade students in Luxembourg and

the USA and designed with classroom use in mind, which has informed many decisions about the shape of the project, including:

- An inclusive, player-centered development process in which early versions of the game were tested by pupils and teachers, whose feedback was continuously taken into account in the further development of the game.
- An active learning approach to serious games, in which students should gain increased motivation for their own learning goals, while teachers have several choices to refine the use of the game in the classroom to maximize their specific instructional objectives.
- Localization and language translation, both as relates to communicating playable characters experiences, like crossing borders and grappling with unfamiliar languages, and the choice of in-game localization being keyed to target audiences (e.g. Luxembourgish or English).

4. **Authenticity over Accuracy**

A successful balanced historical game should embrace authenticity (recreating conditions that historical actors would plausibly have encountered) over one hundred percent accuracy (exactly capturing every attested historical detail). An effective historical game is more similar to a Period Piece film set in the framework of a certain historical and material culture or a Period Room in a museum, in which things have been brought together which might have been collected in a single place at a given time, rather than a documentary film or historical monograph that hews as closely as possible to the historical record. Since the agency of the individual is important for both good history and good game design, it is sometimes necessary to change aspects of the documented historical record in order to teach a more humane history through the game. A loss in terms of accuracy can often be a win in terms of both playability and learning outcomes.

7 Acknowledgements

We would like to extend our appreciation and thanks to all of our collaborators who have worked on this project over the past four years who are not co-authors, but whose dedicated hard work made the game possible; particularly, the numerous undergraduate and graduate student team members who contributed from the University of Luxembourg, Cologne Game Lab, and Carleton College. We would also like to thank the editors and three anonymous reviewers whose very helpful feedback on a draft manuscript of this article greatly improved the final result. All images by Alina Menten, Cologne Game Lab, 2024.

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MythFic Metadata

Gendered Power Dynamics in Fanfiction about Greek Myth

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This paper analyzes metadata from *Archive of Our Own* (AO3), one of the largest online repositories of fanfiction. I use tags to map the relationship between violence and the gender of the fictional characters in relationships in fanfiction about Greek myth to test two hypotheses:

- 1. The affirmative hypothesis: fanfiction perpetuates the patriarchal worldview of Greek myth. Violence-related tags correlate positively with tags referencing female/male relationships.
- 2. The transformative hypothesis: fanfiction subverts the patriarchal worldview of Greek myth. There is no relationship, or a negative correlation, between heterosexual relationship-tags and violence-tags.

In other words, does violent fanfiction perpetuate the dominant cultural narrative that casts men as perpetrators and women as victims, or does it subvert this dynamic? To operationalize violence, I selected all violence-related tags from the most-frequent additional tags in the metadata, leading to five violence-types: physical violence, sexual violence, roughness, captivity, and death. To find stories containing particular types of relationships, I used existing relationship tags: female/male, male/male, female/female, no relationships, no relationships tagged, multiple relationships, or other. I find some patterns in support of the affirmative hypothesis, since two violence-types – sexual violence and captivity – correlated positively with heterosexual relationships. In the case of captivity, this relationship was especially pronounced: more than half of all fanfiction tagged with captivity featured a female/male relationship. I conclude that on AO3, reference to Greek myth is used both in progressive stories celebrating female agency and in more ideologically complicated narratives exploring the darkness – and sometimes the imagined appeal – of gendered oppression and violence.

Keywords: fanfiction, Greek mythology, gender, violence, metadata

Figure 1: Absolute frequency of occurrence for 10 most-frequent characters in *MythFic Metadata*.

1. Introduction

With more than 11 million stories written by over 6 million users, *Archive of Our Own* is one of the largest online repositories of fanfiction. This paper analyzes a collection of metadata from that archive, which I call *MythFic Metadata*, to investigate a corpus of fanfiction about Ancient Greek myth. Specifically, I use relationship tags and additional tags applied by fanfiction authors to identify correlations between the types of romantic relationships and the occurrence of violent interactions in the fanfiction. I ask:

In fanfiction about Greek mythology, what is the relationship between the occurrence of violence and the gender of the fictional characters in relationships?

Greek mythology often contains narratives where male characters act violently towards female characters and exert force and power over them. For example, in the myth of Hades and Persephone, Persephone is abducted by Hades and tricked into spending part of each year in the Underworld with him. This myth does not depict Persephone as having any agency, and her abduction is also often described as violent. In the myth of Apollo and Daphne, the nymph Daphne is transformed into a tree so she can escape the unwanted sexual advances of the god Apollo. In the process, her human self is obliterated. The god Zeus is perhaps most strongly associated with the kidnapping and overpowering of those he wants to have sex with. His victims include Europa, Leda, and Ganymede. Although, as the example of Ganymede shows, (sexual) violence and abduction in mythology is not exclusively targeted at females, many of these myths are underpinned by a patriarchal worldview.¹ The characters most prominently present in those myths – Hades, Persephone, Zeus, and Apollo – are also the most popular characters in the *MythFic* corpus (Figure 1).

Because of these characters' prominence in these stories, and because of the patri-

¹ These mythological examples come from *Mythology Unbound: An Online Textbook for Classical Mythology* by Mellenthin and Shapiro (2017).

archal basis of many Greek myths, it is possible to define two opposing hypotheses regarding the occurrence of violence in the fanfiction dataset:

1. The affirmative hypothesis: fanfiction perpetuates the patriarchal worldview of Greek myth. In this case, I would expect violence-tags to co-occur more frequently with tags referencing heterosexual (F/M or female/male) relationships.
2. The transformative hypothesis: fanfiction subverts the patriarchal worldview of Greek myth. In this case, I would expect to see no relationship, or even a negative correlation, between heterosexual relationship-tags and violence-tags.

The paper begins by defining fanfiction and explaining its transformative potential. Then, I briefly touch on the representation of violence in Greek mythology. This is the norm or worldview, I argue, that fanfiction has the potential to transform. Next, I explain why gendered violence, both in Greek myth and in the fanfiction corpus, can be understood as a proxy for gendered power dynamics. Subsequently, I introduce the dataset, *MythFic Metadata*, and explain the method of metadata analysis. Then, I also elaborate on the advantages and disadvantages of using fanfiction tags as a unit of measurement for the textual characteristics of fanfiction. Finally, I present the results of the metadata analysis, assess their statistical validity and conclude by outlining some directions for future research.

Before I continue, a note on scope: the cultural materials transformed by those writing fanfiction about Greek mythology is multiform. While fanfiction often transforms clearly circumscribed cultural material that is united by the copyright of one author or corporation – for example, everything that happened in the *Hunger Games* books and movies, and was therefore created with the approval of author Suzanne Collins – fanfiction about Greek mythology has more diffuse origins, and the source materials that fans take up in their writing are, in turn, diverse. For the purposes of this paper, Greek mythology is therefore best understood through the German concept of *Stoffe*, applied to the study of reception and adaptation by Walter Bernhart. Bernhart writes that adaptations "are rarely cases of direct intermedial transposition but generally pass through a more abstract, essentially media-indifferent stage, which is based on the Stoff, or 'subject matter' of the literary source" (Bernhart, 2008). In line with this theoretical model, the comparison presented here focuses not on the ways fanfiction transforms particular iterations of Greek mythology and their representations of gendered violence, but on the way the Stoff or cultural material of Greek myth is taken up in different ways by different kinds of fanfiction. As such, my focus is on comparing the occurrence of violence between groups of fanfiction differentiated by the relationships they represent, and not on comparing fanfiction about Greek mythology to the diffuse set of cultural materials that make up Greek mythology. I thus study fanfiction not as derivative of or even necessarily relational to any literary canon, but rather as independently transformative of culturally dominant narratives of gendered violence.

2. Background

2.1. Fanfiction's Transformative Potential

For the purposes of this research, I define fanfiction as stories written by and for fans, inspired by existing stories, and published online for free, following previous work on fanfiction (Neugarten, 2021). Writing fanfiction can be classified as transformational

fandom, a type of fan activity that transforms the source material that is the focus of fans' attention. Transformational fandom stands in opposition to affirmational fandom. These two types of fandom were originally coined by Livejournal user Obsession Inc. (2009), and later taken up in fan studies by scholars like Hofmann (2018) and Scott (2019). In their online essay, Obsession Inc. describes affirmational fandom as fandom where "the source material is re-stated, the author's purpose divined to the community's satisfaction, [and] rules established on how the characters are and how the universe works." Such fandom engages with the details of a text and seeks to fix their meaning, often referring to creators or source materials to do so. Affirmational fandom generally does not question the literal message of the canon or its ideological underpinnings.

By contrast, transformational fandom, as explained by Obsession Inc., "is all about laying hands upon the source and twisting it to the fans' own purposes, whether that is to fix a disappointing issue (...) in the source material, or using the source material to illustrate a point, or just to have a whale of a good time." This type of fandom takes source materials as a starting point from which fans come up with their own ideas and storylines and puts these materials to an incredibly wide variety of uses. Fanfiction can thus be classified as transformational fandom, since it enables fans – but crucially, does not require them – to transform culturally dominant narratives.

Fanfiction is overwhelmingly written and read by women and people in the LGBTQ+ community. According to a demographic survey conducted by Rouse and Stanfill (2023), only 5,39% of users of *Archive of Our Own* were cisgender men and only 13,92% were heterosexual. Catherine Tosenberger notes that "it's not surprising that transformational fandom is often populated by those considered marginal audiences, who are more likely to feel a need to rework a beloved story to suit their own desires" (Tosenberger, 2014). The reworkings or transformations that fanfiction enacts on its source material can relate to, among other things, ideas about gender (Wills, 2013), sexuality (Floegel, 2020) and race (Fowler, 2019; Thomas, 2019). This way, fanfiction can be a tool for "restorying, a process by which people reshape narratives to represent a diversity of perspectives and experiences that are often missing or silenced in mainstream texts, media, and popular discourse" (Thomas and Stornaiuolo, 2016).

However, fanfiction can also affirm and perpetuate gender stereotypes. In an analysis of fanfiction about 90's TV show *The X-Files*, Emily Regan Wills notes that "not everything is possible in fandom. The world of canon sets limits on discursive production" (Wills, 2013). The contestation of dominant discourses in fanfiction is always inhibited by "the implicit limits that are set for them by canon". In Wills' research, these limits include gendered characterizations and power dynamics between characters. More generally, Kenneth Kidd observes that "the social biases and exclusions that characterize our world and popular culture manifest in fanfiction too" (Kidd, 2023). In other words, the inequalities of our social world limit the transformative possibilities of fanfiction.

To summarize: based on existing research, fanfiction can best be understood as *potentially* transformative. It has the potential to either question or reinforce ideas about identity categories and the power dynamics between them. This potentiality mirrors my two hypotheses: does violent fanfiction perpetuate the cultural narrative that casts men as perpetrators and women as victims, as suggested in the affirmative hypothesis, or does it subvert this dynamic, as suggested in the transformative hypothesis?

2.2. Gendered Violence and Power

This paper presents first steps in the research project *Achoring and Innovating Classical Motifs in Fanfiction*² which analyzes how contemporary online fanfiction represents and transforms myths from Greco-Roman antiquity. This is important since recent scholarship has identified a tendency in online spaces, like alt-right communities, to “[read] themselves into Classical Antiquity (...) as a site for discursive negotiation of their place in the history of white male culture” (Zuckerberg, 2018). Hardwick (2003) similarly notes “the capacity of classical texts to operate in supposedly deserted artistic and political spaces” which “has enabled social and political critique”. Nonetheless, re-reading texts from classical antiquity can also “offer modern readers the opportunity to investigate (...) power dynamics” (Libatique, 2021). Thus, interpretations of antiquity are becoming a political battleground where classical texts are used to legitimize varying perspectives on politics and power, including ideas about gender equality.

Violence, especially sexual violence, frequently occurs in ancient mythology, where “many young women (...) suffer sexual violence at the hands of gods” (Deacy et al., 2002). Narratives about gendered violence, like the myths of Persephone, Daphne, Europa, and many others, give visibility to persistent cultural ideas about male strength overpowering female vulnerability and male dominance enforcing female subordination. These stories’ relevance to contemporary cultural discourses – as signaled by scholars like Zuckerberg (2018), Hardwick (2003) and Libatique (2021) – makes them into a suitable case study for assessing the transformative potential of fanfiction: does fanfiction about Greek myth perpetuate or subvert the gendered power dynamics present in much of Ancient Greek mythology?

Power dynamics between men and women have been theorized in several ways that can be roughly divided into three types: power as a resource, power as domination, and power as empowerment (Allen, 2022). Additionally, there is a distinction between power-to, which relates to the freedom of individuals to exercise their will, and power-over, which relates to individuals’ ability to exert power over others. In many ways, this paper follows the conceptualization of power as a resource. The transformative potential of fanfiction in the realm of gendered power dynamics, then, resides in stories’ ability to redistribute power between (fictional) actors in accordance with a conception of gendered power structures that deviates from the dominant conception of power structures perpetuated by the source material. Thus, while Greek mythology tends to represent power as a resource possessed primarily by male gods, fanfiction has the potential to redistribute power to female characters.

Viewing power as a resource that can be redistributed between agents has one important downside: the risk of obscuring the structural nature of power. The distinction made by Sally Haslanger (2012) – between structural oppression and agent oppression – is useful in this context. In cases of agent oppression, as Allen (2022) quotes Haslanger (2012): “a person or persons (the oppressor(s)) inflicts harm upon another (the oppressed) wrongfully or unjustly.” In cases of structural oppression, by contrast, “the oppression is not an individual wrong but a social/political wrong; that is, it is a problem lying in our collective arrangements, an injustice in our practices or institutions.” Analysis of fanfiction necessarily uses re-writings of fictional characters as proxies for gender inequality. Individually these stories, in which one character inflicts violence or harm on another, are best understood as fictional representations of agent oppression. However, patterns in the fanfiction corpus as a whole

² To find out more about the project, visit the website.

may point to patterns of structural oppression, or the subversions of such patterns, in their representation of gendered power dynamics.

3. Data and Methods

To assess large-scale patterns in literary data, scholarship in computational literary studies often employs proxies to model the phenomena under scrutiny (Piper, 2017). Here, I employ violence tags as a proxy for more subtle power dynamics between fictional characters in the fanfiction. Existing scholarship in the digital humanities shows that such proxy-based analysis can be a fruitful method for assessing representations of gender difference in Dutch literary fiction (Smeets, 2021), shifting gender roles in English-language fiction over time (Underwood et al., 2018), hierarchically structured gender dynamics in contemporary English-language fiction (Kraicer and Piper, 2019) and even the role of gender in perceptions of literary quality in the Dutch literary sphere (Koolen, 2018). This paper builds on such studies, proposing a method to analyze gendered dynamics in fanfiction through the available metadata.

The paper also builds on existing scholarship that uses fanfiction metadata, specifically tags, as a source for studying online (fan) activity. Previous studies in this vein include Pianzola et al. (2020) which uses fanfiction metadata to study processes of cultural evolution, Price (2019) which uses analysis of fanfiction tags to study how *Archive of Our Own* – often abbreviated to AO3 – develops and maintains its own tag taxonomy, and Brottrager et al. (2023), which uses metadata from German fanfiction platform Fanfiktion.de to identify shared attributes in fanfiction sub-communities.

Inspired by these successful analyses of fanfiction tags, *MythFic Metadata* was born (Neugarten and Smeets, 2023).³ The dataset was collected using the AO3Scraper (Radiolorian, 2022). The scraper allows researchers to collect all metadata and text for fanfiction selected through AO3's interface (Li and Sterman, 2017). The URL generated by a specific AO3 search query serves as input for the scraper. The search query had the following parameters:

- Works tagged with the fandom *Ancient Greek Religion and Lore*
- Including Crossovers
- Complete works only
- Language: English

These settings have methodological implications. Including crossovers means that stories tagged with more than one fandom are included in the dataset. These were mostly fandoms that also engage in some way with mythology, such as Homer's *Iliad* (461 stories), Madeleine Miller's 2017 novel *The Song of Achilles* (289 stories), and the 2018 video game *Hades* (148 stories). These fandoms all have their own discursive norms when it comes to representing gender, violence, and the relationship between the two, which may influence results. Additionally, I selected only complete works for data collection because completeness is a prerequisite for some of the analysis I plan to do in the future regarding textual aspects like narrative structure. Finally, I selected only stories in English out of practical considerations; it is the only language prominent in fandom that I am fluent in. While the vast majority of works on the

³ Data collection was a collaboration between myself and Dr. Roel Smeets (Radboud University).

archive are in English,⁴ it is worth noting that the site supports 137 languages and that AO3 itself represents only a subset of the multilingual and multicultural fanfiction production happening all over the internet.

MythFic Metadata thus provides information on the content and popularity of 5.154 works of English-language fanfiction about Greek mythology marked completed in December 2022, gathered from fanfiction repository *Archive of Our Own*. The dataset contains all tags attached to all fanfiction about Greek myth available on AO3 on that date. Appendix A lists and explains all metadata fields available in *MythFic Metadata*.

Figure 2: Screenshot of a partial heading of a story on *Archive of Our Own*.

Figure 2 is a partial (anonymized) screenshot of one story's heading on the archive. In this case, the author has provided an age rating, chosen not to use any of the archive's standard warnings (for graphic depictions of violence, major character death, sexual violence, or underage sex), categorized the story as female/male, sorted it in the Greek myth fandom,⁵ and provided details on the characters present in the story and their relationships. The additional tags inform potential readers of some content-level elements of the story.

Two types of metadata are relevant to my research question: relationship categories and additional tags. On AO3, authors can tag their stories with seven types of relationships. These are listed, along with a brief explanation and their absolute frequency of occurrence in the dataset, in Table 1. For completeness, the fanfiction not tagged with any relationships is also listed here. However, because the focus of this paper is on the relationship between violence and types of romantic relationships in these stories, the 413 stories not tagged with any relationship types are disregarded in the rest of the analysis. Although non-romantic relationships are of course also imbued with gendered power dynamics, these dynamics are not the focus of the current research.

AO3 also lets authors provide additional tags. These tags are freeform, meaning they can contain any information the author chooses to communicate in them. The *MythFic Metadata* dataset contains 13.935 unique additional tags. It is common for

⁴ In November 2023, AO3 reached the milestone of 12 million works (Rebaza, 2023). As of February 2024, slightly over 11 million of those works were in English.

⁵ This fandom used to be labeled 'Greek Mythology' by the archive's interface. Recently, they decided to change all fandoms labeled as a 'mythology' to 'religion and lore', so the fandom in *MythFic Metadata* is now labeled 'Ancient Greek Religion and Lore'. For an explanation of this decision, see the blog of the Tag Wrangling Committee (Committee, 2023). While the committee felt that the term 'mythology' is often used to disparage religious beliefs, I do not share that opinion in relation to Greek myth and feel that it is both accurate and respectful to refer to the source material of this fanfiction as 'myth'.

Table 1: Explanation and Absolute Frequencies of Relationship Categories.

Category Tag	Explanation	Frequency
F/M	Female/Male	2.045
Gen	No romantic or sexual pairings	1.367
M/M	Male/Male	1.301
F/F	Female/Female	481
None	No romantic or sexual pairings tagged	413
Other	Does not fit other tags	278
Multi	Multiple romantic or sexual pairings	250

Table 2: Absolute Frequency of Violence-Tags in *MythFic Metadata*.

Total number of stories	5.154
stories tagged with 0 violence-types	4.461
stories tagged with 1 violence-type	572
stories tagged with 2 violence-types	106
stories tagged with 3 violence-types	14
stories tagged with 4 violence-types	1
stories tagged with all violence-types	0
stories tagged with any violence-type	693

additional tags on *Archive of Our Own* to inform potential readers about the genre, plot elements, or formal characteristics of a story. Authors also sometimes use these tags to reflect on the writing process. Popular additional tags in *MythFic Metadata* include ‘Angst’ (used 335 times) ‘Fluff’ (304) ‘Hurt/Comfort’ (135) and ‘Smut’ (92), which all refer to fanfiction genres, plot elements such as ‘Alternate Universe – Modern Setting’ (194), ‘Happy Ending’ (51) or ‘Marriage’ (43), and references to the formal characteristics of the story, such as ‘Drabble’ (a story of exactly 100 words, used 136 times), ‘Poetry’ (251) or ‘Crossover’ (a story that contains elements from more than one fictional universe or fandom, used 69 times). Tags informing potential readers about the sexual acts present in a story (‘Oral Sex’ (115), ‘First Time’ (58), ‘Explicit Sexual Content’ (51)) are also prevalent.

To find stories containing violence, I manually selected all violence-related tags from the 500 most frequently-used additional tags in the dataset. Because of my emphasis on gendered agent oppression, I decided to examine violence on the interpersonal and not the societal or structural level, so I disregarded war-related tags (‘War’ (58), ‘Trojan War’ (143)). I also disregarded tags describing mental pain (‘Depression’ (25), ‘Grief/Mourning’ (91), ‘PTSD’ (23)), because not all pain is the result of violence and mental pain often lacks a clear perpetrator/victim dynamic. Furthermore, I disregarded tags referencing violence against children (‘Child Abuse’ (15), ‘Implied/Referenced Child Abuse’ (23)), because I hypothesize that in those cases age, rather than gender, is the identity category structuring power dynamics. 36 tags in 5 violence-related sub-categories remained: *physical violence*, *sexual violence*, *roughness*, *captivity*, and *death*. Appendix B lists the selected violence-tags that make up each category. Table 2 shows how many stories were tagged with violence.

Using additional tags to analyze the content of stories has limitations: tags only reflect what authors choose to disclose, and tagging practices change over time (Pi-

anzola et al., 2020). Opinions on the meaning of tags, like the distinction between 'Non-Graphic Violence' and 'Minor Violence' may differ between users. I minimized this problem by grouping tags together, so 'Non-Graphic Violence' (18) and 'Minor Violence' (17) were combined under physical violence. Previous research shows that the archive's tagging system "generally describes content accurately" (Price, 2019). Overall, users – both readers and writers – are invested in keeping the tagging system informative and accurate to ensure that everyone can have a pleasant and safe reading experience. Additionally, a team of volunteers or 'tag wranglers' adheres to a strict set of guidelines to keep the platform's tagging system consistent. As a final caveat, tag frequency can be challenging to interpret because some stories have multiple tags with the same meaning. If a story is tagged both 'Kidnapping' and 'Abduction' in *MythFic Metadata*, I count it as one instance of captivity in this analysis.

4. Results

This section begins by reporting the absolute frequencies of the occurrence of tags and expressing these frequencies as percentages of the entire dataset and as percentages of the various subsets of violence-types and relationship-categories. These frequencies were counted using a Python script and visualized in Excel. I then report the results of a χ^2 -test of independence, conducted pairwise for each combination of relationship-type and violence-category.⁶ Finally, I use the results of a crosstabulation⁷ to determine the direction of the correlation for those pairs of variables found to be significant in the statistical test. Statistical testing was conducted using SPSS Statistics (SPS, 2020).

Table 3 lists the frequencies of each violence-type per relationship-category and expresses each violence-type as the percentage of occurrences of that violence-type and as the percentage of total occurrences of that relationship-category. Note that percentages can add up to more than 100% because many stories are tagged with multiple violence- and relationship-tags. Similarly, the total number of non-violent stories is higher here (4.890) than in Table 2 (4.461), because here a non-violent story is counted once for each relationship it is tagged with. Figure 3 visualizes the absolute frequency of each violence type per relationship category, so you can see the proportion of stories per violence type with a specific relationship category. Figure 4 visualizes the percentage of each relationship-type per violence-category. For example, the first bar in Figure 4 shows that 34,5% of all stories tagged physical violence were F/M. Figure 5 visualizes the percentage of each violence-category per relationship-type. I then tested the statistical significance of these results (Table 4) and found that the co-occurrence of the F/M-tag and all violence categories except physical violence was statistically significant. I also found some other meaningful correlations.

Because the presence of categories was indicated using zeros and ones, degrees of freedom were 1 in each case. The threshold for significance is a p-value < 0,05, marked in green. Cramer's V measures the strength of the relationship between variables.⁸ With none of the Cramer's V values even meeting the threshold for a weak correlation,

⁶ The χ^2 -test of independence is a statistical test used to measure whether two categorical variables are related.

⁷ Crosstabulation is a method for quantitatively analyzing the relationship between variables. By placing the data in a contingency table, one can see whether the relationship between variables has a positive direction (increase in one variable is associated with increase in another variable, or decrease associated with decrease), or a negative direction (increase in one variable associated with decrease in another variable or vice versa).

⁸ To interpret Cramer's V, 0,1 = weak, 0,3 = moderate, 0,5 = strong.

Table 3: Frequencies and Percentages of Relevant Tags.

Type	F/M	M/M	Gen	Other	F/F	Multi	Total
Physical	68	64	57	26	25	16	197
% of violence cat.	34,5%	32,5%	28,9%	13,2%	12,7%	8,1%	
% of relationship cat.	3,3%	4,9%	4,2%	9,4%	5,2%	6,4%	
Sexual	120	78	38	25	35	31	254
% of violence cat.	47,2%	30,7%	15,0%	9,8%	13,8%	12,2%	
% of relationship cat.	5,9%	4,9%	2,8%	9,0%	7,3%	12,4%	
Roughness	51	37	1	7	9	7	91
% of violence cat.	56,0%	40,7%	1,1%	7,7%	9,9%	7,7%	
% of relationship cat.	2,5%	2,8%	0,1%	2,5%	5,2%	2,8%	
Captivity	45	22	20	6	5	2	84
% of violence cat.	53,6%	26,2%	23,8%	7,1%	6,0%	2,4%	
% of relationship cat.	2,2%	1,7%	1,5%	2,2%	1,0%	0,80%	
Death	66	65	51	16	19	8	204
% of violence cat.	32,4%	31,9%	25,0%	7,8%	9,3%	3,9%	
% of relationship cat.	3,2%	5,0%	3,7%	5,8%	4,0%	3,20%	
No Violence Tags	1.755	1.083	1.231	216	407	198	4.890
% of relationship cat.	85,5%	83,2%	90,1%	77,7%	85,6%	79,2%	
Total relationship fq.	2.045	1.301	1.367	278	481	413	250

Figure 3: Absolute Frequency of Violence Type per Relationship Category .

Figure 4: Relationship Type per Violence Category.

Figure 5: Violence Category per Relationship Type.

Table 4: Pearson's χ^2 -Test of Independence and Cramer's V.

Relationship	Statistic	physical	sexual	roughness	captivity	death
F/M	χ^2	2.279	6.390	10.367	6.887	4.762
	p-value	0,114	0,011	0,001	0,009	0,029
	Cramer's V	0,021	0,035	0,045	0,037	0,030
M/M	χ^2	5.697	4.230	11.668	0.041	4.933
	p-value	0,017	0,040	0,001	0,840	0,026
	Cramer's V	0,033	0,029	0,048	0,003	0,031
F/F	χ^2	2.729	6.244	0.034	1.153	0.000
	p-value	0,099	0,012	0.854	0,283	0,992
	Cramer's V	0,023	0,035	0,003	0,015	0,000
Gen	χ^2	0.611	18.328	30.725	0.323	0.253
	p-value	0,434	0,000	0,000	0,570	0,615
	Cramer's V	0,011	0,060	0,077	0,008	0,007
Multi	χ^2	4.749	31.307	1.621	1.128	0.397
	p-value	0,029	0,000	0,203	0,288	0,529
	Cramer's V	0,030	0,078	0,018	0,015	0,009
Other	χ^2	24.447	10.361	0.959a	0.512	2.497
	p-value	0,000	0,001	0,327	0,474	0,114
	Cramer's V	0,069	0,045	0,014	0,010	0,022

Table 5: Positive and negative association between variables.

	physical	sexual	roughness	captivity	death
F/M	NULL	positive	positive	positive	positive
M/M	negative	positive	positive	NULL	positive
Gen	NULL	negative	negative	NULL	NULL
Other	positive	positive	NULL	NULL	NULL
F/F	NULL	positive	NULL	NULL	NULL
Multi	positive	positive	NULL	NULL	NULL

it seems that the relationship between the variables is not very strong. It is important to note that the data had a large sample size, and that the χ^2 -statistic is very sensitive to sample size. This means that statistically significant correlations as identified in the data should not necessarily be considered strong patterns, especially as all Cramer's V values are low.

However, the direction of these correlations (listed in Table 5) further helps answer my research question. This direction is based on a crosstabulation and a comparison of the expected counts and observed counts of tags in the dataset. 'NULL' indicates that no statistically significant correlation between variables was detected using the χ^2 -statistic. Filled cells indicate a statistically significant correlation, with 'positive' indicating a positive association and 'negative' indicating a negative association between variables. For example, this table shows that there was a significantly larger percentage of female/male stories in the sexual-violence-subset than in the dataset overall, but a significantly smaller percentage of female/male stories in the death-subset than in the dataset overall.

Heterosexual relationships were especially overrepresented in stories containing

sexual violence, roughness, and captivity. While 39,7% of all stories contained female/male relationships, 47,2% of stories containing sexual violence, 56% of stories containing roughness and 53,6% of stories containing captivity featured heterosexual relationships. On the other hand, heterosexual relationships were underrepresented in stories tagged with death. Death, however, more often occurred in stories containing male/male relationships. This suggests that fanfiction containing male/male relationships may be influenced by the mainstream media trope known as ‘bury your gays’, a tendency to have LGBTQ+-characters die in narratives at a rate disproportionate to their heterosexual counterparts (see for example Cameron (2018)). However, research shows that “queer women have borne the brunt of this trope, especially on television, such that it has come to be known as the Dead Lesbian Trope or Dead Lesbian Syndrome” (Bridges, 2018). And yet *MythFic Metadata* shows no statistically significant correlation between female/female relationships and the occurrence of character death. It is also possible that some of the death-related tags included in this analysis have not succeeded at measuring violence. Of the 223 occurrences of death-tags in *MythFic Metadata*, only 32 were ‘Murder’. The other tags, including ‘Death’ (76) and ‘Implied/Referenced Character Death’ (51) may not be accurate indicators of violence.

Female/female relationships were only significantly correlated with sexual violence. This is remarkable because F/F relationships do not have male characters in them, so the correlation suggests that these stories are subverting the cultural norm from Greek mythology that frequently portrays male characters as the perpetrators of sexual violence. The positive correlation between sexual violence and F/F-relationships is also interesting since previous work by fan statistician Toastystats (destinationtoast) shows that F/F fanfiction overall is less sexually explicit than stories in other relationship tags. In a comparison of tags used for various relationship categories on *Archive of Our Own*, they found that “F/F is much less likely to be explicit and more likely to be clean” than F/M and M/M fanfiction.

The findings also suggest that the category of roughness may have failed at detecting violence in the fanfiction. While 26,5% of stories in the dataset overall were tagged ‘Gen’, these ‘Gen’ relationships were present in only 1,1% of stories tagged with roughness. Gen is fanfiction without romantic or sexual relationships, which means that sexual acts are rarely depicted in these stories. The absence of roughness-related tags in fanfiction tagged ‘Gen’ seems to indicate that these tags – ‘Rough Sex’ (60), ‘Biting’ (16), ‘Hair-pulling’ (15), and ‘Spanking’ (14) – are perhaps most frequently used to indicate the presence of (consensual) sexual acts rather than real violence. Toastystats (destinationtoast) also found that F/F fanfiction has the smallest percentage of stories tagged ‘Rough Sex’ (3,3% for F/F compared to 7,4% for F/M and 4,6% for M/M). These percentages align with the positive correlation detected here between F/M and M/M relationships and the roughness category, suggesting that I may have been measuring the correlation between relationship types and rough sex rather than between relationship types and violent encounters. Future research should carefully consider the difference between these tags and the other types of violence operationalized through tagsets in this paper.

Finally, the positive relationship between the relationship-categories ‘Multi’ and ‘Other’ and the physical and sexual violence-categories stand out. Although the archive defines ‘Multi’ as “more than one kind of relationship, or a relationship with multiple partners,” it is also not uncommon for users to tag each relationship separately if multiple relationships are present in a work. It is difficult to say how the ‘Other’ tag is used overall, but it is possible that the ‘Other’ tag correlates with the sexual violence

category because it contains the 'Bestiality' tag (14 occurrences in the dataset). Perhaps bestiality is frequently tagged as an 'Other' type of relationship. Overall, stories containing complicated ('Other') and multiple ('Multi') types of relationships are positively associated with the occurrence of physical and sexual violence in fanfiction.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

This metadata analysis shows some interesting patterns in support of the affirmative hypothesis, since two types of violence – sexual violence and captivity – were positively correlated in fanfiction with the presence of heterosexual relationships. In the case of captivity, this relationship was especially pronounced: more than half of all fanfiction tagged with captivity featured a female/male relationship. However, I found no significant correlation between physical violence or death and heterosexual relationships. While heterosexual relationships were also overrepresented in the subset of stories tagged with roughness, I found evidence to suggest that the roughness-tagset was not an accurate proxy for the occurrence of violence in fanfiction.

To understand how (gendered) power operates in the *MythFic* corpus, it is important to take into consideration that the digital infrastructure of fandom is not neutral. As Dennis Jansen notes (Jansen, 2020), the *Archive of Our Own* is itself also a power structure. The social and discursive norms of the archive, as well as the technical affordances and limitations of the interface and the tagging system, influence the tags and metadata analyzed in this paper. Social factors, such as the desire to increase the visibility and popularity of a story, are also likely to influence how authors tag their works.

Additionally, fandom has historically had a tendency “to presume that sex- and gender-based violence can be understood in isolation from other social systems — in particular, race” (Lothian and Stanfill, 2021). This tendency has informed the platform design of the *Archive of Our Own*. For example, users can warn each other of sexual violence in fanfiction much more easily than of racialized violence, because of the platform’s system of archive warnings. The influence of the platforms’ norms and affordances needs to be taken into consideration when evaluating the results of the current research and the validity of *MythFic Metadata* as a whole. While the research presented in this paper has focused solely on story-internal power dynamics and has isolated the interaction between violence-tags and characters’ sexual orientation and gender, the functioning of tags in the archive and the representation of violence in fanfiction are also linked to communal and extradiegetic discourses on race, age, (dis)ability and various other factors that require further academic scrutiny.

This metadata exploration is a first step towards the overarching goals of *Achoring and Innovating Classical Motifs in Fanfiction*, to analyze how and why antiquity is represented and transformed in contemporary online fanfiction. One drawback of the metadata-analysis approach is that it does not enable an analysis of the dynamics between individual characters in fanfiction, which would add important context and nuance to our understanding of agent oppression between fictional characters. To gain more insight at the level of individual texts, I plan in future work to analyze these stories with Riveter (Antoniak et al., 2023), an NLP pipeline which measures social dynamics between fictional characters. This could help identify how power and agency are distributed between fictional agents. This way, I hope to discover which characters fanfiction most often portrays as victims and perpetrators of violence.

The metadata analysis presented in this paper is thus an exploratory first step

towards the analysis of the *MythFic* corpus through NLP-pipelines such as Riveter (Antoniak et al., 2023). Two characters, Hades and Persephone, featured prominently in *MythFic Metadata*: Hades occurred 488 times in the 5.145 stories, and Persephone was tagged 442 times. In this paper, I detected a statistically significant correlation between F/M-stories and tags related to captivity, a narrative element that is central to the Hades/Persephone myth. Because of these findings, and because of the increasing popularity of retellings centering on Hades and Persephone in contemporary popular culture (Hays, 2023), I will focus future pipeline-based analysis on the dynamic between Hades and Persephone in the *MythFic* corpus. The results presented here thus helped identify a future case study for understanding how dynamics of violence are potentially transformed in fanfiction.

To conclude: I was surprised to find no statistically meaningful correlation between tags referring to physical violence and the presence of female/male relationships. Because women are often the victims of physical violence at the hands of men in Greek mythology, I had expected to find a statistically significant relationship between these types of tags in *MythFic Metadata*, either perpetuating or subverting the canon's dynamic. Based on the results, however, it remains difficult to say whether the fanfiction in the *MythFic* dataset tends to subvert or perpetuate the discursive norms of its canon overall.

These inconclusive results also raise the possibility that the norm of gendered violence I posited as prevalent in the Stoffe of Greek mythology is either not as prominent as I presumed, or has already been transformed in the other rewritings and adaptations that fans are basing their fanfiction on. In recent popular adaptations of the Hades/Persephone myth, such as the *Lore Olympus* webcomic (Smythe, 2021), the violent beginning of the relationship between these characters, and the unequal power dynamics that ensue, are transformed into a gentle and equal courtship. Similarly, in contemporary young adult literature about Persephone, such as the popular *Girl, Goddess, Queen* (Fitzgerald, 2023), she is frequently depicted as independent and powerful, while Hades takes on the role of a desirable if somewhat dark love interest. If the fanfiction covered in *MythFic Metadata* bases (part of) its representations of gendered power dynamics on these sources rather than on more patriarchal and hierarchical versions of Greek myth, this could explain my findings. Further research into the content of the fanfiction could elucidate this as well.

Elsewhere on the internet, reference to Greco-Roman antiquity is employed in discourses on the far right of the political spectrum to argue for the oppression of women (Zuckerberg, 2018). On *Archive of Our Own*, reference to Greek myth is used both in progressive stories celebrating female agency and in more ideologically complicated narratives exploring the darkness – and sometimes the imagined appeal – of gendered oppression and violence. The tag analysis presented in this paper has primarily led to myriad new questions. It has shown the richness and diversity of fanfiction production, and supported my claim that fanfiction has transformative potential: while some stories use this potential to radically transform the classical canon, other stories instead affirm the patriarchal worldview that underpins the source material.

6. Acknowledgements

Many thanks to my daily supervisor, Dr. Roel Smeets (Radboud University) for his support in collecting the *MythFic Metadata* dataset, help with presenting an earlier

version of this research at the DH Benelux 2022 conference, and for providing feedback on drafts of this article.

This research is supported by the Dutch ministry of Education, Culture and Science (OCW) through the Dutch Research Council (NWO), as part of the Anchoring Innovation Gravitation Grant research agenda of OIKOS, the National Research School in Classical Studies, the Netherlands (project number 024.003.012).

7. Data Access Statement

In the Radboud Data Repository, I have uploaded an anonymized version of *MythFic Metadata*, with work-ID's and author usernames redacted, in Excel and csv-format, as well as the Excel-sheet of analysis that was used to create many of the tables and figures. This data is available here: <https://doi.org/10.34973/2mye-8468>.

On Github, I have uploaded the anonymized *MythFic Metadata* in csv-format, as well as the Jupyter Notebook used to calculate tag frequencies, compile tag sets, and generate some figures. This data is available here.

To protect the privacy of the fanfiction community, the scraped fanfiction itself will not be made available. Researchers are free to scrape their own fanfiction-dataset. I recommend using Radiolorian's AO3-Scraper (Radiolorian, 2022).

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A. Appendix: Metadata Fields in *MythFic Metadata*

Note that the work-ID and author username were redacted from the anonymized dataset uploaded to GitHub and the Radboud Data Repository.

Metadata Field	Explanation
work-ID	A unique identifier assigned to the work by AO3.
title	The work's title.
author	AO3 username of the work's author.
rating	Options: Not Rated, General Audiences, Teen and Up Audiences, Mature, Explicit.
category	Options: F/F, F/M, Gen, M/M, Multi, Other. 413 stories are not tagged with any category.
fandom	All stories were selected for the tag <i>Ancient Greek Religion and Lore</i> . Many stories are tagged with multiple fandoms.
relationship	Tags naming two or more characters involved in a relationship within the story. A slash indicates a romantic or sexual relationship. An ampersand indicates friendship or social interaction. 1.244 stories are not tagged with any relationship.
character	Tags listing the characters present or mentioned in the story. 293 stories are not tagged with any characters.
additional tags	These tags can contain all sorts of information about the story. Examples include themes, plot elements, content warnings or authors' reflections. 616 stories are not tagged with any additional tags.
language	In this corpus, all works are in English.
published	Date of initial publication.
status	In this corpus, all works are 'Completed.' Works in progress were excluded from the data collection. AO3 began in 2009, but stories can be backdated.
status date	Here, the date that the work was marked 'Completed.'
words	Number of words in the work. 60 stories have a wordcount of zero. These are probably other fanworks such as art.
chapters	Number of chapters in the work.
comments	Number of comments left by readers. 1.585 stories received no comments.
kudos	Number of Kudos (similar to 'Likes' on Facebook) left by readers. 122 stories received no Kudos.
bookmarks	Number of readers who bookmarked the story. 1.162 stories were never bookmarked.
hits	Number of page views. Note that viewing is not equivalent to reading. Only one story received zero hits.

B. Appendix: Overview of Violence Tags

These tags were selected manually from the 500 most frequently used additional tags in *MythFic Metadata* to measure story-violence. They are sorted within each category here by frequency of occurrence, with the frequency listed after the tag. A content warning applies to these tags, some of which mention specific acts of violence.

Physical Violence

Canon-Typical Violence - 52
Violence - 35
Blood - 29
Blood and Violence- 19
Non-Graphic Violence - 18
Minor Violence - 17
Past Abuse - 14
Torture - 13
Cannibalism - 12
Pain - 11
Implied/Referenced Torture - 10
Total: 230

Sexual Violence

Implied/Referenced Rape/Non-con- 73
Incest- 44
Dubious Consent- 43
Rape/Non-con Elements- 33
Sibling Incest - 28
Past Rape/Non-con - 27
Rape - 14
Bestiality - 14
Gang Rape - 12
Mildly Dubious Consent - 12
Implied/Referenced Incest - 11
Total: 311

Roughness

Rough Sex- 60
Biting - 16
Hair-pulling - 15
Spanking - 14
Total: 105

Captivity

Kidnapping - 49
Abduction - 15
Captivity - 15
Imprisonment - 11
Total: 90

Death

Death - 76
Implied/Referenced Character Death - 51
Minor Character Death - 36
Murder - 32
Temporary Character Death - 16
Past Character Death - 12
Total: 223

Cross-linguistic annotation transfer in geoparsing experiments with Classical texts

The case of Pliny the Elder’s *Natural History*

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The *Natural History* is an encyclopedic work written by the Latin author Pliny the Elder (first century CE). In this extensive text in 37 books, geography plays a pivotal role, with hundreds of mentions of ancient place names. In this paper, a geoparsing experiment is conducted on the *Natural History* with the scope of automatically identifying and extracting place entities. To achieve this, we take advantage of state-of-the-art NLP models to develop a multistage pipeline involving English Named Entity Recognition, English-Latin sentence alignment, and entity projection. The paper demonstrates how cross-lingual annotation transfer can be applied from a translation in a modern language back to the original text in the context of low-/medium-resource languages, such as Latin. The efficacy of the proposed pipeline is evaluated through the use of both standard metrics and a comprehensive manual error analysis. Additionally, the results are compared to those obtained by other Latin NER tools. Both analyses demonstrate that the proposed methodology achieves a superior f1-score. Finally, the majority of place entities were automatically associated with unique identifiers that enable geolocation by the projection of pre-disambiguated annotations derived from another geo-spatial project.

Keywords: Named Entity Recognition, Latin, text alignment, annotation projection, Pliny the Elder

1 Introduction

Geoparsing is the process that involves the automated identification of geographical entities within an unstructured text (Gregory et al., 2015). This task plays a significant role in the realm of Natural Language Processing (NLP) and information retrieval, and more specifically as a subtask within the framework of Named Entity Recognition (NER) and Named Entity Linking (NEL). NER consists of detecting and classifying named entities, that is, elements in texts that act as a rigid designator for a reference, typically of the types *Person*, *Location*, and *Organization*. NEL is a related but more complex task that involves disambiguating entities through a knowledge base. The kind of activity that we call “geoparsing” in a computational domain has long been of

interest to scholars, with applications in a range of research fields. From linguistics to the science of the environment through history and literature, the identification of the place entities mentioned in written sources has several applications representing the starting point of various kinds of data analysis.

In the context of geoparsing historical data, a number of additional factors come into play. One of the most significant is the often-noted underdevelopment of NLP systems tailored for languages beyond the modern ones. The scarcity of robust linguistic models, coupled with the fact that they are usually trained on specific language domains, significantly restricts their fine-tuning to limited NER tasks (Ehrmann et al., 2023; González-Gallardo et al., 2023; Won et al., 2018). Further challenges are posed by the nature of the spatial knowledge embedded in historical documents. Such knowledge often reflects a world that no longer exists, where city names may have changed, villages may have disappeared, and rivers may have changed course over time. In addition, the very paradigms used to understand space, including spatial concepts and spatial categories, are culture-specific (Geus and Thiering, 2014). The scope of the geoparsing analysis in historical data is, therefore, to address the variability in how individuals have historically described their environment by investigating the shifts that have influenced the perception and conceptualisation of space (Barker et al., 2016; Palladino, 2021).

In this study, I discuss a geoparsing case study of the *Natural History* (*NH* henceforth), an encyclopaedic work written by the Latin author Pliny the Elder in the first century CE. This massive 37-book text covers a wide range of topics, including geography, medicine, astronomy and art, among others. In particular, geography plays a pivotal role, since Pliny aims to provide a comprehensive description of the world (Doody, 2010; Murphy, 2004). As a result, significant portions of the encyclopaedia are devoted to the description of various geographical entities (Books 3-6), with an extensive catalogue of “bare names” (*NH* 3.2: *nuda nomina*) of cities, mountains, rivers, and seas. In some cases, Pliny is the only witness to a place name, making him an unparalleled source of knowledge of ancient geography. In the rest of the work, places are mentioned in order to anchor the various topics in space. For instance, in the books on botany and agriculture place names occur in relation to the origin of species¹ or the provenance of goods.²

The aim of this paper is to provide a pipeline for the automatic identification of place entities in the *NH*. Taking advantage of state-of-the-art NLP models and applying them in the context of low-resource languages, the paper presents a projection-based methodology for annotating named entities and specifically places in Latin texts through a multi-stage workflow that outperforms the currently available NER taggers in terms of precision and recall. The data, along with the code for the project, is available online in the GitHub repository for further review.³

2 Related work

Until a few years ago, the automatic identification of place names in historical texts was carried out using more or less sophisticated string matching-techniques. This approach relied on the existence of manually curated gazetteers in digital format, specifically designed to curate authority lists of place names from the ancient Greek and Latin

¹ *NH* 12.53: *in Aegypto nascitur et maron*, “Cat-thyme also grows in Egypt.”

² *NH* 13.2: *Et macir ex India advehitur*, “Also macir is imported from India.”

³ https://github.com/laurensmile/Geoparsing_Pliny/tree/main.

world. By including place names in original language and modern translation, these resources, such as the *Pleiades Gazetteer*⁴ and *Trismegistos Place*,⁵ held immense potential for conducting automated geoparsing experiments on classical texts. In 2015, Kiesling presented the *ToposText* project,⁶ whose scope was the annotation of all mentions of place names in classical literature in English translation. The *ToposText* annotations were primarily derived from the *Pleiades Gazetteer* in the sense that the place names were automatically extracted by various string-matching heuristics and disambiguated by an alphanumeric unique identifier linked to an external knowledge base. Another relevant project in the field of classical geography was *Hestia*, conducted by Barker et al. (2013). *Hestia* investigated the geography of the ancient world as described by the Greek author Herodotus in his *Histories*. One of the goals of the project was to georeference all the places mentioned by Herodotus. To do this, the project relied on the annotations available in the English translation of the *Histories* from the *Perseus Digital Library* (Crane et al., 2000), which were derived from the application of string-matching techniques. A consistent limitation of this methodology, however, is that it is inherently dependent on the comprehensiveness and granularity of the gazetteers used. Place names that are not already present in the authority list cannot be retrieved from the text and unseen data is missed. Finally, string-matching methods have only been applied to modern translations of classical texts, while the annotation of the original sources has never been experimented with.

In recent years, the advent of machine learning models has ushered in a new era of technologies for the geo-spatial analysis of historical texts. This shift is exemplified by the development of various pre-trained Named Entity Recognition systems, which have transformed the automated identification of place names in unstructured texts. The strength of these models lies in their ability to generalize from training data, operating independently of the completeness of the reference list, and allowing the expansion of gazetteers with unseen, new data. In the context of ancient languages, Erdmann et al. (2016, 2019) developed a neural BiLSTM-CRF (Bidirectional Long-Short Term Memory) entity classifier trained on Latin texts (*Herodotos-Project-Latin-NER-Tagger*) with the scope of annotating ancient ethnic groups. More recently, Torres Aguilar (2022) fine-tuned the transformer-based BERT and RoBERTa models for Medieval Latin and the *SpaCy* pipeline for Latin (*LatinCy*) became available, including a NER toolkit (Burns, 2023). In addition, Beersmans et al. (2023) fine-tuned two new transformer-based *LatinBERT* models for the task of NER. In their conclusions, the authors pointed out that the identification of places achieved lower performances in terms of accuracy when compared to the annotation of persons, and that multi-tokens place entities were rarely recognized. Similar conclusions were reached by Palladino and Yousef (2024), who found that place names are still the most challenging entity type for Ancient Greek NER due to the lack of a consistent annotation strategy in the available training datasets. Finally, in the context of classical geography, it is worth mentioning the development of *Recogito*⁷, a *JavaScript* library specifically designed for geo-spatial tasks. The tool integrates the use of the *Stanford CoreNLP* models for NER tagging with the default language model for English only, but it has also experimented with Latin NER through the *Herodotos-Project-Latin-NER-Tagger* plugin.

One potential solution to the challenge of performing NLP tasks on languages

⁴ <https://pleiades.stoa.org>.

⁵ <https://www.trismegistos.org/geo/>.

⁶ <https://topostext.org>.

⁷ <https://recogito.pelagios.org>.

with limited resources is the cross-lingual projection, which involves transferring linguistic annotations over parallel texts from a high-resource language to a low- or medium-resource language. Applying cutting-edge machine learning technologies to poorly annotated corpora, this approach has proven to be adaptable across various language pairs (Jain et al., 2019). In the context of classical languages, Yousef et al. (2023) recently fine-tuned a multi-lingual XML-RoBERTa-based language model (*UGARIT/gr-alignment*)⁸ for the word alignment, and transferred NER annotations across parallel corpora in Ancient Greek, Latin and English. The language model was trained on a substantial corpus of parallel sentences, primarily in Ancient Greek-English and Ancient Greek-Latin, and then tested in conjunction with a variety of alignment heuristics (Yousef et al., 2022a,b).

3 Corpus

For this study, the parallel corpus of the *NH* in Latin and English was used. The Latin text (487,289 tokens) was obtained from the *PerseusDL/canonical-latinLit*⁹ in the .XML tokenized and lemmatized form published by Clérice (2021). For the English translation (804,866 tokens), I used the *Perseus Project* .HTML text file available from *ToposText*.¹⁰

4 Methodology

The pipeline consisted of four main steps, which are fully described in the following sub-sections. The first step involved preprocessing the *ToposText* English text file, as described in 4.1. The second step entailed applying the state-of-the-art *flairNLP* system to the English translation of the *NH* for the automated NER prediction (4.2). This resulted in the *ToposText* annotations being integrated with new place entities detected by the NER. In parallel, an automated alignment model was employed to align the English and Latin texts at the sentence (4.3) and word levels (4.4). By extracting the translation equivalents for place names, the annotations were transferred accordingly by a direct projection heuristic. As a result, an automatically annotated Latin text for place entities was obtained. Place name attestations that were already annotated in *ToposText* were also automatically geo-identified and linked to an external knowledge base. The results obtained from each stage of the workflow are discussed in the Results.

4.1 Preprocessing

The .HTML text file from *ToposText* was tokenized using the *segtok* library.¹¹ In a .CSV file, each token was associated with a unique identifier and with the reference position at the book.chapter.paragraph level. For each token within a *ToposText* <place> tag (e.g., <place>Athens</place>), the *ToposText* unique identifier provided within the tag (e.g., '380237PAtH' for 'Athens') was extracted and associated with the corresponding token. The original file contained 8,895 *ToposText* tags for places.

⁸ <https://huggingface.co/UGARIT/grc-alignment>.

⁹ urn_cts_latinLit_phi0978_phi001.perseus-lat2.xml.

¹⁰ Apart from *ToposText*, no other publicly available digital annotated version of the *NH* exists. In 2022, the *Pliny the Elder's World* project conducted by B. Turner and R. Talbert published a list of geo-referenced place names from the geographical books of the *NH* (<https://isaw.nyu.edu/research/pliny-the-elder/>).

¹¹ <https://pypi.org/project/segtok/>.

As there is currently no evaluation of the quality of the *ToposText* annotation, our first objective was to assess its accuracy against a ground truth annotation. The gold standard was manually curated for Book 4 (18,664 tokens), dedicated to the geographical description of Central Europe and particularly representative of the entity types to be identified, consisting of a long list of place names. The annotations were encoded in Beginning-Inside-Outside (BIO) format. According to the BIO-format conventions, the first or only word of an entity is indicated with the B- prefix, whereas words within a multi-word entity are specified by the prefix I-, as shown in the example below (Table 1). Tokens located outside the entities are marked with an ‘O’.

The		O
city		B-LOC
of		I-LOC
Athens		I-LOC
.		O

Table 1: Named entity tagging in BIO style of the phrase “The city of Athens.”

In order to ensure consistency, clear guidelines were established, encompassing specific criteria for named entity types and annotation granularity. In summary, the gold standard was crafted in accordance with the conventions established by Romanello and Najem-Meyer (2022) as follows:

- **Definition of the entity type:** locations (LOC). References to named places within the text – that is, all the proper names for geographic locations – were annotated.¹² These include:
 - administrative locations including regions, cities, towns, districts, and villages;
 - physical places such as mountains, deserts, plains, islands, lands, seas, rivers, lakes, canals, and springs;
 - streets, squares, roads, and highways;
 - buildings, such as temples, sanctuaries, gates, forts, and stations.
- **Entity boundaries:** The annotation encompasses multi-word entities, including pre- and post- modifiers, such as “Mount Pindus”, “gulf of Corinth” and “Red Sea”. Articles are excluded from the annotation. The gold standard does not contain nested annotations.
- **Adjectives** derived from toponyms (e.g., “Corinthian”) are only annotated if they pertain to places (e.g., “Corinthian gulf”), not to other entities such as people (e.g., “Perikles the Athenian”), or objects (e.g., “Corinthian bronzes”).
- **Ethnics** are omitted from the annotation. In ancient sources, certain regions were named after the groups of people inhabiting them, rather than having specific place names. However, including ethnic names in the annotation would

¹² The notion of “place” is not straightforward, and there is a lively scholarly debate about the conceptualization of spatiality in antiquity. For practical reasons, an extensive discussion is beyond the scope of this paper. In this study, a broad definition of “place” will be adopted in accordance with the guidelines provided by the *Pleiades Gazetteer*.

have extended beyond the project’s primary focus, which centered on physical locations.

Each named location was manually annotated in the gold standard. Subsequently, the gold standard was employed as a benchmark to assess the accuracy of various systems of automated place name extraction, as described in Section 5.1.

4.2 Named Entity Recognition

In this step, a comparative evaluation was conducted of various NER systems to identify the optimal model for the translation of the *NH*. Two cutting-edge English NER tagging tools, *SpaCy*¹³ and *flairNLP*,¹⁴ were tested for the annotation of LOC labels (in the case of *Spacy*, both the LOC and GPE labels were extracted). The inspection of the results revealed that the *flairNER-large* model exhibited superior accuracy and recall capabilities, as discussed in Section 5.1. Finally, a validation process was initiated to determine whether each identified entity was either fully or partially represented in *ToposText*.

4.3 Automatic Text Alignment

The parallel texts were automatically aligned using *Vecalign* (Thompson and Koehn, 2019), a state-of-the-art method for bilingual sentence alignment. The method operates on the assumption that when parallel sentences from two different languages are represented in a vector space, their sentence embeddings become closely related. *Vecalign* was employed in conjunction with embeddings generated by the Language-agnostic BERT Sentence Embedding (*LaBSE*) (Feng et al., 2022), a multilingual transformer model fine-tuned for bitext mining. *LaBSE* has been demonstrated to be more accurate than other models, particularly in scenarios where there is limited training data, as recently evidenced by Petruccioli (2022) in the context of the alignment of Latin texts.

The *Vecalign* method is initialized with the input of the text files in .TXT format, one for each language, containing a list of the sentences to be aligned. The sentences were obtained by segmenting the text at the level of the full stop and, in the case of English, also in the presence of the punctuation marks ? and !. During the process of splitting Latin sentences, certain challenges were encountered due to some specific features of the text. These include the frequent use of full stops to indicate abbreviations (e.g. abbreviated proper nouns) and the presence of noise (e.g. sequences of ? ? ?) due to issues in the quality of OCR. Consequently, only full stops preceded by a token longer than two characters were considered for sentence splitting. In general, it was observed that the use of longer sentences was preferable when employing the *Vecalign* method.

Vecalign generated .TXT overlap files containing sentence concatenations (i.e., sentence 1, sentence 1 + sentence 2, sentence 1 + sentence 2 + sentence 3, and so on) from the input .TXT files. The overlap files were employed to generate sentence embeddings. *Vecalign* then employed the pre-processed files, the overlap files and the derived sentence embeddings to compute sentence similarity. In *Vecalign*, each sentence can be aligned to one (one-to-one alignment) or more sentences (one-to-many alignment). The output of the alignment process was a list of index pairs, corresponding to the indexes of the aligned sentences, along with a floating-point number representing the computed alignment cost. The scoring function was based on the normalized cosine

¹³ <https://spacy.io/>.

¹⁴ <https://github.com/flairNLP/flair>.

distance between the sentence embeddings, whereby the higher the cost, the more distant are the embeddings of the aligned sentences. In the event that no alignment was found, the alignment cost was set to zero.

4.4 Annotation Projection

The translation alignment is the process of establishing a correspondence between words in the source text and their equivalents in the translation. In this experiment, I used *SimAlign* (Sabet et al., 2020), an automated alignment method that utilizes cross-lingual semantic similarity between tokens based on static and contextualized embeddings. Among the various extraction algorithms proposed by Sabet et al. (2020), the iterative method *Itermax* was selected, which showed better performance particularly for distant languages. *Itermax* employs the simple *SimAlign* baseline iteratively, by modifying the similarity matrix conditioned on the alignment edges of the preceding iteration. The model also allows a token to be aligned with several other tokens, improving the identification of alignment edges when a single word corresponds to two or more words in the target language. The word embeddings were derived from the *UGARIT/gr-alignment* language model (see Related work), which had previously been tested in conjunction with *SimAlign* and *Itermax* (Yousef et al., 2023).

The aligned sentences obtained in the previous step (4.3) were used as input for the word alignment process. Initially, each sentence was tokenized, and the resulting tokens underwent vectorization. The cosine similarity was then computed as a similarity measure, and the *Itermax* algorithm extracted the translation pairs from the similarity matrix. The outcome of the word alignment process was a list of word index pairs for each sentence pair. Finally, the annotations were projected from the English tokens to their Latin equivalents. Given that the word order may differ between English and Latin, and tokens representing the same entity may not be consecutive, the projection process did not account for the distinction between B(eginning)- and I(nside)- labels. Each English attestation of a place name was associated with an identifier, which was linked to all the token(s) pertaining to the entity (e.g., 'id1' and 'id2' in Figure 1). Once the equivalent Latin token(s) had been aligned, the identifier was transferred. Finally, new BIO labels were assigned according to the relative position of the tokens.

Figure 1: Example of the annotation projection between two sentences.

5 Results

The combination of the *ToposText* annotations and the output of the *flairNER-large* resulted in the annotation of 13,964 place entities in the English text of the *NH*. The automated projection yielded 14,391 annotated Latin tokens, comprising 13,099 B-LOC and 1,292 I-LOC annotations. A total of 8,404 place entities were automatically

disambiguated in the Latin text. The following sections present an assessment of the accuracy of the output of the different steps of the workflow when applied out-of-the-box to Book 4, for which gold data was manually curated. The quantity and type of errors occurring at each stage were examined, and their impact on the final projection was analysed. Finally, the competing NER methods *LatinCy* and *Herodotos-Project-Latin-NER-Tagger* were applied directly to the Latin text of Book 4, and the output was compared with the result of the projection. With regard to *LatinCy*, I tested the large (*la-core-web-lg*) pipeline and the *la-core-web-trf* model, which is backed by the multilingual BERT transformer architecture.

5.1 Named Entity Recognition

The evaluation of the annotation task was conducted using three standard classification metrics: precision, recall, and f1-score. Evaluated against the gold standard, the *ToposText* annotation in Book 4 exhibited remarkably high precision (0.991), indicating that the majority of the annotations are correct (Table 2). However, it should be noted that *ToposText* is substantially incomplete, with a considerable number of place names missing, which as resulted in a low recall value (0.671). Given the absence of guidelines for entity boundaries in *ToposText*, the quality assessment was conducted at the named entity level, instead of the token level, and partial matches with the gold data were considered as true positives as long as they contained at least one capitalized word. To illustrate, if the gold standard included the annotation “Mount [B-LOC], Pindus [I-LOC]” and, at the same position, *ToposText* only annotated “Pindus [B-LOC]” (but not the pre-modifier), this would be counted as correct, despite differing labels for tokens at the same position.

	Place Entities	Precision	Recall	F1-score
<i>ToposText</i>	1,309	0.991	0.671	0.800
<i>flairNER</i>	1,338	0.905	0.637	0.748
<i>flairNER-large</i>	1,912	0.952	0.938	0.945
<i>SpaCy-trf</i>	1,937	0.938	0.938	0.938
<i>ToposText</i> + <i>flairNER-large</i>	1,983	0.949	0.968	0.958
Gold standard	1,931			

Table 2: Precision, recall and f1-scores of *ToposText*, *flairNLP*, *SpaCy* and *ToposText* combined with *flairNER-large* on Book 4.

When applied on Book 4, the NER systems *flairNER*, *flairNER-large*, and *SpaCy-trf* produced different outputs, as illustrated in Table 2. *FlairNER-large* outperformed the other systems, achieving a high-quality annotation with an f1-score of 0.945, along with strong precision and recall values. The model failed to identify 119 place entities and while it did manage to detect 115 of these, they were not correctly labeled as places. Notably, *flairNER-large* and *SpaCy-trf* exhibited similarities in their annotation styles, as evidenced by the annotation agreement (PAA = 81.7) computed by counting label matches at the token level.

The combination of *ToposText* with *flairNER* led to a further improvement in results with total of 795 new annotations. In comparison to using *ToposText* alone, there was a significant increase in recall (0.968), which was primarily due to a substantial drop in

false negatives. Although the resulting precision decreased from 0.991 to 0.949, due to an increase in false positives, the overall annotation quality showed a considerable improvement. This enhancement is highlighted by the f1-score, which reached the highest value obtained (0.958).

5.2 Automatic Text Alignment

The *Vecalign* method produced 395 alignments between 510 English sentences and 457 Latin sentences in Book 4. Manual inspection of a sample of the alignments revealed that out of 200 English sentences, 191 were correctly aligned, 8 were partially aligned and 1 was misaligned. In our evaluation, we considered an alignment to be strictly correct (SC) if the English sentence was completely contained within the aligned Latin sentence(s). Conversely, if the English sentence was not found within the aligned Latin sentence(s), we categorised it as misalignment (MIS). Alignments where the English sentence only partially overlapped within the aligned Latin sentence(s) were labelled as partially correct (PC).

In the qualitative assessment of the results, we found that the most influential factor on the quality of the alignment was the closeness of the translation to the parallel text, in particular similarity in sentence length and syntactic distribution. In cases where syntactic differences were present, *Vecalign* tried to align the sentences through one-to-many alignments, which occasionally led to errors. For example, consider the following alignments:

[185] At this spot there is another Isthmus, similar in name to the other, and of about equal width; and, in a manner by no means dissimilar, two cities formerly stood on the shore, one on either side, Pactye on the side of the Propontis, and Cardia on that of the Gulf of Melas, the latter deriving its name from the shape which the land assumes.

[169] *Alius namque ibi Isthmos angustias similes eodem nomine et pari latitudine inlustrat.* [170] *Duae urbes utrimque litora haut dissimili modo tenuere, Pactye a Propontide, Cardia a Melane sinu, haec ex facie loci nomine accepto, utraeque comprehensae postea Lysimachea V p. a Longis Muris.*

[186] **These, however, were afterwards united with Lysimachia, which stands at a distance of five miles from Macron Tichos.** [187] The Chersonesus formerly had, on the side of the Propontis, the towns of Tiristasis, Crithotes, and Cissa, on the banks of the river Aegos; it now has, at a distance of twenty-two miles from the colony of Apros, Resistos, which stands opposite to the colony of Parium.

[171] *Cherronesos a Propontide habuit Tiristasin, Crithoten, Cissam flumini Aegos adpositam; nunc habet a colonia Apro XXII p. Resisthon, ex adverso coloniae Parianae.*

The English sentence with index [186]: “These, however, were afterwards united with Lysimachia, etc.” was incorrectly aligned with the Latin sentence [171], rather than the corresponding Latin sentence [170]: *utraeque comprehensae postea Lysimachea* etc. This discrepancy can be attributed to the fact that the English translation does not accurately reflect the syntactic structure of the Latin text. In this instance, the Latin sentence [170] was translated into two separate English sentences [185] and [186], which resulted in the alignment method failing to correctly associate one of them with its corresponding Latin counterpart.

A comparable observation can be made when examining partial alignments, as illustrated by the following example.

[14] Passing out of the Ambracian Gulf into the Ionian Sea, we come to the coast of Leucadia, with the Promontory of Leucate, and then the Gulf and the peninsula of Leucadia, which

last was formerly called Neritis. [15] By the exertions of the inhabitants it was once cut off from the mainland, but was again joined to it by the vast bodies of sand accumulated through the action of the winds.

[12] *Egressos sinu Ambracio in Ionium excipit Leucadium litus, promunturium Leucates, dein sinus et Leucadia ipsa paeninsula, quondam Neritis appellata, opere accolarum abscisa continenti ac reddita ventorum flatu congeriem harenae adtumulantium, qui locus vocatur Dioryctos stadiorum longitudine trium.*

[16] **This spot is called Dioryctos, and is three stadia in length: on the peninsula is the town of Leucas, formerly called Neritus.**

[13] *Oppidum in ea Leucas, quondam Neritum dictum.*

In this case, the English sentence [16] was aligned with the Latin sentence [13], which only partially overlaps it. In particular, only the latter part of the sentence, “On the peninsula is the town of Leucas, formerly called Neritus”, corresponds to the Latin phrasing. Conversely, the first part of the English sentence, “This spot is called Dioryctos, and is three stadia in length”, aligns with the Latin sentence [12]: *qui locus vocatur Dioryctos stadiorum longitudine trium*. Since the information distribution differs between the two texts, this resulted in a partial alignment. Finally, no discernible patterns emerged between the alignment scores of strictly correct, partially correct and mis-alignments.

5.3 Annotation Projection

The utilization of *SimAlign* on Book 4 resulted in the projection of 1,850 entities on a total of 1,983, with 133 entities missed. The quality assessment of the annotation transfer was performed on a sample of 100 sentences for a total of 2,107 tokens and 485 manual annotated place entities. As for the English gold standard, the quality assessment of the Latin NER was conducted at the entity level, with at least one capitalized word annotated.

As illustrated in Table 3, our annotation projection achieved the best overall performance, attaining the highest f1-score (0.923). This value is significantly higher than the other f1 scores, in particular the *LatinCy-trf* system. This result can be attributed to a significantly higher recall value of our method (0.956), which can be explained by the fact that the initial English *ToposText+flairNER* annotation was almost complete.

	Precision	Recall	F1-score
<i>LatinCy-lg</i>	0.762	0.550	0.639
<i>LatinCy-trf</i>	0.949	0.232	0.374
<i>Herodotos-Project</i>	0.877	0.340	0.490
Annotation projection	0.892	0.956	0.923

Table 3: Precision, recall and f1-scores of *LatinCy* models, *Herodotos-Project-Latin-NER-Tagger* and our projection method on 100 sentences of Book 4.

The qualitative analysis of the results showed that several factors influenced the alignment quality. First, false negative and false positive annotations in the English NER led to projection errors. Second, correct sentence alignment proved critical for word alignment. In fact, partially aligned or misaligned sentences consistently caused word misalignments. Third, the quality of the alignment depended on the accuracy of

the translation. In our case study, English place names are generally very similar to the Latin original, which contributed to correct alignment. In addition, Book 4 contains long lists of names with relatively simple syntactic structures, which facilitated token alignment. In other cases, however, a place name was the translation of a Latin ethnic name (“Thessalians” for *Thessalia*), which resulted in an incorrect annotation of the Latin text, demonstrating a consistent limitation of the transfer approach. Finally, the projection of proper names was found to be more accurate than the projection of common nouns in multi-token entities. In certain instances, annotated English common nouns lacked a Latin equivalent, but were added by the translators for the sake of clarity or due to English grammatical constraints. When transferred, the projection resulted in an erroneous annotation of the Latin text, as no suitable equivalent could be identified. In other instances, despite the presence of an equivalent Latin word, the model failed to align it correctly. This is exemplified by the sentence “Here is also Mount Taygetus, the river Eurotas, the town of Psamathus, the gulf of Gytheum” (*NH* 4.8), where the word “gulf” was aligned with the word *oppidum* instead of the correct word *sinus*.

6 Conclusions

In this study, we conducted a geoparsing experiment on Pliny the Elder’s *NH*. To address the challenges of performing NER tasks on languages with limited resources, a cross-lingual multi-stage approach was used to automatically align sentence pairs and transfer annotations from the English translation back to the original Latin text. The methodology proved to be more effective for this task than other NER baselines applied directly to the Latin text, showing better performance, especially in terms of recall. Moreover, the approach can be generalized to other Latin texts, exploiting on the potential of translated parallel texts to expand Latin NER datasets without the necessity for additional training data. However, many factors can influence the performance of the annotation. The quality achieved in each automated component of the workflow (English NER, sentence alignment, word alignment) significantly influences the final output and errors propagate across the pipeline. Accurate translations are required to achieve good results and various factors, including syntactic complexity, text genre, and language style, can influence the efficacy of the alignment process. In addition, the resulting Latin annotation lacks consistency in annotation style, especially in the case of multi-token entities, due to the absence of guidelines in *ToposText* and the differing annotation styles of *ToposText* and *flairNER*. Finally, the projection method is not context-aware, unlike NER systems, which attempt to capture the meaning of words in the source language. In future work, the pipeline will be tested on documents that are not geographically specific and that exhibit a greater degree of syntactic complexity, without the benefit of prior annotation. This will permit further evaluation of the effectiveness of the NER and the annotation transfer across parallel corpora of ancient sources and their modern translations.

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OCR Error Detection and Post-Correction with Word2vec and BERTje on Dutch Historical Data

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High-quality Optical Character Recognition (OCR) output is essential for enhancing the accessibility of documents and enabling various Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks. However, historical documents often present significant OCR errors due to their condition and variability in fonts and spellings. This study addresses the post-processing correction of OCR errors in Dutch historical documents, comparing the effectiveness of two widely used word embedding models: static word2vec and contextual BERT. Although BERT has shown promising results in previous studies, the reasons for its superior performance remain unclear. This research aims to identify the specific challenges faced by word2vec and determine if BERT can mitigate these issues more effectively. By analyzing both models in detail for error detection and correction tasks, we provide insights into their respective strengths and limitations. Our findings suggest that while both models have their merits, BERT demonstrates a notable advantage in handling some of the complexities of historical data, making it a valuable tool for OCR post-correction in digital humanities.

Keywords: OCR post-correction, Natural Language Processing, Word Embedding Models, historical data, digital heritage

1 Introduction

In digital humanities, particularly in the context of historical document analysis, the improvement of Optical Character Recognition (OCR) technology is of great importance. With a high quality of OCR-output, documents become more accessible to readers, and Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks can thrive on the data. However, the extent to which all this is possible is dependent on the quality of the OCR-output. OCR on historical data often creates significant errors due to the poor condition of documents and variations in font size and spelling.

In this context, our research addresses the critical need for post-processing of OCR-generated machine-readable text. Specifically, our focus is on historical documents written in Dutch. We employ word embedding models (WEMs) as a key component to tackle this task effectively. WEMs have been shown to be promising for the task of post-correcting OCR-output Hämäläinen and Hengchen (2019); Nguyen et al. (2020); Pal and Mustafi (2020). They can be divided into static word embeddings and the more novel context-aware word embeddings. We turn our attention to two popular WEMs to represent them; static word2vec and context-aware BERTje (a Dutch version of BERT) Hämäläinen and Hengchen (2019); Nguyen et al. (2020).

Although alternative models might be interesting for this research, word2vec and BERTje have been selected for several reasons. FastText’s character-level n-gram approach might be more effective than word2vec at capturing variations in historical spellings and surface errors. However, word2vec is a well-established model that offers a relatively straightforward implementation. Word2vec also serves as a common baseline for evaluating newer word embedding models Devlin et al. (2018); Pennington et al. (2014). For these reasons, it allows for a clearer comparison of BERTje’s performance against a standard approach. Recently, GysBERT has been introduced as a strong contender against BERTje. Its training on historical data makes it a strong candidate for understanding the nuances of historical language, potentially leading to superior performance on the OCR post-correction task. However, at the start of our project, GysBERT was still in development. Additionally, comparing word2vec and BERTje, both non-specialized in historical data, provides more insight into the architecture and application of the models themselves. In contrast, using a specialized model like GysBERT would focus more on the influence of the data it was trained on. Therefore using BERTje instead of GysBERT can lead to clarifying insights.

Despite BERT showing promising results in OCR post-correction, existing studies lack an in-depth analysis of its performance when compared to previous models. This study aims to fill this research gap by thoroughly comparing BERTje and word2vec. Specifically, We compare the performance of contextualized word embeddings from BERTje and static word embeddings from word2vec in post-correcting OCR output from Dutch historical documents. By doing so, we aim to understand how different word embedding methods can benefit the processing of historical documents and improve the state-of-the-art.

This project is structured into three phases: first, we isolate the task of error detection; second, we conduct an isolated experiment on error correction; and third, we combine error detection and correction in a comprehensive evaluation process.

In this study, our primary objective goes beyond merely comparing the performance of BERT with word2vec in OCR post-correction. We also aim to delve into the underlying reasons for performance disparities, specifically by examining how each model addresses specific challenges; namely homonyms, historical spelling variations, out-of-vocabulary words, infrequent words, and real-word errors Wevers and Koolen (2020).

2 Background

2.1 OCR Post-correction

OCR post-correction involves three primary approaches, each with its set of merits and limitations Hämäläinen and Hengchen (2019); Nguyen et al. (2020); Salimzadeh

(2019).

Firstly, there's the crowdsourcing or manual error correction approach, which relies on people manually verifying and correcting OCR-generated output. While this method offers careful error correction, it is remarkably time-intensive.

The second approach, known as lexical error correction, employs a quicker process. It identifies and rectifies errors through dictionary-based comparisons. However, it struggles when confronted with words that are absent in the reference dictionary. This limitation becomes more pronounced when dealing with historical language, given the scarcity of relevant lexicons and the diverse linguistic nature of historical documents.

The third approach, statistical error correction, represents a diverse spectrum of methods, including machine translation and recurrent neural networks (RNNs). These methods are distinct in that they rely less on dictionaries. However, they may not fully capture nuanced linguistic differences in historical documents due to their statistical models being primarily based on modern language conventions. Word embeddings belong to this category.

2.2 Word embeddings

Word embeddings add a layer of semantics which is useful when dealing with historical data, known for its variability. This semantic layer enables independent text comprehension, which reduces reliance on statistical rules that are primarily based on modern language.

There are two main types of word embeddings: contextualized and context-free. Context-free or static models create a single embedding for each word, combining all possible senses. On the other hand, contextualized models, such as BERT, assign different vectors to different senses of the same word. Static WEMs like word2vec have some limitations, such as their data hunger, struggles with handling polysemy, and a tendency to rely on lexical approaches. They also face challenges with infrequent historical expressions and out-of-vocabulary words Hämäläinen and Hengchen (2019); Wevers and Koolen (2020); Wiedemann et al. (2019).

While static WEMs have found uses in tasks like lexical semantics, lexicalsemantic tasks, concept-based search, and (sentiment) classification, for OCR post-correction they have less often been applied Egense (2017); Malte and Ratadiya (2019); Rezaeinia et al. (2019); Tulkens et al. (2016). However, Transformer models like BERT have already shown impressive performance in this context Nguyen et al. (2020). Previous comparisons between BERT and static WEMs have primarily focused on classification tasks. There has been limited exploration of the reason for BERT's effectiveness in OCR post-correction.

Several factors might possibly account for BERT's superior performance over static WEMs. BERT's heightened sensitivity to infrequent expressions makes it well-suited for smaller historical datasets. It effectively handles out-of-vocabulary words by breaking them into subtokens, enabling the understanding of less common historical expressions Wevers and Koolen (2020). For instance, when encountering the out-of-vocabulary word 'lantaarnopsteker' ('lamplighter', a word that will likely not be frequently used in modern documents), BERT identifies the subtokens that form the words 'lantaarn' and 'opsteker,' making it easier to grasp the word's meaning. This feature is particularly useful for Dutch, where composite words are often written as single tokens. BERT also addresses the challenge of polysemy by training separate vectors for different meanings of homonyms. Its training approach, involving the completion of masked words, aligns well with the task of OCR error correction, which will be

further explained in section 3.5. Lastly, BERT’s bidirectional transformer architecture considers both the context on the left and the right of a word, setting it apart from its predecessor ELMo Wiedemann et al. (2019).

Additionally, we explore an intriguing phenomenon not previously explicitly recognized as a word2vec pitfall in the literature: the "real word error" (RWE), which occurs when an OCR machine generates an erroneous token that happens to be a valid word in the dictionary. For instance, consider the transformation of ‘grass’ into ‘glass.’ A dictionary-based method would fail to flag this as incorrect. Thus, part of the research goal revolves around the effectiveness of the discussed techniques in detecting and rectifying these unique tokens as well just mentioned, as well as real word errors.

However, BERT is not immune to limitations. It demands significant computational resources, making it less accessible for broader training on a diverse collection of datasets, which has led to historical datasets being more frequently overlooked. Moreover, due to its complexity and size, BERT lacks the transparency needed for understanding its inner workings Malte and Ratadiya (2019); Wevers and Koolen (2020).

3 Experimental setup

3.1 The dataset

The dataset consists of the OCR-output of nearly 40,000 historical documents in Dutch. The documents are from the seventeenth up to the twentieth century, in five different categories: complete newspapers, individual news articles, books, book pages and typewritten radio bulletins. The dataset is freely accessible and in possession of the KB, National Library of the Netherlands, which additionally commissioned the creation of a ground-truth (GT) that is 99.95 percent accurate GT; Giovanni Colavizza (2021). The OCR has been performed by ABBYY. The data come along with multiple meta-datasets met (a,b); Wilms et al. (2020).

For the purpose of analysing the efficiency of word2vec and BERTje at post-correcting specific tokens particularly, such as historical terms and homonyms, we used curated lists provided by the Dutch Language Institute Mol.

Computational limitations led to only using part of the data, with a proportional selection of the genres and centuries used.

We conducted a thorough selection and sampling process to create a balanced and representative dataset. Initially, redundant files were removed to streamline the dataset.

Figure 1: Distribution of historical documents in the KB Dataset categorized by century and genre

For documents with multiple OCR outputs, the most recent output was selected to ensure the highest quality.

The dataset was further reduced in size due to computational constraints, aiming to take half a page from each document on average. This decision was based on the average length of a book page (272.25 words) and the average number of characters per word (5, including punctuation)cha; (pseud. van H. Brandt Corstius.). This consistent metric was applied across all document types.

As some documents were shorter than the cutoff, the final dataset included 13,390 pages from the original 378,008 pages. To ensure even distribution across the centuries, we adjusted the amount of text taken from each document based on the total number of documents available per century. This method ensured that each century and document type was adequately represented, maintaining a balanced dataset that reflects the diversity of historical documents. Due to computational expense, the models were eventually evaluated on a random selection of five hundred of these adapted pages. The experiment could however easily be repeated with more time and computational power on the complete 13,390 pages.

3.2 Models

The Dutch word2vec used was trained on Belgian magazines, Wikipedia, websites, the Social Media Dataset, and the SoNaR corpus consisting of newsletters, press releases, books, magazines, and newspapersTulkens et al. (2016).

Like BERT, BERTje is trained for two tasks: masked language modelling and next sentence prediction. It uses the same architecture and parameters as BERT. It is equivalent to BERTbase with 12 transformer blocks. It is more extensively trained on Dutch data than the multilingual BERT. Like Dutch word2vec, it has been trained on Wikipedia, the SoNar corpus, websites, but also books, including historical novels de Vries et al. (2019). The soft masked BERT models used for OCR post-correction, as well as the word2vec applications, are often applied together with other (deep learning) techniques that boost the performance. However, since this study is trying to compare the word embeddings themselves in their 'natural' state and is not focused on boosting performance, other models are not applied here.

As a baseline, we employ a lexical approach, using a dictionary to detect and rectify errors. This decision is consistent with established practices for OCR post-correction, as described in section 2 'Background'.

3.3 Preprocessing

The optimal preprocessing decisions for post-correction of OCR output are still under discussionKhirbat (2017). This is crucial, as it can significantly influence the entire process and its outcomes. In this project, preprocessing steps were applied to both the ground truth and the OCR output to enable a meaningful comparison. The following decisions were made regarding preprocessing:

- Punctuation was selectively removed, with exceptions made for full stops and hyphens to preserve hyphenated words. Full stops were retained to distinguish sentences from each other but were later removed during the evaluation phase. Although characters like question and exclamation marks could also serve as sentence separators, they were deemed unnecessary, as the primary objective was to segment the text into manageable portions.

- All capital letters were converted to lowercase.
- Lemmatization was intentionally avoided for the correction process, as advised by Khirbat in the literature Khirbat (2017). Lemmatization would potentially leave out crucial structural information. For example, if ‘has’ were lemmatized to ‘have,’ the word embedding model would lose the context necessary to determine whether it should be preceded by ‘they’ or ‘he’ for example. These nuances are essential in the context of text correction with statistical methods.

The training phase encompassed all data combined, with no specific century-wise training, but for the last task the data were categorized by century. For this task of performing error detection and correction in a continuous pipeline, the results were provided by century to better analyse the efficiency of the models on older versus newer historical data. An alternative would be categorization by genre, but as a major challenge for OCR post-correction is the drastic change of language over time Nguyen et al. (2020), the division of the data was based on this aspect.

3.4 Alignment of the OCR-output and the ground truth

An essential preliminary task for evaluating the OCR post-correction output is aligning the ground truth with the OCR output. This has not yet been done in the provided dataset. The alignment process comprises of two steps: initial sentence-level alignment followed by word-level alignment.

To align sentences from the ground truth with the OCR output, we use approximate string matching for two primary purposes: First, it addresses situations where the ABBYY software missed complete sentences, parts of sentences, or entire pages, resulting in missing OCR output. Consequently, the ground truth for these missing sentences and pages is also removed. The calculation of the Word Error Rate (WER, the percentage of words transcribed incorrectly during the OCR process) and Character Error Rate (CER, the percentage of characters transcribed incorrectly during the OCR process), which indicate OCR output quality, occurs only after this step. This approach ensures that the WER reflects only the impact of OCR post-correction, without the added effect of redundant ground truth removal. The second purpose of approximate string matching for sentence alignment is to facilitate word-level alignment.

For the word-level alignment, each word in the OCR-output is aligned to its counterpart in the ground truth. This way, it can be determined whether an OCR token is an error and if a suggested correction is indeed correct, see fig. 2.

Figure 2: Example of word alignment between ground truth and OCR output

The word alignment in this study is based on the Fast Recursive Text Alignment Scheme (RETAS), which aligns texts by recursively cutting them into smaller parts Yalniz and Manmatha (2011). The texts were first divided into sentences and then aligned word by word from both directions (front to back and back to front). Unlike RETAS, this method uses anchor words—unique and less frequent words—as reference points for alignment. Due to errors and missing words in the OCR output, approximate string matching was employed. An alignment checker was developed

to ensure the quality of alignment by warning about bad alignments and excluding them from evaluation. This checker was validated and found to be highly accurate, with precision, recall, and F1-scores all above 0.95. Eventually, the word alignment looks as in Figure 2. The bad alignments are removed for the evaluation using the forementioned alignment checker. The code for both the word alignment and the alignment checker can be found through the link provided in the appendix.

3.5 Approach

As mentioned in the introduction, this project is structured into an isolated detection task, an isolated correction task, and a final experiment where error detection and correction are combined consecutively, thus not in isolation. This approach follows a two-step process for OCR correction, as suggested by Schaefer et al. (2020), which enables us to reduce the likelihood of erroneously correcting OCR-output that is already correct (Schaefer and Neudecker (2020)). Additionally, this approach enhances our ability to pinpoint the precise stages, either the detection stage or the correction stage, where errors occur in the post-correction process. Furthermore, it allows us to fine-tune our strategies for each distinct stage, tailoring them based on each stage's specific requirements.

3.5.1 Detection task

To begin with, it is crucial to highlight that the detection task is performed on all tokens, both correct and incorrect. This ensures that the models are assessed on their ability to correctly identify errors without falsely labeling correct tokens.

The detection for the dictionary method, which is the baseline for this project, is the most straightforward: if a token is not in the dictionary, it is considered to be an error.

Many word2vec detection and correction tasks are as well reliant on a dictionary. Word clusters of words that are similar to the OCR token are created and the correct spellings are selected with a dictionary. Proposed methods that avoid this dependency do yet not generate a higher accuracy than those that do not (Hammarström et al. (2017)). This problem will not be solved in the scope of this project, but since dependency on lexicons was mentioned as one of the pitfalls of word2vec OCR post-correction models, a lexicon will not be used. Alternatively, a method closer in approach to BERT's error detection process, namely Continuous Bag of Words (CBOW), is employed, as illustrated in Figure 3. This choice simplifies the process of comparing our approach to BERT's methodology.

In the CBOW version of word2vec, context words are used as input. The output consists of words that are semantically similar, determined by cosine similarity. The length of the list of predicted tokens can be specified with a parameter. The amount of input words is determined by the window size; in this project of size five. A larger window size (greater than 15) results in the model generating output words closely related in semantics to the input. On the contrary, a smaller window size (less than 15) yields tokens that are interchangeable, such as synonyms (Rong (2014); Yang (2024)). For this project, a smaller window size of five is selected to ensure the model suggests words that could co-occur with the input words, see fig. 3a.

Figure 3: Token prediction methods used by Word2Vec and BERTje

The same principle is applied with BERTje. However, instead of a window size with context words, the whole sentence is used as context, as BERT is trained and finetuned on sentences. The predicted candidates to fill the mask are ordered based on probability instead of cosine similarity. See fig. 3b.

The positioning of words within the list of output words can serve as an indicator of whether they are likely to be errors. Take the example from Figure fig. 3: "what a ??? day today". The word 'mooie' ('beautiful'), which appears as the top word in the suggestions to fill in the blank, is correctly spelled. However, if it were a misspelling, it would likely have rarely occurred in the provided context during pretraining and fine-tuning, resulting in its appearance at a lower position in the list. Therefore, the relative position of an OCR token in the candidates' list can be used to gauge whether it is an error or notHu et al. (2020).

However, where should the line in this list between likely correct tokens and likely erroneous ones be drawn? Determining the optimal parameter for the cutoff position, which signifies whether a token is an error, is performed through validation set analysis. It should be positioned at the transition point between the higher rankings in the candidate list, where mostly accurate tokens are found, and the lower rankings, where mostly erroneous tokens reside. While related literature often finds optimal parameters by running the model multiple times with various parameters[15], this approach can be computationally intensive. In contrast, by plotting the positions of correct and erroneous tokens, the optimal parameter can be found more conveniently, see figure fig. 4.

Figure 4: Distribution of accurate and erroneous tokens in the candidate lists generated by Word2Vec and BERTje during validation

The optimal detection parameters are ideally positioned where you can observe the orange lines in Figure 4. In the upper ranks of the candidates list, to the left of the orange line, the likelihood of encountering accurate tokens is higher than that of encountering erroneous ones. Conversely, to the right of the orange line, further down the candidates list, the tokens are predominantly erroneous, such as misspelled words. Thus, the orange line serves as the threshold for determining whether a token is likely to be erroneous; if it falls below this position in the list, it is considered likely erroneous and, hence, an error.

From figure fig. 4, a cutoff parameter of 250 is chosen for word2vec, while BERT performs best with a setting of 50. These values will be employed for the detection task. However, to gain insights into the impact of a more cautious parameter setting on the overall task, a value of 500 is retained for the complete task. This reduces the likelihood of the model unintentionally changing correctly spelled words into incorrect ones by mistakenly labeling them as errors.

3.5.2 Correction task

The isolated correction task, as mentioned, was performed solely on the tokens considered to be erroneous according to the gold truth dataset.

For correction, a similar candidate list method as the one used for detection is employed. Again, the validation set is used. This time, the optimal correction candidate for the error found in the validation set's ground truth is selected from the list. Since detection and correction are distinct tasks, a separate optimal parameter needs to be determined. This parameter determines how many correction candidates are considered. Generally, a higher value for this parameter results in better model performance as the actual ground truth correction is more likely to be on the candidates list, but it also increases computational time as more candidates have to be created and considered.

To identify the most effective parameter, a plot is generated to determine the typical position of correct corrections (ground truth tokens) within the candidates' list. For the model to perform well, it is crucial to include as many correct tokens as possible in the candidates list. If a ground truth token is not present in the list, the model cannot provide the correct correction. Figure fig. 5 displays the positions of correct tokens within the candidates lists generated by word2vec and BERT in the validation set. The

visualization extends up to position five hundred, which is the maximum value used in the literatureHu et al. (2020). Positions beyond five hundred are unattainable and are recorded as position five hundred in the plot.

Evidently, approximately 80% of the ground truth tokens are further down the candidates list than position five hundred. Consequently, the "topn correction" parameter should be substantially higher than five hundred. Ideally, improving the model's ability to recommend the correct candidates, such as by more extensive finetuning, would be the optimal solution. However, for the time being, the parameter is set to five hundred for both word2vec and BERTje.

Now how will the correction process be conducted? Let's begin by revisiting the straightforward baseline method. The baseline method relies on a dictionary to rectify erroneous tokens by replacing them with words found in the dictionary. This correction process is accomplished using the Levenshtein distance (LD), which measures the minimum number of character edits (insertions, deletions, or substitutions) required to transform one word into another. Given that OCR errors often result from character editsSalimzadeh (2019), the LD is a suitable choice. However, in this study, a Levenshtein ratio is employed, derived from the LD. To illustrate why, consider the LD between "now" and "not" as well as between "nowadays" and the misspelled "nowadayf." Surprisingly, the LD is identical for both pairs of words. However, when assessing the context, "nowadayf" is more likely to contain an error than "not". The Levenshtein ratio thus considers the length of the tokens as well.

When considering the Levenshtein ratio, a value of one indicates an exact match between tokens, while zero implies no similarity whatsoever. In the baseline method, the predicted correction is determined by selecting the word from the dictionary that, when compared to the OCR token, have the highest Levenshtein ratio. However, due to computational constraints, this ratio is only computed for words that possess the same character count as the OCR error or at most one character less or one character more. This broader range accounts for potential errors resulting from insertions or deletions.

Figure 5: Positions of correct tokens (ground truth tokens) in the candidate lists generated by Word2Vec and BERTje from the validation set

Sorting method			
	Levenshtein ratio	Cosine (word2vec)	Probability (BERTje)
"nieuwe"	0.91	0.179	0.161
"nieuws"	0.91	0.051	0.128
"mooie"	0.40	0.385	0.009
"grijze"	0.36	0.384	0.001

Figure 6: Method for selecting the optimal correction candidate. Candidates are first sorted based on the Levenshtein ratio and then further sorted based on likelihood (cosine similarity for word2vec or probability for BERTje) from the context

For the correction with WEMs, there are two approaches of context sensitive text correction with WEMs mentioned in the literature Fivez et al. (2017); Hu et al. (2020). The first approach relies on a lexicon, which, as previously noted, is a pitfall this project tries to avoid. The other uses a list of candidates as was previously described. This method will be used in this project. The selection of the right candidate for correction is based on the Levenshtein ratio and also a cosine similarity for word2vec and a probability for BERT.

Typically, two primary methods are employed for this candidate selection task. These approaches have been compared in this study to determine the most suitable one for application. The first involves sorting candidates based on the Levenshtein distance, followed by considering either cosine similarity or probability. However, this method exhibits a bias towards frequently occurring words. For instance, "van" (meaning "of") is often suggested. This is especially done by word2vec, because "van" frequently appears in various contexts, and word2vec lacks grammatical structure indicators like BERTje. Consequently, in the case of word2vec, there's some debate in related literature regarding the removal of stopwords Hämäläinen and Hengchen (2019); Kim et al. (2019).

The other approach to this is the 'calculation method,' where a metric is calculated to determine the sorting order. A pre-existing calculation derived from literature, where the highest 'score' provides the best correction candidate, goes as follows [12]:

$$score = normalized\ cos\ or\ prob / (1 - LR)$$

The candidate with the highest score is selected as the correction. In this study, the Levenshtein ratio is used. However, unlike the Levenshtein distance, where a lower value indicates a close match, a high LR indicates a close match. An LR value of one means an exact match. Therefore, (1 - LR) is employed in this context. Additionally, to ensure a fair comparison between word2vec and BERT, the cosine similarity and probabilities were normalized for more consistent calculations.

These ranking methods was experimented with on the validation set. As the 'sort method without removing stopwords' performs best for both techniques on the validation set section 7, this method will be used on the test set. This means stopwords are removed from the candidates list and correction candidates will be sorted based on the Levenshtein distance first and subsequently by either cosine similarity or probability.

3.5.3 Complete OCR post-correction task

Instead of now performing detection and correction in isolation, the whole process is combined in this last task. This is done a fluent pipeline by first performing the

detection task on both the correct and the erroneous tokens, then feeding the tokens detected as errors to the correction task.

3.6 Evaluation

In the evaluation of the detection task, metrics such as recall, precision, and F1-score are employed, complemented by accuracy. We chose recall, precision, F1-score, and accuracy to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the models, capturing both the quality of the positive predictions and the overall correctness of the results. The metrics are chosen to evaluate true negatives and false positives on correct tokens as well as false negatives and true positives on erroneous tokens. This thorough evaluation ensures that both the accurate detection of errors and the avoidance of incorrectly labeling correct tokens are taken into account.

However, for the correction task, only accuracy is considered as this is a binary classification task. To comprehensively assess the overall method's performance, we calculate the CER and WER using the OCR post-corrected dataset. These metrics can be compared to the CER and WER from the pre-correction OCR output, as discussed in the preprocessing section.

As this project is mostly interested in the effect of the pitfalls of word2vec on both word2vec and BERTje's performance, the performance on these specific pitfalls is also measured using recall, precision and F1-score for the detection and accuracy for the correction task. These pitfalls were mentioned earlier to be homonyms, historical spelling variations, out-of-vocabulary words, infrequent words, and real word errors.

This analysis is also applied on the detection and correction of tokens that contain these special tokens in their context (a window for word2vec and the whole sentence for BERT). Something like a real word error or homonym in the context window could potentially mess up the detection and correction of a token as well, as wrong candidates might be suggested.

Thus the evaluation during the detection, correction, and combined task is applied on three levels: all available tokens, these mentioned special tokens like homonyms and real word errors, and words that have these special tokens in their direct environment.

4 Results

In bold are the F1 and accuracy scores of the methods that perform the best in each category (token or century) compared to the other methods. An asterisk indicates the F1 or accuracy scores that are lower than the average performance of that method on all tokens or all centuries combined. Scores marked with an asterisk thus suggest suboptimal performance compared to the overall average. For instance, in Table 1, the F1 score for the baseline method on historical tokens is 0.765, which is in bold because it is the highest among the methods. In contrast, the F1 score for word2vec on homonyms is 0.416, marked with an asterisk because it is lower than word2vec's average F1 score on all tokens, which is 0.424.

4.1 Detection task

Table 1 presents the error detection performance by token type. Table 2 shows the metrics on the detection task when certain tokens are in the model's context. Here the occurrence refers to the number of times the model has seen a specific token, like a homonym, in its context during the whole task. This occurrence value is different for

each model because word2vec uses a window, while BERTje uses the whole sentence as context. Table 3 shows the results by century.

The baseline method achieved strong overall performance. BERTje outperformed other methods in detecting Out-of-Vocabulary (OOV) and Real Word Error (RWE) tokens, and achieved exceptional overall detection.

Both WEMs showed a significant advantage over the baseline in detecting OOV and RWE errors, as expected for methods that go beyond dictionary-based approaches.

	special token:	homonyms	historical	OOV	infrequent	RWE	none	all
occurrence		9797	32679	differs	32450	32450	3510	38533
precision	baseline	0.869	0.927	0.453	0.792	0	0.901	0.784
	word2vec	0.576	0.419	0.750	0.417	0.917	0.071	0.433
	BERTje	0.222	0.185	0.686	0.186	0.976	0.129	0.733
recall	baseline	0.780	0.708	0.292	0.602	0	0.795	0.555
	word2vec	0.647	0.470	0.499	0.478	0.477	0.152	0.465
	BERTje	0.325	0.423	0.799	0.443	0.858	0.129	0.826
F1	baseline	0.796	0.765	0.330*	0.654	0	0.828	0.615
	word2vec	0.576	0.416*	0.516	0.420*	0.612	0.082	0.424
	BERTje	0.241*	0.236*	0.708*	0.242*	0.990	0.129	0.750
accuracy	baseline	0.932	0.868	0.270	0.813	0	0.933	0.778
	word2vec	0.713	0.536	0.379	0.542	0.477	0.051	0.527
	BERTje	0.442	0.320	0.659	0.318	0.858	0.171	0.463

Table 1: Precision, Recall, F1-score, and Accuracy of the error detection task by token type

Figure 7: F1-scores on error detection task by token by model, , where 'all' stands for all tokens (special and non-special tokens together)

Word2vec seems to consistently show a superior performance compared to BERTje when homonyms, historical words, OOV tokens and infrequent words are in its context.

	token in context:	homonyms	historical	OOV	infrequent	RWE	none	all
occurrence	word2vec →	20903	33395	9239	33460	4902	112	38533
occurrence	BERTje →	29561	32992	26241	38351	13122	695	38533
precision	word2vec	0.865	0.591	0.610	0.570	0.761	0.894	0.443
	BERTje	0.733	0.439	0.460	0.424	0.747	0.626	0.733
recall	word2vec	0.956	0.784	0.751	0.771	0.852	0.894	0.465
	BERTje	0.826	0.652	0.650	0.642	0.848	0.636	0.826
F1	word2vec	0.878	0.635	0.645	0.617	0.785	0.894	0.424
	BERTje	0.750	0.491*	0.505*	0.477*	0.772	0.629	0.750
accuracy	word2vec	0.744	0.676	0.667	0.659	0.538	0.071	0.527
	BERTje	0.463	0.419	0.422	0.412	0.478	0.099	0.463

Table 2: Precision, Recall, F1-score, and Accuracy of the error detection task for tokens in context

	by century:	1600s	1700s	1800s	1900s	all
occurrence	→	3949	2865	15318	15052	37184
precision	baseline	0.820	0.845	0.585	0.458	0.799
	word2vec	0.820	0.845	0.585	0.458	0.799
	BERTje	0.231	0.221	0.166	0.165	0.225
recall	baseline	0.623	0.311	0.182	0.218	0.586
	word2vec	0.465	0.434	0.478	0.488	0.465
	BERTje	0.456	0.794	0.806	0.798	0.497
F1	baseline	0.683	0.421*	0.269*	0.260*	0.643
	word2vec	0.453	0.258*	0.207*	0.168*	0.424
	BERTje	0.292	0.327	0.262*	0.242*	0.290
accuracy	baseline	0.7701	0.807	0.829	0.853	0.778
	word2vec	0.549	0.392	0.349	0.336	0.527
	BERTje	0.308	0.532	0.560	0.613	0.340

Table 3: Precision, Recall, F1-score, and Accuracy of the error detection task by century

Figure 8: F1-scores on error detection task by century, where 'all' stands for all centuries together

Surprisingly, all methods showed better detection rates on older documents compared to newer ones. Especially the baseline dictionary-based method outperforms both word2vec and BERTje in texts from the seventeenth and eighteenth century at the detection task when considering all tokens from these centuries' datasets, not just the special tokens.

4.2 Correction task

Table 4 shows the results on the error correction task by token type. In contrast to the other tokens, only the occurrence of out-of-vocabulary words witnessed by the models differs for each model, as they each use their own vocabularies. Table 5 shows the results for tokens in context. Table 6 aggregates the results by century.

Word2vec excels in error correction for special tokens, despite its previously identified reliance on lexical methods as a potential weakness.

	special tokens:	homonyms	historical	OOV	infrequent	RWE	none	all
	occurrence →	656	3788	differs	3950	3510	differs	6772
baseline	accuracy	0.142*	0.333	0.397	0.337	0*	0.408	0.332
word2vec	accuracy	0.581	0.618	0.436	0.647	0.442	0.5	0.593
BERTje	accuracy	0.537	0.505	0.421*	0.509	0.414*	Nan	0.485

Table 4: Accuracy of the error correction task by token type

Figure 9: Accuracies on error correction task by token by model, where ‘all’ stands for all tokens (special and non-special tokens together)

	special tokens in context:	homonyms	historical	OOV	infrequent	RWE	none	all
	occurrence word2vec →	1569	3104	1873	3109	1533	80	6772
	occurrence BERTje →	2503	3222	2798	3228	2152	58	6772
word2vec	accuracy	0.151	0.305	0.258	0.299	0.172	0	0.593
BERTje	accuracy	0.100*	0.050*	0.048*	0.047*	0.052*	0.058	0.485

Table 5: Accuracy on correction task by token in context.

	by century:	1600s	1700s	1800s	1900s	all
	occurrence →	1666	728	2538	1702	6634
baseline	accuracy	0.362	0.225*	0.182	0.206*	0.332
word2vec	accuracy	0.622*	0.473*	0.466*	0.508*	0.593
BERTje	accuracy	0.494	0.468	0.426*	0.452*	0.485

Table 6: Accuracy on correction task by century.

Figure 10: Accuracies on error correction task by century, where 'all' stands for all centuries together

4.3 Complete OCR post-correction task

Table 7 shows the result on the end-to-end OCR post-correction task. The Character Error Rate and Word Error Rate can be interpreted as percentages. An improvement of 40% however should not be interpreted as an improvement of 40 percent in regard to the old CER or WER, but as a decrease of 40 CER or WER expressed in percentages. As the improvement in Table 7 appears negative, this means that the amount of errors after the end-to-end task has become worse. Word2vec and BERTje appear to perform at least less suboptimal than the baseline in this regard.

		old WER	new WER	improvement	old CER	new CER	improvement	total words
1600s	baseline	24.842	67.192	-41.190	7.187	51.320	-42.412	45505
	word2vec	24.842	56.644	-28.999	7.187	42.329	-31.414	45505
	BERTje	24.842	74.800	-48.528*	7.187	51.320	-42.412	45505
1700s	baseline	21.833	77.605	-55.251*	6.826	73.009	-65.555*	52316
	word2vec	21.833	61.671	-38.946*	6.826	47.880	-39.842*	52316
	BERTje	21.833	57.783	-34.968	6.826	45.922	-37.839	52316
1800s	baseline	14.278	61.520	-47.242*	5.670	72.972	-67.302*	128608
	word2vec	14.278	61.435	-47.158*	5.670	55.306	-49.636	128608
	BERTje	14.278	50.789	-36.512	5.670	50.637	-44.967*	128608
1900s	baseline	13.224	51.844	-38.620	6.044	47.994	-41.950	114225
	word2vec	13.224	58.822	-45.598*	6.044	41.739	-35.695*	114225
	BERTje	13.224	43.596	-30.372	6.044	34.281	-28.237	114225
all	baseline	16.496	61.503	-44.772	6.176	61.710	-55.208	340654
	word2vec	16.496	59.955	-42.948	6.176	47.883	-41.023	340654
	BERTje	16.496	52.659	-35.821	6.176	44.520	-37.921	340654

Table 7: Performance on the complete OCR post-correction task by century

5 Discussion

5.1 Detection task

BERTje faced challenges with all types of special tokens. This seemed especially problematic when BERTje was applied to not the special tokens themselves per se, but sentences that contained those special tokens. This suggests BERTje might not have been fine-tuned sufficiently on historical data to accurately embed these tokens. Word2vec outperformed BERTje on the detection task involving special tokens in context words, indicating a potentially better alignment with such tokens. This might be explained by Word2vec’s ability to create word clusters based on semantic similarity and its static nature, which can result in more stable representations for certain contexts. However, a significant part could also be due to BERTje’s data-intensive nature, as it requires more data for effective training.

As noticed, all methods showed better detection rates on older documents compared to newer ones. While the baseline’s success can be explained by its historical dictionary, further explanations for the other models are explored in the following paragraphs.

5.2 Correction task

Word2vec’s strong performance on Real Word Error tokens challenges the notion that its dependency on lexical methods has to be detrimental. Regarding its performance on other special tokens, one possible explanation for the baseline’s lower accuracy could be its lack of a tie-breaking strategy for instances where multiple candidates share the same Levenshtein ratio. Given its extensive dictionary, such ties are frequent, and the baseline essentially makes a random selection from among these candidates. This highlights the significant advantage offered by word embeddings. It is worth noting that BERTje may perform marginally worse than word2vec due to its potentially lesser familiarity with the dataset at this stage.

As mentioned in the results, during the correction phase, just as during the detection phase, all methods exhibit reduced performance on modern data. For WEMs, there is an interesting explanation for this trend. While attempting to correct modern text, BERTje consistently suggests contemporary equivalents for historical spelling

variations. This issue may also contribute to the detection challenges, as historical spelling variants could potentially be interpreted as errors.

5.3 Complete OCR post-correction task

When considering the post-correction task in its entirety, it becomes clear from the results that this task is a very complex endeavor. This underscores the importance of analyzing the correction and detection tasks separately. Since accurate tokens and characters outnumber erroneous ones (as indicated by the Word Error Rate and Character Error Rate), there is a higher likelihood of a correct token being mistakenly identified as an error if a model is not adjusted for this bias. This introduces the risk of erroneously correcting tokens that are already accurate, thereby increasing the WER and CER. In contrast, erroneous tokens are less common, making the chance of correcting them relatively smaller.

A major challenge with all these methods, as evidenced by the increase in CER and WER rates, is their tendency to make inappropriate corrections. The models often misidentify correct tokens as errors and alter them unnecessarily, leading to a net increase in errors. However, this does not mean that OCR post-correction is an unpromising endeavor. During this research, several pitfalls, such as the data hungriness of BERTje, have been identified. By addressing these issues, conducting more experiments, and combining the strengths of various models, it is possible that better results could be achieved.

5.4 Limitations

Due to the computational constraints of this study, a smaller dataset was used. This resulted in less fine-tuning, a less representative performance, and reduced evaluation materials. BERT may require more extensive fine-tuning to reach peak performance on historical data.

There are some smaller limitations of this research in the analysis. One problem with the analysis of the performance of the detection task on special tokens, is that its design is more fit for the analysis on the correction task. It is mostly considered whether the ground truth token is a special token, such as an OOV word, to see how often these can be accurately corrected. This is however less relevant for the detection since the detection task its focus is on the OCR output. There are more analysis tasks that should get a more fitting and in-depth analysis, as this study was merely a broad overview of many aspects of OCR-post correction.

6 Conclusion and future work

BERTje appears to perform the least suboptimally in the overall OCR post-correction task. In the separate detection and correction tasks, the dictionary method and word2vec alternatively yield the best results. Assessing BERTje's performance in detecting and correcting special tokens or words within their context does not definitively resolve whether BERTje can overcome the limitations of word2vec. However, it also cannot be ruled out.

Nonetheless, it is valuable to adopt a more expansive perspective and concentrate on the overarching objective rather than delving into the detailed analyses. This principle is particularly relevant when considering the application of these methods to historical data. This project aims to extend beyond the methods themselves and their potential

contributions to enhancing the state of the art. It also addresses the types of historical documents that could benefit from these techniques. This was done by looking at special tokens and different centuries, for example.

Highlighting the differences between data from diverse time periods would be a great contribution. Additionally, exploring whether fine-tuning on these periods separately or on all periods combined yields better results would be interesting. Future research could examine the effect of varying amounts of fine-tuning of word2vec and BERT on both modern data and different centuries. This would help determine the impact on any bias towards modern language. In this sense, this study serves as an invitation to embrace the challenges presented in this domain, which is an interdisciplinary task. This project is also an invitation to engage in this challenge.

While this study provides valuable insights into the performance of BERTje and word2vec on OCR post-correction for historical documents, several limitations must be acknowledged. Firstly, the research faced computational constraints, which led to the use of a reduced dataset size. This limitation affected the extent of fine-tuning that could be performed on the models. Additionally, the study did not include GysBERT, a model specifically trained on historical data, during its initial phase. The absence of GysBERT potentially limited the accuracy of the results. Moreover, the training data used for the models might have introduced a bias towards modern language, which could affect the generalizability of the findings to historical texts.

Future research should address these limitations by utilizing larger and more diverse datasets. Incorporating advanced models such as GysBERT, which is specifically designed for historical data, could enhance OCR post-correction accuracy. Additionally, exploring the impact of varying levels of fine-tuning on both modern and historical data would provide deeper insights into the models' performance. Specifically, investigating how different fine-tuning strategies on data from various centuries influence the results could offer significant improvements.

Recent advancements in the field, such as the use of transformers by models like ChatGPT, should be explored for OCR post-correction. GysBERT, a historical adaptation of BERTje, represents a promising avenue for future research. Evaluating its performance against the models used in this study could help address some of the limitations identified when working with historical data. By focusing on these areas, future studies can contribute to the development of more effective methods for processing historical documents.

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7 Appendix

The code can be found at https://github.com/VantHof-Thesis/OCR-post-correction/tree/main/all_code.

7.1 BERTje specifics

BERTje specifics	
Optimizer:	Adam
Learning rate:	5e-5
Epochs:	4
Dropout:	0.1
Layers:	12 (BERT base)
Attention heads:	12 (BERT base)
Max_padding:	512 (BERT base)

7.2 Validation figures

Figure 11: Performance of correction methods on the validation set. This figure compares the effectiveness of different ranking methods used for selecting correction candidates, highlighting the best performing approach for both word2vec and BERTje

From London to Florence: Discovering Information Flow in Early Modern Europe with Bayesian Time-to-Event Analysis

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Amerigo Salvetti was the Florentine resident ambassador in London between 1618 and 1657. During his tenure, Salvetti sent weekly newsletters and dispatches to the Grand Ducal Court of the Medici in Florence. This paper studies a transcribed corpus of Salvetti’s news letters and dispatches. Specifically, the paper focuses on the geographical span of Salvetti news’ producing activity and proposes a novel technique to quantify information flow: Bayesian time-to-event analysis applied in biostatistics, reliability engineering, and volcanology. In this paper, the technique is used to investigate the time the Medici had to wait for Salvetti to send information related to different locations, countries, and continents; hence, the paper uses “waiting time” - in combination with Bayesian inference and the Poisson and Gamma probability distributions - as a proxy to quantify information flow. The paper sheds light on Salvetti’s information producing activity, as well as his catchment area and those parts of the world he was silent about; by situating its findings in the context of previous scholarship, it contributes to the understanding of early modern information culture and diplomacy, and to time series analysis in History and Digital Humanities.

Keywords: Early Modern History; Digital History; Historical Data Science; Bayesian Statistics; Information Culture; History of Diplomacy

1 Introduction: a 17th century newsagent and resident ambassador

Historical actors who are known by two different names are always of great interest. So is Amerigo Salvetti, also known as Alessandro Antelminelli (Miani, 1961; Villani, 2004). Salvetti, the main protagonist of this paper, was born in the Tuscan city, Lucca, in 1572. His life was full of adventures and unexpected twists. He was the son of a wealthy merchant, Bernardino di Baldassare Antelminelli. When Salvetti was in his early twenties, his father sent him to Antwerp for an apprenticeship. However, when he turned twenty-four, something unexpected happened. Salvetti’s father and brother

were arrested in Lucca. The economic fortune of the Antelminelli was in decline, and the older Antelminelli began to collaborate with the Medici of Florence to prepare a future Medicean takeover of Lucca. The takeover never happened and Salvetti's father and brother were executed for treason. This sealed the fate of the young Salvetti as well. Even though Salvetti did not participate in the plot, he was sentenced to death in absence, which was the beginning of his almost lifelong exile. The life of the young and exiled Salvetti was not easy. All the properties of his family were confiscated and he had to find a new home far away from the Italian peninsula. He reached London around 1597 where he later settled in 1607. Meanwhile, he extensively traveled in Europe and survived various assassination attempts by the Lucchese authorities. To hide his identity, in 1599 he gave up his birth name and assumed the new name, Amerigo Salvetti. In 1635 Salvetti married the daughter of an influential English aristocrat and had six children. Most probably, the Medici grand dukes, Cosimo II (1609 - 1621) and then Ferdinand II (1621 - 1670), never forgot the services of his father and Salvetti remained in their orbit throughout his entire life. In 1618 Cosimo II nominated him to be the Florentine resident ambassador in London, a duty he had until his death in 1657. Today, Salvetti is known as an important eyewitness of the English Civil War, which he chronicled in the diplomatic correspondence he sent from London to Florence.

In fact, Salvetti was not only a resident ambassador. He was also a newsagent who sent weekly newsletters and dispatches to Florence. In this paper, I will investigate what Salvetti produced as a newsagent and I will focus on the geographical span of the information he sent to the Medici in his diplomatic correspondence (the analysis of themes and discourse of Salvetti's news sheets are subjects of further studies). Specifically, the goal of my paper is to discover the intensity of information flow from various countries and continents, as realized in thousands of news reports sent by Salvetti to Florence. Since Digital History has no methodology available to analyze information flow in historical records, in this paper I will propose a statistical approach and demonstrate its use through the analysis of Salvetti's diplomatic correspondence. This will open new research directions and will have further implications for future research. In brief, throughout this paper, I will address three research questions:

- How intensive was the information flow from different countries and continents in the weekly diplomatic correspondence that Salvetti sent to Florence?
- What does the intensity of information flow suggest about the everyday information gathering activity of resident ambassadors of early modern Europe?
- More generally, what does the intensity of information flow say about the diplomatic culture and practice of the period?

By addressing these research questions and by proposing a novel quantitative method to analyze the information world underlying a diplomatic correspondence, I hope to contribute to a new and emerging branch of early modern Diplomatic History. While earlier scholarship mainly focused on foreign policy and international politics, a number of recent studies have approached the early modern history of diplomacy through the lenses of everyday processes and practices by diplomats (Carrió-Invernizzi, 2013; Watkins, 2008). I hope that the approach presented here will further this direction of research, particularly the effort of scholarship to understand the information-gathering activities of individual diplomats.

Following this introduction, I will first elaborate on the historical context of Salvetti's news-producing activities, discuss his diplomatic correspondence, and describe it as a

data set. Second, I will address the problem of analyzing information flow and present the methodology that I propose; the discussion in this section will remain accessible to those who have no background in statistics; a more complex and formalized description of the statistical models applied in this paper are in the Appendix10. I will also critically reflect on the statistical models that I apply to discover information flow in the Salvetti diplomatic correspondence; I will discuss its core assumptions, point out some of its shortcomings, and address its general use in historical scholarship. Third, I will present my findings and evaluate them in terms of three broader historical trends of the early modern period. In the Conclusion, I will reflect on how my findings further our understanding of early modern diplomatic practice.

In line with the core theme of this special issue of the DH Benelux, I will also reflect on how the transformation of one modality, diplomatic correspondence in textual data, into another modality, time series (i.e. chronologically ordered sequence of data points) representing time-to-event dynamics, can open new directions of research beyond early modern diplomatic history.

2 The historical context: information flow towards the Grand Ducal Court of the Medici

The Medici grand dukes had good reasons to have a resident ambassador in London and in other European urban centers. The Florence of the 16th and the 17th centuries was very different from the famous Renaissance city state in the 15th century (Cochrane, 2013). The Medici of the 15th century were expelled from Florence and their exile gave rise to a short republican government in 1527. However, in 1530, with the help of emperor Charles V (1519 - 1556), Pope Clement VII (1523 - 1534) restored the Medicean rule in Florence. This resulted in the establishment of a hereditary seigneurial system in a city with a rich republican tradition. The Medici became the de facto rulers of the Tuscan city-state (in the Quattrocento, they controlled Florence through an informal network without holding any major public office). With the new political system, Florence and her Medici leaders became less independent and gradually more reliant on the protection of the Emperor. At the same time, the Medici also tried to avoid becoming a vassal of the Emperor and to maintain the appearance of independence. They also sought to establish themselves as a legitimate and prestigious dynasty, an effort that culminated in 1569 with obtaining the title of grand duke from Pope Pius V (Diaz, 1976). All this was in parallel with a general economic, political, and social decline that characterized the Florence of the 16th and 17th century (Mazzei, 1987). Just like other Italian states, Florence had less and less influence in international politics, defined by long-standing conflicts between great European powers such as France, Spain, the Holy Roman Empire, and England. Despite their political and economic decline, Italian states desperately tried to remain active in European politics during the early modern period. To project more power than they had and to navigate through the international power games of the early modern period, Italian city states turned to diplomacy (Contini, 2000; de Vivo, 2007). They particularly relied on the institution of resident ambassador since permanent diplomatic representation in foreign courts implied legitimacy, prestige, and power. But resident ambassadors' role was not only symbolic; Salvetti and other resident ambassadors provided the state they represented with a constant flow of information. The office of the resident ambassador was, in the words of Alessandra Contini, a "vital 'workshop' of political information." (Contini, 2000, p. 50) By providing up-to-date information about the world, resident

ambassadors such as Salvetti helped sovereigns navigate through international politics and power games.

In addition to standard letters and dispatches, to convey information, Salvetti and other Florentine resident ambassadors relied on a very specific genre. They sent weekly or biweekly handwritten news sheets or “avvisi” in Italian. A news sheet is a set of consecutive and short (usually 8 - 10) paragraphs that describe news from different places; usually, each paragraph is dedicated to news from a different location (Pettegree, 2018). The difference between dispatches and avvisi in Salvetti’s diplomatic correspondence has been described by the Euronews Project that aims to create its new digital edition:

First there are diplomatic dispatches (in Salvetti’s diplomatic correspondence), sent weekly to the Secretary of State of the Grand Duke of Tuscany. Private and diplomatic topics are reported and discussed, such as issues involving ceremonials, commercial and legal affairs etc. The second type consists of the manuscript newsletters known in Italian as “avvisi”. Unlike the dispatches, avvisi have a purely informational function. Written in the third person and unsigned, they offer a broader view, addressing not only the world of the court but also English society of the time. (<https://www.euronewsproject.org/the-salvetti-project>, last accessed 15 February 2024)

Handwritten news sheets significantly contributed to the early modern information revolution; they are thought to have preceded and paved the way for printed newspapers, which they co-existed with until the 18th century (Infelise, 2002). It is important to note that avvisi had importance well beyond the world of diplomacy. Avvisi were part of the everyday life of those who could read and write in early modern Europe that witnessed the widespread circulation of these documents (Dooley, 2016; Droste and Salmi-Niklander, 2019). In short, formal and informal newsagents, such as for instance diplomats, ambassadors, postmasters, and spies, compiled handwritten news sheets in the large urban centers of early modern Europe and sent them to their ‘clients’ or ‘subscribers’ that included courts (such as for instance the Grand Ducal Court of the Medici), merchants (such as for instance the Fuggers in Augsburg), and aristocrats. In fact, Salvetti was also an information and news agent. Since some of his news sheets can today be found not only in Florentine but also other Italian collections, it is reasonable to assume that they had a wider circulation (Villani, 2004). Whether Salvetti’s news sheets were leaked or Salvetti himself sent them to courts other than the Medici is unknown. As an information agent, Salvetti gathered intelligence in London from a great variety of sources, such as handwritten news sheets by other diplomats, formal and informal contacts, and perhaps printed newspapers. Salvetti’s exact sources are unknown; what is, however, certain is that he had good connections with the English political and social elite, which definitely helped him produce his weekly news sheets.

3 Description of the data set: the Villani transcripts

Amerigo Salvetti was a very active news agent. He provided the Medici with all sorts of information arriving at London for almost forty years. Throughout these years he produced thousands of dispatches and news sheets. In fact, he had a reputation for being a particularly well-prepared diplomat with excellent writing skills. Parts of Salvetti’s

diplomatic production have been transcribed and prepared for a traditional printed edition by Professor Stefano Villani (Villani, 2004). Unfortunately, this edition has never been published. However, Professor Villani gave me access to his transcriptions, which are the base data underlying this paper (his transcriptions are also available in the MIA database of the Medici Archive Project, (<https://www.medi.org/access-mia/>, last accessed 15 February 2024)). Precisely, I was given a gigantic MS Word File containing more than a thousand documents (mainly news sheets and dispatches) and around 820,000 words. In this section, I am giving a short description of this data set (henceforth, Villani transcripts).

The Villani transcripts are a rich data set that is a unique access point to discover information flow in early modern Europe. It covers the period between December 1648 and 1660 June; it also includes documents compiled by Salvetti's son, who was the Florentine resident ambassador after the death of his father in 1657. However, this paper studies the diplomatic production of the older Salvetti only; the work of his son is the subject of future research. Hence, the period this paper investigates is between January 1649 and August 1657. Most of the original documents in the Villani transcripts are preserved in the Fondo Mediceo del Principato of the Florentine State Archive. Unlike previous selective editions of Salvetti's diplomatic production (Antelminelli, 1997; Manuscripts, 1887), the Villani transcripts are meant to be as complete as possible; supposedly, they include all surviving news sheets (or avviso as described above) and dispatches that Salvetti sent to the Medici Court in Florence between 1649 and 1657. As Figure 1 demonstrates, Salvetti sent a letter or dispatch with a news sheet attached every week - mostly on Friday - to Florence. In his news sheets he transmitted the most important pieces of information that reached London, as well as descriptions of events happening in the English capital. Both the dispatches and the news sheets are dated; Salvetti provided them with a header whereby he marked the location where they were produced (usually London). In this paper, I study Salvetti's dispatches and the news sheets together since they were parts of the same information-gathering activity, and, in reality, they complemented each other. The overall goal of my study is to explore the information flow as a whole, irrespective of the genre through which it was transmitted.

At the same time, there was an obstacle to realize a truly holistic approach. Even though the information flow between Salvetti and the Medici government in Florence must have been continuous, the Villani transcripts still contain some gaps. As Figure 2 demonstrates, the weekly number of documents in the Villani transcripts varies. On average, there are two documents per week; there are, however, some weeks from which the Villani transcripts do not contain any document. Most probably, these gaps are due to archival loss. As I will shortly explain, missing records in the dataset required the application of a specific statistical tool, named Bayesian estimation or Bayesian inference.

In short, even though the data set I worked with does not cover the entire life of Salvetti and features some lacunas, it still offers outstanding insights into his work as an information agent.

4 The research problem and the methodology: measuring the intensity of information flow by focusing on the waiting time

A key strength of the Villani transcripts is the place and name index that accompanies them. In practice, professor Villani created an inventory of names and places, and

Figure 1: Total number of documents that Salvetti sent on different days of the week between January 1649 and August 1657

Figure 2: Number of documents in the Villani transcripts that Salvetti sent each week to Florence between January 1649 and August 1657

Figure 3: Overview of the geographical span of the news that Salvetti sent from London to Florence between January 1649 and August 1657

Figure 4: News from Paris in the Salvetti newsletters between January 1649 and August 1657; A is a timeline and it shows those points in time when Salvetti sent news related to Paris; B shows the frequency counts for the waiting period (in days) preceding the arrival of each newsletter

cross-referenced the entries with single documents in his transcriptions. This is a particularly valuable resource since place names occur normalized without orthographical variations (as in the original documents by Salvetti himself). Furthermore, the place name index enables us to reconstruct the geographical span of the information Salvetti sent to Florence (see Figure 3). However, neither the place name index nor the map on Figure 3) gives insight into the intensity of information flow from different locations.

To study the importance of different places in handwritten news corpora, previous scholarship drew on count and relative frequency. For instance, Nikolaus Schobesberger investigated a corpus of newsletters that reached the Fuggers between 1568 and 1605. He inferred the importance of each source location in the corpus by counting the number of news sheets that mention them; next, he calculated the relative frequency, i.e. the percentage of total newsheets that mention a given location (Schobesberger, 2016). Even though this offers a basic insight into the importance of a given place, it does not uncover the intensity of information flow from that place. The following illustrative example sheds light on the problem. You have two friends, Jenny and Johnny. With Johnny you exchange a message once a month; with Jenny, you exchange twelve messages but only once per year. The number of messages (or the count) you exchange with Jenny and Johnny per year is equal. However, intuitively, we feel that the relationships with the two friends are of different nature; they involve different degrees of periodicity and therefore intensity, which count as a metric cannot express. Similarly, by just counting the number of news sheets that mention a given location in a news sheet corpus, we would overlook periodicity, which is an essential component of the intensity of information flow from that given location.

In fact, to uncover the intensity of information flow from a given location, we also need to take into account the usual length of time that elapses between news from

that location. This would reveal how much time the Medici in Florence usually had to wait to hear news about a place from Salvetti. The intensity of information flow from a location and the usual waiting time to hear news from that location were actually interrelated; the more intense the information flow was, the shorter the waiting time was. Therefore, I propose to shift the focus from the count of news that arrived from a place to the expected or average waiting time for news from a place.

To recover the expected waiting time, I have combined Villani's place name index with his transcripts and represented the result through time series. I am explaining this procedure through the example of Paris. As a first step, by drawing on the place name index, I extracted the list of all documents that mention Paris in the Villani transcripts. Next, by using the compilation date of each document, I reconstructed those points in time when Salvetti forwarded information related to Paris (I assume that the mentioning of Paris in a document implied that some kind of information related to Paris was transmitted to Florence by Salvetti). As a result, I had a time series with points in time when information related to Paris was forwarded to Florence (see Figure 4 A). Finally, I calculated the lengths of time that elapse between these points of time; Figure 4 B summarizes all possible lengths of time, including their respective counts, between moments when Salvetti sent information related to Paris. I repeated this procedure with each location, country, and continent (I grouped locations in terms of their respective countries and continents, or sometimes the larger geographical region in which they were, see the example of Italy below), which uncovered the set of possible waiting times to hear news from there.

However, Figure 4 highlights a fundamental problem. Salvetti forwarded news from Paris periodically but this periodicity featured irregularity. The length of time the Medici had to wait for Salvetti to send news related to Paris is sometimes 2 weeks; sometimes it is 5 weeks, and so on (see Figure 4 B). How can we then infer the usual (or the expected) waiting time for news from Paris if the waiting times we observe in the Villani transcripts vary and feature irregularity? Interestingly, a similar problem arises in both natural sciences and engineering. For instance, volcanoes erupt periodically, but this periodicity is also somewhat irregular; the length of time that elapses between two eruptions may vary (De la Cruz-Reyna, 1991). In other words, the waiting time for an eruption is sometimes 2 months; sometimes it is 2 weeks, and so on. Similarly, engine parts fail periodically but the waiting time for the next failure is uncertain (Meeker et al., 2021). There is a specific branch of statistics, called time-to-event analysis, that offers a quantitative framework to study the repeated but random occurrences of an event (Denfeld et al., 2023).

In this context, randomness means that the exact waiting time for an event to occur is unknown and the empirical data we have involves some degree of uncertainty and variation. Note that neither the variation nor the resulting uncertainty are necessarily due to true randomness; they are due to factors that are unknown to us, to the observers who have an incomplete knowledge. Hence, we represent the set of all possible waiting times with a specific type of random variable that is provided by time-to-event analysis (see the technical specification in the Implementation section 10). This in turn enables us to address the following questions:

- Given some observations of the same event reoccurring at variable intervals (for instance, eruptions of a volcano, failure of an engine part, Salvetti forwarding news related to Paris), how long is the expected or the usual waiting time for the event to occur again?

- On average, how many events occur in a unit of time (i.e. per week, day, etc)?
- How long is the waiting time for the event to occur with 50% probability?
- How long is the waiting time for multiple events (for instance, the time until Salvetti sent five pieces of news related to Paris) to occur with 100% probability?

To summarize, with time-to-event analysis one can study periodicity that features irregularity. The focus of this branch of statistics is not the number of times a given event occurs but the amount of time (aka waiting time) between individual occurrences of the same event. The strength of time-to-event statistics is that it effectively connects the waiting time for an event to occur with probability (see for instance Figure 6).

In the context of this research, I used time-to-event analysis to infer the following pieces of information. First, I calculated (technically speaking, estimated) the average weekly number of news (referred as λ or rate of arrival of news on Figure 5 7 9; also discussed as β in the Appendix) related to a given location that the Medici received from Salvetti. Second, I calculated the expected waiting time for one piece of news from a given location. Note that the expected waiting time for one piece of news and the average weekly number of news are the inverse of each other (see further explanation in the Appendix). Again, I assumed that the shorter the waiting time, the more intense was the information flow from a place. Third, I modeled the probability that the Medici received ten pieces of news related to a given location from Salvetti in the function of the waiting time for these ten pieces of news to reach Florence (see, for instance, Figure 6). Finally, I compared the information flow from different places by comparing the results related to different locations. The two statistical models, the Poisson distribution and the Gamma distribution, used for these calculations are presented in the Appendix.

At the same time, we cannot forget about a key feature of the Villani transcripts: incompleteness. Again, the example of Paris can highlight this feature. It is possible that those news sheets that got lost and are not present in the Villani transcripts do mention news from Paris; hence, when calculating the average waiting time for news from Paris, we risk overlooking these missing records. To cope with incompleteness, I relied on a specific statistical approach, called Bayesian estimation (Nyberg, 2018). In simple words and without explaining technicalities, given an incomplete set of observations of an event occurring repeatedly but randomly over time, with the help of this statistical method, we can estimate the number of events happening in a unit of time (λ , or weekly rate of news related to a given location sent by Salvetti to the Medici in Florence). An estimate gives an overview of all possible λ values, including the most likely one, the mean (see for instance Figure 5). Once the most likely λ is available, we can also calculate the most likely waiting time for one or more news. Again, the detailed mathematical procedure of Bayesian estimation applied here is explained in the Appendix.

As a whole, to gauge the importance of source locations in a news corpus and to calculate the intensity of information flow from them, I am proposing to focus on the usual or expected waiting time for news from these sources. In the next section, I am presenting the insights that this approach brought about. However, the statistical models (Poisson distribution and Gamma distribution explained in the Appendix) applied here have three key shortcomings to be addressed in future research.

First, the models I worked with assume that the events occurring repeatedly but randomly are independent from each other. Again, this assumption can be explained with the example of Paris. According to the assumption of independence, the fact that

Salvetti forwarded news related to Paris at moment t_2 is independent of the fact that he had also forwarded news earlier, for instance at moment t_1 . To summarize, I made the following assumptions:

- In moment t_2 Salvetti looked at news and information available from different places
- He selected the ones that were relevant for the Medici at that moment
- His selection at t_2 was independent from his selection at t_1 ; he did not select news from certain places at t_2 because news from these places had already been selected at t_1 .

To which extent are these assumptions correct? It is unfortunately impossible to answer. Today, we do not have enough information about the editorial activity of diplomats who compiled news. However, it is true that in history repeated events are often not independent from each other. Hence, further historical research aiming to exploit time-to-event dynamics in historical documents, would also need statistical models that can be extended to sequences of not only independent but also dependent events.

Second, the statistical models in this paper are based on another key assumption: during the period studied the rate by which pieces of news related to a given location occur in the Salvetti diplomatic correspondence did not undergo significant changes. Given that the period is relatively short, it is reasonable to suppose that there was a central tendency (or a firm value) which the rate gravitated towards. This firm value is obtained by means of the Bayesian estimation, i.e. by calculating the expected rate (or the mean rate) given the observations we have about a place in the period (see the Implementation section of the Appendix 10). However, historians often study longer periods and they also need to observe shifts in the rate by which repeated events occurred. Elaboration of models that can uncover shifts and changes is another future direction for scholarship aiming to discover time-to-event dynamics in historical sources and generally in the past.

Third, the statistical model used in this paper treats different geographical areas independently from each other. In reality, there could have been connections between news from different regions and cities. For instance, news from the Netherlands might have implied news from Brussels as well. These hidden interconnections might have also influenced the waiting time for news from different locations. Since this paper aims to develop only the very first steps towards the application of time-to-event analysis in the study of historical information flow, the problem of interconnectedness remains to be resolved in future research.

5 Results: the focused intelligence gathering by Salvetti

Introduction

The early modern period witnessed a number of political and economic developments that contributed to the formation of a new world order. In this section, I present my major findings and I evaluate them in light of three key developments that characterized the early modern period.

Figure 5: Estimation of the average number (λ) of international (A) and local English (B) news that Salvetti sent from London to Florence each week

Figure 6: Modeling the probability that the Medici received ten pieces of international (A) and local English (B) news in the function of the waiting time until these ten pieces of news arrived

Figure 7: Estimation of the average number (λ) of news related to different countries that Salvetti sent from London to Florence each week

Figure 8: Modeling the probability that the Medici received ten pieces of news related to different countries in the function of the waiting time until these ten pieces of news arrived

Figure 9: Estimation of the average number (λ) of European (A) and not European (B) news that Salvetti sent from London to Florence each week

Figure 10: Modeling the probability that the Medici received ten pieces of news related to Europe and to the world outside Europe in the function of the waiting time until these ten pieces of news arrived

Balance of power

Throughout the early modern period a novel system of international relations was born. The cornerstone of this new system was the principle of balance of power (Little, 2007). In short, European states actively sought to maintain an international political and power setting that did not let any state become more powerful than the others. However, the principle of balance of power presented a key challenge to those who were involved in the day-to-day running of governments. Brendan Simms gave a succinct description of the problem: “Either way, the functioning of the balance of power was neither mechanical nor automatic. It required human recognition and agency. Its price was eternal vigilance” (Simms, 2015, p. 654). In other words, to be successful in the system of international relations marked by the principle of balance of power, governments had to constantly monitor the development of international politics.

As the information flow in Salvetti’s diplomatic correspondence demonstrates, the foot soldiers of this monitoring activity were diplomats and resident ambassadors. Salvetti was eager to keep the Medici in Florence up-to-date about the developments of international affairs. I found that on average he included information related to six international (i.e. non English) geographical locations in his weekly correspondence (see Figure 5). As a result, the Medici in Florence certainly received information related to ten international locations within just two weeks (see Figure 6). However, my findings suggest that Salvetti was quite focused and he usually sent information related to specific countries and geographical areas (see Figure 7 and 8). In other words, he was in charge of providing information from these locations. The countries he covered were France, Netherlands, Ireland (I treated Ireland as a country separate from England, though in the 17th century it was already part of the British Empire), and to a lesser extent Spain. My findings suggest that on average he included one piece of information related to these countries in his weekly documents sent to Florence. This means that the information flow from the countries he was in charge of was constant and the amount of available information was steadily accumulating in the Medici court. As Figure 8 shows, within about four months the Medici certainly heard about the countries Salvetti was in charge at least ten times. By contrast, he was relatively silent about other European countries. For instance, the waiting time until the Medici heard about the Holy Roman Empire from Salvetti was significantly longer than the countries he was focused on. Does his silence about countries out of his area of focus imply that information about these other countries was not available in London? Or does it mean that he intentionally neglected them? It is a question I will address in the Conclusions section.

What is plausible is that Salvetti’s focus on certain areas was not a unique feature of his information-gathering and forwarding activity. Florentine resident ambassadors in other countries must have had their own areas of focus about which they extensively reported. As a result, the Medici officials in Florence were provided with a steady stream of information about international affairs, which came from different diplomats and resident ambassadors, that is to say, through different channels. Most importantly, focused information arriving through different channels complemented each other, which enabled the Medici to navigate in an increasingly complex international environment marked by a fragile balance of power.

The principle of balance of power was present not only in international politics but also locally on the Italian peninsula. Actually, scholarship (Frigo, 2000) has long

maintained that this principle started to take shape there following the peace of Lodi (1454) and later the Peace of Cateau-Cambrésis (1559). The Italian balance of power did not, however, thwart certain states from attempting to achieve a leadership role on the peninsula. This was in fact a key element of the Medici's foreign policy, specifically of Ferdinand II, whom Salvetti represented in London (Diaz, 1976, p. 376). It is therefore not surprising that Salvetti actively monitored information related to the Italian peninsula and forwarded it to Florence. In his correspondence, we can see a particularly intensive flow of information related to Italy. Yet, as Figure 7 and 8 show, Salvetti sent more information related to different geographical locations in the Italian peninsula than in other countries, except England, which I am shortly discussing. Most probably, Italian news that Salvetti sent from London to Florence were secondary compared to the ones that directly arrived from sources in other Italian states. However, news by Salvetti must have helped the Medici officials to assess information already available from local sources residing in other Italian cities.

Finally, it is important to note another challenge related to the balance of power system in early modern Europe. This is the fragile nature of this system, which again increased the importance of information gathering activity of diplomats and resident ambassadors. European states constantly faced the prospect of foreign intervention; in early modern Europe, territorial sovereignty was respected only to a limited degree and the danger of foreign intervention into local affairs was always on the table. Examples of foreign interventions throughout the period are numerous. For instance, the French intervened into the internal affairs of the Habsburgs by supporting Hungarian rebels at the beginning of the 17th century. Earlier, in the 16th century France also intervened into local affairs in Florence by supporting Florentine exiles living in Paris. What European states could do to prevent the intervention of other states into their domestic affairs was remaining vigilant and collecting intelligence through informants and diplomats such as Salvetti.

Revolutionary forces

The stability of early modern Europe was on the one hand assured by the system of balance of power. On the other hand, this stability was often challenged by revolutionary forces that aimed to change the established status quo. The English Civil War (1642 - 1651), which brought about the execution of a sovereign, was one of the most important revolutions in the history of early modern Europe. It was an event that shocked the European ruling elite. It must have been particularly shocking for the Medici, a family that had witnessed a number of revolutionary movements throughout its history: the Ciompi in the 14th century; Savonarola and his movement in the 15th century; the short Republican government of Florence at the beginning of the 16th century. In light of this, it is not surprising that the Medici in Florence were eager to follow the events in England during the Civil War and afterwards; it was an event that posed a serious risk to the European status quo, and subsequently to the balance of power.

The Medici's very active interest in events unfolding following the Civil War is unsurprising; their interest is apparent when we look at the intensity of information flow related to England in Salvetti's diplomatic correspondence. As the comparison of waiting times for news from different countries on Figure 8 demonstrates, the shortest waiting time for news was from England. Furthermore, the city about which Salvetti sent most of the information was London and he also extensively covered events

unfolding in the English countryside. Overall, the dominance of England in Salvetti's news indicates the Medici's interest in the revolution that took place in the country.

At the same time, the dominance of information about England in Salvetti's diplomatic correspondence is surprising in light of findings by previous scholarship. To which extent the early modern news market covered international and local news is a theme that has been often discussed by previous scholarship. For instance, Andrew Pettegree has argued that "most newspapers devoted eighty percent or more of their space to foreign dispatches. Coverage of events nearer home seldom extended beyond the relatively safe terrain of ships safely arriving in port or the movements of the Prince" (Pettegree, 2018, p. 372). Similarly, Heiko Droste has argued that early modern handwritten news had mainly addressed information related to international affairs (Droste, 2021). As Pettegree points out, conveying local news was politically dangerous since it could easily catch the attention of local censors. Salvetti and his news coverage do not fit into this picture. He was actually very much involved in local affairs, perhaps as much as in international affairs.

Colonization

Perhaps the most important development of the early modern period was the colonization of the world outside Europe. By the time Salvetti started to send his weekly correspondence to Florence, the expansion of Europe towards the Americas had definitely gained momentum. Even though neither Salvetti in London nor the Medici in Florence were directly involved in colonization, they must have experienced its impact through a myriad of different ways. First, ships from the overseas territories of European empires carrying exotic products such as coffee and tobacco frequently arrived at the ports of Europe; these exotic products then made their way to the households of the European elite, such as, for instance, the Medici or even Salvetti. Second, overseas territories became the flashpoints of power struggles between European countries. The Medici and Salvetti must have been aware of this since news from overseas territories often occurred in printed journals. Third, thanks to improving maritime technologies and the subsequent transformation of exploration into a professional and scientific activity in the 17th century, there was a constant expansion of trade routes during the lifetime of Salvetti. All this gave rise to a novel global economy and continually increased the importance of the world outside Europe.

Despite the increasing importance of overseas territories, Salvetti remained relatively silent about the world beyond Europe. I compared the amount of time the Medici had to wait for Salvetti to send news about Europe (England excluded) and the world beyond Europe. As Figure 10 demonstrates, Salvetti very rarely sent news related to locations in the Americas, Asia, and Africa. His silence is intriguing because there was certainly information available in early modern London. For instance, as said above, contemporary printed journals do discuss news related to overseas territories; furthermore, events happening in the colonies must have been present in the everyday talks of Londoners. What explains then the silence of Salvetti? This is a question that I will address in the conclusion.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, I adopted a quantitative approach, time-to-event analysis, from natural sciences and engineering. I applied this approach to analyze the information flow in

the diplomatic correspondence that Amerigo Salvetti sent from London to Florence in the 17th century. Time-to-event analysis enabled me to calculate the usual length of time the Medici in Florence had to wait until Salvetti sent them news related to different locations, countries, and continents, which in turn gave insights into the information flow from these places. The application of time-to-event analysis revealed that Salvetti was quite selective and his information gathering activity was focused on certain countries and geographical locations. Even though Salvetti was only one of the many resident ambassadors in the early modern period, I believe that these features of his information gathering activity might be revealing about the operation of early modern diplomacy in general.

Previous scholarship has suggested that throughout the early modern period diplomats, such as for instance resident ambassadors, became increasingly more specialized (Jörg and Jucker, 2010). This meant that they had a well-defined 'catchment area' about which they were meant to collect information. My analysis of Salvetti's diplomatic correspondence confirms this hypothesis. As pointed out above, Salvetti was mainly but not exclusively in charge of collecting intelligence from the so-called Atlantic empires, which formed his catchment area; one of his tasks was to provide a steady stream of information about the countries in his catchment area. There are good reasons to believe that news from countries out of his catchment area were also available in London, which was an important information hub of the time. However, as my findings show, Salvetti must have ignored these news and rather focused on information coming from his own area of expertise. Regional specialization by Salvetti and presumably by other diplomats of his time points towards another broader trend. This is the gradual professionalization of diplomatic activity in early modern Europe (Sowerby and Hennings, 2017). For instance, in Florence a system of "career diplomats" developed and gave rise to a highly efficient and professional foreign service (Diaz, 1976). Both the regional specialization and the professionalization of diplomatic activity indicate that the information gathering activity by Salvetti and by other resident ambassadors was not at all an ad hoc operation; yet, it followed some predefined patterns. All this raises the question of who defined these predefined patterns, as well as the catchment area of a resident ambassador.

Scholarship has suggested that in early modern states foreign affairs were managed directly by the sovereign (Frigo, 2000). So was in Florence where diplomats were often provided with written instructions of what they were expected to achieve throughout their missions (in the case of Salvetti, written instructions are not available). Hence, ambassadors' territorial specialization and their intelligence-gathering activity reflect the interest of the sovereign they represented; they also show the types of information that were relevant to running foreign affairs. In this regard, Salvetti's silence about the world outside Europe is striking. Was Ferdinand II disinterested in it? Alternatively, did he receive information about the Americas through other channels? In this paper, I cannot offer definitive answers. However, I believe that the world outside Europe was less relevant for the day-to-day running of the Florentine government; Salvetti thus prioritized those countries that were particularly important for the Medici. We cannot forget that the genre of news sheets or *avviso* put some practical limitations on the amount of information that could be transmitted. To put it simply, a news sheet could not be infinitely long and a resident ambassador was expected to be pragmatic and selective. I also believe that the pragmatism expected from diplomats might reflect the way foreign affairs were generally managed in the early modern period. As it has been argued, the development of diplomacy throughout the early

modern period largely contributed to the formation of the modern state that relied on an effective and increasingly more pragmatic bureaucratic apparatus (Mattingly, 2010). This also brought about an institutional culture that hallmarked the *modus operandi* of diplomats, including their everyday information-gathering and processing activity. Hence, resident ambassadors' intelligence-gathering activity reflected not only the interest of the sovereign they represented but also the institutional culture that underlied foreign affairs in the early modern period. To summarize, by analyzing the information flow in Amerigo Salvetti's diplomatic correspondence, this paper has identified two key components of early modern diplomatic practice: pragmatism and territorial specialization.

In this paper, I have presented how a modality, 'time series representing time-to-event dynamics', that had so-far received little attention from historians, can produce fresh insights and confirm existing hypotheses in early modern diplomatic history. Even though this modality has remained relatively unexplored by historians, it is actually ubiquitous in the study of the past. For instance, historians have long been interested in the time until people got married in different historical periods; similarly, there has been interest in the time until one decides to emigrate from her or his country. As the different figures in this paper show, the statistically rigorous investigation of waiting times for events to realize can on the one hand give rise to novel comparative approaches in history. On the other, it can help cope with the randomness of repeated historical events unfolding over time. The figures in this paper demonstrate how waiting times for single or multiple events can be mapped to probabilities, which is an important means to unlock the randomness of these events. At the same time, the modality of time series representing time-to-event dynamics still needs further refinements so that it can be fully applied for historical research.

7 Acknowledgements

I am most thankful to Brendan Dooley and Stefano Villani for giving access to the dataset underlying this work and for giving me advice on how to proceed with this paper. I am also grateful to Wouter Kreuze for providing me with an initial version of the script that I used to process the dataset. Finally, I am thankful to the Center for Contemporary and Digital History (CO²DH) at the University of Luxembourg for supporting this project.

8 Data Availability

Most of Salvetti's transcribed news sheets and diplomatic correspondence are available in the MIA Database of the Medici Archive Project (<https://www.medici.org/access-mia/>, last accessed 15 February 2024). The base data underlying this project is currently not shareable.

9 Softwares Used

This research used Python programming language to accomplish the data processing and analysis. Specifically, it drew on the following Python libraries: Scipy, Numpy, PYMC3, and Pandas. The publication of the research code is being planned.

10 Appendix - Implementation

I am here giving a technical description of the statistical approaches I applied in this paper. This section requires a good command of statistics and probability theory, as well as an understanding of Bayesian inference and estimation (Burr, 2004). Explanation of specific technical terms and statistical concepts used in this section is beyond the scope of this paper.

Let the occurrences of news related to a given location in the Salvetti diplomatic correspondence be represented by the discrete time series X with week as unit of time. Hence, X includes the consecutive steps of the time series, as well as the count of events (e.g. number of times (x) a location is mentioned) at each step. Finally, let N be the total number of steps in the discrete time series:

$$X = \{x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_N\} \quad (1)$$

Next, let's suppose that the unfolding of events over time (e.g. mentioning of a given location in the Salvetti diplomatic correspondence), represented by the time series X , follows a Poisson distribution (Haight, 1967), see Equation (2). This implies that a location occurred in the Salvetti diplomatic correspondence at a constant rate but at random. The Poisson distribution is parameterized with lambda (λ), which stands for the rate of events per unit of time. In our case, lambda is the average weekly number of times the location is mentioned:

$$X \sim \text{Poisson}(\lambda) \quad (2)$$

Furthermore, theta (θ), also known as the scale parameter, stands for the average waiting time for an event to occur, as follows:

$$\theta = \frac{1}{\lambda} \quad (3)$$

In case the data is complete and there are no unobserved events, the rate parameter can be obtained by calculating the arithmetic mean:

$$\lambda = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + \dots + x_N}{N} \quad (4)$$

However, the dataset I worked with was incomplete; as explained above, there are good reasons to believe that some documents sent by Salvetti from London to Florence got lost and are absent from the Villani transcripts. To infer λ , the technique of Bayesian estimation was therefore applied (Miller, 1980). Within the Poisson distribution framework, the goal of the Bayesian estimation is to find all possible values for λ (including the most likely one) and their respective probabilities (p) given an incomplete set of observations:

$$p(\lambda|X) \quad (5)$$

This can be resolved with the process of Bayesian update (Garcia Trillos and Sanz-Alonso, 2020). As a first step, we can assume that λ was one, e.g. the location was, on average, mentioned once a week, which will be our prior. Given that the conjugate prior of the Poisson distribution is the Gamma distribution (Dubey, 1970), we can use it to express the prior as follows:

$$\text{Gamma}(\alpha, \beta) \sim \text{Gamma}(1, 1) \quad (6)$$

where α represents the number of events for which the waiting time is modeled and β , the scale parameter, is the inverse of the average number of events occurring in a unit of time λ .

Next, by using the Bayesian formula, we update the prior in light of the observation we have, which will in turn give a posterior distribution rendering all possible values of λ .

$$p(\lambda|X) = p(X|\lambda)p(\lambda) \quad (7)$$

The derived equations for Equation (7) are described in detail in Gelman et al. (2013). The simplified formula used in this paper is as follows:

$$p(\lambda|X) = \text{Gamma}(\sum X_N + \alpha, N + \beta) \quad (8)$$

Figure 5, 7, and 9 show the results of this calculation process with different locations, e.g. the posterior distributions of λ related to different locations.

The posterior mean (e.g. the most likely λ given the incomplete observations X we have) is calculated as follows:

$$\hat{\lambda} = \frac{\sum x_N + \alpha}{N + \beta} \quad (9)$$

Once the inferred λ is available, we can calculate the probability of receiving multiple news in the function of the waiting time.

For this process, I again use the Gamma distribution since it is a continuous distribution and it can model the waiting time until multiple events occur (Dubey, 1970). To model the probability of a location occurring multiple number of times in the Salvetti diplomatic correspondence in the function of the waiting time, the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the Gamma distribution (which is represented by the function F below) is used (Dubey, 1970):

$$F(x) = \frac{\gamma(\alpha, \beta x)}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \quad (10)$$

where $\Gamma(\alpha)$ stands for the Gamma function and $\gamma(\alpha, \beta x)$ is the lower incomplete Gamma function. Figure 6, 8, and 10 are based on the Gamma CDF with mean λ (i.e. inverse of β), calculated with Bayesian estimation as demonstrated in equation 9, and with $\alpha = 10$.

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Immersive 3D Visualizations of Early-Twentieth-Century Home Cinema

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This article draws on recent developments in both the cultural heritage field and the scholarly domain to reflect on the potential of 3D digitization for documenting, contextualizing, and presenting cultural heritage objects and knowledge about them. It addresses the role 3D technologies can play in the virtual reconstruction of cultural heritage objects so that the objects’ material characteristics and usages become part of the virtual and immersive user experiences. It focuses on the development of a 3D real-time application and virtual environment that recreates two early-twentieth-century home cinema technologies: a Kinora motion picture viewer (ca. 1907) and a Pathé Baby 9.5mm film projector (ca. 1924). The objective of the application, called Virtual Viewing Experiences (VVE), was not only to represent these two media historical objects digitally and convey historical information about them, but also to provide an interactive and immersive “hands-on” yet virtual user experience. Using computer-based 3D visualization, the application depicts the materiality and functionality of the two historical home cinema devices, allowing the user to “view” a Kinora reel on the Kinora viewer and to “project” a 9.5mm film using the Pathé Baby projector. Documenting the application development process – from the digitization of cultural heritage objects to their digital recreation and presentation in a virtual environment with simulated functionality – the article reflects on the process of making the 3D application. It explores how 3D technologies and immersive virtual environments can play an important role not only in preserving media heritage objects in digital form, but also in “re-animating” them through user interaction and digital storytelling to disseminate knowledge about their histories of use.¹

Keywords: 3D, immersion, digital storytelling, cultural heritage, media history, digital materiality, user experience, media historical collections, Kinora, Pathé Baby

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¹ The Virtual Viewing Experiences project was a project by Tim van der Heijden and Theodoros Georgiakakis, developed within the framework of Theodoros Georgiakakis’ research internship at the Open University of the Netherlands in collaboration with Maastricht University. It was conducted to support the project CRAFTED: Enrich and promote traditional and contemporary crafts, co-financed by the Connecting Europe Facility of the European Commission (Europeana, 2021).

1 Introduction

Digital technologies are rapidly transforming the cultural heritage field, ranging from massive digitization and enrichment processes to the rise of online digital heritage platforms, virtual museums and tours. Museums, archives, libraries, and other cultural heritage institutions increasingly invest in enhancing visitor experiences by implementing interactive, participatory scenarios and digital storytelling, particularly in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic. XR and 3D technologies have been used to engage visitors with cultural heritage objects and collections in interactive and multi-sensory ways. In doing so, the cultural heritage field is dealing with “digital artefacts” (de Almeida et al., 2018, p.10), which in the case of 3D may be either digitized objects, synthesized based on photographs using Photogrammetry (Guery et al., 2018), or complete virtual reconstructions of cultural objects with an aim for accuracy and fidelity (Pavlidis et al., 2007). The emergence of 3D technologies and digital artifacts has not only transformed the field of cultural heritage, but also shaped new research practices. They led, for instance, to the creation of new digital knowledge platforms, such as 3D Digital Scholarly Editions (DSEs). Aimed to better communicate the process and outcomes of 3D scholarship, DSEs open up new possibilities for digital scholarship due to their enhanced annotation capabilities, in addition to text, including “audio, video, images, and data linked from other sources” (Papadopoulos and Schreibman, 2019). One of the main innovative aspects DSEs can offer is to make the “textual” information co-exist and remain linked with its “contextual” data, all under the same platform (Schreibman and Papadopoulos, 2019, p.222).²

This article draws on these recent developments in both the cultural heritage field and the scholarly domain to reflect on the potential of 3D digitization for documenting, contextualizing, and presenting cultural heritage objects and knowledge about them. It addresses the role 3D technologies can play in the virtual reconstruction of cultural heritage objects so that the objects’ material characteristics and (historical) usages become part of the virtual and immersive user experiences. As a case study, it focuses on the development of a 3D real-time application and virtual environment that recreates two early-twentieth-century home cinema technologies: a Kinora viewer (ca. 1907) and a Pathé Baby 9.5mm film projector (ca. 1924). (Figure 1) These media historical devices represent two different constellations – or “*dispositifs*”³ – of watching moving images at home in the early twentieth century. The Kinora was initially designed as an individual *viewing* apparatus, limiting the moving image experience to a single viewer, while the Pathé Baby film projector was primarily designed as a domestic *screening* device, enabling the projection of moving images on a screen for multiple viewers. These devices thus constitute different user experiences with home cinema as an emerging practice in the early twentieth century (van der Heijden, 2024). One of the project’s objectives was to explore how to recreate those user experiences in the digital domain.

² For various examples of 3D digital scholarly editions, visit the PURE3D platform, an infrastructure for publishing and preserving 3D scholarship: <https://pure3d.eu/>. In developing the Virtual Viewing Experiences application described in this article, we were inspired by these developments to create a standalone project with some presentational or methodological similarities to DSEs.

³ The term *dispositif* refers to a concept from film studies developed in Jean-Louis Baudry’s “apparatus theory” (Baudry, 1978). The concept considers both the material and spatial dimensions of the cinematic experience. See van der Heijden (2018) for an application of the *dispositif*-concept to the historical study of home movies as twentieth-century family memory practices.

Figure 1: A Kinora viewer with reel (left) and hand-cranked Pathé Baby 9.5mm film projector (right).
Courtesy of C2DH / University of Luxembourg.

The Kinora viewer and Pathé Baby 9.5mm film projector were digitized as part of the CRAFTED project (Europeana, 2021) and subsequently displayed on the Europeana online platform of digital cultural heritage.⁴ Linaza et al. (2014) refer to Europeana as an “outstanding example” of an online platform that aggregates and makes available “large amounts of annotated multimedia cultural data” (p.104). However, they also highlight a significant gap. Despite the vast amount of digital information about cultural heritage objects available on Europeana, the content is neither reused nor contextualized as part of a vivid and interactive user experience. As a result, they argue: “there is an urgent need to turn this content into a valuable and coherent experience for users” (p.104).

By developing an immersive 3D application, we aimed to investigate this potential for creating user experiences based on digitized cultural heritage objects and reflect on the methodological challenges that this presents. As digital artifacts, the 3D representations of the Kinora viewer and Pathé Baby projector are naturally isolated from their original materiality and historical contexts of use. The application aimed to restore some of these material and immaterial qualities, thereby reconstructing and disseminating knowledge about the objects’ histories of use. Consequently, a key objective of the project was to contribute to the question of how 3D technologies can be used to preserve and present both “tangible” and “intangible” forms of cultural heritage (UNESCO, 2023):

How can historical media technologies and hands-on user practices be simulated in a virtual environment using 3D representations of cultural heritage objects so that the material characteristics of these objects and their (historical) usages become part of the virtual and immersive user experience?

⁴ <https://www.europeana.eu/>.

In exploring this research question, we aimed to address issues of digital materiality, immersion, and user experience in the presentation of cultural heritage objects. Our immersive 3D application, from now on called the Virtual Viewing Experiences (VVE) application, aimed to recreate the aforementioned media historical objects in 3D as accurately as possible in terms of their materiality, functionality, and historical usages. These characteristics were interactively presented to the user via prompts for input. The objective of the application was not only to represent the two cultural heritage artifacts digitally and convey historical information about them, but also to provide an interactive and immersive “hands-on” yet virtual user experience. The VVE application is intended for students and scholars of media and film history, as well as those interested in digital approaches to cultural heritage. The application is created with the intention of being used during lectures and demonstrations.

2 Methodology

The London Charter for the Computer-Based Visualisation of Cultural Heritage, which established “internationally-recognized principles for the use of computer-based visualization by researchers, educators and cultural heritage organizations” (The London Charter, 2009, n.p.), served as methodological guidance for the development of the VVE application. The London Charter emphasizes that computer-aided visualization should only be used when it is the “most appropriate available method” for the scope of the research (p.6). In our case, the development of the digital application accounts for a large part of the project’s overall scope because it addresses issues of digital materiality, immersion, and user experiences as part of the research question. Immersion refers to the experience of being deeply mentally involved in a virtual environment that differs from one’s own physical environment (Agrawal et al., 2019; Grau, 2003). While we apply the concept of immersion in our project to the “virtual viewing experiences” enabled by the VVE application, immersive user experiences are not limited to virtual reality or 3D digital applications. They have a longer history with other media, such as cinema and panoramas (Griffiths, 2008; Kenderdine, 2015). According to Schumacher (2010, p.8), user experience encompasses “all of the actions, thoughts, and feelings one has when engaging with a product or service over time”. In the context of the VVE application, user experience refers to how the application simulates hands-on interactions with the Kinora and Pathé Baby as cultural heritage objects within a virtual environment.

A report with guidelines from the European Commission (2020) emphasizes the value of and need for 3D digitization for the conservation, preservation, and reproduction of cultural heritage objects, making them available for further exploration in both research and education (Europeana Network Association Members Council, 2019). Documenting the application development process, from the digitization of cultural heritage objects to their digital recreation and presentation in a virtual environment with simulated functionality, was therefore an important aspect of our methodology. Providing step-by-step documentation of a project’s development facilitates reproducibility. It allows other researchers to replicate the process, enabling them to augment, revise, cross-reference, or even refute hypotheses or findings. When conducting digital scholarship, documentation also helps explain the heuristic value of the development process. The London Charter states that the development process of a computer-aided visualization project should be sufficiently documented to allow for an understanding of the methods used and the outcomes in relation to the “contexts

and purposes for which they are deployed” (The London Charter, 2009, p.8). Scholars have repeatedly highlighted the importance of documentation in 3D cultural heritage reconstructions (de Kramer, 2022). Pfarr-Harfst and Grellert (2016) argue that preserving both the technical readability of the primary datasets and the underlying depth of knowledge is crucial to ensure the viability of the 3D model (p.41). A critical aspect of producing comprehensive documentation is not only recording the recreated models, but also incorporating the research context as “research sources”. According to methodological studies, a project’s process and outcomes are invariably shaped by its goals, intentions, and application context (Pfarr-Harfst and Wefers, 2016, p.547).

The London Charter and European Commission guidelines for doing 3D scholarship heavily influenced our project’s various creative and design decisions. Other decisions regarding the techniques used to create and animate the models are also explained in this article for transparency. As explained in the following section, certain decisions were influenced by technical constraints, such as compatibility issues encountered during dataset transfer between the different software applications used during development.

3 Application Development

The VVE application was developed in four stages: (1) digitization, (2) conceptualization, (3) contextualization, and (4) digital storytelling. The following sections reflect on these four stages of the development process and explain how each stage contributes to the overall research question.

3.1 Step 1: Digitization

The digitization of the cultural heritage objects preceded the actual development of the VVE application. This is why the conceptualization of the application occurs after the digitization of the objects as steps in the application development process, rather than the other way around. As stated in the introduction, various media historical objects were digitized as part of the CRAFTED project to make them available on the Europeana platform of digital cultural heritage (Europeana, 2021). In addition to 3D objects, the dataset contains high-quality photos, videos, sound recordings, and 360-degree photos (van der Heijden, 2023). As media historical objects, the Kinora viewer and Pathé Baby projector were thus digitized as part of a larger digitization process that included the scanning of 15 media historical objects using 360-degree photography technologies. The captures were made in a professionally equipped studio at the Digital History Lab of the University of Luxembourg. Each object was placed on a rotating glass plate and photographed 36 times at a 10-degree interval using a Phase One 360 photo camera and its Capture One software. After cropping, background removal in Photoshop, and exporting in a PNG or JPEG format, the images could be viewed in a 360-degree image viewer. The Photogrammetry method (Guery et al., 2018) was used to convert the 360-degree images into 3D objects. More specifically, the 36 photos per object were synthesized into three-dimensional models by an AI-powered algorithm from the web-based application Polycam.⁵

The AI-synthesized 3D objects of the Kinora and Pathé Baby were subsequently utilized in the development of the VVE application. More specifically and to better serve the purpose of this project, after the AI-assisted model recreation, we chose

⁵ <https://poly.cam/>.

to manually recreate the two objects in the 3D design software Blender. Blender is a free and open-source 3D creation tool that “supports the entirety of the 3D design pipeline: modeling, rigging, animation, simulation, rendering, compositing and motion tracking”.⁶ The software provides a versatile toolbox for accurately modeling 3D replicas of real-world artifacts. Furthermore, it enables precise and highly customizable animations and physics simulations for the reels. Consequently, we chose Blender for our project for two reasons: (1) animations for the moving parts are only possible if these are separate from the rest of the 3D mesh, and (2) by manually recreating the objects, we achieved higher visual fidelity and realism for the final 3D objects. The synthesized 3D models of the Kinora viewer and Pathé Baby projector were imported into Blender to serve as visual references for their manual recreation using this software. The imported reference models provided an accurate three-dimensional representation of the reconstructed objects’ actual dimensions, ensuring correct proportions and precise placement of additional components and details, such as holes, screws, levers, and hinges. Figure 2 shows the Kinora viewer as a 3D scanned object, the manually recreated 3D object in Blender, and a composite view of the two artifacts overlapping, demonstrating the precision with which they were designed. Figure 3 depicts the 3D model of the Pathé Baby projector in the same three phases.

Figure 2: The Kinora viewer 3D scanned object (left); the Kinora viewer manually 3D recreated object (middle); composite view of the two objects in an overlap pose (right).

The digitization process transforms cultural heritage objects into digital representations or surrogates. These “digital artifacts” preserve the visual information of the original objects, withstanding time-related attrition due to their digital nature, while their new form allows for easier access and reuse. After reconstructing the objects in Blender, we created animations for the moving parts. These animations served to demonstrate some of the object’s functions. The animations were created using various techniques, each with its own set of considerations. The animations’ aims included accuracy, organicity, compatibility, and transferability for the subsequent transition to Unity. Unity is a real-time 3D development platform that “lets artists, designers, and developers collaborate to create immersive and interactive experiences”.⁷ Unity allowed us to demonstrate the objects and the exhibition space in 3D, as well as to code behaviors for them and present them alongside other media in real time. In other words, Unity integrates 3D visualization functionalities with scripting capabili-

⁶ <https://www.blender.org/about/>.

⁷ <https://unity.com/products/unity-engine>, accessed September 17, 2024.

Figure 3: The Pathé Baby projector 3D scanned object (left); the Pathé Baby projector manually 3D recreated object (middle); composite view of the two objects in an overlap pose (right).

ties, supplemented by various multimedia elements. Within Unity, we designed the presentation elements (such as camera transitions, user interface, and textual information) and the interactive features (including menu button functionalities and object behaviors) for our project. The animations were an important part of the presentation because they showed the objects in use and thus represented the hands-on aspect of the artifacts. The animations were combined with actual recorded sounds of the devices in use in order to create a multisensory impression of their operation.

In the case of the Kinora viewer, the animation depicts the mechanism of the rotating reel activated by turning the crank. The operation appears straightforward, but becomes more complex when replicating it using 3D animation. The main reason for this difficulty lies in the cyclical design of the reel and the large number of frames it holds. Each frame is part of a curved image card attached to the center of the reel. When the image card passes through the lens, the stop mechanism flattens it, making it visible in the Kinora viewer (Anthony, 1996, p.4). In the 3D animation, each singular frame was duplicated multiple times across the circular center using the array modifier, which was set to use a central point-of-reference (pivot point). According to van der Heijden and Wolf (2022), reflecting on the process of making a working 3D replica of the Kinora system, an original Kinora reel holds 640 frames placed in the center along 315 degrees. For this project, and to optimize real-time performance of the application, we found it necessary to limit the number of frames exported for both the reel animations. This decision was made out of pure necessity, as the animations' excessive data generated by the chosen format used for the animations (what is called "Shape Keys" in Blender), caused Unity to repeatedly freeze indefinitely during import. As a result, we chose to use shorter reel animations, which are essentially the same animations albeit condensed into fewer frames and therefore played back at a faster rate. This approach effectively communicates the reel's functionality while avoiding insurmountable technical challenges. The animation was created by simulating cloth physics⁸ for the reel's frames, albeit with higher values for the "tension" and "bending" qualities of the material combined with lower geometry (fewer subdivisions on each

⁸ Cloth physics is a computer graphics simulation technique that realistically animates the behavior of fabrics and textiles – in our case, paper from the Kinora reels – in virtual environments.

frame) for the actual mesh to make it appear more rigid and thus resemble thick paper rather than actual cloth.

In line with the Kinora's original working, the frames collided with a stop mesh containing a physics collider that was laid flat at the point of observation and then sprang forward, following the one preceding it. The physics simulation was then "baked", which means it was no longer calculated at runtime, so it did not require any computational resources for running, only for displaying the animation. Baking the animation was required when transferring it from Blender to Unity. More specifically, Blender was used to perform and set up the physics calculations for the cloth simulation, followed by the baking process, which converted the shape of the mesh using each keyframe.⁹ In order to bake the generated physics simulation, Blender uses "Shape Keys", which are essentially different instances of the base mesh, one for each animation frame, marked as a keyframe, and plays the animation by interpolating between different configurations of the mesh on each frame. Unity then (being fully compatible with Blender's Shape Keys) "reads" these keyframes and displays the resulting animation. The rotation animation for the handle was also created, using the technical specifications from van der Heijden and Wolf (2022) as a reference, at one rotation per second, with the center of the arm's handle serving as the pivot point.

The animation of the Pathé Baby projector features a rotating handle that unfolds the 9.5mm film strip from the reel after guiding it through the gate and folding it around the center of the device's "take-up chamber" (van der Heijden and Santi, 2022, p.101). While this may appear more complicated than rotating a reel in the Kinora viewer, it is much simpler to recreate in a 3D animation. The reel follows a predetermined path while folding and unfolding around two centers. Consequently, a fixed path was created by connecting two Archimedean spirals around the device's folding points. A single film frame was duplicated multiple times along the initial spiral path with an array modifier to create the film strip. An empty object was assigned to guide the tape's movement along the path by manually moving along the x-axis.

Materials that utilize the Physically Based Rendering (PBR) model were used to display the objects' materials as realistically as possible. The PBR materials pipeline is now considered a standard practice for 3D visualizations, whether ray-traced or real-time. These materials use various images as "maps" to display different surface properties, such as color, shadow, bas-relief, metallicity, roughness, and light emission. For some of each device's larger surfaces, generic materials were used (e.g., wood, painted iron, glass), sometimes mixed with rust or decayed materials to add realism and inspire a sense of organicity. The materials in Blender's built-in shader¹⁰ were created by connecting node inputs and outputs, while the maps were used by connecting image files to the respective shader node inputs. A mix shader node, which is used to combine two different shaders, also has a factor input that controls how and whether the two shaders will mix. By combining the two shaders in a specific way, the decay may only occur at certain areas of the surface. The logos for each device were created using two distinct methods. Because the Kinora logo is simply a bas-relief protruding from the eyepiece, it was first auto-traced¹¹ from an image into a black-and-white vector file before being used as a bas-relief map. The bas-relief (or height/bump) map is essentially a non-color map that receives values ranging from 0 to 1 and cre-

⁹ Keyframes signify specific moments or playback positions in an animation or video sequence. They serve as reference points for animation software or video players, allowing for interpolation between different states or effects to create intermediary frames.

¹⁰ Shaders control how 3D computer graphics render objects' surfaces.

¹¹ Auto-tracing is a graphic design process that converts pixel-based raster images to vector images.

ates a simulated protuberance on the surface (0 for lowest, 1 for highest elevation). For the Pathé Baby, whose logo is far more intricate and specific, a projection of the logo extracted from the 360-degree photos was applied to the surface. Other, more distinctive-looking materials were synthesized from the 360-degree photos and edited to look seamless using photo editing software (Adobe Photoshop).

3.2 Step 2: Conceptualization

The digital inspires new perspectives on cultural heritage and enables new research methodologies. There are numerous digital tools and methods for displaying and analyzing data, ranging from displaying historical information to simulating practices and experiences. Visual technologies provide a new perspective for investigating and analyzing objects, histories, and phenomena. Pink et al. (2016) observe a shift in the design anthropology discipline, influenced by material culture studies, toward reimagining the object through digital means (p.19). They discover that combining the physical and digital worlds as two distinct entities creates new apparent realities. The VVE application draws on this concept of “digital materialities” (p.7) as it attempts to bring material qualities and reality-based practices (such as the use of a media historical device) into the digital realm.

In digital historical scholarship, the concept of “digital hermeneutics” provides a valuable framework to “critically reflect on the various interventions of digital research infrastructures, tools, databases and dissemination platforms in the process of thinking, doing and narrating history” (Fickers, 2022, p.140-141). When an analogue object is digitized or recreated digitally, the methods used not only present a challenge in terms of documentation and ethical implications of such a work, with and within the digital, but also demand a self-reflexive approach (Fickers, 2022, p.142). For our project, both the 3D design and use of digital storytelling should therefore be reflected upon.

Telling stories across multiple platforms with content that is scaled, timed, and placed appropriately can result in a “larger, more profitable, cohesive and rewarding experience” (Pratten, 2015, p.4). Pratten contends that only through transmedia storytelling can the audience be put at the center of any experience design. Our application employs transmedia storytelling in the sense that it uses computer-based 3D visualization to depict the materiality and functionality of two historical media technologies. Inside the VVE application, the user can “project” a 9.5mm film using the Pathé Baby projector and “view” a Kinora reel on the Kinora viewer (in the form of an image sequence), resulting in two “virtual viewing experiences” (hence the application’s name). Through the virtual environment, the digital rendering of the objects, and their simulated functions, the objects arguably transcend their original context and historical usages.

We were inspired by a variety of similar projects when developing the VVE application’s digital storytelling component. For example, in a project from the University of Groningen, an interactive 3D model of the Lumière Cinématographe is presented using the zSpace application (Harkema and Rosendaal, 2020). The zSpace monitor provides a 3D interactive, spatial simulation that falls somewhere between augmented reality and virtual reality, allowing viewers to interact with simulated objects in various ways while wearing 3D glasses. Despite being a screen medium, it “simulates an interactive space that is within one’s reach” (Harkema and Rosendaal, 2020, p.76). With a stylus, the object can be picked up and dropped, moved, rotated, or brought closer, as well as used to control the application’s menus. As such, the project aimed to deepen student’s understanding of a technological medium and its socio-technological effects

through practice-based pedagogy – or “thinkering”¹² (Huhtamo, 2010) – as a framework for the application’s interaction design. Similar to our project, the project uses 3D recreated models to create animations. The application uses digital storytelling and user interaction to enable users to navigate and explore historical media devices in a virtual environment. The project arguably takes immersion and the learning-by-doing approach a step further, namely through the use of hybrid screen technology and its extended interactivity capabilities to educate and disseminate knowledge about the materiality and usages of the artifacts it represents. The hands-on aspect is key to this project and the digital application’s overall user experience.

Another project that influenced the conceptualization of our application is the Virtual Interiors project (Huurdeeman and Piccoli, 2020, 2021). In this project’s virtual environment, several historical Amsterdam homes are recreated using 3D visualization, along with references to contextual data and information about the degree of ambiguity in the suggested 3D model. Huurdeeman and Piccoli use the house of Pieter de Graeff, an Amsterdam regent from the 17th century, as a case study. Selected objects from nearly one thousand objects were created as 3D models and placed in “its reconstructed historical domestic context” (Huurdeeman and Piccoli, 2020, p.338). The authors argue that these 3D reconstructions, along with an increasing number of virtual reconstructions and reality-based 3D models created for other projects, provide a variety of new approaches to learning about and engaging with historical settings for audiences ranging from the general public to specialized scholars.¹³ The project’s digital storytelling makes use of 3D recreated models and annotations on those models as name tags. Tags are essentially two-dimensional user interface objects that exist in the 3D space, but hide their two-dimensionality by always facing the scene’s main camera. Because the Virtual Interiors project can only be accessed through a web browser, user immersion is limited. The 3D virtual environment serves as a menu for selecting which objects to view and provides the user with a wealth of contextual and historical information. The user is thus given extensive control over the scene’s viewport size, camera movement, lighting conditions, and the ability to examine the same content from various analytical perspectives. The project inspired us to incorporate similar forms of user interaction and historical contextualization into the VVE application.

3.3 Step 3: Contextualization

The historical context is translated into a virtual environment during the contextualization phase. This phase entails spatially integrating the two cultural heritage objects into their respective historical and practical settings. The term “context” is used here in its broadest sense, encompassing not only the exhibition space, but also information about the functionality or historical uses of the objects, as well as the media displayed by the objects (i.e., moving images). Each of these major elements has multiple sub-items. For example, the exhibition space features a historically informed design. The usage of the objects is tied to historical user practices and technical standards (e.g., crank operation, role of lighting, reel functioning). Finally, the media these objects display contain both visual and audio components. Besides the moving images, which

¹² “Thinkering” is a hands-on method of ‘thinking while doing’ that is applied within experimental media archaeology as an object-oriented and sensorial approach to media historical research and teaching (Fickers and van den Oever, 2022; van der Heijden and Kolkowski, 2023)

¹³ See in this context also the project Cinema Parisien 3D by Noordegraaf et al. (2016), in which 3D visualization is used as a tool for narrating the history of cinemagoing in Amsterdam.

were silent, the devices produced mechanical sounds or noises during operation.

Regarding the design of the virtual environment, it was decided that the artifacts would be positioned in a domestic interior as they were primarily used at home. The historical context is an important part of presenting historical artifacts, so the exhibition room was designed to correspond visually and architecturally with the period from which the artifacts originated. The aesthetic design of the virtual room was informed by archival research in the photo archive of the Regional Historical Center of Limburg (Regionaal Historisch Centrum Limburg). The digital archive, which can be accessed online¹⁴, contains a large collection of digital photos of home interiors in the Dutch province of Limburg. The collection was helpful to the project because it was easily accessible and allowed for making historically informed decisions about the design process of the application's virtual environment. The objective for the room aesthetics was to design a domestic interior of a central European middle-class home from the first quarter of the twentieth century. During this era, however, many architectural styles are present in Europe (e.g., Victorian, Art Nouveau, Art Deco, and Bauhaus). Instead of pursuing a specific architectural style, an effort was made to create a generic space from that era, embellished with ornaments that are present but do not overpower the other elements in the room. The rationale for this decision was that the virtual space was intended to be persuasive but not invasive to the experience; after all, its purpose is to frame and complement the exhibits.

Figure 4: A screenshot of the “room view” in the VVE application.

The room's walls were divided into nearly square sections across their width, separated by small wooden columns with vertical ornamental lines and other extruded miscellaneous ornamental details at their beginning and end. Vertically, the entire room was divided at about waist high, with the bottom section extruded by a small amount and assigned a wood material. The top part's square wall sections were embellished with a wooden frame, as was common in that era's interiors. A suitable-style image texture was selected to act as the floor material for the flooring texture. The ceiling was divided into small squares, with the borders beveled to form a rectangular grid that was then extruded from the rest to create depth. A second prototype for the

¹⁴ <https://beeldbank.rhcl.nl/>.

ceiling featured an attic-style angled wooden ceiling. Perhaps the only distinguishing feature of the virtual space is the design of the curtains for the room's windows. For this design, three different curtains were used: the back, side (drawn apart in the middle), and top, which hung loosely in the center. (Figure 4)

Each of the two artifacts was placed on top of furniture and positioned on one side of the virtual room. The Kinora viewer and its 3D scanned reels were placed on a table, while the Pathé Baby projector was mounted on top of a small, shelved table, with its reels on one of the shelves below. Some miscellaneous objects were used to populate the virtual space, including open-licensed 3D scanned objects from Sketchfab and others that were manually created specifically for this project. A 3D scanned Beshr sofa, a coffee table, a carpet, an armchair, a desk with several books, a lamp and some sheets of paper on it, two bookcases, a grandfather clock, a coat stand, a nightstand with a telephone on it, two planted pots, a feather pen inside an ink bottle, a globe, and eight wall-mounted lamps are among the additional items. The exhibition scene also includes a functional fireplace; the fire in the fireplace is the only element that adds organicity to an otherwise static scene. In this context, "organicity" refers to how realistic or natural a digital object or space appears to the user. Real-world objects typically have flaws and irregularities in both shape and material. When a digital 3D object is designed too uniformly or flawlessly, it can give the impression of artificiality, which disrupts user immersion. As a result, 3D artists frequently use noise maps like Voronoi Noise and Perlin Noise to introduce distortions or variations in elements such as textures, camera movements (to simulate camera shake), and animations (to add irregularities to their playback). For this project, the fire effect uses multiple layered noise maps to define and animate the flame shapes. (Figure 5)

Figure 5: The selection menu for the two objects.

3.4 Step 4: Digital storytelling

Digital storytelling is fundamental to this project as it enables the power of interactivity within the narrative, which greatly enhances and contributes to user immersion. This approach ensures a consistent, personalized, and memorable user experience. According to Miller (2004), interactivity is what distinguishes digital from traditional

storytelling in terms of user experience. According to the author, interactivity is a more active way of engaging with the content than simply watching, listening, or reading. The experience of interactive content transforms the user's role into an active participant who has direct control and influence over the material in a "two-way exchange" (Miller, 2004, p.56). Interactive entertainment provides users, gamers, and visitors with two advantages that audiences of passive entertainment never have: choice and control (Miller, 2004, p.57). In an interactive piece, users can choose what to see and do, and their decisions influence what happens next. When the full potential of digital storytelling is realized, the narrative evolves from a linear to a multidimensional experience. The user is not passively presented with a story, but rather actively participates through the use of intersections with multiple options and the ability to return to a previous point in the narrative. The user actively selects what content to view and, if (dis)satisfied, is given the option to return to the previous intersection and take a different "route".

Pujol and Champion (2012) argue that "ideally, virtual heritage environments should not merely be 3D reconstructions but also interactive learning environments" (p.89). Arguably, the interactivity design in a computer-based presentation of a cultural artifact and the overall user experience influence how a user perceives a given artifact and thus what they learn. Notably, it also works the other way around: the desired outcome, or what we want to demonstrate about a cultural object, influences the interactivity design and context in which the artifact is presented. The user's virtual presence is the first and most important consideration when choosing its role within this application. More specifically, the user is not embodied in the virtual environment, so there is no walking animation or manual user movement. Instead, camera transitions based on user input allow the user to explore the virtual space. The transition between fixed camera positions with a single user input (one key press per transition) adds a cause-and-effect quality to the experience, keeping the user focused on the presentation of the exhibits rather than the navigation. For the cameras, we used the Unity Technologies' Cinemachine module. The use of Cinemachine gives the developer extensive control over the camera selections, transitions, focus points, and additional functionality via scripts. Cinemachine contributes significantly to the user's immersion. The number of user interface elements (UI) has been kept to a minimum. The only UI elements in the scene are the main menu (accessed automatically at the start or by pressing the Escape key at any time) and various user tooltip prompts that appear when an action is available. With only a few UI elements in the scene, users can better immerse themselves in the virtual space.

In this project, we see digital storytelling as the unifying element, bringing together various elements of the story about the Kinora and Pathé Baby as historical media technologies. These elements are already taxonomized in layers according to their nature. The first layer is the visual layer, which includes both the visual appearance of the objects and the moving images they are designed to reproduce. This layer contains all the visual information surrounding the objects and their associated media. The exhibition scene's lighting and photography (camera angle) are also categorized under the visual layer. The second layer is the audio layer, which is bound to the moving image projections. While the moving images are silent, the audio accompanying them includes the mechanical sounds of each device. We found that the audio layer significantly contributes to user immersion and a sense of control over the device. The ability of the user to control some of the devices' functions comprises a third layer: the usage layer. For example, the user can interact with the crank using its

operating principle, a feature that both devices share. More specifically, the user starts to turn the crank of the respective device, and the speed at which the crank rotates determines the playback speed of the moving images and the audio. Control of the video playback speed through crank rotation is implemented via a script in Unity. First, the script determines the direction of the mouse relative to the center of rotation. Then, it calculates the angle between the previous and current directions along with the time elapsed since the last update. Using these calculations, the script derives the rotations per second, adjusts the playback speed accordingly and then updates the video's progress. Furthermore, it controls audio and video playback based on the direction and speed of rotation, while synchronizing the reel animation with the crank rotation speed. (Figures 6 and 7)

Figure 6: The Pathé Baby film projector and screen, simulated within the application.

Figure 7: The Kinora viewer, simulated within the application.

A fourth layer in the digital application presents the historical information of each object. This layer can be accessed via a dedicated button after the user has selected one of the two devices for a closer look. The historical information layer, which is central to the application, is animated upon (de)activation. The annotations in the exhibition scene are also part of this layer. According to Lehmann and Döllner (2013), labeling or annotating 3D content is critical for enabling target-oriented exploration and navigation in interactive environments, such as digital 3D cities or indoor models. Annotating 3D models is a common practice in 3D scholarship. Pfarr-Harfst and Grellert (2016) note that, in addition to the research output accompanying the digital scholarship in the form of text, researchers attempt to incorporate annotations containing relevant information about the 3D models themselves (p.43-44). Over the last decade, several initiatives have addressed the challenges of 3D annotations for semantic enrichment. Santos et al. (2014) conclude that, while available technologies produce promising results, they do not provide a complete solution, and additional challenges must be addressed before developing a comprehensive semantic enrichment pipeline. In our project, annotations help the user identify each object and highlight the presence of the usage layer.

Finally, the fifth layer is a tutorial layer that helps the user navigate the digital narrative. The purpose of this layer is to inform the user about the application's navigation (controls) and usage (features). Indications or pointers are needed to show how to use and interact with the application's various features, especially for applications with features not present in everyday use.

Figure 8: The tutorial layer of the application.

Consequently, the digital narrative of our exhibition scene unfolds as follows:

1. The user is introduced to the scene via a welcome screen in the shape of a period poster containing two main buttons: *Start* and *Quit*. A third button, *About*, in the bottom right corner, provides background information about the VVE project.
2. When the user clicks *Start*, the camera transitions to a different angle behind the initial camera and moves backward to reveal both the objects and the exhibits. Two new buttons are then introduced, one for the Pathé Baby and one for the

Kinora, each reading the names of the devices, including their logos. This view also allows the user to toggle on or off the control sheet containing information about the application's control buttons.

3. When the user selects a device for a closer look, the camera switches to a view focusing on the selected object. New functions are then introduced in the form of buttons. The user can access the object's historical information by clicking the Read More button, and they can activate annotations to learn about the device's operating capabilities. The user can also view the moving images that each device projects or can go back to the previous intersection and select a different option. Thus, the device can be operated manually by moving the mouse around the crank's rotational axis, or the moving images and audio can be played back automatically if the user only wants to watch the historical media.
4. While navigating the application, the user can perform a few actions at any time. By pressing the *Escape* key, a menu UI appears in the foreground, and all other UI elements that may be open are disabled. The "escape menu" offers the user several options, including (a) continuing the exhibition, (b) restarting the scene, (c) changing the camera angle to view the rest of the exhibition room, (d) viewing accreditations for additional contributions to the project, and (e) quitting the application. At any point, the user can zoom in on the camera view by adjusting the camera's Field of View value, as well as rotate the objects along their vertical axis to obtain a more spherical or complete view.

4 Conclusion

Cultural heritage deals with preserving knowledge from the past to pass it on to future generations. One of the advantages that digital technologies can provide to the cultural heritage field is easy access to information. Digitization enables one to capture and preserve a physical object in a digital format that others can easily access, distribute, and view. However, this digital form poses the challenge of preserving and presenting the tangible and intangible characteristics of cultural heritage objects in the digital realm. Reflecting on the VVE application's development, this article has shown how 3D technologies and immersive virtual environments can play an important role not only in preserving media heritage objects in digital form, but also in "re-animating" them through user interaction and digital storytelling to disseminate knowledge about their operation and histories of use.

As collections of digitized content expand, new ways of presenting digital collections must be explored and discovered. We believe digital storytelling and computer-based 3D visualizations can offer novel approaches to creating interactive and immersive user experiences with digital heritage objects. Thus, the digital and the material are not mutually exclusive. Drawing on the concept of digital materialities, they can be combined as entities in a unified or augmented experience that starts from the physical object and extends to the digital realm, or vice versa.

Although the VVE application is still a "work in progress" that could benefit from more user feedback and the addition of more interactive elements and annotations, we decided to publish the current prototype on Zenodo (Georgiakakis and van der Heijden, 2023b). (Figure 9) Zenodo, an online accessible and sustainable repository, allows one to include "versions" of publications. With the release of version 1.0 of the VVE application, which serves as a reference for this article and our poster

zenodo

Published June 6, 2023 | Version v1

Virtual Viewing Experiences (Application)

Georgiakakis, Theodoros¹; van der Heijden, Tim²

How to simulate hands-on media practices in a virtual environment using 3D-represented cultural heritage objects in such a way that the material characteristics of the objects and their usages become part of the virtual and immersive user experience? In this project, we have explored this question by focusing on two media historical objects: the Kinora motion picture viewer (ca. 1907) and the Pathé Baby 9.5mm film projector (ca. 1924) as early-twentieth-century technologies of home cinema. The application development was carried out in four stages: (1) digitization, (2) conceptualization, (3) contextualization, and (4) digital storytelling.

The project was developed within the framework of a research internship at the Open University of the Netherlands in collaboration with Maastricht University, the Netherlands. It was conducted in support of the project CRAFTED: *Enrich and promote traditional and contemporary crafts*, co-financed by the Connecting Europe Facility of the European Commission.

Video demonstration of the application: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8UnoPSDZCiw>

Files

Name	Size	Download all
VVE PatheKinora.jpg	1.0 MB	Preview Download
VVE RoomView1.jpg	5.4 MB	Preview Download
VVE RoomView2.jpg	3.8 MB	Preview Download
VVE VirtualPoster.jpg	11.2 MB	Preview Download
VVE_App_v1.0.zip	788.9 MB	Preview Download

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10.5281/zenodo.8011420 | Jun 6, 2023

Keywords and subjects: 3D modelling, digital history, media history, Kinora, Pathé Baby, home cinema, motion picture technology, experimental media archaeology

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8011420](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8011420)

Resource type: Dataset

Publisher: Zenodo

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Citation: Georgiakakis, T. & van der Heijden, T. (2023). Virtual Viewing Experiences (Application) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8011420>

Figure 9: The first version of the VVE application, published on Zenodo.

presentation at the DH Benelux 2023 conference at the Royal Library of Belgium in Brussels (Georgiakakis and van der Heijden, 2023a), we like to share our work with the Media Studies and Digital Humanities communities, encouraging the application's use and testing. In addition to the Zenodo publication of the VVE application, we have published a demonstration video on YouTube that showcases the application's features as well as the aforementioned steps of digitally narrating and conveying the "virtual viewing experiences" of the Kinora and Pathé Baby as early-twentieth-century home cinema technologies.¹⁵

In conclusion, the development of the VVE application allowed us to reflect on the potential of 3D technologies in the preservation and presentation of cultural heritage objects and media historical collections. In future project stages, we aim to investigate ways to improve the application's usability based on empirical user tests and reception studies. Any subsequent iterations of the application's design should also be informed by or co-produced with stakeholders from the cultural heritage field. Incorporating such user perspectives from audiences and potential parties of interest in the development process, or in specific cases, would be crucial for optimizing the immersive effect, usability, and potential implementation of the application in cultural heritage institutional spaces, both online and on-site. Bringing together these perspectives from researchers, developers, users, audiences, and stakeholders is critical to realizing the potential and implementation of 3D technologies and virtual environments for the preservation and presentation of cultural heritage collections.

¹⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8UnoPSDZCiw>.

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank Europeana and the CRAFTED project team for their support. We would furthermore like to thank the anonymous reviewers for their constructive feedback on an earlier version of this article.

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